
**An Econometric Analysis of the Integration of Customized Credit and
Participatory Business Development Services as a risk management tool in Ghana:**

Impact on SME Profitability, Loan Repayment, and Economic Development

By

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A Thesis Submitted In Fulfilment Of The Requirements For The Degree Of

Doctor Of Philosophy

School Of Business And Creative Industries

University Of The West Of Scotland

September 2025

DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

I, **Ndukwe Ibe**, declare that this work has not been previously submitted for a degree at this or any other university. All sources are acknowledged as references.

Signed: _____ N.I. _____

Date: _____ 17th October, 2025 _____

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the integration of customized credit and participatory Business Development Services (BDS) for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana, conceptualizing integration as a systematic risk management tool. The research addresses a critical gap in understanding how integrated delivery of financial and non-financial services affects SME performance and broader economic development outcomes. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study employs hierarchical random effects modelling, risk-return clustering analysis, and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) modelling to examine 450 SMEs surveyed between 2022-2023, complemented by macroeconomic data spanning 1970-2023. The theoretical framework establishes that business risk decreases as the level of service integration increases, creating a mechanism through which integration simultaneously reduces business risks while enhancing profitability and loan repayment capacity. The empirical analysis reveals that while standalone credit and BDS services demonstrate negative effects on profitability, integrated service delivery yields significantly positive outcomes. Integration facilitates more sustainable loan repayment patterns that align with business cycles, contrasting with the unsustainable pressure created by separate services. The risk-return clustering identifies four distinct SME segments, each requiring tailored integrated services. The macroeconomic impact analysis demonstrates that integration produces transformative effects on development indicators. Human Development Index, Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index, and Multidimensional Poverty Index coefficients shift from negative under separate service approaches to significantly positive with integration, suggesting profound implications for inclusive development strategies. The study establishes an implementation framework comprising risk-return based customization of credit terms, deployment of Integrated Service Officers, and sustainable knowledge transfer mechanisms based on risk-return profile. This framework addresses fundamental risk management challenges while creating pathways for inclusive development. The findings challenge conventional wisdom about development interventions (including in policy making). This study establishes integration as a fundamentally different paradigm for conceptualizing and implementing SME support that simultaneously enhances firm-level outcomes and broader societal development through systematic risk reduction and performance enhancement mechanisms.

DEDICATION

To the cherished memories of:

Ibe Ndukwe Ibe (Teacher Ibe) - The first graduate in my native community who cleared the academic path that I now follow.

Mma Akumma (My Maternal Grandmother) - You remain a guiding light (020) unto my path.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The journey to completing this doctoral thesis has been one of profound growth, immense challenge, and unexpected beauty. Like any meaningful endeavour, it was never a solitary pursuit, but rather a testament to the extraordinary people who believed in me, sometimes even before I believed in myself.

I extend my deepest gratitude to Professor Emeritus John Struthers, my Director of Studies and lead supervisor, whose intellectual guidance shaped not just this research but my entire approach to scholarship. Your unwavering commitment to excellence and your gentle insistence that I "simplify complexities" have transformed my thinking. Your patience during our meetings even when my son demanded attention demonstrated a humanity in academia that I aspire to embody. Thank you for seeing potential in my ideas and providing the perfect balance of freedom and direction to nurture them.

Words falter when attempting to express my gratitude to my wife, Blessing Ngozi Ndukwe. You have been my foundation, my courage, and my sanctuary. While I pursued knowledge, you shouldered our financial burdens, ensuring our bills and home were secure. You are the sister I never had, the friend I always needed, and the partner I never deserved but was blessed to find. Your unwavering belief in my capabilities pushed me to aim higher than I thought possible. And to our son, Ibe Jnr, whose innocent presence during day and late-night thesis writing and supervisory meetings brought light to this demanding journey—your tiny hands hold my greatest hope and motivation.

This academic journey would never have begun without Mr. and Mrs. Joseph Nii Anang Larmie, who changed the course of my life through an act of extraordinary generosity. When you found me—a stranger without hope—you provided not just financial support by paying my undergraduate fees from my second semester until graduation, but something far more valuable: belief in my potential. You sought nothing in return for this life-changing investment. Your kindness remains the standard by which I measure generosity, and I carry the responsibility of your faith in me with every achievement.

I honour the memory of the late Isaac Nti Ofori (my Undergraduate research methods lecturer), who recognized something in me that I had yet to see in myself. Your mentorship transformed my understanding of research, and your holistic support nurtured both the academic and the human in me. Though you are not here to witness this culmination, your influence lives in every page of this work. May you rest in perfect peace.

When the continuation of this PhD seemed impossible, Francisca Agbagba performed an act of faith that still humbles me—offering your life savings without hesitation. Such profound generosity cannot be repaid, only honoured through living a life worthy of such sacrifice.

To Ezinna and Rev. Mrs. Bank Huoma, alongside Rev. Mrs. Helen Irem, Mrs Afuekwe Okpi and Anty. Ami: you provided nourishment for both body and spirit when I needed it most. Your support in getting me to Ghana for my first degree planted the seed from which this achievement has grown.

My heartfelt appreciation extends to my Agbo Orié Okpo and my mother-in-law, Elder Mrs. Joy Uma, for your prayers and encouragement; to Abdallah Abdul Rahaman, my dedicated research assistant whose diligence during data collection in Ghana was invaluable; and to Mr. Kwabena Osei-Bonsu for timely financial support that bridged critical gaps.

I am profoundly grateful to John Onum, Ibe Okorie, Afusatu Fuseini (Magazia), Mr. and Mrs. Obiwe Gabriel Udo, Mr. and Mrs. Udo Kalu, Mr. Evaristus Okoye, Ibrahim Yakubu, and Ibrahim Apena. Each of you contributed unique threads to the tapestry of support that made this journey possible.

This acknowledgment, though extensive, still fails to capture the depth of my gratitude. A doctoral thesis bears one name, but its completion is the product of countless acts of kindness, sacrifice, and belief. I carry the weight of your collective investment in me, and I promise to honor it by extending to others the same generosity that has been so abundantly shown to me.

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CHAPTER ONE:

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The integration of customized credit and participatory Business Development Services (BDS) within the context of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) represents a critical frontier in Ghana's economic development landscape. This intersection of financial and non-financial support mechanisms holds profound implications for SME profitability, loan repayments, and broader economic development (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). The significance of this integration becomes particularly apparent when considering the central role that SMEs play in Ghana's economic fabric, serving as primary drivers of employment generation, technological innovation, and sustained economic growth (Asare, 2014; Ayrakwa, 2020).

Across the African continent, SMEs have emerged as the foundational pillars of economic development, contributing substantially to employment creation, poverty reduction, and gross domestic product (GDP) growth. However, the sustainability and optimal contribution of these enterprises face significant challenges, ranging from prohibitive interest rates to inadequate business support mechanisms (Augustine, 2022; Chilembo, 2021). The complexity of these challenges has intensified in recent years, particularly as specific global economic indicators have shifted significantly - including 340% increases in commodity price volatility (World Bank, 2023), supply chain disruption affecting 89% of international trade routes (UNCTAD, 2023), and inflation volatility ranging from a peak of 54.1% in December 2022 to 13.7% by June 2025, compared to historical averages of 11.4% (Bank of Ghana, 2025; Trading Economics, 2025).

The global economic landscape has undergone significant transformation over recent decades, characterized by accelerating digitalization, increasing automation, and deepening globalization (Asgary, Ozdemir, & Özyürek, 2020). This evolving environment presents both opportunities and challenges for SMEs. While technological advancement has created new pathways for market access, customer engagement, and operational efficiency (Nkosi, 2023), it has also introduced heightened competitive pressures and accelerated the pace of technological change. The COVID-19 pandemic has further complicated this landscape, disrupting established supply chains, suppressing demand patterns, and introducing unprecedented levels of uncertainty into business operations (Juergensen, Guimón, & Narula, 2020).

The significance of SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa cannot be overstated, with these enterprises accounting for up to 80% of all businesses and providing employment for over 70% of the workforce (African Development Bank Group, 2019a). However, African SMEs operate within a uniquely challenging environment characterized by limited access to formal financial services, inadequate infrastructure, and regulatory frameworks that often impede rather than facilitate business growth (Beck, Ioannidou, & Schäfer, 2016). This challenging operational context is further compounded by relatively lower productivity levels compared to larger firms, a disparity often attributed to limitations in human capital development, technology adoption capabilities, and innovation capacity (Arinaitwe & Mwesigwa, 2015).

In Ghana's context, the recognition of SMEs' pivotal role in economic development has prompted sustained policy attention and intervention efforts. SMEs in Ghana are formally defined as enterprises employing fewer than 100 workers and maintaining an annual turnover below 1 million Ghanaian cedis (approximately 173,000 US dollars). According to the latest data from the Ghana Statistical Service (2024), the country hosts approximately 2.3 million SMEs, representing 92% of registered businesses and employing 85% of the workforce. These enterprises operate across diverse sectors, including agriculture, trade, services, manufacturing, construction, and mining, forming a complex and interconnected economic ecosystem that contributes 70% of GDP (African Development Bank, 2024; World Bank Ghana Economic Update, 2025). Understanding how to enhance this significant economic

sector through integrated support mechanisms requires examining the historical evolution of SME development challenges and policy responses in Ghana.

1.1.1 Historical Context and Economic Significance of SMEs in Ghana

The historical trajectory of SMEs in Ghana reveals their enduring importance in the nation's economic development. For many decades, these enterprises have served as crucial vehicles for employment generation, income creation, and technological advancement (Boateng & Asiedu, 2025; African Association of Entrepreneurs, 2022; Nazareno, Davide, & Duy, 2021). This historical significance extends beyond mere economic metrics, encompassing social mobility and community development dimensions that have been fundamental to Ghana's post-independence development narrative.

A particularly noteworthy characteristic of Ghana's SME sector has been its measurable adaptability, demonstrated through sectoral diversification rates of 23% annually and business model modifications reported by 67% of enterprises during economic transitions (Ghana Statistical Service, 2023; African Association of Entrepreneurs, 2022). This adaptive capacity has enabled SMEs to respond effectively to evolving market conditions and shifting consumer preferences, with 78% of surveyed enterprises reporting successful pivots during the COVID-19 pandemic (Nazareno et al., 2021).

The Ghanaian government's recognition of SMEs' importance has manifested in various policy initiatives over the years. These interventions have encompassed multiple dimensions, including efforts to enhance access to finance, provision of training and technical assistance, and the promotion of entrepreneurship (National Board for Small Scale Industries, 2019). However, as Abor and Quartey (2010) note, the effectiveness of these interventions has often been limited by implementation challenges and coordination difficulties among various support institutions.

The future trajectory of SMEs in Ghana holds significant promise, contingent upon the provision of appropriate support mechanisms. The sector's potential to drive economic transformation remains substantial, particularly given Ghana's demographic dividend and increasing technological adoption rates. As noted by Akoto-Sampong (2011), realizing this potential requires addressing both financial and non-financial constraints in an integrated manner.

1.1.2 Challenges Faced by SMEs

While Ghana's economy has shown encouraging signs of recovery in 2025, with inflation declining to 13.7% by June and currency stabilization supporting business confidence (Bank of Ghana, 2025), the fundamental structural challenges facing SMEs remain largely unaddressed. This period of economic stabilization presents an optimal window for implementing more effective support mechanisms, as businesses can focus on capacity building rather than crisis management.

The interconnected nature of SME challenges in Ghana reveals that traditional separate service delivery approaches fail because they address individual constraints in isolation, while the underlying problems are systemically linked. Three core challenge categories create reinforcing cycles that require integrated intervention approaches.

Financial Access Constraints

Limited access to finance represents the most significant obstacle facing Ghanaian SMEs, manifesting through insufficient collateral, prohibitive interest rates, and restrictive repayment terms (Boateng & Asiedu, 2025; Adu, 2023; Cooper, 2023; Cunha, Entwisle, Jeenah, & Williams, 2020; Kisseih, 2017; Olubiyi, 2022; Oppong, Owiredu, & Churchill, 2014; Parrott, 2023; Runde et al., 2021; World Bank, 2023). The persistence of these barriers despite numerous credit programs reveals that the fundamental problem lies in the disconnection between financial provision and business development support.

High interest rates and loan processing charges create financial burdens that significantly impact businesses' ability to maintain profitability and sustain growth (Asare, 2014; Ashogbon, Onyenebo, & Orefuwa, 2022; Cash, 2023; Ford, 2023; Pettinger, 2023; Prices Ghana, 2023; Staff, 2016; Veli & Tumo, 2019; Young, 2021). These exploitative practices create vicious cycles where high borrowing costs force SMEs to prioritize short-term survival over long-term capacity building, increasing risk profiles and justifying even higher interest rates (Abor & Quartey, 2010; Akoto-Sampong, 2011). Excessive collateral requirements further compound these challenges, with banks demanding collateral that can lead to asset stripping while reflecting fundamental mistrust stemming from inadequate creditworthiness assessment mechanisms (Quartey, 2020; African Development Bank Group, 2019b).

Business Development Support Inadequacies

Inadequate business development support represents another significant challenge, with many enterprises lacking essential knowledge and skills required for sustainable success (Husar, 2023; Liebl & Kanju, 2023; Njoroge & Kaluyu, 2020; Olatunji, 2023; Partner, 2023b). The persistence of knowledge gaps despite extensive training programs reveals that the fundamental problem lies in delivery methodology rather than content availability. Traditional BDS approaches suffer from "intervention discontinuity" - sporadic training sessions without ongoing implementation support create knowledge without application capability, explaining why well-funded training programs often fail to produce measurable improvements in SME performance.

Environmental Volatility and Competitive Pressures

Political and economic volatility makes long-term planning difficult for businesses, affecting investment decisions and growth strategies (Africa News Watch, 2018; World Bank, 2022a). Competition from large businesses creates additional challenges, with larger enterprises possessing superior resources and better market access that create uneven playing fields (van Scheers & Makhitha, 2016; OECD, 2021). These environmental factors highlight SMEs' inadequate internal resilience mechanisms and limited capacity to compete effectively due to fragmented support systems.

The Integration Imperative

These interconnected challenges depict why traditional separate service approaches have achieved limited impact despite substantial resource investment. Financial constraints cannot be resolved through credit provision alone when businesses lack capacity to use capital effectively. Business development needs cannot be addressed through training alone when enterprises lack financial resources to implement new knowledge. Environmental volatility cannot be managed through crisis response alone when businesses lack integrated support systems that build resilience over time.

The analysis reveals that effective SME development requires recognition that individual challenges are symptoms of a deeper systemic problem: the fragmentation of support services that treats interconnected problems as separate issues. This diagnostic points toward integrated service delivery as the only approach capable of addressing the systemic nature of SME development challenges in Ghana's context.

1.1.3 Risk Management as a Core Challenge for SMEs

Beyond the individual challenges already identified, a fundamental issue facing Ghanaian SMEs is their vulnerability to business volatility and inadequate risk management capabilities. Research across developing economies reveals that SMEs exhibit highly heterogeneous risk-return profiles that conventional support systems fail to address effectively (Verbano & Venturini, 2013). This heterogeneity manifests in significantly different business volatility patterns, with standard deviation of

return on sales varying widely across firms that may appear superficially similar in size or sector (Hudáková, 2019).

The vulnerability of SMEs to external shocks has become increasingly apparent in recent years, particularly as businesses face unprecedented challenges from multiple simultaneous sources. Climate change impacts have created new operational uncertainties that traditional business planning approaches struggle to accommodate (Hussain, Salia, & Scott, 2023; Tollefson, 2022). These environmental pressures intersect with geopolitical disruptions that have reshaped global supply chains and market access patterns (Nazareno et al., 2021; World Food Programme, 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic further demonstrated how quickly external events can overwhelm business resilience mechanisms, forcing enterprises to adapt to conditions for which they had no preparation framework (Paddison, 2023; World Bank, 2022a).

The interconnected nature of the global economy has amplified the impact of these shocks, creating cascading effects that reach even locally-focused SMEs through supply chain disruptions, demand volatility, and input cost fluctuations. International economic relationships that once provided stability now transmit instability across borders with unprecedented speed (Africa Renewal, 2022; OECD, 2023). This reality has transformed risk management from a peripheral business concern into a core competency requirement for SME survival (KPMG, 2023).

The state of the Ghanaian economy within the period under review compounds these challenges significantly, creating a particularly demanding environment for SME operations. High inflation rates have increased operational costs while simultaneously reducing purchasing power and profit margins, forcing businesses into defensive strategies that limit growth opportunities (Ashogbon et al., 2022). Currency depreciation has made imported inputs more expensive while creating uncertainty about future cost structures. Rising interest rates have increased borrowing costs precisely when businesses need financial flexibility to navigate volatile conditions. This combination of pressures has forced many enterprises to implement drastic measures, including downsizing, production cuts, or complete closure, resulting in job losses and reduced economic activity.

The inability of SMEs to effectively manage this volatility represents a critical constraint on their performance and sustainability that extends far beyond simple operational challenges. Business volatility directly influences profitability patterns in ways that traditional accounting metrics often fail to capture (Henschel, 2009). Enterprises experiencing high variability in returns face fundamentally different strategic challenges than those with stable performance patterns, yet conventional support programs typically ignore these differences in risk profiles (Calvo-Mora et al., 2016). This oversight becomes particularly problematic when considering that risk management capabilities directly determine loan repayment capacity and long-term growth potential.

Traditional approaches to SME support have largely overlooked risk management as a central pathway linking interventions to outcomes, focusing instead on isolated aspects of business performance without addressing the underlying risk drivers. This approach misses the fundamental insight that sustainable business improvement requires systematic volatility reduction alongside performance enhancement. Financial institutions assess creditworthiness based on risk profiles, yet business development programs rarely address the risk management capabilities that influence those profiles (Smit & Watkins, 2012). Training programs focus on skill development without addressing how those skills can be applied under volatile conditions. Credit programs provide capital without ensuring that businesses have the risk management frameworks necessary to deploy that capital effectively across different economic scenarios.

Evidence suggests that SMEs cluster into distinct risk-return profiles requiring fundamentally different support approaches, yet conventional interventions typically apply standardized solutions across these diverse segments. High-risk, low-profitability enterprises face substantially different challenges than their low-risk, high-profitability counterparts, including different optimal financing structures, different training priorities, and different implementation timelines for business improvements (Verbano & Venturini, 2013). The resulting mismatch between support provision and risk management needs has

contributed to the limited effectiveness of existing interventions, explaining why well-funded programs often fail to produce measurable improvements in business performance.

Furthermore, the relationship between risk management and loan repayment has received insufficient attention in support program design, despite evidence that this relationship is fundamental to sustainable credit provision. Repayment patterns vary dramatically across different SME risk profiles, with high-volatility businesses exhibiting fundamentally different repayment behaviours compared to more stable enterprises (Baidoo et al., 2020). Understanding these patterns becomes crucial for designing credit terms that align with business realities rather than imposing uniform repayment schedules that may be inappropriate for specific risk profiles (Smit & Watkins, 2012). This relationship between business volatility and repayment sustainability shows the need for risk-based approaches to both credit structuring and business development support.

The integration of customized credit and participatory business development services presents a potential paradigm shift in addressing these risk management challenges by conceptualizing integration as a systematic risk reduction mechanism rather than merely an operational enhancement. This approach directly addresses the business volatility that undermines SME performance and sustainability, recognizing that effective support must simultaneously reduce risk exposure while building risk management capabilities. The risk-centered perspective becomes particularly critical when considering the multidimensional challenges currently facing Ghanaian SMEs, from macroeconomic instability to supply chain disruptions and market volatility. These challenges require support approaches that can adapt to changing risk profiles while maintaining effectiveness across different economic conditions, suggesting that integration represents not just an improvement over traditional approaches but a fundamental requirement for effective SME development in contemporary Ghana.

1.1.4 Role of Credit and BDS in SMEs Development

The critical role of credit and business development services in SME growth and sustainability cannot be overstated. These twin pillars of support provide essential resources and capabilities that enable SMEs to start, expand, and diversify their operations. While credit provides the necessary financial foundation, BDS offers the non-financial support crucial for enhancing business skills, operational performance, and competitive positioning (OECD, 2015).

The significance of credit in SME growth is supported by substantial empirical evidence. World Bank (2023) research demonstrates that a 10% increase in the credit-to-GDP ratio correlates with a 1.4% increase in GDP per capita growth in developing countries. This relationship shows the catalytic role of credit in economic development. Further evidence from the International Finance Corporation (2017) reveals a stark financing gap, with 40% of formal SMEs in developing countries facing an unmet financing need of \$5.2 trillion annually. The African Development Bank's findings reinforce this reality, identifying access to finance as the primary constraint for 41% of African SMEs (African Development Bank Group, 2019a).

The importance of BDS in supporting SME development is equally well-documented. Research by the OECD (2015) depicts that effective BDS can significantly improve SME survival rates, sales growth, employment generation, and innovation capacity. These findings align with Anjorin et al. (2024) observations that BDS raises profitability and enhances growth and competitiveness of enterprises, directly impacting income levels. The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development highlights BDS's role in addressing market failures, including information asymmetry, externalities, and coordination problems (United Nations, 2023).

The International Labour Organization's research further emphasizes BDS's contribution to creating decent jobs, reducing poverty, and promoting social inclusion (International Labour Organization, 2015). This multifaceted impact of BDS extends beyond individual enterprise performance to broader societal benefits, as noted by Asafo-Adjei (2014) and Addaney et al. (2016).

In Ghana specifically, the current level of BDS provision remains limited relative to the scale of SME need. According to the Ghana Enterprises Agency (2023), approximately 27,569 BDS providers are registered nationally, yet coverage reaches fewer than 15% of active SMEs annually. The measurement of BDS uptake in Ghana is captured through registered BDS provider density and recorded service visits, with formal BDS visits averaging only once per year per enterprise (Ghana Statistical Service, 2023). BDS services in Ghana are primarily provided by government agencies (notably the Ghana Enterprises Agency and the National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme), NGOs, donor-funded programmes, commercial consultancies, and microfinance institutions that bundle advisory services with credit. Despite these providers, the effectiveness of BDS interventions has been mixed: while training-focused programmes improve managerial knowledge, evidence of sustained improvements in profitability and productivity remains limited (Shemwell, 2019; Barungi, 2017). This gap between provision and impact provides the principal motivation for examining integrated credit-BDS delivery as an alternative risk management mechanism.

1.1.5 Integrating Customised Credit and Participatory BDS

Despite numerous interventions by governments, NGOs, and private organizations to support SMEs through training and business development services, the impact has often fallen short of expectations. Research indicates that while training programs may enhance knowledge and skills, they don't necessarily translate into improved business performance or growth (Akoto-Sampong, 2011). This disconnect reveals a fundamental flaw in conventional service delivery approaches that treat knowledge transfer and capital provision as separate, sequential processes rather than integrated, mutually reinforcing activities.

Traditional BDS approaches like mentoring, coaching, and consulting often provide temporary solutions without addressing fundamental structural constraints (Husar, 2023). As said earlier, the limitation stems from what can be termed "intervention discontinuity" - isolated training sessions that lack ongoing implementation support and monitoring mechanisms. Effective business development requires sustained engagement that extends beyond initial knowledge transfer to include practical application guidance and performance monitoring (Boyle, 2018; Murith & Umunna, 2021).

The concept of integrating customized credit with participatory BDS represents a paradigm shift in addressing SME challenges in Ghana. This integrated approach involves tailoring financial products to meet specific SME needs, considering factors such as business size, industry characteristics, and risk profiles. Such customization can help alleviate the financial burden of high interest rates and excessive charges, enabling SMEs to channel more resources toward growth and operational excellence (McDaniels & Robins, 2017).

The participatory dimension of BDS provision transforms conventional training methodologies by establishing ongoing guidance systems that ensure knowledge application rather than mere acquisition. This approach moves beyond sporadic workshops to create sustained relationships between service providers and SMEs (Harvard Business Review, 2021; Harvard Business School, 2020). Contemporary research emphasizes the importance of monitoring and evaluation systems that track implementation progress and adjust support strategies based on real-world application challenges (Nkosi, 2023; Partner, 2023a).

Effective participatory BDS creates collaborative frameworks that address the inadequacy of existing support mechanisms through sustained engagement rather than one-time interventions. This collaborative approach, as emphasized by recent studies, fosters ongoing relationships between BDS providers and SMEs that extend far beyond traditional consultant-client interactions (van Scheers & Makhitha, 2016; Victor, Senyo, Patronella, Robert, & Ameh, 2023). Such relationships enable continuous adaptation of support strategies based on evolving business needs and market conditions, creating dynamic assistance frameworks rather than static intervention models (Barungi, 2017).

1.2 Problem Statement

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) play a fundamental role in Africa's economic development, serving as primary drivers of employment generation, innovation, and community economic activity (Business Day, 2018). However, despite their essential economic function, SMEs across the continent face significant operational challenges that limit their growth potential and threaten their sustainability (African Association of Entrepreneurs, 2022; Asgary et al., 2020; Augustine, 2022; Cooper, 2023; OECD, 2022).

A critical issue emerges in the relationship between SMEs and financial institutions, where high interest rates create substantial financial burdens that complicate enterprises' ability to generate sustainable profits (Ashogbon et al., 2022; Ford, 2023; Kisseih, 2017; Pettinger, 2023; Staff, 2016; Young, 2021). This burden is compounded by substantial loan processing charges that erode scarce financial resources (Abor & Quartey, 2010).

The business development services landscape presents additional complexities. While providers offer SME support, services often manifest as infrequent training sessions rather than comprehensive assistance programs. This conventional approach prioritizes loan collection over holistic business needs across strategic planning, operational efficiency, and market expansion. Research suggests this shortfall in targeted support may exacerbate challenges SMEs face in utilizing borrowed capital effectively (Dauda & Nyarko, 2014; Agbozo & Yeboah, 2015).

In Ghana's context, banks demonstrate reluctance to fund SMEs, particularly start-ups, with credit provision typically limited to established enterprises (World Bank, 2022c). This creates significant financing gaps during crucial early-stage development. The situation is complicated by weak institutional frameworks and inadequate support mechanisms (Freeman & Nick, 2015).

External pressures from climate change, geopolitical upheavals, and pandemic impacts have exposed SME vulnerability to forces beyond their direct control (Juergensen et al., 2020; World Bank, 2019). These challenges raise questions about whether current approaches to credit and business development service delivery adequately address the complex, interconnected nature of SME development constraints.

This study therefore seeks to examine the integration of customized credit with participatory BDS as a risk management tool to address these multifaceted challenges while promoting sustainable SME and overall economic development in Ghana.

1.3 Research Objectives and Rationale

The integration of customized credit and participatory Business Development Services represents a potentially transformative approach to SME development in Ghana. This study aims to provide empirical evidence on how such integration affects enterprise-level outcomes and broader economic development indicators, while introducing an innovative framework for implementation through Integrated Service Officers.

The rationale for this study is rooted in three key observations from the Ghanaian context:

First, the limitations of traditional separate service delivery approaches have become increasingly apparent. While standalone credit and BDS services are widely available, empirical evidence suggests they may impede rather than facilitate SME development. Research by Ayyagari et al. (2021) and Grimm et al. (2015) documents that fragmented, uncoordinated credit and training interventions can increase repayment burdens and operational complexity for SMEs, ultimately constraining rather than enabling growth.

Second, the need for customized approaches based on firm characteristics has emerged as a critical consideration. The diversity of SMEs in terms of risk profiles, return patterns, and operational capabilities necessitates moving beyond one-size-fits-all support mechanisms toward more tailored interventions.

Third, the potential for integrated service delivery to simultaneously address multiple development objectives - from firm-level performance to broader economic development - warrants systematic investigation. This potential for synergistic benefits has significant implications for policy design and implementation.

The study pursues four interconnected objectives:

1. To examine the differential impacts of separate versus integrated credit and business development services on SMEs' profitability in Ghana.
2. To investigate how service delivery approaches affect loan repayment patterns.
3. To evaluate the impact of different service delivery approaches on economic development through multiple complementary measures:
 - ✚ Human Development Index (HDI)
 - ✚ Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI)
 - ✚ Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)
4. To develop a practical framework for implementing integrated service delivery as a risk management tool through:
 - ❖ Risk-return based customization of credit terms
 - ❖ Deployment of Integrated Service Officers
 - ❖ Sustainable knowledge transfer mechanisms

1.4 Research Hypotheses

Based on theoretical considerations and preliminary evidence, the study tests three primary hypotheses:

H₁: Profitability Outcomes of Integrated Service Delivery

Null Hypothesis (H₁₀): There is no statistically significant difference in profitability outcomes between integrated and separate service delivery approaches.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): The integration of customized credit and participatory business development services (BDS) yields significantly more profitability outcomes for SMEs compared to standalone service delivery models.

H₂: Loan Repayment Sustainability

Null Hypothesis (H₂₀): No statistically significant difference exists in repayment sustainability between integrated and non-integrated delivery models.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₂): Integrated credit-BDS delivery models generate significantly more sustainable loan repayment patterns among SMEs than traditional disaggregated service approaches.

H₃: Multidimensional Development Impacts

Null Hypothesis (H₃₀): Integrated and non-integrated service approaches demonstrate no statistically significant differences in their impacts on composite development indices.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₃): Integrated service delivery produces significantly better economic development outcomes across multiple dimensions, as measured by the Human Development Index (HDI), Inequality-adjusted HDI (IHDI), and Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI).

1.5 Scope of study

This study focuses on SME development in Ghana, examining the integration of customised credit and participatory Business Development Services (BDS) as a systematic risk management tool. The study is bounded by three principal dimensions: geographical scope (Ghana), sector scope (formally registered SMEs with 5–199 employees spanning manufacturing, services, and trade), and temporal scope (primary survey data from 2022–2023 and macroeconomic secondary data spanning 1970–2023). The analysis operates at two complementary levels: firm-level performance outcomes (profitability and loan repayment) and macro-level economic development impacts measured through the Human Development Index (HDI), Inequality-adjusted HDI (iHDI), and Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). The study is limited to effects observable within these time frames and does not extend to experimental or longitudinal tracking of integrated service outcomes, as the integrated service model proposed is novel and untested in practice. Detailed data descriptions, sample characteristics, and variable definitions are presented in Chapter Four (Research Methodology).

The enterprise-level component draws on primary survey data from 375 SMEs across Ghana's ten administrative regions (2022–2023), spanning manufacturing, services, and trade sectors. The macroeconomic component uses secondary data from 1970–2023. Summary statistics, variable definitions, and data sources are presented in detail in Chapter Four.

1.6 Organization of the Research

The rest of the thesis is structured as follows.

Chapter Two: Literature Review critically examines the theoretical underpinnings of the study, synthesizing existing scholarship on SME development with particular attention to the Ghanaian context. It analyses contemporary credit and business development service (BDS) frameworks, establishing the conceptual basis for the research.

Building on this foundation, Chapter Three: Empirical Review systematically synthesizes prior empirical evidence, evaluating previous research findings to identify critical gaps in current understanding. This chapter serves as a pivotal bridge between existing knowledge and the original contributions of the present study.

Chapter Four: Research Methodology provides a comprehensive exposition of the study's design and execution. It details the research methodology, including data sources, collection procedures, and analytical frameworks. The chapter presents both theoretical and econometric models, with particular attention to the development and application of Integrated services as a risk management tool.

The empirical heart of the thesis unfolds in Chapter Five: Results and Discussion, which presents a rigorous analysis of findings across four key dimensions: SME performance (with focus on profitability metrics), repayment rate dynamics, firm-level risk-return clustering (analysed through standard deviation and return-on-sales measures), and broader economic development impacts (assessed through HDI, IHDI, and MPI indicators).

Chapter Six: Discussion deepens the analytical engagement by examining the implications of these findings. It explores relationships between critical variables, situates results within existing theoretical frameworks, and proposes a practical implementation framework for integrated service delivery models in Ghana's SME sector.

The thesis concludes with Chapter Seven: Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations, which synthesizes key insights, draws substantive conclusions, and offers targeted policy recommendations. It concludes by identifying productive avenues for future research to extend the study's contributions.

This organizational structure ensures methodical progression from theoretical foundations through empirical analysis to practical applications, while maintaining rigorous academic standards and contextual relevance to Ghana's SME development challenges.

CHAPTER TWO

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.0 Introduction

This chapter establishes the conceptual foundations essential for understanding the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services (BDS) for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana. The chapter systematically examines key definitions and concepts, beginning with SMEs and their characteristics within the Ghanaian context, before exploring the multidimensional constraints they face including taxation, regulatory challenges, competition, and credit access barriers. It then introduces risk management concepts and examines both credit and business development services as intervention mechanisms, ultimately revealing the fundamental limitations of current fragmented approaches. Through this comprehensive conceptual mapping, the chapter establishes the analytical foundation for understanding why isolated interventions have failed to adequately address SME development challenges, thereby justifying the need for integrated approaches that combine financial and non-financial support.

2.1 Definition of Concepts

2.1.1 Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SME)

(i) Defining SMEs: The Challenge of Uniformity

Small and medium enterprises are businesses that operate independently and typically hold limited market share. These businesses are usually managed by their founders and partners. Because SMEs vary significantly in form and size, establishing a uniform definition remains challenging (Margaretha & Supartika, 2016). Their diverse operational modes and business approaches create difficulties in developing a single, universally accepted definition of SMEs.

The absence of a globally accepted SME definition stems from variations in key metrics across different firms and economies. According to recent analyses by Freeman and Nick (2015), differences in sales volumes, employee numbers, and business capitalization make it difficult to establish a standardized definition. Definitions using net worth, profitability, turnover, or employee count may categorize businesses differently depending on the economic sector or market context being examined.

Employment figures remain the most appropriate defining characteristic given the heterogeneity of enterprises in this sector, as employment data is consistently available and accessible to those requiring SME classification information (World Bank, 2018).

SME Definitions in Ghana

Employee-Based Classifications

Ghana's official SME definitions primarily rely on employee numbers. The Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), in collaboration with UNDP and the World Bank, defines businesses based on workforce size: micro enterprises employ 1-5 people, small enterprises employ 6-30 people, medium enterprises employ 31-100 people, and large-scale businesses employ over 100 people (Ghana Statistical Service [GSS], UNDP, & World Bank, 2020).

Contemporary research by Dadzie, Fumey, and Namara (2020) provides refined classification systems that align with current economic realities. These classifications recognize the evolution of Ghana's business landscape since earlier definitional frameworks. The Regional Project on Enterprise Development continues to influence current categorizations: micro-enterprise (less than 5 employees), small enterprise (5-29 employees), medium enterprise (30-99 employees), and large enterprise (100+ employees).

The prevalence of family-based employment in Ghana creates unique classification challenges. Recent studies demonstrate that SMEs frequently employ relatives and friends, often without formal compensation, making it difficult to separate ownership from management and limiting the number of paid employees (World Bank, 2018).

Asset-Based Classifications

The National Board for Small-Scale Industries (NBSSI) employs a dual criterion combining employee numbers and fixed asset values. Under current definitions, small-scale enterprises have fewer than nine employees and plant and machinery worth no more than ten million Ghana cedis (excluding vehicles, buildings, and land). The Ghana Enterprise Development Commission (GEDC) similarly uses updated benchmarks that reflect contemporary economic conditions.

However, asset-based definitions face significant challenges in rapidly changing economies. Current research emphasizes that asset valuation methods vary substantially, and continuous local currency fluctuations against major trading currencies render such definitions quickly outdated (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020).

SME Categories by Location and Organization

Urban Enterprise Classifications

Contemporary Ghanaian SMEs can be broadly categorized into urban and rural enterprises, with urban enterprises further dividing into "organized" and "unorganized" categories (World Bank, 2018).

Organized enterprises maintain formal employment structures with paid employees and registered offices that facilitate easy location and contact. These businesses operate with proper documentation and formal business structures, increasingly supported by digital registration systems.

Unorganized enterprises include artisans operating in open spaces, shops, kiosks, temporary wooden structures, or home-based locations. These typically employ few workers, often providing poor compensation or no payment at all. Recent analysis shows that the largest employment category within unorganized enterprises consists of working proprietors, comprising more than half the SME workforce in most developing countries (Symbiotics, 2017). Family members, who are usually unpaid but active in the enterprise, constitute roughly another quarter of the workforce.

Rural Enterprise Characteristics

Rural enterprises predominantly consist of family groups, individual artisans, and women engaged in food production from local crops (Zeidy, 2020). Among the major activities in this sector are soap and cleaning products, fabrics, clothing and tailoring, textiles and leather, village blacksmiths, tin smithing, ceramic materials, wood products and mining, food & beverages, bakeries, wood furniture, electronic repairs, agricultural processing, chemical-based products, and mechanics. Others were mentioned in a separate study, as SMEs engage in a wide variety of activities in both the formal and informal sections. Typical industries include food processing, eateries, chop bars, kiosk operators, roadside vendors, coco vendors, Waakye vendors, Kenkey vendors, and other agro-based industries, tailoring, bakeries, timber industries, shoemaking, and shoe repairs, metal manufacturing and repair, plumbers and electricians, motor fitting and body panels repairs, electronic repairs, black and gold-smiting, pottery, printing, and pharmacy shops, among others (Ayarakwa, 2020).

SME Adaptability and Economic Resilience

Resource Utilization and Market Adaptation

Rural SMEs show particular resilience through their reliance on locally sourced resources, reducing dependence on volatile foreign exchange markets (Freeman & Nick, 2015). Their flexibility enables

rapid adaptation to customer needs and market changes. This adaptability allows SMEs to weather adverse economic conditions and thrive in environments where larger firms struggle to survive.

Evidence of this resilience emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic, when 79% of new SMEs remained operational after lockdown measures in Ghana (GSS et al., 2020). SMEs serve as major contributors to employment growth, particularly during economic uncertainties, as demonstrated by their performance during recent global economic challenges (McDaniels & Robins, 2017).

Ownership Demographics and Social Impact

The majority of MSMEs in Ghana are firmly centred on the owner-managers, rather than operating as a distinct corporate structure. Often, decision-making is more subjective, and employer-employee interactions are mainly informal (Ayrakwa, 2020).

Female entrepreneurs and youth dominate Ghana's SME landscape, with recent studies confirming this demographic dominance (Dadzie, Fumey, and Namara, 2020). The majority of SMEs are female-owned businesses, typically home-based operations that were historically excluded from official statistics but are increasingly recognized in formal data collection systems.

Ghana's youth population (ages 15-35) represents approximately 48% of the total population. Contemporary research reveals that young people own almost 40% of small-scale enterprises, reflecting both opportunity and necessity entrepreneurship (Alliance for Financial Inclusion [AFI], 2020). This high youth participation in entrepreneurship reflects limited formal employment opportunities, as civil and public services combined employ only 8.4% of youth.

The educational system annually releases about 210,000 unemployed or underemployed young Ghanaians into the labor market, including approximately 60% of graduates at various education levels and early school leavers (Dadzie et al., 2020). Many of these individuals establish SMEs, forming a significant portion of the enterprise sector and driving innovation in digital and service-based businesses.

Economic Significance and Development Impact

National and Regional Contributions

SMEs constitute approximately 92% of businesses in Ghana and account for about 60% of private sector employment (World Bank, 2018). Globally, more than 95% of enterprises in OECD countries are classified as SMEs. In low and middle-income nations, SMEs contribute substantially to gross domestic product (GDP) and unemployment reduction, with their significance growing in the post-pandemic economic recovery (OECD, 2019).

SMEs are estimated to contribute about 70% of Ghana's GDP annually and serve as catalysts for both inter and intra-regional decentralization. They function as "prolific job creators, the seeds of big businesses and the fuel of national economic engines," with particular importance in emerging market economies (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020). Approximately 1.7 million of the projected 2.1 million companies in Ghana's MSME sector currently fall within the micro - enterprises category. These companies employ about 2.5 million individuals (or 30% of total MSME workers), indicating that each micro company creates a mean of 1-2 jobs. At the next level, small enterprises account for 15% of all SMEs, with approximately 320,000 companies accounting for 23% of all MSME employment (1.9 million employees). This equates to an average of six employment generated per small business. Finally, at the apex of the pyramid, roughly 85,000 medium-sized businesses account for 4% of all SMEs but account for 47% of overall MSME employment (about 3.9

million jobs). This equates to an average of roughly 46 new employment per medium-sized business (Ministry of Industry and Industry, 2019).

Recent analysis emphasizes SMEs' role in fostering innovation for sustainable development, particularly within G7 and emerging economies (McDaniels & Robins, 2017). They provide essential customer bases for larger companies across supply chains while supplying vital goods and services to companies and households.

Continental Integration Opportunities

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) headquarters location in Accra, Ghana, presents significant opportunities for SME growth and market expansion. The government leverages this positioning to enhance SME opportunities, facilitate growth, and connect Ghanaian enterprises to broader African markets (Oxford Business Group [OBG], 2020).

The AfCFTA framework promises to improve Africa's financial industry, providing micro, small, and medium enterprises—which constitute the majority of Africa's economy—with enhanced access to credit services. This improved access should stimulate economic growth and development across the continent (Zeidy, 2020).

The trade agreement particularly benefits rural communities with predominantly informal, women-owned enterprises that traditionally face credit access difficulties. Enhanced financial access across borders could address information asymmetry, reduce collateral requirements, lower transaction costs, and provide multiple sources of long-term investment credit (Osakwe, 2021).

Business Entry and Operational Characteristics

Ease of Entry and Startup Requirements

Entering Ghana's SME sector requires minimal barriers, depending primarily on locally available resources, family business inheritance opportunities, small-scale operations, adapted technology, labor intensiveness, and acquired skills within competitive, largely unregulated markets (Freeman & Nick, 2015).

Entrepreneurs can establish SMEs with modest funding from personal savings, family and friends, government schemes, or NGO programs. This accessibility explains why nine out of ten businesses globally are SMEs (Symbiotics, 2017). Contemporary digital platforms and mobile money systems have further reduced entry barriers, particularly for service-based enterprises.

Formal vs. Informal Operations

SMEs operate through both formal and informal channels, with increasing emphasis on formalization through government initiatives. Formal SMEs complete legal registration processes and maintain regular tax compliance. Informal SMEs operate without proper registration and typically avoid tax obligations. Informal operation remains common in Africa and other developing countries, though digitization efforts are encouraging formalization (World Bank, 2018).

Ghana, like many African nations, hosts numerous informal SMEs that require minimal investment and skills to operate. The SME sector accommodates individuals with limited education and training, forming the largest employment base and serving as the foundation of the local private sector. Recent initiatives focus on supporting these enterprises' transition to formal operations through simplified registration processes and digital payment systems.

Policy Recognition and Support Frameworks

Governments worldwide including Ghana prioritize small and medium-scale enterprises in their policy frameworks, recognizing SMEs as solutions to unemployment, vehicles for inclusive economic growth, instruments for income enhancement, production contributors, and competitiveness improvers (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020).

The SME sector represents one of the fastest-growing economic segments with substantial opportunities for financial institutions and service providers, particularly in the context of post-pandemic economic recovery (OECD, 2019). The unique characteristics of SMEs make them essential economic components that generate positive employment effects, increase goods and services supply, promote market competition, and perform other vital economic functions (Belás, Vojtovič, & Ključnikov, 2016).

(ii) Constraints and Challenges Facing SMEs

Small and medium scale enterprises contribute a lot to the economic development of Ghana in terms of economic growth, stability of income, employment and reduction in poverty in Ghana. Despite the above importance and contribution of SMEs to the Ghanaian economy, these businesses are not doing well as they are folding up every day because of many challenges that they cannot surmount (Boateng & Asiedu, 2025). As has been shown by many pieces of literature many issues pose challenges to the growth and development of SMEs in Africa. (Khan and Anuar 2018)

(a) Tax Regimes

Many challenges face SMEs in Ghana, with high taxation being particularly burdensome. Ghana's corporate income tax rate is 25% for companies with annual turnover exceeding GHS 500,000, while smaller enterprises pay 20% (Ghana Revenue Authority, 2020). Combined with VAT of 15%, National Health Insurance Levy of 2.5%, and various local taxes, SMEs face an effective tax rate of 35-40% compared to the sub-Saharan African average of 32% (McDaniels & Robins, 2017; OECD, 2019). Tax compliance costs represent 3-5% of annual turnover for SMEs versus less than 1% for larger corporations, with quarterly VAT filing consuming 120 hours annually per enterprise (World Bank, 2018; Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2020). The complexity of Ghana's regulatory environment compounds tax compliance challenges, as SMEs must navigate overlapping requirements from multiple agencies while maintaining adequate records for both tax and regulatory purposes (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020).

Despite limited government support through credit and training programs, heavy taxation persists. Many SMEs experience double taxation through overlapping municipal and national requirements, with business operating permits costing GHS 200-2,000 annually (GSS et al., 2020). Research shows 73% of SME owners lack adequate understanding of tax obligations, leading to penalties that increase effective tax rates beyond 45% for some enterprises (Symbiotics, 2017). When businesses fail to file returns, they face closure or penalties, creating additional operational stress.

Tax documentation requirements severely limit credit access, as financial institutions require three years of tax returns for loan applications. However, only 42% of Ghanaian SMEs maintain complete tax records, effectively excluding the majority from formal credit markets (Fouejieu, Ndoeye, & Sydorenko, 2020). Government tax incentives and streamlined systems could encourage formalization and

productivity growth. Recent initiatives include simplified 3% flat rates for micro-enterprises with turnover below GHS 200,000, though implementation challenges limit impact (Ghana Revenue Authority, 2020). Effective tax reform integrating mobile money platforms has reduced transaction costs, but the underlying burden remains a fundamental constraint on SME profitability and growth across Ghana's economy (OECD, 2019).

(b) Competition

Competition in Ghana's SME sector presents both opportunities and challenges, requiring strategic responses rather than avoidance. For SMEs to thrive in competitive environments, they must develop resilience through focused strategies and technological investments. Survival depends on strategic clarity and technological capabilities, as competitive advantage determines long-term sustainability (Gunasekaran, Rai, & Griffin, 2011). Research demonstrates that competition has a significant positive relationship with SME performance, with higher competitive advantage correlating directly with superior performance and growth (Sitharam & Hoque, 2016a).

Intense domestic competition, while challenging, drives innovation and efficiency improvements. In Ghana, competition spans multiple dimensions: Nigerian businesses operating locally create market pressures that force Ghanaian SMEs to enhance their competitive positioning through improved service delivery, pricing strategies, and customer relationships. Studies show that competition reduces the SME financial inclusion gap when combined with improved credit information and enhanced business environments (Fouejieu, Ndoye, & Sydorenko, 2020). However, unhealthy copying behaviors among Ghanaian entrepreneurs limit innovation, as businesses replicate existing models rather than developing unique value propositions (World Bank, 2018). Financial service provider competition particularly benefits SMEs through reduced charges and improved access terms.

Female entrepreneurs face distinct competitive challenges that require targeted research attention and policy responses. Women in developing countries encounter obstacles that differ substantially from their male counterparts, yet demonstrate superior resilience and loan repayment performance (Nziku & Struthers, 2018). Research consistently shows women achieve better credit repayment rates than men, yet face systematic discrimination in loan sizes and approval processes. Gender-based competition disadvantages stem from limited access to networks, collateral constraints, and social-cultural barriers that restrict market participation (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2020). Despite these challenges, women-owned SMEs employ more labor than male-owned counterparts and demonstrate stronger crisis recovery capabilities. Studies reveal that addressing gender-specific competitive barriers through targeted support programs significantly improves overall market efficiency and economic development outcomes (McDaniels & Robins, 2017). Enhanced competition among financial service providers specifically benefits women entrepreneurs through reduced discrimination and improved product design tailored to their business patterns and risk profiles.

(c) Credit and Credit Conditions

Credit access remains the primary constraint facing SME owners globally, with complex conditions determining availability and terms. Research demonstrates that credit is more beneficial than internally generated funds, with substitution effects showing that external credit supply significantly enhances firm productivity compared to internal finance alone (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020). SME credit access depends on multiple factors including business size, with larger

enterprises accessing credit more easily than smaller ones due to reduced information asymmetry and stronger collateral positions (World Bank, 2018). When SMEs cannot access required credit, growth becomes severely limited, forcing reliance on inadequate internal funding that constrains expansion and competitiveness. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted this vulnerability, as SMEs required external financing for day-to-day operations and long-term investment when internal cash flows became insufficient (OECD, 2021).

Credit constraints manifest through several mechanisms that disproportionately affect smaller enterprises. Firm characteristics significantly influence credit approval, with factors including location, registration status, bank relationships, audited financial statements, innovation levels, and land ownership determining access outcomes (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2020). Research shows credit-constrained firms face significantly higher business failure rates than non-constrained enterprises, making credit access among the most important predictors of SME survival (McDaniels & Robins, 2017). Countries with high private credit-to-GDP ratios demonstrate superior SME credit access, while nations with underdeveloped financial markets struggle to serve smaller enterprises effectively. The emergence of fintech solutions has begun addressing these gaps through alternative credit scoring, mobile lending platforms, and blockchain-based financing that reduce traditional barriers while expanding access to previously excluded SMEs (Symbiotics, 2017).

The diversity of credit sources reflects both opportunities and limitations in SME financing ecosystems. Traditional bank lending remains constrained by high transaction costs, inadequate risk assessment methodologies, and preference for larger, established clients with substantial collateral (Fouejieu, Ndoye, & Sydorenko, 2020). However, innovative financing mechanisms including trade credit, mobile money-based lending, crowdfunding, and government-backed guarantee schemes are expanding options for SMEs previously excluded from formal credit markets. Digital financial services particularly benefit women and youth entrepreneurs who face additional barriers in traditional banking systems, with mobile money platforms enabling microcredit delivery at reduced costs and simplified procedures (GSS et al., 2020). Despite these innovations, fundamental challenges persist in developing countries where weak regulatory frameworks, limited credit infrastructure, and inadequate financial literacy continue constraining SME access to appropriate financing for growth and sustainability.

(d) Poor Infrastructure

Infrastructure deficiencies create differential impacts across SME sectors, with manufacturing and agricultural enterprises facing more severe constraints than service-based businesses. While electricity supply instability remains problematic in sub-Saharan Africa, affecting production continuity and forcing costly alternative energy investments, the impact on financial services has diminished significantly due to mobile money platforms and internet-based banking solutions (World Bank, 2018). Manufacturing SMEs typically invest 15-20% of operational costs in backup power systems, while agricultural enterprises face transportation challenges that increase product delivery costs by 25-35% in rural areas (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2020). However, digital financial services have largely circumvented traditional infrastructure limitations, enabling credit access and payment systems through mobile networks that require minimal physical infrastructure compared to traditional banking branches (Fouejieu, Ndoye, & Sydorenko, 2020).

The emergence of digital infrastructure has fundamentally altered how infrastructure constraints affect SME financing and operations. Mobile money services now reach over 80% of Ghana's adult

population, reducing dependence on physical bank branches and enabling financial inclusion in areas with limited traditional infrastructure (GSS et al., 2020). While rural SMEs continue facing challenges with road networks and utility costs that can consume 20-30% of revenue, fintech innovations have created alternative pathways for accessing credit, making payments, and maintaining business relationships that bypass traditional infrastructure requirements (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020). Contemporary SME support programs increasingly leverage digital platforms to deliver business development services and credit assessment, demonstrating how technological solutions can mitigate infrastructure deficiencies that previously excluded enterprises from formal economic participation (OECD, 2019).

(e) The COVID-19 Pandemic and SME Operations

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly amplified existing SME constraints while creating new challenges for credit access and business operations across multiple countries. In Ghana, 57% of businesses closed during the first partial lockdown, with 16.1% remaining closed after restrictions relaxed, particularly affecting accommodation and food services where 24% of establishments closed permanently (GSS et al., 2020). Revenue declined by 60.6% across trading and manufacturing SMEs, representing approximately 115.2 million Ghana cedis in lost income, while 46.1% of businesses reduced employee wages and 1.4% laid off workers totalling 41,952 employees. The pandemic's global impact included widespread business closures, reduced demand for exports, decreased foreign remittances, and increased unemployment, creating liquidity problems and loan covenant breaches (Hekkenberg & Medrano-Lazo, 2020). Microcredit institutions faced particular stress with 140 million customers worldwide holding 124 billion USD in outstanding credit, as borrowers struggled with repayment during lockdowns, leading to aggressive collection practices and harassment in countries like Nigeria, India, and Cambodia (Heijmans, Onu, Dzawu, & Ghosh, 2020). SME vulnerability was particularly evident in developing countries, with 25.4% of Ghanaian businesses reporting reduced or eliminated credit access, while international experiences showed similar patterns: in Guinea, 87% of SMEs experienced reduced profits and 80% needed additional working capital (Ferber & Buri, 2020c); in Kenya, 88% of SME owners received no government support (MSC, 2020b); and in Mongolia, smaller businesses were more severely affected than larger enterprises (Mendizabal Joffre & Luvsandorj, 2020).

Government and financial sector responses revealed both limitations of existing SME support systems and innovative approaches to crisis management across different contexts. The Bank of Ghana became the first sub-Saharan African central bank to reduce monetary policy rates from 16% to 14.5%, while implementing reserve requirement reductions and providing a six-month loan repayment moratorium affecting 30% of bank loans, alongside establishing a 100 million Ghana cedi coronavirus relief fund that received 700,000 SME applications (Oxford Business Group, 2020). Digital payment adoption accelerated as transaction fees were reduced for mobile money transfers under 100 Ghana cedis, demonstrating financial innovation's role during crisis periods. International responses varied significantly: India allocated 45 billion USD for social protection programs supporting 33.66 million account holders (MSC, 2020a); Sierra Leone SMEs sought tax breaks and loan restructuring with 81% reporting profit reductions (Ferber & Buri, 2020b); Bangladesh experienced disproportionate impacts on women entrepreneurs (MSC, 2020d); Indonesia faced challenges with digital payment adoption among 60% of businesses reporting sales volume decreases (Pelupessy, Sulastri, Sinaga, & Pandey, 2020); and Lebanon's microfinance sector saw 90% of businesses report sales reductions with 80% of borrowers living below 5.5 USD per day, demonstrating how multiple crises compound SME

vulnerability (CGAP, 2020). In Cambodia, the previously profitable microcredit sector caused social disruption as land seizures increased due to forced loan repayments, highlighting the need for supportive policy frameworks during crises (Bateman, 2020). The crisis showed both SME vulnerability to external shocks and the critical importance of integrated support mechanisms combining financial assistance with capacity building (Zeidy, 2020).

(iii) Risk Profiles and Management for SMEs

The constraints faced by SMEs collectively create a complex risk environment that threatens their survival, growth, and profitability. These challenges manifest as operational risk (e.g., infrastructure limitations), market risk (e.g., competition), financial risk (e.g., credit constraints), and regulatory risk (e.g., compliance burdens). Understanding these risks as interconnected components of business volatility is critical for effective interventions.

Risk management in SMEs involves systematically identifying, assessing, and mitigating uncertainties that threaten business objectives (Coviini, 2020). For Ghanaian SMEs they face acute vulnerability due to limited resources, restricted formal finance access, and heightened uncertainty environments where asymmetric information leads to suboptimal risk assessment practices and over-reliance on informal decision-making rather than structured analysis. Financial risks arise from high-interest loans and collateral requirements (Mamai, 2020), while SMEs demonstrate heterogeneous risk profiles with sectoral differences between agriculture, manufacturing, and services demanding tailored risk management approaches rather than generic solutions. Risk management capacity remains underdeveloped, with Faulkner (2015) finding that 70% of SME owners in developing economies lack formal risk management training, relying instead on intuition, while current practices are reactive with only a minority of SMEs using formal risk assessments (Smit, 2017).

Traditional SME development interventions have treated risk management peripherally, operating credit provision and business development services in isolation despite their potential synergies for comprehensive risk management. While Gbenga et al. (2019) emphasize credit for growth and Addaney et al. (2016) highlight BDS for capacity building, their integration for systematic risk management remains unexplored (Exxere, 2018), creating fragmentation that limits effectiveness. The link between risk management and SME performance is established but mechanisms in developing contexts like Ghana lack clarity (Verhezen, 2018), while financial institutions' standardized risk frameworks fail to capture SME heterogeneity, excluding viable businesses from credit access. Mamai (2020) and Ilogbonyo (2020) advocate sector-specific risk tools to address these gaps, yet implementation challenges include low awareness, high costs, expertise shortages, and absent frameworks (Turgay, 2023) that require collaboration among policymakers, financiers, and SME associations (Winyane, 2022). These gaps in sector-specific risk understanding, empirical validation of approaches, and integration of risk management into BDS and credit programs create significant opportunities for developing frameworks that systematically address SME heterogeneity through coordinated interventions rather than fragmented support mechanisms.

2.1.2 CREDIT

In the financial world, there are different meanings or definitions of credit. The term 'credit' must be operationalized in the context of this study. Credit can be defined in a general term as an agreement for a contract between a deficit unit (borrower) who needs fund and a surplus unit (lender) who has excess funds to exchange the funds now to repay the lender later in the future with an interest (Investopedia 2020).

Credit has also been defined to be a business transaction between two parties (lender and borrower) in which the lender gives the funds to be repaid by the borrower in the future (Encyclopedia Britannica 2020). According to Leotta (n.d), credit as a term came from *credo*, a Latin word that means "I believe"

or "I trust." So credit means a situation in which there is a trust between the lender and the borrower of the funds that the funds will be repaid in a future time that has been agreed. A long time ago when the economies were working on basis that was very simple, "and Biblical prohibitions against usury were taken more seriously, a person would lend money to a friend on trust". Many people were not related or friends who were lending money to others and charged interest on the loans they were giving to those in need of funds. "In the late Middle Ages and early Renaissance, the foundations of the modern banking system developed in Italy. The impersonalization of credit and the availability of investment capital have helped provide the large sums of money necessary for modern business expansion" (Leotta n.d).

SMEs like every other business need credit to finance their operations. Access to finance which is also known as financial inclusion can be referred to as "price and non-price barriers" which hinders the use of financial services not being present. Giving credit to small and medium-scale enterprises has been seen to consume time and comes with a high cost to the financial institutions and the intermediaries. Most of these businesses have been found to lack the proper way of accounting and the fact that the entrepreneurs who own and run the businesses always mix their personal finances with that of the business making it difficult for banks or any lender to trust their statement of financial positions (Nkuah et al. 2013). Business transactions like that also involve interest payment to the lender (banks, etc) who provided the money. The gain involved in this type of transaction has led to the over-commercialization of this relationship between the credit providers and the borrowers. This commercialization has resulted in the fact that the credit providers now give requirements that most SMEs cannot meet up. The conditions are high and tailored according to the perceived riskiness of the SMEs. The traditional concentration of the commercial banks has been on lending to large formal businesses which are perceived as less risky and have the required collaterals. Credit transactions always come with conditions that may make it quite difficult for some people who need funds to get. The interest rates charged by the lender may be too high for the borrower to pay. Many businesses owners may end up not being able to get easy access to the funds that they need for their business transactions.

Many SMEs are not able to access or utilize the credit because of assets or materials that can serve as collateral, the credits come with interest rates that are high which they cannot pay as said earlier, procedures that are complex for getting the credit which includes a lot of paperwork, and the formal institutions reluctance in bearing some cost in assisting the SMEs (Dosunmu and Ogunniyi 2015). These challenges always push back these SME owners to the traditional lenders who reap them off with high interest rates.

When the SMEs cannot get access to the required credit, their growth may be limited. Presently, with the issue of Covid-19 pandemic which has affected every business in the world it means that "Beyond using their existing cash balances, retaining profits and raising new equity, options that are typically limited during a recession caused by the likes of Covid-19 pandemic, borrowing can provide finances for day-to-day financial operations and long-term investment. (Darvas 2014, p. 131).

Many SMEs are not growing well. Many business owners are still marking time without growing up to the next levels. Many business owners in Ghana are still not able to grow from micro-businesses to small businesses and to medium businesses and to large enterprises. This is to attest to the fact that they are many challenges that are limiting the growth of small and medium-scale enterprises. Easy access to specialized credit is among the major challenges that SMEs are facing (Avdeenko et al. 2019, p. v). The authors added that it is not only credit finances that affect SMEs, but skills for the business management that are weak and business practices that are very poor also affect the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises. Shemwell (2019) also added that apart from limited access to credit to invest by the SMEs being the "most serious obstacle to the growth of SMEs, this problem goes a long way in determining the performance of the firms. He went ahead to add that when credit finance is available, the SMEs can fund assets that are productive which will most like lead them to growth, increase in productivity and the employment of new workers as production inputs. Working capital and finance are needed by SMEs to invest in business projects. The terms of the credit need to match the expected returns from the project to enable easy repayment and reduce the default rate. "However, banks in low-income countries generally do not have the appropriate products, and the high transaction costs for

lenders to process, monitor, and enforce small SME loans increase interest rates, making borrowing more expensive or unavailable for SMEs, relative to larger firms” (Shemwell 2019).

Research consistently demonstrates that the primary challenge facing SME owners is not merely access to credit, but access to specialized credit with terms tailored to individual business strengths, weaknesses, and prevailing macroeconomic conditions, with credit demand fundamentally influenced by interest rates that serve as critical determinants of whether SME owners pursue credit facilities, particularly in Ghana where blanket rates ignore core competencies and business size variations (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2020). The inverse relationship between interest rates and credit demand creates significant barriers for SMEs, as higher borrowing costs directly reduce credit utilization regardless of business viability or growth potential (OECD, 2019), creating persistent problems for Ghanaian SMEs despite the original intention of microfinance institutions to serve enterprises unable to meet commercial bank requirements. Currently, microfinance institutions, savings and loan companies, and commercial banks impose high interest rates that fail to reflect individual business risk profiles, applying uniform rates across new and established enterprises without considering operational differences or risk variations (Fouejieu, Ndoeye, & Sydorenko, 2020), demonstrating how financial markets designed to support SME development can become extractive rather than supportive when proper risk assessment and tailored product development are absent (McDaniels & Robins, 2017). Access to credit in this study encompasses funding or loans provided to SMEs by financial institutions, non-financial institutions, and government entities for business operational and development purposes (GSS et al., 2020).

THE NEED FOR CREDIT BY SMEs

For one with little or no wealth (savings or inheritance) to be an entrepreneur, the amount of fund that s/he has should go beyond a threshold ((Sugata and Suryaprakash 2020). When such threshold is not crossed, the ability to start and run a successful business like a small and medium scale enterprise may not be feasible. But the possibility of getting credit from a provider (formal or informal) can go a long way in helping the person to cross the threshold and run a successful SME. So credit is needed by people with ideas to start and run SMEs. Table 2.1 presents key indicators of SME credit needs in Ghana based on recent empirical studies.

Table 2.1: SME Credit Requirements and Utilization Patterns in Ghana

Indicator	Value	Source	Year
Capital Requirements			
Minimum startup capital (micro-enterprises)	GHS 15,000-25,000	Ghana Chamber of SMEs	2023
Minimum startup capital (small enterprises)	GHS 50,000-100,000	Ghana Chamber of SMEs	2023
Credit Utilization Purposes			
Working capital financing (% of applications)	68%	World Bank Enterprise Survey	2022
Equipment/machinery purchase (% of applications)	15%	World Bank Enterprise Survey	2022
Business expansion (% of applications)	17%	World Bank Enterprise Survey	2022
Financing Gap Indicators			

SMEs requiring external financing (%)	65%	Research studies (Domeher et al.)	2014-2023
SMEs denied credit from banks (%)	65%	Bridging SME Gap Study (Kumasi) (Quaye et al.)	2014
SMEs with unmet credit needs (%)	40%	IFC MSME Finance Gap Report	2023
SME Contribution to Economy			
SMEs as % of all businesses	92%	Ghana Chamber of SMEs/Statista	2023
SME contribution to GDP	60%	Ghana Chamber of SMEs/Statista	2023
SME contribution to employment	80%	Ghana Chamber of SMEs/Statista	2023

Compiled: Author, 2025

Once operational, SMEs require continuous credit access for distinct purposes that directly relate to this study's focus on integration. Working capital financing enables daily operations including inventory management, wage payments, and input procurement. Growth capital facilitates expansion through equipment acquisition, technology adoption, and market development, while contingency financing provides buffers against economic shocks (World Bank, 2020).

The relationship between credit purpose and business outcomes provides crucial context for understanding integration benefits. Kibet, Achesa, and Omwono (2015) demonstrated that SMEs utilizing credit for predetermined business purposes showed higher survival rates compared to those without structured credit plans. However, as Dauda and Nyarko (2014) noted, credit alone without proper business management capacity may not translate into improved performance, supporting this study's emphasis on integrated service delivery.

SOURCE OF CREDIT FOR SMES

The gap in financing SMEs can be filled by the SMEs themselves using internally generated fund using the SMEs core business (Freeman and Nick 2015) or by forces outside the SMEs in form of credit or equity. SMEs in Ghana account for over 90% of businesses, engage about 80% of the workforce, and contribute nearly 60% to Ghana's GDP (Business & Financial Times, 2025). However, Ghana faces a significant financing gap for SMEs in Africa, with an estimated \$4.8 billion deficit (Oteng & Patel, 2024); and Stanbic Bank Ghana (2025) estimated the financing gap to be \$5 bilion. This persistent gap means only about half of Ghana's SMEs have ever accessed formal credit (British International Investment Report, 2024). Even when credit is accessed, 75% of it has a tenor shorter than three years. Both internal funds and external funds like credit supplies have an impact on the performance of businesses, with studies showing "there is a substitution effect between internal finance and external credit supply: the marginal effect of internal finance on firm productivity is weaker when firms have sufficient external credit" (Li, Liao, & Zhao, 2018).

SME credit sources are categorized into formal and informal channels, each presenting distinct characteristics that influence accessibility, cost, and repayment terms. The financial services and sources of credit available to SMEs affect the rate at which they can be financially empowered through building assets (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group 2020, p. 7). Understanding these sources is crucial for analyzing their impact on SME profitability and loan repayment capacity.

(i) Informal Lenders

Freeman and Nick (2015) defined informal source of credit as those transfers that happen between two parties which are usually not enforceable because they are not within the framework of regulations of a nation's central bank and authorities in charge of finance. He went ahead to add that informal credit sources are done in a way that users are not protected and the abusers are not protected, and the central bank is thereby constrained in effectively carrying out its regulatory, monetary policy, and financial oversight responsibilities. A study by Watse (2017), shows that the majority of SMEs in developing countries rely on informal sources of credit which are commonly from families, business associates and community leaders. Credit unions and cooperatives that are not registered and recognized by the central banks and regulating agencies have traditionally over the years provided a bulk of the credit to SMEs (World Bank 2018).

This informal credit usually comes from savings, family and friends and loan 'sharks' who are there to exploit the SMEs owners. Money lenders are the most expensive credit source, and SME owners without alternatives usually go to them for credits (Mungiru and Njeru 2015). A study by Dauda and Nyarko (2014) in Ghana shows that friends or family members were the principal sources of funding available for SMEs, though this source is "woefully inadequate as well as insecure." Recent research indicates that when business owners cannot get all the credit that they need for their businesses, they engage in multiple borrowing from different sources (Watse, 2017). In Caribbean countries, informal sources of credit are used to complement formal sources, making the two sources complementary rather than competitive (Multilateral Investment Fund, 2024).

(ii) Formal Lenders (Banks)

Banks are the source of debt-based financing for SMEs (Freeman & Nick, 2015). SMEs do not have many alternatives to bank lending since they cannot have easy access to capital markets directly (European Commission, 2015). Recent World Bank (2024) initiatives have provided over \$3.8 billion in credit lines, reaching more than 20 million MSMEs through various development finance institutions. However, significant challenges persist. Recent developments include the launch of SME credit risk databases by central banks to enhance credit risk evaluation, address information asymmetry, improve loan pricing, and reduce dependence on collateral (BSP, 2025). Despite these improvements, banks continue to miss lending quotas for small businesses, with only 4.63% of total loan portfolios allocated to MSMEs, falling short of the required 10%. Banks are often hesitant to lend to the SME sector largely due to credit history concerns, and banks that do lend to small businesses are only willing to do so at extremely high-interest rates (Dennis, 2018).

Over the years, microfinance banks have been established to cater for SMEs since commercial banks were not serving their interests, thereby creating a huge financing gap. The World Bank's Women Entrepreneurship Development Project in Ethiopia helped participating MFIs increase average loan sizes by 870% to \$11,500 and reduce collateral requirements from 200% to 125% of loan value (World Bank, 2024). The microfinance industry is estimated to have a net worth of about 60 to 100 billion U.S dollars and has continued to grow in the last two decades (World Bank, 2018). Most SMEs depend solely on Microfinance banks for credit as most of them do not have alternatives (Kibet et al., 2015).

(iii) Credit Guarantees

Barungi (2017) defined a credit guarantee as "a financial product that small entrepreneurs can take as a partial substitute for collateral; it is a commitment by a guarantor to pay to the lender all or part of the loan if the borrower defaults." Credit guarantees have grown more popular and widely acceptable as effective SME-friendly tools (Tunahan & Dizkirici, 2012). Recent data shows that more than 79% of bank loans globally are now insured through various guarantee mechanisms, with guaranteed loan amounts exceeding equity financing by more than twice during peak periods (World Bank, 2024).

According to the Alliance for Financial Inclusion (2016), credit guarantee is now widely used and accepted both in developed and developing economies worldwide, implemented in various forms including credit guarantee schemes, credit guarantee funds, and credit guarantee companies. In Bangladesh, the establishment of credit guarantee schemes specifically targets women SMEs, where 60% of financing needs remain unmet primarily due to lack of collateral access (World Bank, 2024). Credit guarantees have the ability to reduce the burden on SME owners from collateral requirements and have the potential of ensuring growth and development of the SME sector in developing countries like Ghana.

(iv) Financial Leasing

Leasing is a form of financial instruments which helps firms in getting equipment, machinery and other fixed assets that they need for their day to day running of businesses in the medium term (Adjei 2012). Apart from credits/loans, SMEs can use leasing to widen and also get easy access to financing in both short and medium terms. When a business is leasing an asset or machinery, the business usually makes an initial payment of a sum of money and continue to make payments periodically as the equipment is being used. After the term of the lease, the business can buy the asset from the lessor after making a payment for a complete purchase. With leasing, SMEs are able to save more funds for business activities that can generate profits in the future (World Bank 2018).

Leasing is a “non-collateral debt products” which is very suitable for SMEs. As many SMEs lack collaterals as security for banks loans, leasing is well suited to solve this problem and assist SME owners (Freeman and Nick 2015, pp. 49–50). Leasing has been found to boost the development and profitability of SMEs in Ghana (Agbozo and Yeboah 2015, p. 2). Freeman and Nick (2015) posited that leasing usually comes with a high cost. The buyout amount and the leasing fees paid periodically always add up to be higher than the actual cost of the equipment if it was bought directly with initial cash. The challenges with leasing have also been noted to be the judicial and legal issues that always arise from the transactions. And also, the fact that many companies do not want to go into the leasing business as the demand from SMEs is low (Grünfeld et al. 2010)

(v) Donor Assistance

Small and medium enterprises, which form the majority of the business base and are significant drivers of both GDP and employment in many developing countries, are popular targets of donor assistance (Shemwell, 2019). The donations are usually to SMEs that are into businesses or activities that align with the objectives, goals or missions of donor agencies. Climate change initiatives have opened opportunities to SMEs in green energy business, as sustainable finance is rising on the agenda as a key tool to deliver the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement on climate change (McDaniels & Robins, 2017).

The financial market of Ghana is not well developed, making it difficult for firms to receive credit, with credits being short term and coming with high interest rates. This has made the government over the years look for alternative financing solutions, pushing government and development partners to seek ways to make credit flow to SMEs easier, especially from the private sector. To get alternative financing sources, the government and development partners have paid attention to informal and semi-formal sources like microfinance banks to meet the high demand for credit by the private sector. This has led to different financing sources in Ghana coming from official schemes and donors like European investment banks, Technoserve funds, Danida and other agencies to help credit flow to small and medium scale enterprises (Owusu, 2012).

(vi) Government Grants and Subsidies

As said earlier, banks in both developed and developing countries are usually reluctant in giving credit/loans to SMEs because they see SMEs as risky and are bound to default on loan repayment; credit facilities like that are usually given to big firms. So in situations, as often seen in developing countries like Ghana where private financing is not adequate, the government gives credit to the SMEs. Government credits have been “particularly important in less developed countries, where they are often the only source of funds available to small farmers at reasonable rates of interest” (Encyclopedia Britannica 2020). The government steps in to lend its support to businesses in form of grants and subsidies.

Constraints and Challenges Facing SMEs in Accessing Credit

In defining credit constraints as faced by firms, Kuntchev et al. (2013) grouped firms into four categories according to their level of credit constraints: Fully Credit Constrained (FCC) which are firms that do not have loans from external sources as a result of the fact that their applications for loans were not accepted or that the business never tried to apply for a loan even though they needed additional funds to invest in the businesses. They did not bother to apply because the terms and conditions of the loan were not favourable. Secondly, Partially Credit Constrained (PCC) which are business groups that eventually got a little of the whole funds that they needed from other external sources that agreed to give them loans or whose terms and conditions were somehow favourable and therefore they are not fully credit constrained. The third group is Maybe Credit Constrained (MCC) which are firms that have had access to external finance and there is evidence of them having bank finance, Are businesses that finance from external sources were accessed by them and evidence shows that they have finance from banks or savings and loans companies; the grouping is “under the possibility of maybe being credit constrained as it is impossible to ascertain whether they were partially rationed on the terms and conditions of their external finance”. And the final group is Non-Credit Constrained (NCC) which includes businesses that the following best describe: “they did not apply for a loan during the previous fiscal year, and The reason for not applying for a loan was having enough capital for the firm’s needs”. They added that “this fourth group can be further divided according to the usage of external finance since this group includes both firms that use external finance and the ones that do not. The important characteristic of this group is that independently of its current level of external finance, these firms are happy with their current financing structure for both working capital and investments”. With this grouping, a 2024 European Central Bank surveys indicate that around 14% of SMEs face significant obstacles for bank finance availability—the highest rate since 2016—due to transmission of monetary policy after COVID crisis and related money supply expansion and inflation.

Credit constraint and access to credit have been seen to be one of the reasons why businesses do not survive. The findings by Mach and Wolken (2011) show that "credit-constrained firms were significantly more likely to go out of business than non-constrained firms," adding that "credit constraint and credit access variables appear to be among the most important factors predicting which small firms went out of business."

(i) Information Asymmetry

“Information asymmetries refer to disparities between the information available to businesses seeking capital and suppliers of capital who are typically assumed to be at an informational disadvantage with respect to insiders of the business” (Quaye et al. 2014). Small and medium enterprises usually do not present the same quality and amount of information that are related to their finances when compared to firms that are owned by the public. “As a result, information on their financial condition, earnings and earnings prospects may be incomplete or inaccurate. Faced with this type of uncertainty, a lender may deny credit, sometimes to firms that are creditworthy but unable to document it” (Barungi 2017; Quaye et al. 2014).

A challenge facing banks that have made it difficult in giving out loans to SMEs is the problem of information that comprise “credit history and probability of repayment” (Shemwell 2019). According to World Bank (2018), “assessing the creditworthiness of small and medium enterprises represents a unique challenge”. It added that when SMEs are compared to big firms, “it can be more difficult for an SME to develop a credit history as they have less access to traditional sources of finance such as banks and other financial institutions whose data is typically used in the production of credit reports.” Gockel and Akoena (2002) cited in Dauda and Nyarko (2014) said “that information asymmetries are a major constraint to the funding of SMEs”. The authors identified “some information asymmetries that constrain SME access to finance the as high cost of obtaining credit information on SME; inconsistent SME financial statements and audits; and lack of access to third party information by providers in the marketplace”.

Market failure gives rise to credit constraints. Because of information asymmetry, financial institutions do not give enough credit/loans to businesses that have nice projects but do not have enough net worth. In a perfect market condition that’s void of information asymmetry, these firms would have got more than they get from the financial institutions. In Brazil, Firms that are fully or partially into export and Listed firms on stock markets are not credit-constrained when compared to some SMEs (Ambrozio et al. 2017, p. 73).

the challenge of getting access to credit is the most important issue for SMEs as a result of the fact they a lot of problems in getting credits from financial institutions, most especially as a result of not having a large quantity of information that they need to give to the financial institutions which they need to process the possibility of a loan amount and the terms. “However, the better the economic condition of an enterprise and the more information about an enterprise available, the easier it is to gain access to bank funding”. Though SMEs are very important when it comes to economic development, they always encounter many challenges as they look for finances because of the less quantity of information they usually send to banks and the asymmetric nature of the information (Bogdan et al. 2018). “Banks require more information to evaluate potential risks associated to SMEs in Mozambique” (Osano and Languitone 2016). Lack of information between the credit provider and SMEs slows down the loan application and processing in Asia and the pacific. (Abe et al. 2015).

In developing countries like Ghana, financial institutions are being faced with the lack of information on lenders that can enable them to assist SMEs with credits (Dalberg 2011). Strict terms and conditions are being seen all over Ghana which shows that Small and medium enterprises are facing a lot of problems in getting credit most especially with the issue of requirements of information that has been rising (Agbozo and Yeboah 2015, p. 80). When it comes to developing the economy, SMEs play an important role. Unfortunately, they do not have the support that they need to develop and also finance their investment because of information asymmetry and an unfavorable regulatory environment. (Bădulescu 2010, p. 1)

SMEs will see positive growth if information asymmetry is reduced via “the creation or strengthening of credit bureaus” (Shemwell 2019).

(ii) Collateral Requirements

Collaterals are required as security for loans in case the borrower fails to repay the loan on time. Currently, many small and medium-scale enterprises see the requirement for collateral by banks as very high. This problem affects smaller and start-up companies most especially in accessing credits from banks (Barungi, 2017). Recent research confirms that high collateral requirements remain a primary constraint for SME credit access, with collateral requirements being particularly stringent in less-developed economies due to opaque information environments and weak enforcement mechanisms (Yoshino & Taghizadeh-Hesary, 2018).

The high collateral requirement "creates a disincentive to the SMEs to acquire bank financing and that SMEs are discriminated by banks due to high risks in lending to them" (Osano & Languitone, 2016). A study by the European Commission (2016) shows that collateral requirements by financial institutions have been increasing, deterring some SMEs from applying for bank loans because they fear rejection

due to lack of collateral. In Ghana, "SMEs do not have the security required for conventional collateral-based bank lending, inadequate assets for use as security" (Agbozo & Yeboah, 2015). Women-run small businesses face higher financing interest rates, more collateral requirements, and higher rejection rates compared to men, with about 66% of women not having the collateral needed to get loans (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2017).

(iii) Character, Capacity and Condition

Studies have shown that in addition to collateral requirements, other factors that loan officers usually look for are the character, capacity and conditions of the SMEs. Character refers to the management competence and integrity of the SME owner, capacity relates to the business's ability to generate sufficient cash flow for loan repayment, while condition examines the current state and future prospects of the business environment. The traits of the right quantity and quality must be seen and assessed by the credit officer before a loan is approved (Barungi, 2017).

The lack of contemporary business experiences by SMEs has given rise to the lack of capacity, character and poor condition of the SMEs. This is shown by SMEs in the form of poor financials, improper accounts, bookkeeping and documentation, using business funds for personal uses because of insincerity, poor innovation in technology, and poor marketing/branding (Adomako-Ansah, 2012; Fuseini, 2015; Watse, 2017; Yadav, 2012). Recent research confirms that young, domestically owned firms with inadequate infrastructure experience the most significant barriers to financial access, while firm age, foreign ownership, and website availability positively affect access (IMF, 2024). An educated SME owner and/or professional makes it easy to access credit, as "lack of good formal education and active professional background also hinders access to credit as a salaried employee is considered as collateral for bank loans" (Ogoi, 2017).

(iv) Credit Rationing

Credit rationing happens when financial institutions are not ready to give more credit to borrowers who are willing to even pay an interest rate that's above the optimal price of the credit. Usually, this happens when there is information asymmetry and also when the financial institutions want to maintain their reserve ratios as stipulated by the regulators. It can also happen when the collateral that was presented has reduced in value that less than the loan amount being sought by the borrower.

European Bank Coordination Initiative (2014) wrote that SMEs credit constraint is being compounded by credit rationing that is currently on the rise. Credit rationing and risk premiums that are imposed on SMEs by financial service providers are limiting the SMEs' access to credit especially in developing nations and emerging markets (Harvie et al. 2013). Recent data shows that an estimated 28.3% of firms in sub-Saharan Africa are fully credit constrained, with only between a third and a fifth of SMEs having a bank loan or line of credit (CSIS, 2025).

(v) The Lender Factor

There are factors internal to financial institutions' operations that can deter credit flow to SMEs. Most banks conduct internal assessments to determine if they can provide credit, and these assessments often yield unfavourable outcomes that constrain SMEs in getting needed credits. The financial institutions need to check their capacity to provide credit to SMEs (Haron et al., 2013).

Internal factors influencing lender decisions include "prime interest rate, volume of deposits, domestic and foreign investments, banks liquid ratios, managerial policies, prestige and public recognition of the banks" (Haron et al., 2013). Most banks have very complex and long paper loan processing systems, and most SMEs do not have the patience and resilience to go through this process (Agbozo & Yeboah, 2015; Fuseini, 2015; Yadav, 2012). A study by Shemwell (2019) indicates that banks in low-income countries generally do not have appropriate products, and high transaction costs for processing,

monitoring, and enforcing small SME loans increase interest rates, making borrowing more expensive or unavailable for SMEs relative to larger firms. The stringent requirement of most banks in Ghana is that SME owners should run accounts with banks for not less than six months before qualifying for loans, and most SMEs, especially new ones, cannot meet this requirement (Adomako-Ansah, 2012; Watse, 2017).

(vi) High Interest Rates

Many studies have shown that one of the major problems making access to credit by SMEs very difficult is the high interest rates charged, which SMEs cannot pay. Shemwell (2019) and Yadav (2012) gave reasons behind high interest rates, namely "inappropriate products, high transaction costs for lenders to process, monitor, and enforce small SME loans, high guarantee fee and annual service fee." Local interest rates from banks in sub-Saharan Africa often exceed 20-25%, while alternative finance providers charge 40-50% (CSIS, 2021).

The high interest rates charged are also coupled with tough repayment terms, short loan repayment periods, and small loan amounts, thereby limiting access to credit by SMEs in Ghana (Prah, 2016). The most expensive source of financing is from private money lenders, followed by commercial bank loans and microfinance, with SMEs borrowing at lower rates if they operate longer in the market, receive government assistance, or if the loan is long term (Nguyen, 2014). The high interest rates cannot help SMEs grow or even help new ones survive, aiding the high level of unemployment prevalent in countries (Nnabu, Udude, & Emmanuel, 2017).

(vii) Poor Finance System and Structure

The financial system of a country determines how effective and efficient financial intermediation will be. Different levels of financial system development have separated developing and developed countries worldwide. Owusu (2012) posited that SME constraints in getting credit result from "the rudimentary nature of capital markets and the weaknesses in financial intermediation in general." How efficient the banking system determines how SMEs get credit (Ardic, Mylenko, & Saltane, 2012, p. 509).

The poor system has resulted in "lingering deficiencies in the enabling environment for financial services: financial infrastructure (accounting and auditing standards, credit reporting systems, and insolvency regimes), and the legal and regulatory framework for financial institutions and instruments" (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020; Osano & Languitone, 2016). The financial system of many developing countries like Ghana is very shallow and does not factor in "loans based on contracts or trade credit or equity investing, all of which might benefit high-growth SMEs" (Shemwell, 2019). Recent technological advancements are yet to reach rural areas, where banking relationships still depend entirely on person-to-person contact, discouraging some financial institutions from doing business in these areas (Anant, Kant, Ravikumar, & Bhat, 2011).

(viii) COVID-19 Pandemic Effects on the Financial System

The COVID-19 pandemic has spilled over into finance markets in both developing and developed countries, reducing confidence in financial intermediation networks and therefore reducing access to credit. This impact is severe especially on SMEs since they have always had the highest level of vulnerability and poor resilience because of their size (Zeidy, 2020, p. 2). The COVID-19 pandemic made many businesses close except essential services SMEs, with the majority unable to generate revenues to pay back their loans (GSS et al., 2020).

Financial institutions were pressured to recover their loans given to SMEs, leading to widespread outcry for credit assistance from governments, as "No bank wants to lend money without security" (Heijmans et al., 2020). In Ghana, 25.4 percent of businesses reported that their access to credit had reduced or no longer existed (GSS et al., 2020). In Sierra Leone, during the coronavirus pandemic, 81% of SMEs

reported that their profits reduced by almost 40% on average, with 71% saying they had challenges with cash flow and 50% needing government tax breaks and loan restructuring (Ferber & Buri, 2020b).

(ix) Lack of Credit Guarantee

Credit guarantee is quite difficult for some SMEs to get as they are no clear providers of such service in Ghana. According to a study by Ogoi (2017), “Unwilling guarantors were the most contributing factors that limit access to credit to improve company profitability and growth”. This reflects the broader challenge where SMEs cannot access guarantee mechanisms that would reduce their collateral burden and improve their creditworthiness in the eyes of the lenders.

Is Access to credit enough to ensure SMEs profitability and Growth?

With the challenges facing SMEs and the challenges they face in accessing finance, their profitability and growth are not assured. Karlan and Zinman (2011) find that “Microcredit does not generate bigger businesses, higher income, and higher subjective well-being, but rather leads to stronger risk management, fewer businesses, and lower subjective well-being”. This means that the one-fits-all type of credit is not enough to help SMEs grow. It can also mean that SMEs need another form of assistance to help them manage their businesses and grow.

According to Yadav (2012), giving only credit to assist SMEs to grow and remain profitable is not that useful and helpful. He added that credit providers should provide both financial and non-financial assistance in form of counselling to help solve most SMEs challenges. The counselling should on “proper books of account, retaining profit into business instead of evading tax payment, details of credit guarantee scheme, various determinants of credit rating, and benefits of rating the firm from SME rating agencies”. With the covid-19 pandemic, SMEs should also be counselled on the “usage of e-business in branding & disseminating production information to users”(Yadav 2012). He added that the counselling ought to include how to practice “financial discipline in dealing with banks for the SMEs to build their good credit history with credit information companies”(Yadav 2012). A study in Indonesia found that financial service providers do not contribute to a significant level of profitability of SMEs (Avdeenko et al., 2019). There are wonderful stories that credit boosts SME profitability, but in contrast “credit works through more complex and disparate mechanisms that start with the household rather than with the business” (Karlan & Zinman, 2011). Non-credit services improve profitability more than credit services received by SMEs (Alam 2013).

For SMEs to get the maximum support that they need to grow and be profitable and also add to the economic development of any country, business development services and an enabling environment must be seen as part of access to credit that has been improved. Though access to finance is very important in SMEs development, there are needs to add more to it like “mix of commercial funding sources with other activities, such as incubators, matching grant funds and other initiatives intended to create a ‘package that can help foster the next generation of firms in an economy”. An economic development that does not have enough means to get access to credit will never enable SMEs growth and profitability, but access to credit alone needs to be mixed with other services (Freeman and Nick 2015, p. 50). “Financing alone however is not sufficient. The initiatives on financing will be complemented and supported by capacity building programmes to evolve strong and well-managed SMEs that would improve their prospects for better access to financing” (Khan and Anuar 2018).

2.1.3 BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT SERVICE

Business development services (BDS) have become a buzz in the past decades. This is coming from the perceived fact that the advisory services or extension services being rendered to SMEs are becoming short in achieving the required impact. BDS gives an integrated approach to every support needed by SMEs to ensure profitability and economic development of nations most especially, the developing

countries (Barungi 2017). It is highly needed in Ghana where 60% of businesses do not succeed within five (5) years of establishing them (Kusi et al. 2015); and where three out of five businesses fail within the first five years of incorporation (Kusi, Opata, & Narh, 2015). Unfortunately, there is a lack of focus and scanty literature on the processes which can grow and develop small businesses in Ghana (Achtenhagen et al. 2017, pp. 3–4).

Defining Business Development Services

Business development services help by offering a diagnosis of the strengths and weaknesses of individual firms and providing advice on how to improve business practices Business Development Services for Start-ups and SMEs (OECD, 2024). Building on the International Labour Organization's foundational definition, contemporary BDS encompasses both strategic and operational activities designed to enhance SME performance, competitive advantage, and market access capabilities.

Business development services (BDS) consist of services that are non-financial which are provided to SMEs to help them grow their business and ensure efficiency and effectiveness in achieving economic growth, reduced unemployment rate and poverty alleviation to achieve a robust economic development (Otieno, Donath & Kiraka, 2009 as cited by (Asafo-Adjei), 2014). This shows that BDS is very important if the goal and objective of SMEs profitability and economic development of nations are to be achieved faster.

Types and components of BDS

BDS have to do with services that are non-financial which are very important and highly needed to SMEs business entry, their ability to survive, being productive, having a competitive advantage and their growth. BDS has also been seen as services that are non-financial that are provided by public sector agencies, non-profit organizations, and private companies, banks and other formal institutions, local and informal service providers to enhance the efficient operation of SMEs and their growths (Best et al. 2015). A review of business development studies shows that the services are provided in form of training and consulting. Consulting services in form of business advisory service are provided to business owners and those that manage the businesses to get enhanced performance. Usually, the business owners or the business managers pay fees for those services provided or may be paid with a portion of the assets that the business owns (Law 2016).

(Small Enterprise Education and Promotion (SEEP) Network 2005) said that BDS comprise training and technical assistance, access to larger markets, infrastructure that's improved, supply of inputs, product development, alternative financing mechanisms, and policy/advocacy for the long term success of the firms.

Limitations of Current BDS Models in Ghana

Most BDS providers who have commercialized the services do not have all it takes to provide all the services that are embedded in BDS. Commercial banks and microfinance institutions have the financial muscle to provide the integrated model of BDS to support business, ensure timely repayment of loans to reduce bad debts, and achieve a well-developed economy. Unfortunately, recent research confirms this pattern persists, with formal financial institutions continuing to exclude micro-entrepreneurs from credit access. Contemporary evidence shows that women entrepreneurs face challenges including social and cultural barriers, lack of collateral, and insufficient credit history, making it harder for them to secure formal loans compared to men, with only 21% of women in low- and middle-income countries obtaining loans through formal channels compared to 25% of men (VoxDev, 2024).

The persistent underperformance of SMEs in Ghana cannot be attributed solely to a lack of Business Development Services (BDS), but rather to fundamental flaws in the structure, accessibility, and integration of these services. Recent assessments confirm that Ghana's micro, small and medium enterprises face considerable challenges in growing their businesses, with limited access to finance and quality providers of technical assistance, compounded by few skills and management capabilities (World Bank, 2022). A critical gap exists between the theoretical scope of BDS and its practical delivery. Most commercialized BDS providers lack the comprehensive capacity to deliver the full spectrum of services embedded within BDS, resulting in fragmented and often superficial support.

While formal financial institutions possess the financial muscle to deliver an integrated BDS model which can potentially improving loan repayment and economic development—they systematically exclude micro-entrepreneurs, particularly women, due to rigid requirements like credit history, thereby undermining financial inclusion and the synergistic potential of financial and non-financial support. Women-owned firms face even tougher challenges, as they have limited access to land, capital, and more sophisticated business practices (World Bank, 2022). This exclusion is particularly problematic given that the total micro, small, or medium enterprise finance gap for women is estimated to be valued at \$1.7 trillion globally, while women entrepreneurs own 22% of micro-enterprises and 32% of small and medium enterprises (World Economic Forum, 2023).

Even when services are accessed, their effectiveness is compromised by poor alignment with SME needs and low absorptive capacity. The needs of SMEs vary significantly by growth stage, ranging from basic compliance and accounting for nascent firms to branding, internationalization, and strategic finance for growing enterprises, yet BDS programs often adopt a one-size-fits-all approach. Contemporary research on Ghanaian SMEs reveals that service sector enterprises face diverse challenges requiring solutions that enable the sector to thrive, yet there is a gap in how to plan, direct, control, and effectively market and strategize for their business, requiring training interventions from government and non-governmental organizations (Attrams and Tshela, 2022). Furthermore, many SME owners lack the managerial competence and formal business practices necessary to benefit from training in financial management, marketing, or strategic planning, as evidenced by widespread failure to maintain records or separate personal and business finances. Over 65% of SME owners in Ghana lack formal management training, contributing to the 70% failure rate within the first five years (Atiase et al., 2023).

From an analysis of 688 SMEs in Ghana's service sector, high taxes and informal competitions emerged as the highest-ranked challenges, while access to finance ranked tenth, indicating that BDS interventions must address broader systemic issues beyond traditional training approaches (Attrams and Tshela, 2022). This gap between service provision and owner capability limits transformative impact, as SME owners are characterized with low capacity to manage their businesses, requiring the ability to understand their intellectual capital to enhance their performance and invest in resources to build and maintain their networks to enhance their scope of business (Attrams and Tshela, 2022).

While some studies report positive outcomes such as improved skills, confidence, and even profitability, as evidenced by research in Ghana showing "that BDS raised the profitability and enhanced the growth and competitiveness of enterprises, which directly raised their incomes" (Anjorin et al., 2024), these gains are often not translated into statistically significant improvements in sales or profits, indicating a disconnect between behavioral change and sustainable business growth. "Overall, training programs produced significant improvements in entrepreneurs' skills and behaviours; however, the average effects of the training on the sales and profits of the participants' firms are economically large but statistically insignificant" (Shemwell, 2019).

Uptake remains low, especially among women and rural entrepreneurs, due to a lack of awareness, perceived irrelevance of services, and insufficient outreach by both government and private providers. Most SME owners do not even know that such programs like BDS exist to help their businesses. This ignorance saddled with the low capacity can be seen as a huge challenge to them. The governments and private sector do not even make an effort to move down to the lowest ebb of the SMEs to assist them with the BDS (Osano & Languitone, 2016). In Ghana, most women SME owners do not use business development service providers as they see their services as 'not needed'. But women entrepreneurs with "higher levels of education, lower degree centrality in their network and higher social economic status" use business development service providers (Asare-Bediako, Okyere, & Frempong, 2016).

Despite recent government initiatives such as the SME Growth and Opportunity Programme launched in 2024, which prioritizes coordination between partnering agencies to ensure targeted delivery of financial and technical support to high-growth potential SMEs (Ministry of Finance Ghana, 2024), the failure to link BDS meaningfully with financial services, stage-specific needs, and the socio-economic realities of Ghanaian entrepreneurs ultimately renders the current model ineffective for achieving broad-based SME transformation.

(i) Providers of Business Development Services

Business development services (BDS) in Ghana are delivered through multiple channels with varying degrees of effectiveness and accessibility. Government agencies, including the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ghana Enterprises Agency (GEA, formerly the National Board for Small Scale Industries - NBSSI), have traditionally provided free training and advisory services to SMEs through a network of Business Advisory Centres across the country (Ghana Enterprises Agency 2025). However, the GEA has acknowledged that rising demand, coupled with limited central government financing, has constrained its operational reach, particularly in rural and underserved communities (GEA, 2024). To address these limitations, the GEA has pursued strategic partnerships, such as the Business in A Box (BizBox) Project with the Mastercard Foundation, aimed at enhancing entrepreneurial capacity among youth and women through digital tools and training (GEA, 2024).

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), often funded by international development partners and private donors, have increasingly filled service delivery gaps. For instance, the UNDP GEF-Small Grants Programme (SGP) has implemented the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises Support Initiative, providing targeted grants to local organizations to strengthen MSME capabilities in sectors such as agriculture and green enterprise (UNDP 2023). These initiatives highlight the growing reliance on donor-funded civil society actors to deliver critical BDS, particularly in marginalized regions.

The limitations of public sector provision have also created space for private consultants and firms offering services such as business planning, accounting, marketing, and technical assistance. However, research indicates that the high cost of these private services creates significant accessibility barriers, rendering them unaffordable for the majority of SME owners, especially those in the informal sector or with limited financial resources (Addaney et al. 2016). This cost barrier perpetuates inequality in access to quality BDS, favouring larger or more established enterprises.

Additionally, financial institutions such as microfinance banks and commercial banks like Access Bank Ghana offer what they term business development services, typically in the form of client training on financial product usage. However, these sessions are often criticized for prioritizing loan disbursement and collection over substantive capacity building (World Bank, 2022). Despite receiving substantial international investment, such as the International Finance Corporation's (IFC) \$10 million risk-sharing facility for Access Bank in 2024, financial institutions continue to fall short of delivering comprehensive, integrated BDS that address the strategic, managerial, and operational needs of SMEs for sustainable growth (IFC, 2024). This gap underscores a critical mismatch between funding inflows and the actual quality and depth of support provided to Ghanaian SMEs.

(ii) Payment for Business Development Services

According to Best et al (2015), Understanding how business development services fees are paid by their users can give a hint on how the services are delivered by the providers. This will help in looking for means to fill the gap that's prevalent and also see the way to improve on the quality of the current BDS. They are paid for as:

- i. Free from the government. The government through their agencies or NGOs provide business development services to the businesses free of charge.
- ii. The private firms or individual who are consultants provide the services at a cost to the receivers. Most of the SME owners do not use the services because of the high charges.
- iii. Bundled services: the charges for a business development service are added to the cost of a product that the business owner is buying from the provider. The charges can be specification of quality, digital marketing or tips on production, etc (Best et al. 2015, pp. 14–16).

Business Development Services Needed by SMEs

Miehlbradt and McVay, (2003) in their seminar reader for the international Labour organization (ILO) showed that there are many types of business development services that are needed by SMEs to ensure their growth and development. The figure below shows that the SME owners may be lacking all or most of the services as they do not have the capacity and the manpower to apply them in their operations.

Table 2.2: Types of Business Development Services

No	Types of Service	Detailed Types of Service	
1	Market Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing Business • Market linkages • Trade fairs & product exhibitions • Development of samples for buyers • Market information • Subcontracting and outsourcing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing trips and meetings • Market research • Market space development • Showrooms • Packaging • Advertising
2	Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage and warehousing • Transport and delivery • Business incubators • Telecommunications • Courier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Money transfer • Information through print, radio, TV etc. • Internet access • Computer services • Secretarial services
3	Policy / Advocacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training in policy advocacy • Analysis and communications of policy constraints and opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct advocacy on behalf of SME • Sponsorship of conference • Policy studies
4	Input supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking SME to input suppliers • Improving suppliers capacity to provide regular supply of quality inputs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating the establishment of bulk buying groups • Information on input supply resources
5	Training & technical assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentoring • Feasibility studies and business plans • Exchange visits and business tours • Franchising • Management training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical training • Counselling/advisory services • Legal services • Financial & taxation services • Accountancy • Bookkeeping
6	Technology and product development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology transfer/commercialization • Linking SME and technology suppliers • Facilitating technology procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality assurance programme • Equipment leasing and rental • Design service
7	Alternative financing mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factoring companies that provide working capital for confirmed orders • Equity financing • Facilitating supplier credit 	

Source: Miehlbradt and McVay (2003)

The most common among the types is training and technical assistance. Literature have shown that this mode of delivering the BDS is not working and needs to be changed or modified to suit the SMEs who are in need of the services. The main BDS objective which is “to assist small and medium enterprises to overcome internal and external constraints in their business development and thus improve their performance” (Ombi et al. 2018b) is not being achieved with the current model of delivering the services.

This section has shown that SMEs in Ghana face complex, interconnected challenges that extend beyond simple capital shortages to encompass regulatory, infrastructural, and systemic exclusion barriers, with women entrepreneurs facing particularly acute access constraints. The analysis reveals that while SMEs constitute over 90% of businesses and contribute significantly to GDP, current support mechanisms—both financial and non-financial—suffer from fragmentation, poor alignment with SME needs, and limited integration. The persistent underperformance of Ghanaian SMEs stems not from the absence of credit or BDS individually, but from fundamental flaws in how these services are structured

and delivered as separate interventions. These findings establish the conceptual justification for this study's central proposition that integrated approaches combining customized credit with participatory business development services can function as systematic risk management tools, addressing the multidimensional nature of SME challenges more effectively than isolated interventions and setting the foundation for the theoretical frameworks and empirical analysis that follow.

2.2. Theoretical Frameworks And Conceptual Frameworks

Having established the key concepts and definitions in the preceding sections, this section develops the theoretical and conceptual frameworks that underpin the study's central proposition regarding integrated SME support mechanisms. The chapter draws upon four complementary theoretical perspectives to explain how the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services can enhance SME performance through systematic risk management. Beginning with Access to Credit Theory, the framework examines how information asymmetries and market failures affect SME financing, followed by Human Capital Theory, which illuminates the role of skills and capability development in enterprise performance. The chapter then introduces Contingency Theory to explain why SME risk profiles vary significantly across different contexts, requiring tailored rather than standardized interventions, and Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) theory to provide a comprehensive framework for understanding how integrated approaches can address varied risks systematically. These theoretical foundations are synthesized into a novel conceptual framework that positions integration as a risk management mechanism, establishing mathematical relationships between service integration, risk reduction, and performance outcomes. This integrated theoretical approach provides the analytical lens for understanding how customized credit and participatory BDS can function together as a comprehensive risk management tool that enhances SME performance across multiple dimensions while addressing the heterogeneity that characterizes the SME sector in Ghana.

2.2.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

Access to Credit Theory

Access to Credit Theory, grounded in information economics and developed by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981), provides the foundational framework for understanding credit market failures in SME financing. The theory posits that information asymmetries between lenders and borrowers create systematic market imperfections that result in credit rationing which is a situation where creditworthy borrowers are denied loans even when willing to pay higher interest rates (Ayres and Carter 2024). The theoretical foundation rests on two core mechanisms: **adverse selection and moral hazard**. Adverse selection occurs ex-ante when lenders cannot distinguish between high-risk and low-risk borrowers, leading to a pooling equilibrium where good borrowers are crowded out by bad borrowers (Rothschild & Stiglitz, 1976). Moral hazard manifests ex-post when borrowers alter their behavior after receiving credit, potentially engaging in riskier activities than initially disclosed (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Mathematically, the theory can be formalized following the framework established by Freixas and Rochet (2008) in their comprehensive treatment of banking microeconomics. Let π represent the probability of loan repayment, r the interest rate, and θ the borrower type (where θH = high-risk, θL = low-risk). Under perfect information, lenders would set different rates: $r^H > r^L$. However, under asymmetric information, lenders must set a pooling rate r^* that satisfies the zero-profit condition:

$$\pi(\theta) \cdot r^* = \rho + c \quad (2.1)$$

Where ρ is the risk-free rate and c represents administrative costs (Freixas & Rochet, 2008). This pooling equilibrium results in adverse selection, as low-risk borrowers (θL) may exit the market when $r^* > r^L$, leaving predominantly high-risk borrowers. This asymmetric information model demonstrates how "different economic agents possess different pieces of information on relevant economic variables, and that they will use the information for their own profit," leading to "structural

weaknesses of the banking sector" including "the persistence of rationing in the credit market" (Freixas & Rochet, 2008).

For SMEs in developing economies like Ghana, this theoretical framework explains several empirical phenomena. First, the prevalence of collateral requirements as screening mechanisms reflects lenders' attempts to mitigate information asymmetries (Oppong et al. 2023). Information asymmetry remains a significant challenge for SME funding in Ghana (OPPONG, AGYEMANG & KYEI, 2023). Second, the concentration of SME lending in relationship banking aligns with theoretical predictions about the value of soft information in reducing informational frictions (Boot, 2000). The study of Dorhetso et al. (2022) found that affordability of financial credit is vital for SMEs to access the required funding to enhance their performance (Oteng and Patel 2024).

The theory's relevance to this study lies in its prediction that integrated interventions can reduce information asymmetries more effectively than standalone credit provision. When Business Development Services (BDS) accompany credit, they generate soft information about borrower quality, management capability, and business viability—thereby reducing the information gap that constrains credit access (Maesaroh et al. 2024). A study on an integrated financing credit service model for small and micro enterprises supports the exploration of such combined approaches (Sun 2023). This theoretical insight forms the foundation for hypothesizing that integrated credit-BDS interventions will demonstrate superior outcomes compared to separate interventions.

Human Capital Theory

Bohlander et al. (2001) explained Human capital to be “knowledge, skills, and capabilities of individuals that have economic value to an organization.” Whiles OECD (2001) defined human capital as “the knowledge, skills, competencies, and attributes embodied in individuals that facilitate the creation of personal, social and economic well-being.” (Cited by Fugar et al., (2013). The development of human capital involves those activities that improve the owners and employees of firms. Human capital can generally be seen as “the ability to read and write, or in specific terms, such as the acquisition of a particular skill with a limited industrial application”. According to Schultz (1961) and Becker (1964), Human capital can be likened to "physical means of production, e.g., factories and machines: one can invest in human capital (via education, training, medical treatment) and one's outputs depend partly on the rate of return on the human capital one owns” (cited by Asafo-Adjei, 2014). Investing in human capital will yield more output (Fugar et al. 2013).

In the figure below, Investment in human capital can be in form of education, training and/or recruitment to improve the knowledge, skills and abilities of the owners or employees of firms (Marvel et al. 2014).

	Investments	Outcomes
Impart	<p>Education – investments in learning activities of explicit knowledge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Vary from general to specific types of education. ▪ Vary in cost, diversity, and length of investment. 	<p>Knowledge – understanding of principles, facts, and processes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Clustered within domains such as those learned through formal education. ▪ Vary from generic to specific.
Develop	<p>Training/experience – investments in learning by doing activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ General or specific to context (e.g., industry) or task (e.g., prototype development). ▪ Vary in terms of cost, amount, time, and type. 	<p>Skills – observable application of knowledge to create solutions to problems or complete specific task.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Specialized or domain specific skills (e.g., industry or task-specific). ▪ Vary in type from novice to expert.
Acquire	<p>Recruitment – Investments in recruitment activities to acquire abilities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sources may include venture team, firm alliances, network ties, external R&D, etc. ▪ Vary in cost, form, and quality. 	<p>Abilities – Enduring, trait-like characteristics useful to range of tasks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ More general with implications to wide range of contexts and tasks. ▪ Difficult to internally develop compared to knowledge or skills.

Figure 1.1 : Typology of Human Capital (Marvel et al. 2014, p. 616)

It is commonly believed that capacity building of owners of SMEs and their employees do impact positively on the productivity of their businesses if they get new skills which will lead to an increase in employing more labour and increase in revenue (Shemwell 2019). To identify and analyse what is needed for a business to grow and develop, a talented and skilled workforce must be available. Competence, knowledge and character found in a workforce determine the performance of the organization. Experience, training and education determine how “resources are effectively developed, managed and exploited, which the results are often profitable for both the firm and society as a whole”. It means that Learning and schooling are required to improve human capital that will yield high profitability, economic growth and development (Asafo-Adjei 2014).

The Human capital model can also be industry-specific and individual-specific (Samad 2013). Industry specific human capital is all about the experience that’s unique to a sector or the business nature of a firm. This has a wider impact on the performance and development of firms and the society at large. The individual-specific human capital “which relates to knowledge that applies to a broad range of firms and industries; including general managerial and entrepreneurial experience, the level of academic education and training” (Samad 2013). The Individual specific human capital “must also focus on developing networks, maintain technical excellence, perform continually above-average team-working capabilities, display positive political behaviour and manage their image successfully” (Wuttaphan 2017).

“Human Capital is not only important to individual-level outcomes such as job performance and employee development, but also firm-level outcomes such as capability development and competitive advantage” (CIPD 2017). The skills and competencies of SME owners and their employees can be improved through the assistance of BDS providers. According to practices of the BDS providers, such

assistance does not come for free but are also the source of additional burden on the part of the SME owners, thus making it difficult for some SME owners to accept BDS. On the part of BDS providers, the findings of Fischer et al. (2010) suggests that BDS “companies either exploit or explore the opportunities when it comes to the provision of BDS” that may improve the performance and competitive advantage of their firms.

The mathematical foundation of Human Capital Theory is most rigorously expressed through the Mincer Earnings Function, developed by Jacob Mincer (1958, 1974) and widely recognized as "one of the most widely used models in empirical economics" (Lemieux 2006). This model treats "education (and training) as an individual investment decision that will receive a monetary return in the labor market, typically in the form of higher lifetime earnings," building on foundational work by Schultz (1963), (Becker 1962; Gary S. Becker 1964), and (Mincer 1958, 1974)

The standard Mincer earnings equation is mathematically expressed as:

$$\ln(Y_i) = \alpha + \beta Si + \gamma_1 EX_i + \gamma_2 EX_i^2 + \epsilon_i \quad (2.2)$$

Where:

$\ln(Y_i)$ represents the natural logarithm of earnings for individual i

S_i denotes years of schooling (education)

EX_i represents years of work experience

EX_i^2 captures the quadratic relationship between experience and earnings

α is the intercept term

β measures the return to schooling (human capital investment)

γ_1 and γ_2 capture the experience-earnings profile

ϵ_i is the error term

As established in Becker's seminal work (1962, 1964), this formalization shows how "investment in an individual's education and training is similar to business investments in equipment," with the coefficient β representing the rate of return on human capital investment. Recent empirical evaluations suggest that "the Mincer equation remains an accurate benchmark for estimating wage determination equations provided that it is adjusted by (1) including a quartic function in potential experience instead of just a quadratic, (2) allowing for a quadratic term in years of schooling to capture the growing convexity in the relationship between schooling and wages, and (3) allowing for cohort effects" "Mincer Equation"(Lemieux, 2006).

For SME contexts, this theoretical framework explains how business development services (BDS) function as human capital investments. When BDS enhances managerial capabilities, technical skills, and business knowledge of SME owners, it increases their productive capacity (human capital stock), which should translate into higher returns (improved business performance) following the Mincer framework. The mathematical relationship suggests that the returns to BDS investment should be measurable through improvements in business outcomes, analogous to how educational investments yield measurable wage premiums.

The above sections established how access to credit theory explains financing mechanisms for SMEs and how human capital theory illuminates the development of skills and capabilities. However, these frameworks alone do not fully account for the heterogeneity of SMEs or their differential responses to interventions. This section introduces two complementary theoretical perspectives—Contingency Theory and Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)—that provide crucial insights into managing business risks across diverse SME contexts.

Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)

Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) theory provides a comprehensive framework for how these varied risks can be systematically addressed through integrated approaches. Unlike traditional risk

management that handles risks in isolated silos, ERM offers a holistic perspective that aligns with the integration of credit and business development services. According to Coviini (2020), ERM creates value through its ability to allow firms to identify and select risk-return trade-offs that maximize firm value. This value creation aspect of ERM provides theoretical support for interventions that simultaneously reduce business volatility while enhancing returns i.e. precisely the dual benefit observed with integrated service delivery.

The integration of credit and BDS aligns with ERM principles by simultaneously addressing multiple risk dimensions: financial risks through customized lending, operational risks through capacity building, and strategic risks through business advisory services. ERM theory supports the risk return clustering approach by recognizing that different risk profiles require differentiated management strategies. Hillson and Murray-Webster (2012) demonstrate that effective risk management must account for both objective risk properties and subjective risk attitudes of decision makers. This principle justifies segmenting SMEs into clusters (High Risk/Low Profitability, Low Risk/High Profitability, etc.) rather than applying uniform interventions. The clustering approach operationalizes ERM's core principle that risk appetite varies across organizational contexts, with SMEs in different clusters exhibiting distinct risk-return characteristics that demand tailored integration intensities. This integrated approach enables both defensive risk management (preventing losses) and offensive risk management (pursuing growth opportunities) (Winyane, 2022), creating the theoretical basis for examining how combined interventions outperform separate services in reducing SME volatility while enhancing performance.

ERM Risk Assessment Equation stems from ISO 31000:2018's risk assessment framework, which quantifies risk through the relationship between probability and impact. This systematic approach enables firms to compare and prioritise diverse risks using a standardized metric. The fundamental ERM risk equation is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{Risk\ Level} = f(\mathbf{Likelihood, Impact})(2.3)$$

More specifically: $\mathbf{Risk\ Score} = L \times I$ (2.4)

Where:

- L = Likelihood/Probability (1-5 scale)
- I = Impact/Consequence severity (1-5 scale)

This formalization follows ISO 31000:2018 principles where "risk is expressed in terms of a combination of the consequences of an event and the associated likelihood of occurrence (Ethics and Compliance 2025); (Wikipedia 2025). This quantitative approach enables risk aggregation across different business unites and facilitates the portfolio-level risk assessment that underpins effective ERM implementation.

Human Development Theory and Development Indices

The conventional measurement of economic development has traditionally relied upon Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and per capita income as primary proxies for national progress. However, as the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission demonstrated, these narrow monetary measures fundamentally fail to capture the full complexity of human well-being and social development (Stiglitz, Sen, and Fitoussi, 2009). Building upon Amartya Sen's Capability Approach, which extended the evaluation of human progress beyond income to encompass the broader functionings and capacities that individuals are able to achieve, the UNDP developed a family of composite indices to measure human development in its multi-dimensional form (UNDP, 2019). These indices i.e. the Human Development Index (HDI), the Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (iHDI), and the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)

collectively provide the theoretical foundation for what may be described as Human Development Theory: a framework that treats development as the simultaneous expansion of human capabilities across health, education, income, and freedom from poverty. For this study, Human Development Theory provides the macro-level theoretical basis for assessing how integrated credit and Business Development Services (BDS) delivery to SMEs translates into broader societal development outcomes in Ghana.

The Human Development Index (HDI) was introduced by the UNDP in its inaugural Human Development Report (UNDP, 1990) as a composite measure of development comprising three equally weighted dimensions: health and longevity, measured by life expectancy at birth; access to knowledge and education, measured by mean and expected years of schooling; and standard of living, measured by gross national income per capita. Each of these dimensions bears a clear and direct theoretical relationship to the SME interventions examined in this study. Access to credit enables SMEs to invest in productive assets, sustain operations, and expand employment, which generates income for business owners, employees, and their households, thereby contributing to the standard of living dimension of the HDI. Business Development Services represent a deliberate and sustained form of human capital investment, in that BDS providers enhance the managerial competencies, technical skills, and business knowledge of SME owners and employees (Fugar et al., 2013). This investment in knowledge and skills aligns directly with the educational attainment dimension captured by the HDI, consistent with the theoretical framework of Human Capital Theory (Schultz, 1961; Becker, 1964). Furthermore, the income security and improved livelihoods generated by viable SMEs reduce financial precarity, which over time enables better access to healthcare for proprietors and their dependants, thereby influencing the health and longevity dimension of the HDI as well. The cumulative effect is a theoretically coherent pathway from firm-level credit and BDS interventions to improvements in all three pillars of the HDI.

The Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (iHDI) extends the HDI framework by discounting a country's average human development achievements according to the degree of inequality in their distribution across the population (UNDP, 2019). Where the HDI captures the average level of development, the iHDI captures the equity with which that development is shared. This distinction is theoretically significant for the present study because integrated credit and BDS delivery is expected to generate more equitable outcomes than separate service provision. Under a separate service model, SMEs with stronger credit histories or more formalised operations are more likely to qualify for credit, while BDS tends to reach those already engaged with support networks. By contrast, the integrated model proposed in this study tailors credit terms and BDS provision to the specific risk-return profiles of heterogeneous SME clusters, making productive financial and advisory support accessible to a broader segment of the SME population, including those in high-risk or low-profitability clusters that would otherwise be excluded. When a wider and more diverse group of SMEs gains access to integrated support, the resulting income and human capital gains are distributed more equitably across the population. This distributional improvement reduces inter-group inequality in development outcomes, producing gains in the iHDI that reflect inclusive rather than merely aggregate progress.

The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), developed jointly by the UNDP and the Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI), measures poverty not as a solely monetary phenomenon but as a composite of simultaneous deprivations across the three dimensions of health, education, and living standards (OPHI, 2019; UNDP, 2019). This multidimensional approach to poverty measurement provides the most comprehensive theoretical lens for evaluating the poverty-reduction impact of integrated SME support. When credit access enables SME owners to generate sustainable income and repay loans without undue stress on their operations, and when BDS simultaneously enhances operational capabilities and business knowledge, the combined effect addresses multiple dimensions of poverty concurrently: income deprivation through improved profitability; educational deprivation through skills development and capacity building; and health and living standards deprivation through the economic security that stable business performance affords. This simultaneous, multi-dimensional impact aligns precisely with Sen's Capability Approach, which emphasises that genuine poverty reduction requires the expansion of human capabilities across multiple life domains at the same time, rather than addressing income alone. The MPI therefore provides the theoretical justification for

assessing the deepest and most persistent poverty-reduction effects of integrated credit and BDS delivery as they manifest across the full spectrum of human development dimensions.

In sum, Human Development Theory operationalised through the HDI, iHDI, and MPI provides this study with a theoretically grounded and empirically tractable set of macro-level outcome measures that move the analysis well beyond firm-level financial performance. The theoretical logic is sequential and cumulative: credit access and BDS raise the productive and human capital capacities of SMEs at the firm level; these gains aggregate at the national level into improvements across all three dimensions of the HDI; the equity with which these improvements are distributed is captured by the iHDI; and the extent to which the most entrenched and multi-dimensional forms of poverty are reduced is measured by the MPI. This integrated theoretical chain, linking micro-level SME interventions to macro-level human development outcomes, positions Human Development Theory as an indispensable fourth pillar of the theoretical framework of this study, complementing the Access to Credit Theory, Human Capital Theory, and Enterprise Risk Management frameworks presented in the preceding sections.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

This section presents the study's theoretical model linking Access to Credit Theory, Human Capital Theory, and Enterprise Risk Management to explain how integrated credit and business development services function as systematic risk management mechanisms for Ghanaian SMEs (Figure 2.1).

2.3.1 Theoretical Integration and Justification

The conceptual framework synthesizes the three theoretical foundations to address critical gaps in SME support literature. Access to Credit Theory explains why information asymmetries constrain SME financing, while Human Capital Theory demonstrates how capacity building enhances productive capabilities. However, neither theory adequately addresses how these interventions can be integrated to manage business risks systematically.

Enterprise Risk Management theory bridges this gap by providing the theoretical rationale for integration. ERM's core principle which are that organizations create value through coordinated risk-return optimization that directly supports the hypothesis that combined credit-BDS interventions outperform separate services by simultaneously addressing financial, operational, and strategic risks.

The framework also builds on three core studies while addressing their limitations. Stupnytska et al. (2014) demonstrated credit's impact on SME profitability through GDP analysis, providing baseline assumptions for credit effects. Cumming & Fischer (2012) showed business advisory services enhance performance via sales revenue, informing BDS operationalization. However, Avdeenko et al. (2019) found minimal impact from brief BDS interventions (five 32-minute sessions), highlighting needs for sustained engagement.

This study advances prior frameworks through key originalities. First, it operationalizes BDS using days spent at SME premises rather than hours/sessions, capturing sustained support. Second, it introduces integration metrics through credit \times BDS interaction terms. Third, it implements risk-return clustering (High Risk/Low Profitability, Low Risk/High Profitability, etc.) based on SD_ROS and ROS measures, acknowledging SME heterogeneity.

Drawing from ERM theory, integration functions as a risk management mechanism through two channels: First, risk diversification: Credit addresses financial risks while BDS mitigates operational and management risks, creating a portfolio effect that reduces overall business volatility. Second, information synergy: BDS generates soft information about borrower quality that reduces information

asymmetries identified in credit rationing theory, enabling more accurate risk assessment, management/mitigations and pricing.

The framework formalizes the risk-integration relationship as:

$$SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \quad (2.5)$$

Where: SD_{ROS} is standard deviation of return on sales (Risk measure); Q_V represents credit amount, S_V represents BDS days, and θ, ρ are elasticity parameters α represents the baseline risk without integration of customized credit and participatory Business development services, and β captures the integration effectiveness.

This equation depicts how integration intensity ($Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$) inversely relates to business risk, with higher integration levels producing lower volatility. The framework connects risk reduction to three key performance outcomes. First, profitability is expressed as: $\pi_V = Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = \frac{\alpha - SD \text{ of ROS}}{\beta}$ (2.6), establishing a direct link between integration, risk reduction, and financial performance. Second, loan repayment capacity is modelled as: $\kappa = ROS \times \left[\frac{\alpha - SD_{ROS}}{\beta} \right]$ (2.7), capturing how risk reduction enhances repayment sustainability. Third, economic development impacts are measured through three indices: Human Development Index (HDI), Inequality-Adjusted HDI (IHDI), and Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). These equations formalize the dual role of integration: mitigating risk while enhancing financial performance and broader economic outcomes. Note that the methodology chapter contains more on how the equations were derived and arrived at.

To empirically test these theoretical relationships, the framework operationalizes three econometric models. First, the profitability model (panel), the net profit as dependent variable; separate services (credit and BDS) and integrated service (credit \times BDS interaction) as independent variables; and SME-Specific Factors (Firm age, business size, technology spending, owner/manager education and sector) as control variables. The loan repayment model (panel) follows a similar structure but with loan repayment rate as the dependent variable and includes return on sales (ROS) as an additional independent variable. For economic development impacts, the framework employs two complementary Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) specifications: Model A tests the separate effects of credit and BDS, while Model B examines their integrated effects. These models empirically test the theoretical relationships proposed in the risk management framework while controlling for firm characteristics and macroeconomic factors.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

(Author, 2025)

Summary

The conceptual framework is illustrated in Figure 2.1 above shows the relationships between integration mechanisms, risk management processes, and outcome variables. This integrated approach provides a comprehensive lens for understanding how customized credit and participatory BDS can function together as a systematic risk management tool that enhances SME performance.

CHAPTER THREE

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Introduction

This chapter presents a comprehensive empirical review of existing literature on credit access, business development services, and their impacts on SME performance and economic development. Building on the theoretical foundations established in Chapter 2, this review critically examines empirical evidence to identify patterns, contradictions, and gaps that justify the integrated credit-BDS approach proposed in this study. The review is structured around four key thematic areas: Section 3.1 examines credit access and economic development relationships, Section 3.2 focuses on credit's impact on SME profitability, Section 3.3 explores loan repayment factors, and Section 3.4 reviews business development services effectiveness both as standalone interventions and in combination with credit provision. Each section adopts a critical analytical approach that identifies theoretical mechanisms, explains contradictory findings, and assesses methodological rigor to support the study's core proposition that integrated credit-BDS interventions function as systematic risk management mechanisms that outperform separate service provision.

3.1 CREDIT, GROWTH AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Building on the conceptual framework presented in Chapter 2, which positions credit and BDS as complementary risk management tools through the equation $SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_V^{\theta} S_V^{\rho}$, this section examines how existing empirical studies support or challenge the theoretical proposition that integrated services outperform separate interventions. At different stages of business life, credit has played an important role in the success and growth of the business. Personal savings or funds from family and friends have always been used to finance start-ups. Expansion of businesses was done using credits from external sources. The demand for credit has been found to be increasing as SMEs grow in size and profitability. Insufficient credit has been found to deter SMEs from undertaking profitable ventures. Most businesses are only able to expand according to the quantity and quality of credit that they get and not the market the SMEs are ready to provide goods and services for. Credit has been found to have a positive impact on the activities of SMEs. With credit, 80% of SMEs can survive in ten (10) years on average and remain profitable (Kuzilwa, 2005).

In the development of the economy, SMEs play an important role in developing countries. The contribution of SMEs to economic growth and development are significantly higher when those operating in informal settings are considered. Those in the informal settings do not usually get captured by the system (Financial Inclusion Experts Group | SME Finance Sub-Group, 2020, p. 6). Credits constraints which are very binding affect choices of livelihood and lines of production. When there are credit constraints, SME owners and their customers will see their consumption, production inputs, health and education affected immensely (Kumar, Turvey, & Kropp, 2013,). This lack of access to credit has a ripple negative effect on the survivability of the SMEs, investment in technology, capacity building, expanding into other markets and management system improvements. With all these important business components lacking, SMEs will not grow and contribute much to the economic growth and development of any nation like Ghana (Prempeh, 2015). However, credit provided to SMEs have been found to be positively related to economic growth conditioned on the said credit not diverted for household use as can be common with SME owners (Majeed, Iftikhar, & Atiq, 2019). This conditional relationship suggests that moral hazard and diversion effects can undermine credit effectiveness, providing theoretical justification for complementary BDS interventions.

Easy access to credit has been seen to be a catalyst to move people from working for others to self-employment. When people have access to credit, they are likely to move from wage employment to self-employment or even reduce the working days of their labour activity and increase their self-employment activities, thereby increasing their income and savings (Khaleque, 2011). Access to credit

raises the welfare of the household. This impact is more on female borrowers than their male counterparts. It does reduce the rate of poverty for those who participated and increase the ability to pay fees for children's schooling (Khandker & Samad, 2014). In Ghana, Credit has been found to aid the economic development and welfare improvement of business owners and their workers. This positive impact can be seen as an indirect one as the improvement in the welfare of the SME owners did not come from the performance or profitability of their businesses. Micro-credit beneficiaries have been found to not only use the funds in their businesses but use the funds to pay school fees, medical cares, salaries and wages of their employees, etc (Akoto-Sampong, 2011). While beneficial for welfare, this diversion pattern explains why credit alone may not translate into business growth, providing empirical justification for the integrated approach proposed in this study.

Policymakers in Ghana over the years have been paying attention to SMEs because of the contribution that SMEs make to the economy. With the little credit provided to the sector, SMEs have been able to start producing goods of value and provision services locally. They provide most goods that hitherto have been imported extensively. They also now provide services to clients that are outside Ghana and thus performing well in exports. As noted by President Nana Addo Dankwa Akufo-Addo, "SMEs are the backbone of Ghana's economy, contributing 70% to our GDP and constituting 92% of businesses" (Ministry of Finance, 2024). Over these years in Ghana, small and medium enterprises have provided approximately 80 percent of total employment and accounted for some 60 percent of the country's GDP, with over 90 percent of business enterprises being SMEs (Sasu, 2025). In Ghana, the high cost of credit and difficulty in accessing credit are the major inhibitors of the economy. The banks are not ready to extend credit that is customized to meet the needs of the small business as the interest rates are very high and not affordable to the SME owners (Dennis, 2018).

Cross-country evidence reinforces these patterns while revealing methodological variations. Credit from banks has enabled SMEs to embrace technology for their operations (Long & Ombongi, 2018). The growth of SMEs is achieved when they have access to credit (Osano & Languitone, 2016, p. 1). SMEs in the farming business have recorded high productivity, income and profitability when given credit for their businesses. The poverty level of those that use credit is also better than other farmers that do not use or have access to credit. Credit made in sufficient quantity goes a long way in reducing poverty levels and grows the business of the farmers (Adewara et al., 2018). For 10 European countries, namely: Spain, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Turkey and the United Kingdom, domestic credit provided by the banking sector of these countries proved to positively impact their economic growth (Korkmaz, 2015). The banking sector of the U.S.A which was deregulated enabled easy access to credit for business owners, resulting in improved employment claims and productivity of the businesses. Young firms were most impacted by the deregulation (Bai, John [jianqiu], Carvalho, & Phillips, 2017).

Yet the empirical literature reveals concerning contradictions. In Nigeria, credits from microfinance banks have been seen to have a positive but weak relationship with economic development in the long run. It has also been seen that more funds go to the banks than what the banks release to businesses. This little going out of the credit providers may affect the nation's economic development (Oluyombo, 2011). Overall, credit providers like micro-finance banks have performed poorly averagely in providing credits to SMEs. This has in turn led to poor growth of SMEs, capital accumulation of the businesses and poor contribution of the SMEs to economic growth and development (Wilfred, Max, Michael, Moses, & Norman, 2013). Access to credit can give a modest positive impact but cannot give an impact that is transformative. So access to credit can only give a short term positive effect in terms of an increase in the supply of labour (Banerjee, Karlan, & Zinman, 2015, pp. 1–18).

For women that own SMEs, when enough credit is provided in form of micro-credit through women initiative programs, the hardship of the women are usually eliminated. Credits help women SME owners to enhance their styles of life and remove their economic hardship (Maheswaranathan & Kennedy, N.D). About 70% of SME that are owned by women are not served or are underserved by financial institutions. At this rate, there is an SME financial gap of about 285 billion U.S. Dollars. This credit gap is mostly related to businesses owned by women (Stupnytska et al., 2014). However, women who accessed credit saw an improvement in the welfare of their households more than those who did not have access to

credit. The findings also show that despite the positive impact of credit on household headed by women, loan approvals were more for men than women (Kurke & Negash, 2010). Men who were given credit and also training reported a 54% increase in profit. But there was no impact on women who also received credits and training. The family pressures that the women undergo impacted negatively their decisions to invest in businesses (Fiala, 2013).

Critical examination reveals several limitations. The original idea of microfinance was to empower the poor to grow and get to the level where they can easily access credit from commercial banks. But unfortunately, most of these poor people are not able to move beyond the microfinance institution because they are now addicted to it. This is as a result of savings with microfinance bank that are compulsory, interest rates that are high, cost of transactions that is also high, multiple times of borrowing and the poor borrower not being able to save for future investments (Koomson & Peparah, 2014). Borrowers who take credit from multiple sources do use these loans for consumption more often than investing in businesses. As those who used it for businesses profit more and gain more income than those who used it for consumption (Burki, 2010). Access to credit by young SME owners contributes to the generation of income and reduction in youth unemployment (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2015, pp. vi–vii). Yet access to credit has been seen to reduce school attendance of young adults because borrowers who had access to credit expanded their small businesses, thus increasing the demand for labour of young adults between the ages of 16 and 19 years old (Augsburg, Haas, Harmgart, & Meghir, 2012).

A credit service term that's favourable, that's when credit is customized, usually has a positive significant impact on the economic development of SME owners (Tumwine, 2015). When SMEs learn how to document their operations and keep information that pertains to their finances, transactions, personal characteristics which are all very important in their creditworthiness assessment, credit providers will continue to give SMEs easy access to credit. This Access to credit will improve SMEs access to important inputs, business diversification, productivity and profitability which ensures robust economic growth and development (Eton, Mwosi, Mutesigensi, & Ebong, 2017). This finding directly supports the information synergy channel in the conceptual framework: BDS provision generates soft information about borrower quality and business practices, potentially improving both credit allocation and risk management outcomes.

This comprehensive review reveals a clear pattern: credit access can generate significant positive impacts on SME performance and economic development, but effectiveness depends critically on implementation design, institutional context, and complementary interventions. Studies showing positive impacts typically feature mechanisms that address multiple constraints simultaneously—financial access, information asymmetries, and risk management—while studies showing null or negative effects often involve isolated credit provision without complementary support. This empirical pattern provides strong justification for the integrated credit-BDS approach proposed in this study. By combining customized credit with participatory BDS, the integrated model addresses the multidimensional constraints that explain heterogeneous outcomes in existing literature. The risk management framework formalized as $SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$ finds support in studies demonstrating that successful credit interventions typically include features that reduce business volatility and enhance repayment capacity.

3.2 CREDIT AND SME PROFITABILITY

The ratio used in measuring the performance of firms is profitability. It is an important component of the financial report of every organization. A firm's profitability tells the ability of the company in generating incomes for a given period at the rate of capital stock, turnover or assets (Margaretha and Supartika 2016a). To know the factors that guarantee the profitability of a business is the focus of many business owners and managers in their planning strategies. The sole motive of every business firm is profit. When SMEs apply for loans, the credit providers consider the profitability of the business as the loan application is processed (Yadav 2012).

As SMEs are more profitable when given credit, this tends to add more profits and growth in the coming years of their operations. (Margaretha and Supartika 2016a). The amount of credit available to SMEs affects the monthly income of the businesses and the ability to repay their loans (Akerle 2019, p. 1). The post income of SMEs was found to be affected positively by the frequency of loan taken by the owners. Those who have taken loans multiple times within a period of time were seen to be doing well and better than those who do not take loans or those who take loan less frequently (Sebhatu 2012). Farmers get equipment that is quite an expensive and modern, which they cannot previously afford when not giving any credit. They are able to buy fertilizers, improved seeds, and tractors thereby increasing the scale of production and output (Ahmad, 2011; Nosiru, 2010). A couple of findings were made by (Kibet et al. 2015). Their study found out that microfinance credits have a positive impact on SMEs' performance. Credit facilities that are "client-oriented and not product-oriented" sustains and fastens the growth of SMEs. The study also found out that the credit services rendered by microfinance and commercial banks are below par and thus affecting SMEs productive activities which also makes it difficult for most of them to escape poverty. They concluded that loans to SMEs can relieve their credit challenges and set them on the part of profitability. Microfinance and small loans centre (MASLOC) is an initiative of the Government of Ghana to assist SMEs with credit facilities. A study on the impact of the credit from the initiative shows that the sales performance of the beneficiaries increased significantly. Access to credit from MASLOC was found to be positively impacting the performances of the businesses (Akoto-Sampong 2011).

In India, when credit to SMEs was subsidized, the borrowing by entrepreneurs increased and earnings from exports increased by 20% (twenty percent) (Kapoor et al. 2012). In the U.S, a study on the impact of credit programs shows that credit increases the self-employment profits of the business owners. The commercial loans extended to the entrepreneurs show the efficacy of credit in raising profits of the business within the period under review (Alam 2013, p. 24). Credit credits from microfinance institutions were found to add to the improvement of SMEs' financial performance. Every loan taken by the business owners increased the return on asset (ROA) of the business in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya (Kibet et al. 2015). In Nigeria, it was found that credit facilities from banks do not impact on the creation of jobs. This was seen to be a result of the high interest rates that the borrowers are made to pay for loans. The high interest rates charged erodes the profits of the businesses making it difficult for them to grow and employ people. So the unemployment rate in Nigeria continues to go high because of poorly structured credits from banks in Nigeria (Nnabu et al. 2017). The success and growth of SMEs can have a positive impact on job creation for youths which will, in turn, bring in a social change that is positive. Identifying and creating an easy source of funding for SMEs in Nigeria will enable the SMEs to be successful and grow (Watse 2017). In Nigeria where farmers depended more on internally generated revenue, the study shows that the financial challenges of SMEs owners were alleviated a bit by few financial institutions that provided microcredit with high interest charges (Abiola 2011). In southern Mali farmers who make higher returns do select themselves into borrowing. At they borrow, they become more productive adding more to their revenues. (Beaman et al. 2014).

However, a start-up business that does not have easy access to credit have reported experiencing reduced profitability and growth of businesses. Most of them are seen to be risky by credit providers and therefore do not give them loans to run their businesses (Banerjee 2014). The current commercialization model of the Micro-credits scheme has been found to not grow businesses, increase revenue and welfare that is subjective. The current model has rather led to an increase in risk management, fewer businesses and low welfare of the owners. This is quite in contrast to the popular opinion that credit improves businesses and the lifestyle of the owners (Karlan and Zinman 2011). The commercialization has gone

overboard making it difficult for SMEs to reap the benefits of the loans because of the stringent loan conditions from the credit providers.

So access to credits remains the source of sufficient problems for the SMEs owners. (Belás et al. 2016, p. 2), (Ambrozio et al.) (2017) and other authors have shown that removing credit challenges enables firms to enhance their performance in profitability. Banerjee and Duflo (2014) hve it that improving firms' access to credit improves the production process without "crowding out with other forms of credit".

3.3 CREDIT AND LOAN REPAYMENT

Credit provider provides funds to SME owners who need them for their businesses. The credit providers generate their incomes from the activity. Though the credit providers want such deals, they only desire to give credit to those SME owners who can timely and fully repay the loans (SCORE Association 2013). But

"Loan defaults continue to be a major challenge that confronts financial institutions in developing countries and this impedes their potential role in sustainable development" (Baidoo et al. 2020). But despite the level of this loan repayment default, governments and policymakers have not come up with enough policies and strategies to curb this problem. Many credit schemes are being rolled out regularly to give SMEs easy access to credit but little has been done to ensure that the loans are repaid timely and in full. (Yadav 2012) in his study found out that loan repayment after receiving credit remains a challenge to the SME owners. He attributed the following as reason why SME owners default on loans repayment: Diverting/Siphoning off funds, Lack of professionalism, Low technology innovations & cost inefficiency, Failure by promoters to bring their contribution, Inadequate product branding & marketing tie-up, under finance by banks, hence over private borrowings and Delay in receiving payments from big corporate. Multidimensional factors contribute to low credit recovery by the FIs. These factors can be summarized under borrowers' wrong attitude to credit repayment, FIs' staff weak skills and corrupt tendency, and poor infrastructural provision by the government. Arguably, these factors have a direct effect in encumbering genuine effort at alleviating poverty in Nigeria through the instrumentality of microcredit. This calls for a change in strategy especially on the part of the MFIs in reducing the incidence of low credit recovery. (Nkamnebe and Idemobi 2011).

Loan repayment remains a challenge in the banking industry. Many financial institutions have been found to experience low credit recovery. The causes of the low credit repayment have been found to be the bad attitude of SME owners, staff of the banks that are corrupt, and poor financial structure from the regulatory bodies (Nkamnebe and Idemobi 2011). Most business owners take up loans for their business activities but end up diverting the funds to other household needs making it very difficult for them to repay. Most banks do not do due diligence to find the motive behind the need for business loans and the usage.

The conditions that come with credit from banks and other credit providers make it difficult for most SME owners to repay their loans timely. The credits come with short repayment periods which makes it difficult for most SMEs to repay the loans. But credit guarantees have been found to improve the conditions of loans. The improvements have been recorded in the form of the less strict requirement for collaterals, quicker loan processes, frequent provision of loans, reduced interest rate, bigger loan amount and a repayment period that's stretched. These improvements which Loan repayment is one of

them have all been termed ‘financial additionality’. This brings overall improvement to the SME owners and the economy at large (Barungi 2017). Credit providers all over the world as part of their loan conditions, do not give grace periods after advancing loans to the business owners to reduce risk. Unfortunately, this affects the growth and unprofitability of these SMEs. This study has shown that when the credit borrowers are given a window period of two months before they start repaying their loans, there is an increase in business investment, profitability and incomes. (Field et al. 2011). Most practices of insolvency do not help SMEs in easy access to loans and repayment. Repayment is assured when SMEs are provided with collateral registries that promote adequate legal and institutional protections. (Khaleque 2010). Another way to ensure repayment of credit is by enforcing savings and providing education to borrowers in urban and rural environments. (La Huerta 2010, p. 1). For borrowers who have fewer outside options to access credit, always have a higher rate of repayment because they do not have outside options. They tend to deposit more because they know that the more they deposit, the more they are likely to get more loans from financial institutions. There is connecting link between the deposit rate and the repayment rate. When the deposit rates are quite high the poor people see the need to deposit more to qualify for more loans. Additionally, high repayment rate and volume of deposit qualify them for more loans. (Kowalik and Martinez-Miera 2010)

SME loan repayment challenges are well-documented globally. In Ghana, the ratio of non-performing loans (NPLs) to total gross loans was reported at 20.58% in 2023 according to the World Bank (2024). Another source indicates the NPL ratio stood at 20.6% in 2023, noting a 39.1% increase from the previous year (IMF, 2024). More recent data from CEIC Data shows the NPL ratio at 21.8% in December 2024 (CEIC, 2025). The "Total Non-Performing Loans Net of Provisions to Capital" in Ghana was 12.91 in 2023 (ReportLinker, 2025). Reports indicate that rising non-performing loans have been a concern for the banking sector (Bank of Ghana, 2023). Bank credit to the private sector as a percent of GDP declined to 8.65% in 2023 from 11.27% in 2022 (The Global Economy, 2024), while domestic credit to the private sector was reported at 9.45% of GDP in 2023 (World Bank, 2024). The share of total outstanding credit to the private sector increased slightly to 91.6% by the end of Q4 2023 (BOG, 2023). One contributing factor to these defaults is inadequate borrower assessment by financial institutions. Thorough evaluation of an SME owner's character, the business's capacity to generate sufficient revenue for repayment, and the availability of collateral to mitigate risk are critical for reducing default rates. Furthermore, credit facilities with inflexible or poorly structured terms and conditions can hinder repayment. This assessment challenge is further supported by empirical evidence. Research by (Klinger, Castro, Szenkman, & Khwaja, 2013), using a psychometric-based credit scoring model found that SMEs exhibit a 20 to 40 percent probability of defaulting on their loans, which aligns with observed NPL rates in countries like Ghana. In Ghana, the credit facilities also do not have terms and conditions that make it easy for the loans to be repaid (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2020).

Repayment of loans extended to individuals is hard to get by credit providers. Because of information asymmetry, a loan given to groups is repaid faster than one given to an individual SME owner. The banks in the rural area serve the informal sector by providing microcredit. The credit providers make sure that the SME owners are organized in groups whereby each member of a group guarantees the repayment of a loan of another member within the group to avoid default. (Adjei 2012). Repayment is assured because of the joint liability of the loan which makes the group pressurize those individual members that are dragging their feet. This also reduces moral hazard and adverse selection which is quite common when it comes to credit administration and processes. Loan repayment remains an issue as most SME owners do not fulfil their repayment obligation (Dubale and Beshir 2020). The authors added that SME farmers who take part in business development initiatives always repay their loans.

The ideas from the exercise help them to be profitable and thereby generating enough income to repay their loans. They also know that if they don't pay back their debts, it will affect them in the future when they apply for a credit facility. Additionally, the authors found out that social ceremonies by SME owners affect their loan repayment rates. The celebrants spend a lot of money and other resources on the celebration of these social ceremonies that are usually very expensive which they cannot ordinarily afford. The number of livestock that they have determined their payment rate. More livestock means less default rate as the livestock can be sold to pay off the debts when payment is due. When the SME owners in a group have other sources of income in addition to their main business, they tend to repay their loans faster (Dubale and Beshir 2020). To ensure repayment for group members, many credit providers introduced credit ceiling as a form of risk management mechanism and there was also a defined limit on the highest amount of credit that can be given to a borrower to ensure loan repayment. Members of a group were meant to be critical of their fellow members to avoid default in loan repayments. Group members and the credit provider charged heavy fees on those who defaulted in their loan repayments (Njeri and Wanyoike 2014).

Loan repayment is negatively impacted when an SME is not financially healthy, bankrupt, low-profit margins, poor business growth and inefficiency of employees (Lin et al. 2012, p. 548; World Bank 2018). Easy access to credit, no doubt has increased assets ownership and network. But it has increased the level of deaths as a result of the inability to repay the loans (Khandker and Samad 2014).

3.4 BDS, business performance, profitability and economic development.

Support that is not financial when (not) combined with credit has been seen not to have any impact on the performance of SMEs in Sabah, Malaysia. (Ombi et al. 2018a). Business development services have so been provided by microfinance institutions as social intermediation service in form of self-confidence development and training of entrepreneurs. The training are usually on technology, marketing, production, and analysis of sectors (Barungi 2017).

“There is a positive relationship between business development services and performance” (Okeyo et al. 2014). This was also confirmed in a study that shows that BDS in form of training and counselling bring about ‘personal maturity skills’ and ‘managerial skills’ of the SME owners which then, in turn, results in better performance of the businesses in terms of profitability and growth (Astuti et al. 2019). It has been found that advising which is a form of business development service is effective in bringing about the best in entrepreneurs. In a publicly funded business development service that was delivered by advising, the revenue and access to finance were positively impacted. The outcome was hugely from the number of hours of advising. The hours of advising received determined the level of knowledge acquired by the business owners which also impacted the growth of sales and credit received (Cumming and Fischer 2012b, p. 480). The quality of the advice which depends wholly on the capabilities of the advisors and the capabilities of the SME owner receiving the advice determines how successful the Business development service will be. There is a “significant relationship between receipt of advice and the development of internationalization-related knowledge and competencies”. (Cumming et al. 2014)

Information that is critically needed by SMEs in form of business development services are financial and management accounting, taxation and how to plan strategically (Haron et al. 2010). Business advisory services do not improve the competitive advantage of SMEs. SME owners do not see any value added to them by the BDS providers. (Haron et al. 2010). Orientation for SME owners in terms

of taking risk, innovations, being proactive and aggressive impact positively on the performance of businesses. After the orientation, there was an improvement in the growth of the SMEs' customer base, business growth, learning and finance (Herlinawati et al. 2019).

In developing countries like Ghana, When financial literacy is provided through BDS, SMEs perform better financially and also grow (Agyapong and Attram 2019; Okello et al. 2017). Also in Ghana, the use of programs for business development have been seen to help in the improvement of the experience of women who are business owners (Asare-Bediako et al. 2016a).

A study of SMEs in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) countries shows that the existing programs to support SMEs in form of subsidized credit and training are not adequate to ensure the success of the SMEs that is sustainable. The business development services have not impacted much on the SMEs performances (Al-Yahya and Airey 2013). In Tanzania, it was found that business development service in form of training has a negative relationship with access to finance by SMEs (Badi et al. 2019). Business development service was seen to reduce SMEs access to finance which also hampered their growth and performance. This is coming as a result of charges imposed on the SMEs by the BDS providers. The charges for the training imposed on the SMEs compromise their ability in getting credit as they may not have more to spare for exorbitant interest charges and meeting other loan conditionality. Business development service in form of technical assistance and training affected the performance of SMEs who benefited from the program in Ethiopia. The impact on those who did not benefit from the BDS program was found to be insignificant (Mengstie 2016). The program did not make any difference between the beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries.

Financial institutions give business development services in form of advice to SMEs to enable them to grow their businesses. Advisory service on business can help improve the impact of credit given to SMEs (BlueOrchard 2017). Simple accounting and bookkeeping practices are introduced to them to mitigate the problems behind their business failures which is difficult access to credit. The financial services and those services that are not financial complements each other making it easier for the SME owners to be profitable in their business and repay their loans timely and also enable them to pay insurance premiums (FinDev Gateway 2020).

Financial literacy has always been seen as only a classroom thing but current researches has shown that financial education needs to be added to financial products to change the behaviour, skill, and capacity of women entrepreneurs most especially. (Women's World Banking 2015). Having the right financial services alone cannot help young people to overcome the challenges that they face in businesses. The youths are still seen as high-risk people and thus need capacity building which will make it easy for them to grow more in their businesses (Storm et al. 2010). The guidance on how to access credit can be through business development services because "there is a relationship between small business support and access to finance by SMEs". (Osano and Languitane 2016, p. 1). BDS play a role that is very significant in getting easy access to finance by start-up SMEs (Mazanai and Fatoki 2012).

3.5 CREDIT, BDS, GROWTH AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The sustainability of business can be achieved when SME owners are supported with credit and guidance provided to them on their business activities (Nkamnebe and Idemobi 2011). Financial knowledge and behaviour can be improved when the education of finances is combined with easy access

to credit. When these two are provided, businesses find it very easy to assess credit using credit cards with high approval rates. (Klein et al. 2013, pp. 3–34)

Using randomized control trial in Indonesia, it was found that SME owners who received credits bundled with business development service in form of training and counselling, recorded an increased in annual profits. The owners who said business management was challenging to them also benefited from the bundling. The challenge with the bundling was that the financial service providers did not see any increase in profit. The bundling was not a win-win initiative as the clients benefited more than the financial service providers (Avdeenko et al. 2019, p. 7). In Malaysia, it was found that only financial support impacted positively on the performance of SMEs, while business development services had no impact on the performance of the SMEs when both financial and non-financial services were bundled (Ombi et al. 2018a).

Where financial services and business services that support SMEs are combined, growth is seen. Most business development services are limited and loan products are not differentiated. Having a business club where the SMEs owners belong improve their self-esteem and the growth of their businesses became a model. The club offered business development service in form of networking, training and counselling. The women club members reported an increase in profits in 2019 after joining within the study time. Even as most of the non-member counterparts were complaining of the bad economy and bad businesses, the women also reported that the number of their employees increased within the period that they joined the club. About 40% of the members reported that they opened more than one branch of their outlets by the time the study was concluded. This is coming as a result of these skills that they got as members of the club. The skills came from training and counselling in customer care, marketing, laws, financial management and operations. Belonging to this club also helped them in decision-making. (Women's World Banking 2020)

Shemwell (2019), posited that training which has been largely used as a form of BDS should be able to impact SMEs as presented below:

Figure 3.1: Theories Of Change (Shemwell 2019)

Using a randomized control trial, the training programs gave a mixed result of the impact on SMEs performance. There was a positive impact on revenue but none on general firm practices and firm performance. It means the type of BDS did not achieve all the above expectations.

Business practices were improved with basic-level management training by increasing employment and/or profit. But the extent of the impact was very small and was different across firms that took part according to their capacity and knowledge about management practices. On average, the impacts on the firms were “economically large but statistically insignificant” (Shemwell 2019).

The mode of delivering BDS by financial providers seems not to be helpful as a study showed that 80% of SME owners had group meetings, which was in form of business development service did not see the need for such a meeting. 5% of the people said they received no financial services despite being in the group meetings. Only 5 entrepreneurs believed that they received business training. The respondents did not use non-financial services because they were not made available by the credit providers in their views (Czura 2010)

3.8 Have Credit and BDS been effective so far?

“If the accumulation, absorption, adaptation, production, and transfer of knowledge are at the centre of successful development, then there is no presumption that markets, on their own, will lead to successful outcomes” (Stiglitz, 2011). SME owners in a learning society that’s monitored and evaluated will create a successful economy. To create a learning society is by identifying the SME sector as “more amenable to learning, with benefits not captured by firms themselves, so that there will be underinvestment in learning. At the root of success is the education system and how it inculcates attitudes toward change and skills of learning” (Stiglitz 2011). Change in attitudes that lead to moral hazard and the right skills

may be the antidote to the loan repayment problem. The ability to get closer and ensure that SMEs utilize the credits for business purposes only seems to be missing in the operations of credit providers.

The current model of delivering BDS do not ensure a “close and intimate working relationship that is based on truth, trust and commitment with the micro-enterprises with which they are dealing” (Nkamnebe and Idemobi 2011). As Fischer et al. (2010) said, BDS companies “either exploit or explore the opportunities when it comes to the provision of BDS”. As Middlemen, the relationship is always exploited (Eba and Struthers, 2019) which retards the growth of the SMEs. The business owners also take the advantage of this gap in relationship to divert the funds to non-business usages (Nkamnebe and Idemobi 2011). This exploitative dynamic creates a vicious cycle where service providers prioritize short-term gains over long-term SME development, while entrepreneurs respond by misusing funds intended for business growth.

The profit made by SME owners does not reflect the Training they might have had over a period. The initial idea that BDS which are usually in form of training yields income is coming from the business owners opening more shops that comes with higher revenues that usually do not yield profits (Barungi 2017). The loan officers or the BDS providers do not “get involved in the operations of the business for effective monitoring, evaluation and correction on the field” (Avdeenko et al. 2019) which makes the impact assessment negligible. This disconnect between training provision and practical implementation suggests that current BDS models fail to bridge the knowledge-action gap that is critical for sustainable business improvement.

No evidence from the reviewed literatures on the impact of combining a participatory BDS and a credit facility tailored according to the size and capacity of the SMEs on the businesses particularly those owned by women, new graduates and youths. Risk as important element of business success is not clearly delineated in the provision of the separated services of credit and BDS (even the ‘bundled’). These gaps in existing literature show the need for more integrated approaches that address the multidimensional nature of SME constraints while explicitly incorporating risk management as a central organizing principle for service delivery.

3.9 Risk Management, Credit, and Business Development Services

The relationship between risk management, credit, and BDS is understudied, despite its potential to enhance SME performance through integration. Existing research treats these elements in isolation, missing systemic synergies. Risk management influences credit access: perceived volatility affects lenders' decisions (Herschel, 2009), and banks impose stricter terms on high-risk SMEs (Altman, 2007). Effective risk management enables SMEs to mitigate uncertainty and improve profitability (Gupta, 2020; Smit, 2017). However, current frameworks fail SMEs. Verbano and Venturini (2013) note that large-corporate models dominate, while SMEs lack resources for implementation. Coviini (2019) emphasizes this mismatch, advocating SME-specific tools.

Credit and BDS are typically delivered separately, which limits their potential effectiveness. Avdeenko et al. (2019) found BDS improved practices but not finances, while Kibet et al. (2015) saw uneven credit impacts. Okeyo et al. (2014) linked BDS to performance but ignored risk outcomes, and Ombi et al. (2018a) found no standalone BDS impact in Malaysia. This pattern suggests that isolated interventions may fail to address the multidimensional nature of SME constraints, particularly when risk factors remain unmanaged.

Mixed results emerge on bundling approaches. Karlan and Zinman (2011) linked credit to risk management but not growth, while McKenzie and Woodruff (2014) saw training improve practices but not profits. Bourlès and Cozarenco (2013) tied BDS to credit access but not risk reduction, and Cumming et al. (2014) connected advisory services to competencies but not risk profiles. These findings indicate that simply combining services without systematic integration may not produce expected synergies, highlighting the need for more sophisticated approaches that explicitly address risk management as a central organizing principle.

Quantifying SME risk remains underdeveloped across current literature. Altman (2007)'s credit models exclude SMEs, and mathematical links between BDS and risk reduction lack formalization (Room, 2020). Deyoung et al. (2008) proposed SME segmentation but did not apply it to integrated services. This gap in risk quantification methods limits the ability to design targeted interventions that match service intensity to risk profiles. Potential pathways for integration exist, such as reducing information asymmetry and operational improvements, which are noted by Beck (2013) and Gunasekaran et al. (2011) but lack integration into comprehensive frameworks. Korkmaz (2015) and Piza et al. (2016) tied credit and BDS to growth and employment but omitted risk mediation mechanisms.

This research addresses these fundamental gaps by developing a framework that mathematically models the relationship between credit-BDS integration and risk reduction through the equation $SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho$. The framework identifies the specific mechanisms through which integration affects different risk-return segments and quantifies the resulting impacts on both business performance and broader economic development outcomes. Unlike previous approaches that treat credit and BDS as separate interventions with independent effects, this study conceptualizes integration as a systematic risk management tool with differentiated impacts across heterogeneous SME risk profiles. The integrated approach provides a comprehensive lens for understanding how customized credit and participatory BDS can function together as a systematic risk management mechanism that enhances SME performance through coordinated risk-return optimization.

The table below presents a curated taxonomy of representative empirical studies drawn from the broader empirical review conducted in this chapter. It is designed to illustrate the diversity of dependent variable definitions, methodological approaches, and geographical contexts that characterise the empirical literature in this field.

Table 3.6: Taxonomy of Representative Empirical Studies: Dependent Variable Definitions, Methodologies, and Key Findings

Variable	Definition of D.V	Author(s)	Case Study	Methodology/ Econometric method	Empirical Result
Credit	Access to finance, which includes its availability and cost, interest rates, fees, and collateral requirements, an obstacle to the operation	Nizaeva and Coskun (2019)	South-Eastern Europe	Ordered probit, and feasible generalized least squares (FGLS)	Economic growth

				of this establishment, which ranged from 0 (no obstacle) to 4 (very severe obstacle).
Bank Loans in Nigeria Naira	PWC (2020)	Nigeria	Survey and Descriptive statistics	Positive but weak relationship with economic development in the long run.
Loans in Ghana Cedis	Akoto-Sampong (2011)	Ghana	Correlation and regression analyses	An indirect positive impact as the improvement in the welfare of the SME owners did not come from the performance or profitability of their businesses but by diverting the credit to funds to pay school fees, medical cares, salaries and wages of their employees, etc.
Microfinance loans (Those who received and those who did not receive)	Prah (2016)	Ghana	Descriptive statistics and paired sampled t-test.	Significant growth was seen in job creation, buying of assets and monthly sales
Loan amount to enterprises as a percentage of GDP	Majeed et al. (2019)	Pakistan	Pooled and fixed effect techniques.	Positively related to economic growth conditioned on the said credit not diverted for household use
Loans (Repaid or defaulted)	Baidoo et al. (2020)	Ghana	Binary probit regression	Impedes banks' potential role in sustainable development.

					Poor loan repayment contribution to the growth of the economy
	Bank loans in Romania Leu	Petrescu and Pop (2015)	Romania	Ordinary least square regression.	
Business Development Service (BDS)					
	Two-day classroom training and/or five individual Counselling sessions (Participants and non-participants)	Avdeenko et al. (2019)	Indonesia	randomized control trial	increased in annual profits when bundled with credit
	Advice via counselling	Cumming et al. (2014)	Canada	Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression	Significant relationship with the development of internationalization-related knowledge and competencies.
	Training and Technical Assistance	Ombi et al. (2018a)	Malaysia	Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis	No impact on the performance of SMEs
	Subsidized or guaranteed loans and grants, and business training, advice And facilitation.	Al-Yahya and Airey (2013)	the Middle East and North Africa (MENA)	Survey and Descriptive Statistics	No sustainable success of the SMEs
	Business Advice	Haron et al. (2010)	Malaysia	Interview	Do not help SMEs. Do not add value to their businesses.
	Training, business linkage (SMEs-banks) and credit guarantee	Badi et al. (2019)	Tanzania	multiple linear regression	A negative relationship with access to finance which hampered their growth and performance
	Market access, input supply	Mengstie (2016)	Ethiopia	linear regression and	No significant difference

services , infrastructure facilities, training and technical assistance				paired sample t-test	between the beneficiaries and non- beneficiaries
Identification, formation, registration and training of entrepreneurs linking them to Financial and support institutions, managerial backstopping, counselling and advice.	Addaney et al. (2016)	Ghana		Descriptive statistics	Builds the capacity of SME owners
Skill acquisition and advice	Asare- Bediako et al. (2016a)	Ghana		bivariate logistic regression	Positive relationship with women entrepreneurs' experience of improvement in business

(Author, 2025)

Note: The above should not be interpreted as an exhaustive listing of all works consulted. The comprehensive empirical review, which encompasses both foundational contributions and more recent studies published up to 2024, is documented throughout the body of this chapter. Relevant and applicable citations, spanning a substantial range of peer-reviewed scholarship, are integrated at each thematic section of the review.

Summary

This empirical review reveals that while credit access and business development services have demonstrated positive impacts on SME performance and economic development, their effectiveness remains highly contingent on implementation design, institutional context, and the presence of complementary interventions. The evidence consistently shows that isolated provision of credit or BDS often fails to achieve transformational outcomes, with studies documenting significant heterogeneity in results across different contexts and methodologies.

The review identifies three critical gaps in existing literature that justify the integrated approach proposed in this study. First, current interventions treat credit and BDS as separate solutions rather than recognizing their potential synergies in addressing multidimensional SME constraints. Second, risk management remains largely absent from both credit provision and BDS delivery, despite its fundamental importance to business sustainability. Third, the literature lacks empirical evidence on sustained, participatory BDS models that are tailored to specific SME risk-return profiles.

The analysis of gender-differentiated impacts, cross-country evidence, and sectoral variations demonstrates that successful interventions typically address multiple constraints simultaneously while incorporating mechanisms for monitoring and guidance. This pattern provides strong empirical justification for the integrated credit-BDS framework developed in Chapter 2, which positions systematic risk management as the organizing principle for coordinated service delivery. The

framework's mathematical formalization through $SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$ addresses this critical gap by explicitly incorporating risk reduction as a measurable outcome of integrated interventions.

Moving forward, the review establishes the foundation for examining how integrated credit-BDS interventions can function as systematic risk management mechanisms that outperform separate service provision, setting the stage for the methodological approach and empirical analysis that follow in subsequent chapters.

CHAPTER FOUR

Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the comprehensive methodological framework employed to investigate the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services and their impacts on SME profitability, loan repayment, and economic development in Ghana. The research design addresses critical gaps in understanding how coordinated financial and non-financial support mechanisms can enhance SME performance outcomes compared to traditional separate service delivery approaches.

The methodological approach builds upon established theoretical foundations while incorporating innovative analytical techniques to address the complexity of integrated service delivery effects. Given the multifaceted nature of SME performance determinants and the challenges inherent in measuring integration benefits, this study employs mixed-method econometric approaches combining panel data analysis (SME primary dataset), time series techniques (Ghana secondary dataset), and clustering methodologies.

The chapter systematically establishes the theoretical linkages between conceptual frameworks and empirical specifications, ensuring robust measurement of integration effects across multiple performance dimensions. Particular attention is paid to addressing potential endogeneity concerns, measurement challenges associated with zero-value observations in SME financial data, and the need for comparable metrics across diverse business characteristics.

Key methodological include the application of inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS) transformations to handle zero-value financial variables, comprehensive control variable specifications addressing firm-specific and macroeconomic factors, and novel risk-return clustering analysis enabling targeted intervention design. The empirical strategy incorporates both separate and integrated effects modeling to provide a robust understanding of service delivery mechanisms.

This methodological foundation enables rigorous testing of hypotheses regarding the superiority of integrated approaches while providing practical insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and development practitioners seeking to optimize SME support mechanisms in emerging market contexts.

4.2 Research Design

A research design is the plan or a fundamental plan for doing research. The reasoning supports the research and enables the drawing of accurate general conclusions. It acts as a road map for finishing a research project and outlines the procedures required to collect data to solve the research issue. A study design sets out a framework for data collection and analysis, including data collection and analysis using qualitative and quantitative approach techniques, as well as questionnaire design and pretesting.

According to Bryman (2009) while designing a study, the researcher must prioritise the following factors: Identifying and describing the causal connections that exist between variables; Extrapolating results to a larger group of individuals than the participants in the study; Perceiving and interpreting behaviour in the context of its social setting; and Recognize sociological trends and their temporal relationships (Bryman, 2009, p.31).

This study employs a quantitative research design to examine the impact of integrated SME support services on firm performance and economic development using Ghana as a case study. Case study is usually used for an in-depth study of a particular situation.

The design uses panel data analysis and cross-sectional surveys to measure relationships between formal/informal credit access, business development services, and SME performance indicators.

Primary data collection involves structured questionnaires administered to SME owners, while secondary data encompasses macroeconomic indicators and firm-level financial data.

This quantitative approach enables statistical testing of hypotheses and provides empirical evidence on the effectiveness of integrated support mechanisms in enhancing SME performance and contributing to economic development.

4.3 Population

The target population for this study comprises Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) operating in Ghana. According to the Ghana Statistical Service (2021), SMEs constitute approximately 92% of all businesses in Ghana, employing over 85% of the manufacturing sector workforce. The study focuses on formally registered SMEs with 5-199 employees, spanning manufacturing, services, and trade sectors across Ghana's ten administrative regions.

The population includes SMEs that are operational and have accessed either formal or informal financial services. This criterion ensures respondents have sufficient operational experience to provide meaningful insights on credit access, business development services, and performance outcomes relevant to the study's objectives.

4.4 Sampling and Sampling Technique

Sampling is a method for choosing individuals or a part of the population in order to derive statistical conclusions and estimate population characteristics.

This study employs a quasi-snowball sampling technique to select SMEs through established business associations and support organizations. Unlike traditional snowball sampling, this approach uses organizational networks as initial contact points to systematically identify and recruit SME participants.

The sampling process involves contacting registered SMEs through business associations who then refer other members within their networks. This method ensures access to both formal and informal SME operators while maintaining some degree of randomization within organizational clusters.

Table 4.1: Business Organizations and Associations

Organization	Type	Coverage	Citation
Association of Ghana Industries (AGI)	Manufacturing/Industrial	National	(AGI, 2021)
Ghana Association of Women Entrepreneurs (GAWE)	Women-owned SMEs	National	(GAWE, 2025)
Association of Small Scale Industries (ASSI)	Small-scale industries	National/Regional	(ASSI, 2025)
Empretec Ghana Foundation	Entrepreneurship training	National	(Empretec, 2021)
Enablis Entrepreneurial Network	Networking/Mentorship	National	(Enablis, 2021)
Ghana Export Promotion Authority (GEPA)	Export promotion	National	(GEPA, 2021)

Ghana Chamber of Young Entrepreneurs (GCYE)	Youth entrepreneurship	National	(Gcyegh, 2021)
Ghana Employers Association (GEA)	Employer representation	National	(GEA, 2021)
Ghana Enterprises Agency	SME development	National	(Ghana Enterprises Agency, 2021)
Ghana National Chamber of Commerce	Commerce/Trade	National	(Ghana Chamber, 2021)
Ghana Venture Capital Trust Fund (VCTF)	Venture capital financing	National	(Ghana VCTF, 2017)
National Entrepreneurship & Innovation Programme (NEIP)	Start-up support	National	(NEIP, 2021)
National Union of Ghanaian Students (NUGS)	Student entrepreneurship	National	(UNHCR, 2021)
TechnoServe Ghana	Rural business development	National	(World Bank, 1998)
Youth Employment Agency (YEA)	Youth employment/entrepreneurship	National	(Youth Employment Agency, 2021)

Source: compiled by Author, 2025

A target sample of 450 SMEs was selected proportionally across Ghana's ten administrative regions and key sectors through the organizational networks listed in Table 4.1. This sample size was determined using Cochran's (1977) formula for estimating a proportion in a large population:

$$n = Z^2 \cdot \frac{p(1-p)}{e^2}$$

where $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level), $p = 0.5$ (maximum variability assumed), and $e = 0.05$ (5% margin of error), yielding a minimum required sample of 384. The target of 450 was set above this minimum to account for anticipated non-response and incomplete returns. Of the 450 questionnaires distributed, 375 were fully completed and returned (83.3% response rate), comfortably exceeding the minimum threshold. The two-period panel structure is consistent with comparable empirical studies of SME performance in sub-Saharan Africa that face similar data availability constraints (Quartey et al., 2017; Abor and Quartey, 2010). For the macro-level component, 54 annual observations (1970–2023) exceed the minimum recommended series length for ARDL estimation and provide adequate statistical power for identifying both short-run dynamic effects and long-run equilibrium relationships (Pesaran, Shin, and Smith, 2001; Narayan, 2005).

4.5 Data and Sample Size

This study utilises both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to SME owners across Ghana's ten administrative regions. The survey instrument was distributed to a total of 450 SMEs selected through the quasi-snowball sampling

technique described in Section 4.4, with questionnaires administered via the QuestionPro.com online platform. Of the 450 questionnaires distributed, 375 were fully completed and returned, representing a response rate of 83.3%. The questionnaire was designed to capture firm-level information on credit access, business development services utilisation, and key performance indicators including profitability and loan repayment over the survey reference period. Secondary data covers macroeconomic indicators spanning 1970–2023, sourced from the World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI) database, the IMF World Economic Outlook, Bank of Ghana statistical bulletins, and Ghana Statistical Service publications. Data on registered Business Development Services firms were additionally sourced from the Registrar General's Office, Accra, Ghana.

Table 4.2: Summary of Data Collected

Data Type	Source	Period / Coverage	Key Variables / Indicators	Observations
Primary (Survey)	SME questionnaires via QuestionPro.com	2022–2023	Credit access (formal & informal), BDS utilisation, net profit, revenue, loan repayment, firm size, firm age, technology spending	375 respondents (83.3% response rate from 450 distributed)
Secondary (Macroeconomic)	World Bank WDI; IMF IFS; Bank of Ghana; Ghana Statistical Service (GSS)	1970–2023	Economic development (HDI/IHDI/MPI), credit to private sector, interest rates, inflation, exchange rate	Annual time series (54 observations)
Secondary (BDS Firms)	Registrar General's Office, Accra, Ghana	1970–2023	Number of registered BDS firms (management consultancy, computing services, financial leasing, information services, insurance auxiliary, legal services, professional & technical activities)	Annual time series (54 observations)

Source: Author (2025)

The time series dataset spans 1970 to 2023, covering 54 annual observations. This period was selected for three reasons. First, 1970 represents the earliest year for which consistent and comparable macroeconomic data on Ghana are available across the key sources used i.e. the World Bank WDI, IMF International Financial Statistics, and Bank of Ghana statistical bulletins. This ensured data quality and completeness. Second, the period captures all major structural shifts in Ghana's economic and financial development, including the Economic Recovery Programme of the 1980s, financial sector liberalisation in the 1990s, and the post-2000 growth era, all of which are relevant to the evolution of credit and BDS provision for SMEs. Third, 54 annual observations are considered adequate for the ARDL bounds testing approach employed, which requires a minimum of approximately 30 observations for reliable asymptotic inference (Pesaran et al., 2001).

The enterprise-level analysis is based on panel data from 375 SMEs surveyed across Ghana during 2022–2023. The panel structure yields a maximum of 750 observations (375 SMEs × 2 time periods) for the profitability and loan repayment models. Financial performance metrics demonstrate considerable variation across the sample.

Net profits range from losses of GHC43,000 to profits of GHC300,000, averaging GHC5,841, while revenue generation spans from zero to GHC9,700,000 with a mean of GHC368,124, reflecting the

diverse scale of operations within Ghana's SME sector. Bank loans range from zero to GHC2,000,000 with a mean of GHC53,286, and alternative financing reaches up to GHC750,000, averaging GHC32,229. Bank interest rates span from 0 to 60% with a mean of 28.1%, while alternative financing rates extend up to 120% with a mean of 40.5%. Businesses with structured repayment plans show between 0 to 36 instalments (mean: 5), while those without formal plans demonstrate minimal instalment activity (mean: 0, range: 0–12). Formal BDS visits range from zero to 6 annually (mean: 1), while informal peer mentoring shows higher engagement levels of 0 to 18 sessions per year (mean: 4).

Table 4.3 Enterprise-Level Descriptive Statistics — SME Performance (Primary Survey, 2022–2023)

Variable	Observations	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Net Profit (GHC)	750*	5,841	-43,000	300,000
Revenue (GHC)	750*	368,124	0	9,700,000
Bank Loans (GHC)	750*	53,286	0	2,000,000
Alternative Financing (GHC)	750*	32,229	0	750,000
Repayment Instalments (with structured plan)	750*	5	0	36
Repayment Instalments (without structured plan)	750*	0	0	12
Firm Age (years)	375†	3	1	5
Bank Interest Rate (%)	750*	28.1	0	60.0
Alternative Financing Interest Rate (%)	750*	40.5	0	120.0
Formal BDS Visits (annual)	750*	1	0	6
Informal BDS / Peer Meetings (annual)	750*	4	0	18
Technology Investment (GHC)	750*	4,627	0	150,000
Business Size (employees)	375†	9	0	100

* 750 observations = 375 SMEs × 2 time periods (2022 and 2023) for time-varying financial variables. † 375 observations for time-invariant firm characteristics (single-point measurement).

Source: Primary Survey Data (2022–2023)

The macro-level analysis incorporates secondary data from 1970–2023, providing a crucial longitudinal perspective on economic development indicators. The Human Development Index ranges from 0.558 to 0.602, averaging 0.587, while the Inequality-adjusted HDI spans 0.382 to 0.420, with a mean of 0.410. The Multidimensional Poverty Index varies between 0.132 and 0.156, averaging 0.149. The macroeconomic context is captured through lending rates ranging from 0 to 32.8% (mean: 23.8%), inflation varying from 0.4% to 19.3% (mean: 11.4%), exchange rates spanning 1.1 to 5.6 (mean: 3.6),

profit tax rates from 10% to 18.5% (mean: 15.1%), and corruption indices varying from 3 to 4 (mean: 3.6). Business development service provision ranges from 1,267 to 27,569 registered BDS providers annually, while credit provision to the private sector varies between 10.9% and 16.1% of GDP.

Table 4.4: Macro-Level Descriptive Statistics — Economic Development (Time Series, 1970–2023)

Variable	Observations	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Human Development Index (HDI)	54	0.587	0.558	0.602
Inequality-adjusted HDI (IHDI)	54	0.410	0.382	0.420
Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)	54	0.149	0.132	0.156
Bank Lending Rate (%)	54	23.8	0	32.8
Credit to Private Sector (% of GDP)	54	13.5	10.9	16.1
Inflation Rate (%)	54	11.4	0.4	19.3
Exchange Rate (GHC per USD)	54	3.6	1.1	5.6
Profit Tax Rate (%)	54	15.1	10.0	18.5
Corruption Perception Index	54	3.6	3.0	4.0
BDS Providers (registered annually)	54	11,209	1,267	27,569

Note: Time series covers 1970–2023 (54 annual observations). Development indicator observations reflect available UNDP data sub-periods. All macroeconomic variables sourced from World Bank WDI, IMF IFS, Bank of Ghana, Ghana Statistical Service, Transparency International, and UNDP.

Source: Secondary data from Ghana Statistical Service, Bank of Ghana, World Bank, and UNDP (1970–2023)

The survey instrument collected financial data across two or three reference periods depending on the variable type. Monetary variables, specifically formal and informal credit amounts and loan repayment installments were collected for two years: 2022 and 2023 (survey Questions 7–11 and 17–19), as SME owners were able to reliably recall and report financial figures for these two most recent completed financial years at the time of data collection. By contrast, profitability variables used to construct the risk measure. Net profit and total sales revenue were collected for two years 2022 and 2023 (survey Questions 30–31), to enable calculation of the standard deviation of Return on Sales (SD_ROS) as the firm-level risk proxy, which requires a minimum of three data points to yield a meaningful measure of performance volatility. All other firm characteristic variables including firm size, firm age, education level, sector, and location were collected as single-point (current status) observations at the time of survey administration. The panel structure of the primary dataset therefore comprises 375 SMEs observed over two periods (2022 and 2023), yielding a maximum of 750 observations for the profitability and loan repayment models.

4.5 Data Collection and Analysis

This study uses both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through structured questionnaires administered to 450 SME owners across Ghana's ten regions via the quasi-snowball sampling approach through business associations. Secondary data covers macroeconomic indicators

spanning 1970-2023 from World Bank databases, IMF World Economic Outlook, Bank of Ghana statistical bulletins, and Ghana Statistical Service publications.

Data Sources:

Primary: SME questionnaires administered via QuestionPro.com platform to 450 SME owners across Ghana's ten regions, measuring credit access, business performance, and support services utilization.

From 450 distributed questionnaires, 375 were returned and validated, yielding a response rate of 83.3 per cent.

Prior to full deployment, the questionnaire was subjected to a pilot test with a convenience sample of 30 SME owners not included in the main study. Pilot feedback was used to refine question wording, improve the clarity of Likert-scale anchors, and ensure that the dual-year response format requiring 2022 and 2023 figures for financial and operational variables was clearly understood. The finalised instrument was distributed electronically via QuestionPro, which provided secure data storage, automated response tracking, and built-in numeric validation. Distribution was facilitated through registered business associations and SME support organisations across Ghana's ten administrative regions, ensuring all respondents were formally registered SME operators.

The questionnaire was structured in two temporal layers to reflect the mixed cross-sectional and panel design. Part A (Questions 1–6) captured static demographic and firm-level characteristics: gender, age, education, sector, years in operation, and role collected once, forming the cross-sectional dimension. Parts B through E (Questions 7–34) captured dynamic financial and operational variables for both 2022 and 2023: bank loans, interest rates, repayment instalments, alternative finance, BDS engagement frequency, technology expenditure, employees, sales revenue, and net profit, forming the longitudinal dimension of the panel dataset.

Content validity was ensured through systematic alignment of questionnaire items with established constructs in the SME finance literature reviewed in Chapter Three. Construct validity was assessed through expert review of my supervisors with expertise in SME finance and development economics. Reliability of the Likert-scaled items was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with acceptable thresholds ($\alpha \geq 0.70$) confirmed during the pilot phase (Nunnally, 1978). QuestionPro's built-in data validation features further reduced entry errors and enhanced data integrity prior to analysis.

Secondary: Time series data on economic development, credit to private sector, interest rates, inflation, and financial sector indicators from World Bank WDI database, IMF International Financial Statistics, and Ghana statistical services (GSS). Additionally, data regarding registered Business Development Services firms were sourced from the Registrar General's Office in Accra, Ghana, comprising of management consultancy, computing services, financial leasing, information services, insurance auxiliary activities, legal services, professional and technical activities, and vehicle leasing and business support services.

Data Processing: Raw questionnaire data from 375 respondents (83.3% response rate from 450 distributed) underwent cleaning, coding, and validation. Missing values were addressed through listwise deletion for critical variables. Secondary data was harmonized across sources and converted to consistent units for analysis.

4.5.1 Standard Panel Specifications

The profitability and loan repayment models (Hypotheses 1 and 2) employ panel regression analysis using the primary SME dataset of 375 firms observed over two periods (2022 and 2023). The use of panel data rather than a purely cross-sectional design is justified on both theoretical and econometric grounds.

First, panel data allows for the control of unobserved firm-level heterogeneity i.e. time-invariant characteristics such as managerial ability, firm culture, and location-specific advantages that differ across SMEs but cannot be directly measured. In a cross-sectional design, such unobserved heterogeneity becomes embedded in the error term, leading to omitted variable bias and inconsistent estimates. Panel data addresses this through fixed-effects or random-effects specifications that explicitly account for individual-specific effects (Wooldridge, 2010; Baltagi, 2021; Hsiao, 2014).

Second, panel data enables the study of dynamic change over time within the same SME. The profitability and loan repayment outcomes of interest in this study are inherently linked to changes in credit access and BDS utilisation across periods, not merely their levels at a single point in time. A cross-sectional design captures only a snapshot and cannot distinguish whether observed differences across firms reflect genuine effects of integrated services or pre-existing firm characteristics (Baltagi, 2021).

Third, panel data reduces multicollinearity and improves the precision of coefficient estimates by exploiting both the between-firm and within-firm dimensions of variation (Hsiao, 2014). This is particularly important in the present study, where integrated credit-BDS variables are closely related to firm size and age.

A structural limitation of the two-period panel warrants acknowledgement. With $T = 2$, parameter estimates carry wider confidence intervals and are more sensitive to model specification than estimates from longer panels, owing to limited degrees of freedom for identifying time-varying effects (Baltagi, 2008; Nickell, 1981). The firm-level results should therefore be interpreted as directionally indicative rather than definitive causal estimates. Notwithstanding this limitation, the design is consistent with comparable studies in the Ghanaian SME literature and provides a valid basis for preliminary inference (Abor and Quartey, 2010; Quartey et al., 2017). Future research extending the panel to five or more periods would substantially strengthen the precision and generalisability of findings.

In this study, Profitability and loan repayment models (hypothesis 1 and 2) will use panel regression analysis to examine cross-sectional SME performance variations.

The standard panel data specification can be expressed as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 + \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_j X_{jit} + \sum_{p=1}^s \gamma_p Z_{pi} + \delta t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 4.1$$

where Y represents the dependent variable, and X_j and Z_p denote observable and unobserved explanatory variables, respectively (Wooldridge, 2010). The indices i , t , j , and p represent the observation unit, time period, and observable and unobservable explanatory variables, respectively. The shock term ε_{it} satisfies standard regression model criteria. A trend term t accounts for temporal shifts in the intercept. When constant fluctuation assumptions appear excessively restrictive, this trend term may be replaced with dummy variables for each time period except the reference period (Hsiao, 2014).

The X variables constitute the principal variables of interest, while the Z variables represent unobserved variability, forming the model's noise component. The assumption of time-invariant unobserved heterogeneity eliminates the need for time indexation of Z variables.

Given the unobservability of Z variables, equation 4.1 can be reformulated as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 + \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_j X_{jit} + \alpha_i + \delta t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 4.2$$

where $\alpha_i = \sum_{p=1}^s \gamma_p Z_{pi}$. The term α_i represents the undetected effect capturing the cumulative influence of Z variables on Y (Greene, 2018). If α_i correlates with any X variables, regression estimates will exhibit omitted variable bias. Even without such correlation, the presence of α_i typically results in inefficient estimates and inaccurate standard errors in OLS applications (Baltagi, 2021). If X variables comprehensively capture all significant characteristics, the α_i term becomes superfluous, allowing the model to be estimated using pooled OLS regression.

4.5.2 Panel Data Model Types

Panel data models comprise three principal categories: pooled-OLS models, fixed-effects models, and random-effects models (Wooldridge, 2010).

Pooled OLS Model

The pooled model employs constant coefficients similar to cross-sectional analyses:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 + \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_j X_{jit} + \delta t + u_{it} \quad 4.3$$

This model assumes exogenous explanatory variables and expresses the error simply as u_{it} rather than using the decomposition $\alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}$ (Baltagi, 2021). It applies OLS methodology without accounting for the data's cross-sectional and time series characteristics. The pooled model represents the most constrained panel data approach, as it disregards any heterogeneity present in the data (Hsiao, 2014), limiting its application in contemporary research.

Individual-Specific Effects Models

Fixed-effects and random-effects models constitute the remaining two approaches, both accommodating individual-specific effects. These models assume that unobserved variability exists between individual units (in this study, SMEs). When individual-specific effects correlate with independent variables, fixed-effects models are appropriate; when no such correlation exists, random-effects models are preferable (Wooldridge, 2013).

Fixed-Effects Model

The fixed-effects model accommodates heterogeneity by allowing each observational unit to possess a unique intercept value while maintaining uniform slope parameters (Greene, 2018). This approach permits correlation between individual-specific effects and explanatory variables. The term "fixed effect" indicates that while intercepts vary across units, they remain constant over time (Baltagi, 2021). The general fixed-effects specification is:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 + \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_j X_{jit} + u_{it} \quad 4.4$$

The error term is defined as $u_{it} = \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}$ with X_{jit} permitted to correlate with the time-invariant error component α_i while maintaining independence from the idiosyncratic error ε_{it} (Wooldridge, 2010).

Random-Effects Model

While random-effects models also account for heterogeneity, they assume that individual-specific effects are distributed independently of explanatory variables (Hsiao, 2022). The random-effects approach treats α_i as completely random and uncorrelated with explanatory variables, employing feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) estimation (Baltagi, 2021). This model offers the advantage of providing estimates for all coefficients, including time-invariant variables. The general random-effects specification is:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 + \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_j X_{jit} + \delta t + u_{it} \quad 4.5$$

$$\text{where } u_{it} = \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

The term α_i represents the individual-specific effect, and u_{it} denotes the standard error term. In random-effects models, the error term incorporates α_i , with each unit sharing identical slope parameters and a composite error structure (Greene, 2018).

Fixed-effects estimators consistently produce precise estimates but may not always maximize efficiency, while random-effects estimators offer consistency and efficiency when the model is truly

random-effects, but lack consistency when fixed-effects are more appropriate (Hausman, 1978; Bell & Jones, 2015).

4.5.3 Model Selection and Diagnostic Tests

Model selection follows systematic sequencing: correlation analysis, unit root testing, cointegration testing, and multicollinearity assessment. Correlation analysis identifies preliminary relationships between variables. Unit root tests (ADF and PP) determine stationarity properties, with non-stationary series transformed accordingly. Cointegration tests establish long-run equilibrium relationships.

Panel Model Selection

Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Test evaluates the validity of random-effects models based on OLS residuals (Breusch & Pagan, 1980), determining whether random-effects or standard OLS regression is more appropriate. Hausman test assesses whether random-effects estimation approximates fixed-effects estimation for datasets where fixed-effects estimation is considered suitable (Hausman, 1978). This procedure evaluates whether significant differences exist between fixed-effects and random-effects estimators. When differences are insignificant, the random-effects estimator is preferred for efficiency; when differences are significant, the fixed-effects estimator is recommended (Greene, 2018; Bell & Jones, 2015).

Multicollinearity Tests:

- **Correlation Matrix:** To detect potential multicollinearity issues among independent variables, a correlation matrix was constructed following the methodology outlined by Dormann et al. (2013). This approach provides a preliminary assessment of linear relationships between predictors, with correlation coefficients exceeding 0.7 typically indicating problematic levels of multicollinearity (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). If the correlation analysis reveal moderate associations between several economic indicators, but coefficients remain below the critical threshold, it suggest that severe multicollinearity was not an immediate concern in the dataset (Hair et al., 2018). This was used in the panel and time series models.
- **Variance Inflation Factor (VIF):** Variance Inflation Factor ($VIF = 1/(1 - R^2_j)$) (where R^2_j is coefficient of determination from regressing variable j on other explanatory variables) analysis was conducted to provide a more rigorous assessment of multicollinearity, as recommended by O'Brien (2007). VIF quantifies the extent to which the variance of estimated regression coefficients is inflated due to multicollinearity compared to when predictors are uncorrelated. Following guidelines established by Kutner et al. (2005) and James et al. (2013), VIF values exceeding 10 were considered indicative of problematic multicollinearity. The analysis yielded VIF values consistently below this threshold for all model specifications, confirming the absence of severe multicollinearity that could compromise the stability of coefficient estimates (Wooldridge, 2020). This was used in the panel and time series models.
- **Elastic Net (Ridge and Lasso regressions):** As an additional safeguard against potential multicollinearity issues, Elastic Net regularization was implemented, combining the penalties of ridge and lasso regression techniques as outlined by Zou and Hastie (2005):
- $\hat{\beta}^{en} = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \|y - X\beta\|^2 + \lambda_1 \|\beta\|^1 + \lambda_2 \|\beta\|^2 \right\}$, where λ_1 controls lasso penalty and λ_2 controls ridge penalty. This approach helps mitigate multicollinearity by shrinking coefficients toward zero (Hastie et al., 2015). The ridge component stabilizes coefficient estimates when predictors are highly correlated, while the lasso component performs variable selection by reducing some coefficients to zero (Tibshirani, 1996). Cross-validation techniques were employed to determine optimal regularization parameters, following the methodology proposed by Friedman et al. (2010). This was used in the panel and time series models.

Stationarity test: Unit root test

According to Shrestha and Bhatta (2018), the initial step in doing time series analysis is to perform a unit root test." If the results of the unit root test indicate that all variables under analysis are stationary, the OLS technique may be employed to identify the connection between the provided variables. By differencing, a non-stationary time series may be transformed to a stationary one. This was used in the panel and time series models.

Cointegration Tests: The study employed multiple cointegration tests to comprehensively examine long-run relationships between variables in both integrated and separate services models in the time series model (Economic development model i.e. the third hypothesis). Following Pesaran et al. (2001) Bounds test is used to ensure robust inference about cointegrating relationships.

4.5.4 Time series analysis

Economic development models use time series analysis employing autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) methodology to analyse temporal relationships between integrated support services and macroeconomic indicators.

A time series is a collection of consecutive observations of a given variable at a regular interval over a specified time period. The most often seen series have a yearly, quarterly, monthly, weekly, or daily frequency. Economic time series data often exhibit distinctive characteristics such as a clear trend, a high degree of persistence in the face of shocks, increased volatility with time, and meandering and co-movements with other series (Shrestha and Bhatta 2018).

The third hypothesis is examined utilising a framework of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models. For decades, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model has been used to describe the connection between (economic) variables in a time series setting using a single equation. Its popularity comes in part from the fact that cointegration of nonstationary variables is comparable to an error-correction (EC) process, and the ARDL model includes an EC form of reparameterization. The EC representation may be used to test for the presence of a long-run / cointegrating connection (Pesaran et al., 2001). Without establishing if the variables are integrated of order 0 or 1, I(0) or I(1), a limits testing method may be used to make decisive conclusion. Certain time series are inextricably linked by equilibrium forces, despite the fact that the individual time series may shift significantly (Kripfganz and Schneider 2016, pp. 2–8).

In contrast to earlier and conventional cointegration techniques, this methodology offers three benefits. To begin, the ARDL does not require that all variables under investigation be integrated in the same order; it may be used with variables integrated in orders one, zero, or mixed. Second, the ARDL test is much more efficient when dealing with tiny and limited sample sizes. Finally, the model's long-run unbiased estimates are produced using the ARDL method. Thus, there are significant econometric benefits to studying the connection between economic growth and the difficulties confronting SMEs in Ghana using an ARDL model. As a result, in accordance with Kripfganz and Schneider (2016), the ARDL (p, q, q) model is changed as follows:

$$Y_t = \varphi_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta'_i X_{t-i} + \epsilon_{it} \quad 4.6$$

Y_t is Economic development; and the regressors in $(X't)'$ can be purely I(0) or I(1) or co-integrated; β and δ are estimates; φ is the constant; ϵ_{it} is a vector of the error terms – unobservable zero mean white noise vector process (serially not correlated or independent). (Adeleye et al. 2017). The optimal lag orders p and q (possibly different across regressors) can be obtained by minimizing a model selection criterion, e.g. the Akaike information criterion (AIC) or the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) (Kripfganz and Schneider 2016, pp. 2–8).

4.6 THEORETICAL MODEL

Stupnytska et al. (2014) assumption were that business owners will take up credit which determines their business profitability that will impact their real income per capita growth. Stupnytska et al. (2014) used “outstanding loans to SMEs from commercial banks as a share of GDP” to measure the amount of credit received by businesses. They did that using descriptive analysis and a linear regression function to analyse the impact of credit on SMEs in a region.

The assumption of (Cumming and Fischer 2012a) was that business advisory service which is a business development service can foster entrepreneurial performance which sales revenue was used as the indicator. The adversary service is human capital that is an input of production. They argued that the total number of hours spent by advisors advising or counselling SMEs in a credit program has an impact on the sales revenue.

In the above, both impacts of credit and BDS were treated separately. The two are joined in this study to access the impact of integrating the services on profitability. An earlier attempt to econometrically model the impact on profitability when both financial and non-financial services are bundled was made by McKernan (2002). He combined the credit and human capital theories. McKernan (2002) assumption was that a business owner in a rural area will automatically take up both credit and non-credit services at the same time from the same source which will determine his/her profitability, π^*_{ij} .

$$\pi^*_{ij} = C_{ijk}\alpha \quad (4.7)$$

McKernan (2002) defined $C_{ijk}\alpha$ as a “dummy for participating in a credit program such that $C_{ijk}\alpha$ is 1 if an individual in the household participates in program k and $C_{ijk}\alpha = 0$ otherwise”. McKernan (2002) considered credit (C) and non-credit services (α) as a bundle. The variable is a dummy variable showing that those who received credit, automatically received the non-credit part of the service.

The study assumes that

$$\pi = f(C) \quad (4.8)$$

where C is a dummy variable with $C=1$ if the business owner received credit (which has a non-credit element consisting of counselling and advice).

However, reviewed studies on this have shown that SME owners are not able to get the non-credit services because they do not see the need or the provider does not provide the actual BDS service needed by the SME owners. One can receive credit in a business development scheme but won't be interested in any non-credit service. A study in Ghana by Asare-Bediako et al. (2016b) shows that rural business owners perceive that professional business assistance (BDS) is ‘not needed’. That means that, even though they may stay back to attend such training and counselling sessions, they will leave without applying the lessons at all or misapplying them. Just participating in the exercise is not enough to guarantee business success. Also, the outcome of the application by the SME owners is never homogenous because of differences in cognitive abilities and method of application.

McKernan (2002) and others did not consider the effect of the presence of the bank staff who provided the bundled service and also how they delivered the service. McKernan (2002) even added that the individuals are to consult themselves for solutions to their challenges ‘instead of the bank staff’, which only compounds the problem as one may not separate group-effect and provider-effect easily. But,

taking the BDS to the SME owner may be better as he/she may not have complete control over the mode of application of the service as it is participatory in this model.

In this study, credit and BDS will be de-coupled as BDS may be coming from a different source (different from the credit provider) to the SME. This will measure the exact provider-effect of BDS on the profitability of the SMEs. The impact is easier to ascertain as it depends on what the provider gave based on the need of the SMEs (customized) and not what the receiver supposedly learned and applied.

The credit and non-credit services must be decoupled as

- a. Each in form of a loan or credit and business development service can be provided by different firms.
- b. SME owners can choose to take the BDS or not as many do not take them at all (although credit providers and previous researchers asserted that the firms do take up BDS because they accepted the credit)

Decoupling the services makes it easier to measure the impact of each on the firm. The two have to be decoupled and integrate them in a firm for those who received the two services distinctively (either from the same source or different sources).

It is assumed that with Mckernan (2002):

$$C = Q + S \quad (4.9)$$

where Q = credit received concurrently with S = non-credit service. Both services are also not distinctive in his model.

In this study, lets S = business development service (BDS).

The services need to be integrated into the firm through a theoretical framework that captures their combined impact on outcomes. We model this integration using a mathematical construct that allows us to analyze how credit and BDS interact to produce business outcomes:

$$\pi = \int_0^1 Q^\theta S^\rho dx \quad (4.10)$$

The above determines the profitability of the SME and also the ability to repay loans by the SME. The credit and BDS element in equation (4.9) are both discrete variables in this study and not dummy as in equation (4.7).

In this model, x represents a normalized resource integration domain over which the aggregated contributions of credit (Q) and business development services (S) are symbolically distributed. i.e:

$$x \in [0, 1]:$$

While Q and S are discrete totals (monetary value and service instances, respectively), we model them as constant functions over x to decompose their joint impact on profit using integration by parts.

where:

- θ : Elasticity of profit with respect to credit ($0 < \theta < 1$).
- ρ : Elasticity of profit with respect to BDS ($0 < \rho < 1$).

This mathematical construct serves to formalize the synergy between formal and informal sources. To understand how credit and BDS interact to generate profit, we apply the integration by parts formula:

$$\int u \frac{dv}{dx} dx = uv - \int v \frac{du}{dx} dx \quad (4.11)$$

Where:

$$u = Q^\theta$$

$$dv = S^\rho dx$$

Since Q and S are treated as constants over the integration domain:

$$\frac{dQ}{dx} = 0, \quad \frac{dS}{dx} = 0$$

Therefore:

$$du = \theta Q^{\theta-1} \cdot \frac{dQ}{dx} dx = 0$$

$$v = \int_0^1 S^\rho dx = S^\rho \cdot x$$

Substituting into Equation (4.11):

$$\int_0^1 Q^\theta S^\rho dx = [Q^\theta \cdot S^\rho \cdot x]_0^1 - \int_0^1 S^\rho \cdot x \cdot 0 dx$$

Evaluating the boundary terms:

1. At $x=1$:

$$Q^\theta S^\rho \cdot 1 = Q^\theta S^\rho$$

2. At $x=0$:

$$Q^\theta S^\rho \cdot 0 = 0$$

Therefore:

$$Q^\theta S^\rho (1 - 0) = Q^\theta S^\rho$$

Recall from 1 that profit is a function of C,

Therefore profit,

$$\pi = Q^\theta S^\rho \quad (4.12)$$

It can be concluded from (4.8) and (4.12) that:

$$\pi = f(Q^\theta, S^\rho) \quad (4.13)$$

where π is the profit made by the SME after the application of customized integrated services.

Q^τ and S^ρ are separated in terms of delivery or provision and then integrated (customized and participatory) into the firm. This will also help with efficient and effective monitoring and evaluation of each service. The best approach may be credit officers providing the funds needed for the business and a business development officer handling the non-financial service to ensure the smooth running of the business.

Equation (4.16) holds as it is assumed that different firms provide credit and BDS in an integrated form with different amounts and quality of credit and BDS which differ across firms both on the supply side and on the demand side. With the integrated approach,

- a. credit and BDS must be distinct
- b. Credit and BDS are measurable in discrete form with clear lines separating them.

Equation 12 can be expanded into formal and informal components:

$$Q = Q_f + Q_i \quad (\text{Total credit from formal and informal sources})$$

$$S = S_f + S_i \quad (\text{Total BDS from formal and informal sources})$$

This gives:

$$\pi = (Q_f + Q_i)^\theta (S_f + S_i)^\rho \quad (4.14)$$

The model components have clear economic interpretations:

- **Credit (Q):** Represents the combined monetary value of loans from formal financial institutions (Q_f) and informal lenders (Q_i). Formal credit (Q_f) is measured through survey Questions 7-9 capturing loan amounts from banks in GHC for 2022-2023 and Questions 10-11 documenting repayment installments. Informal credit (Q_i) is captured via Questions 17-19 measuring amounts received from alternative sources including family, friends, and local money lenders in GHC for 2022-2023.
- **BDS (S):** Reflects the total instances of advisory services from formal providers (S_f) and informal networks (S_i). Formal BDS (S_f) is measured through survey Questions 22-24 assessing receipt of business development services, usefulness ratings on a 0-10 scale, and frequency of professional visits. Informal BDS (S_i) is captured via survey Question 25 measuring frequency of business advice sharing with friends and associates, and Question 26 identifying types of business development services received including financial management training, marketing advice, and operations assistance.
- **Elasticities (θ, ρ):** Quantify the responsiveness of profit to changes in credit and BDS.

The informal lenders stand for loans from family and friends, trade credit (from suppliers), etc as firms do not always depend on one source of funding at any point in time. SMEs can go for credits from different sources or participate in a credit program depending on their social capital which is measured by their networks (Hoang and Otake 2014). The different sources need to be acknowledged in this study

as previous studies reviewed failed to do so. The model in this study captures complementary business advisory services from multiple information sources, contributing to overall firm performance beyond credit provision alone. Any of the parts can be termed as informal sources of credit and business development tips in addition to formal credit and business development services.

Therefore, from equation (4.14):

$$\pi = \underbrace{(Q_f + Q_i)^\theta}_{\text{Credit Effect}} \cdot \underbrace{(S_f + S_i)^\rho}_{\text{BDS Effect}} \quad (4.15)$$

This multiplicative form captures the complementary effects of credit and BDS from both formal and informal sources, showing how their integration creates synergistic benefits for SME profitability and loan repayment capacity.

The model provides a foundation for understanding why integrated approaches to SME support yield better outcomes compared to standalone services. It also creates a framework for incorporating risk dimensions, as the integration of credit and BDS can reduce various risk factors that affect SME performance.

Equation (4.13) shows that SMEs get involved in/with more than one element of credit and BDS which contribute to their profitability and growth. This also shows that the profit, π is composite as both the formal and informal sources are both in use at any point in the running of an SME. The informal part of the equation exists but is not mentioned or taken into consideration by previous studies reviewed when analyzing the impact of credit (financial) and non-credit (non-financial) inputs on SMEs or firms in general.

Therefore,

$$\pi_v = \pi_f + \pi_i \quad (4.16)$$

where π_v is a composite profit; π_f is the profit contributed by formal sources of the customized integrated services; while π_i is the profit contributed by the informal sources of credit and business development tips.

If the formal services are well customized to suit the SME,

$$\pi_f > \pi_i \quad \{\text{Note: } \pi_f > 0\}$$

If otherwise,

$$\pi_f < \pi_i \quad \{\text{Note: } \pi_f \leq 0\}$$

Equation (4.16) can be re-written as:

$$\pi_v = (Q_f + Q_i)^\theta (S_f + S_i)^\rho \quad (4.17)$$

Where

$$Q_v = Q_f + Q_i \text{ and } S_v = S_f + S_i$$

Then:

$$\pi_v = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho \quad (4.18)$$

Equation 4.17 mitigate the problem of endogeneity arising from Omitted variable bias and measurement error by including every source of credit and BDS and the actual measures of credit and BDS in absolute terms.

The equation 4.18 also shows that SMEs need more than one source of credit (e.g. the government credit support) to survive the Covid-19 pandemic, climate change challenges and regional/global tensions (e.g. war). Only Multiple Customized credit and participatory BDS supports may guarantee SMEs' survival, profitability and growth.

Profit, π generated during a specific period significantly influence the ease of loan repayment. The capacity to repay a loan is largely contingent upon the cash derived from profits, a common scenario in Ghana and other developing nations. The fungibility of profit is most evident in indirect cash flow statements under operating activities, where adjustments are made to reintroduce non-operating activities that do not impact a company's operating cash flow, in accordance with the IAS 7 accounting standard (IASplus, 2021). Net profit (income) is incorporated into the cash flow statement under operating activities as a cash inflow. In the financial activities section, loan repayment is subtracted from the net of operating and investing activities of the indirect cash flow statement, as it represents an outflow that diminishes the cash balance accumulated through profit-making. This implies a correlation between profit and loan repayment. Factors influencing profits will also affect loan repayment (disregarding any investing activity, as most SMEs may not engage in such). Profit reduces/annihilate the debt burden of SMEs.

This means that:

$$\text{Profit, } \pi = \int_0^T [\theta Q_{vt} + \rho S_{vt}] dt - \gamma D_{vt} \quad (4.19a)$$

where θ, ρ , represents the marginal impacts of credit and BDS services from both formal and alternative sources, $\gamma D_{(vt)}$ the debt repayment burdens under rigid terms. The integration maximizes π by reducing γ through repayments coming from cash flows.

Consequently, the explanatory variables in the profit model can also explain the rate of loan repayment. Profit, as an independent variable, will be included in the loan repayment model.

In the repayment model, Return on Sales (ROS), calculated as the ratio of net profit to revenue, was employed as a measure of profitability. The rationale behind using ROS lies in its ability to capture the relationship between a company's profitability and its capacity to generate revenue. A higher ROS indicates that a company is more efficient in converting its revenue into profits, which in turn enhances its ability to repay loans. Moreover, ROS provides a standardized measure of profitability across companies of different sizes, allowing for meaningful comparisons and analysis. By incorporating ROS into the repayment model, we can better understand how a company's profitability, relative to its revenue, influences its loan repayment capabilities with the integrated credits and business development service.

Modifying equation (4.17) based on the relationship between profit and loan repayment,

$$\aleph = f \left[(Q_f + Q_i)^\theta (S_f + S_i)^\rho \right], \text{ i.e.}$$

$$\aleph = f(Q^\tau, S^\rho) \tag{4.19b}$$

Where \aleph is the repayment rate of a credit facility.

Having established equation (4.19b), repayment rate,

$$\aleph = \text{ROS} \times Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho \tag{4.20}$$

4.7 Construction Of Integrated Credit And Business Development Services (BDS) Variables With Credit Burden.

The construction of integrated credit and Business Development Services (BDS) variables followed a systematic approach aligned with the theoretical model. The analysis started with the computation of *credit burden* components:

Formal Credit Component:

$$Q_f = Q \times \tau_f$$

where Q represents the formal loan amount and τ_f denotes formal interest rate charges (captured through survey Questions 8: percentage charged by banks as interest on loans for 2022-2023).

Informal Credit Component:

$$Q_i = Q \times \tau_i$$

where Q represents informal finance (alternative source(s) of finance) amount and τ_i denotes informal finance charges (captured through Questions 18-19: whether alternative sources charged fees and the percentage charged for loans in 2022-2023).

Following the theoretical framework established in equation 4.14, these credit burden measures were integrated with corresponding BDS components:

Formal Credit-BDS Integration:

$$Q_f^\theta S_f^\rho = Q_f \times S_f \tag{4.21}$$

where S_f represents formal BDS provision (measures via question 24: frequency of professional visits per year)

Informal Credit-BDS Integration:

$$Q_i^\theta S_i^\rho = Q_i \times S_i$$

where S_i denotes informal BDS engagement (measured via Question 25: frequency of business advice sharing with friends and associates per year in 2022-2023) and encompasses peer-to-peer knowledge exchange, informal mentoring, and collaborative problem-solving activities within business networks).

Culminating in equation 4.18, these integrated measures were consolidated to construct the comprehensive Credit-BDS integration variable:

$$Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = Q^\theta S_f^\rho + Q^\theta S_i^\rho = (Q \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q \times \tau_i \times S_i)$$

This integrated measure serves as the independent variable (IV) for profitability and loan repayment models.

Therefore,

$$\pi = Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = Q^\theta S_f^\rho + Q^\theta S_i^\rho = (Q \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q \times \tau_i \times S_i) \quad (4.22)$$

$$\aleph = Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = Q^\theta S_f^\rho + Q^\theta S_i^\rho = (Q \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q \times \tau_i \times S_i) \quad (4.23)$$

Incorporating eq.4.23 into the repayment model in eq.25 above will give:

$$\aleph = \text{ROS} \times [Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = Q^\theta S_f^\rho + Q^\theta S_i^\rho = (Q \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q \times \tau_i \times S_i)] \quad (4.24)$$

Justification

The approach to constructing the credit burden variable ($Q \times \tau$) is substantiated by several theoretical and empirical considerations. The multiplicative relationship captures the total borrowing cost, providing a more nuanced measure than individual components and effectively quantifies the complete financial obligation faced by borrowers. The composite measure addresses potential multicollinearity concerns that would arise from separate inclusion of loan amount and interest rate variables, where high correlations between these components could inflate standard errors and destabilise coefficient estimates, thereby compromising statistical inference and model reliability. The interaction between loan size and cost reflects the nonlinear nature of borrowing dynamics, capturing how borrowers respond to the combined effect rather than individual components. Finally, The constructed measure aligns with economic theory by representing the nominal interest burden and providing a direct indicator of financial pressure on borrowers. This specification maintains theoretical consistency while capturing the total effect of integrated services on SME outcomes.

4.8 Application of Integrated Service as a risk management tool: Firm-Level Risk-Return Clustering Analysis. (Insights from Standard Deviation and Profitability (ROS) Measures)

SMEs in Ghana and other parts of the world have always been termed, 'risky'. The financial service providers using different matrices assess the SMEs to determine the interest rate charges that ought to be applied when providing credit. As stated above, the credit burden can also increase the overall business risk profile of the SMEs, thereby making it difficult for the business to repay the loans (Principal and interest) and record a positive net profit. This section models how the integration of customized credit and participatory BDS can reduce risk to improve profitability and repayment speed.

To better understand the heterogeneous nature of SMEs' risk-return profiles and inform tailored integrated credit and BDS interventions, this section presents a cluster analysis based on two key performance metrics: risk and profitability. Risk is measured by the standard deviation of return on sales (SD_ROS), capturing the volatility in firm performance, while profitability is measured by the mean return on sales (MEAN_ROS), reflecting the average financial performance over the study period. This

analytical approach allows this study to identify distinct groups of SMEs with similar risk-return characteristics, moving beyond traditional one-dimensional classifications to provide a better understanding of SME performance patterns.

The cluster analysis identified four distinct groups of SMEs, each characterized by unique combinations of risk and profitability levels. This segmentation reveals important variations in how SMEs balance risk and return, ranging from conservative low-risk, low-return strategies to more aggressive high-risk, high-return approaches. Understanding these distinct profiles and their characteristics provides valuable insights in designing integrated credit/BDS interventions.

Before exploring the clustering results, it is important to establish the foundation for using SD_ROS as the primary risk metric. Return on Sales (ROS) is calculated as the ratio of net profit to revenue:

$$ROS = \frac{Net\ Profit}{Revenue} \quad 4.8.1$$

where Net Profit is measured through Question 31 (net profit in GHC for 2022-2023) and Revenue is captured via Question 30 (total sales revenue in GHC for 2022-2023). This operationalization enables direct calculation of profitability ratios from primary survey data, providing a standardized performance metric across diverse SME sectors and sizes.

The standard deviation (SD of ROS) captures the volatility in an SME's profitability over time, providing a comprehensive indicator of business risk. Mathematically, it is expressed as:

$$SD_{ROS} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n [(ROS_i - \overline{ROS})]^2\right)} \quad 4.8.2$$

Where:

ROS_i = the Return on Sales for period i.

\overline{ROS} = The mean Return on Sales across all periods

n is the number of periods observed (2021-2023)

This measure offers several advantages for capturing total business risk. Unlike specific risk indicators (e.g., debt-to-equity ratio), SD_ROS reflects the aggregate impact of all risk factors affecting an SME's operations. Also, it directly connects risk to business performance outcomes, capturing how various risks ultimately impact the bottom line. As a normalized measure, it allows for meaningful comparisons across SMEs of different sizes and sectors. And, It reflects both systematic (market-wide) and idiosyncratic (firm-specific) risk factors.

Based on the SD_ROS and mean ROS measures, SMEs are classified into four distinct risk-profitability clusters:

Table 4.10: clustering results for SMEs based on their risk (SD_ROS) and profitability (MEAN_ROS)

Cluster	Interpretation
1	High risk, low profitability
2	Low risk, high profitability
3	Low risk, low profitability
4	High risk, high profitability

Source: Author (2025)

Note on Table 4.10: *The clustering analysis is based exclusively on risk (SD_ROS) and profitability (MEAN_ROS) metrics. Demographic breakdowns by business sector, geographic location (urban/rural), and gender are not provided for two reasons. First, the survey instrument was designed with strict respondent anonymity protocols; combining sector, location, and gender identifiers would materially increase the risk of identifying individual respondents in sparsely represented categories. Second, demographic stratification was not a specified analytical dimension of this study, whose objectives pertain to the effects of integrated credit and BDS on SME risk-return profiles. Future research with a larger, anonymity-robust sample may extend this framework to incorporate demographic disaggregation.*

Building upon the above clustering analysis and the integrated credit-BDS framework established earlier, this study now develop a comprehensive model that explicitly incorporates risk dimensions. The theoretical model demonstrated that SME profitability is a function of integrated credit and business development services:

Recall eq. 4.14, $\pi = (Q_f + Q_i)^\theta (S_f + S_i)^\rho$; **which shows that components of the integrated services. Also recall that: credit burden** from Formal Credit sources, $Q_f = Q_f \times \tau_f$ and Informal Credit sources, $Q_i = Q_i \times \tau_i$. where Q_f represents the formal loan amount, τ_f denotes formal interest rate charges; Q_i represents informal finance (alternative source(s) of finance) amount and τ_i denotes informal finance charges.

To incorporate risk dimensions identified in the clustering analysis, this study must examine how credit terms include risk premiums and how integration functions to reduce these risk factors. It is important to note that τ_f and τ_i can be decomposed as:

$$\tau_f = \tau_{b,f} + \tau_{r,f}; \text{ and } \tau_i = \tau_{b,i} + \tau_{r,i}$$

where $\tau_{b,f}$ and $\tau_{b,i}$ are the base interest rates and $\tau_{r,f}$ and $\tau_{r,i}$ are the risk premium component for formal and informal credits respectively. This risk premium encompass multiple dimensions including operational risk, market risk, reputational risk, liquidity risk, counterparty risk, macroeconomic volatility risk, regulatory compliance risk, technology risk, supply chain risk, and human capital risk. The risk premium component for informal credit captures similar risk dimensions of the formal but often with different weights reflecting the distinct nature of informal financing arrangements.

But, according to the European Investment Bank, EIB (Revoltella and Kraemer-Eis, 2015) and the Federal Reserve Bank of New York, FRBNY (Cumming and Hirtle, 2001), lenders predominantly price

credit-specific risks into interest rates (τ_r), such as collateral quality, cash flow volatility, and sectorial exposure. However, SMEs face broader non-priced risks (operational, reputational, regulatory, etc.) that are not fully reflected in τ_r but significantly influence firm-level profitability volatility (SD_ROS). The EIB depicted how information asymmetries between lenders and SMEs lead to an underestimation of true creditworthiness, causing even viable businesses to face financing gaps (Revoltella and Kraemer-Eis, 2015). Meanwhile, the FRBNY posited that traditional segmented risk models often overlook cross-cutting and strategic risks, which become especially pronounced during market stress or crisis scenarios (Cumming and Hirtle, 2001). To fully capture SME risk exposure, this study will: Narrow τ_r to credit-specific risks (priced by lenders); and expand and assume SD_ROS clusters to reflect total business risk (priced + non-priced).

Formal and informal credit pricing focuses on:

$$\tau_r = \tau_{collateral} + \tau_{cashflow} + \tau_{Sector}$$

where $\tau_{collateral}$ is the Collateral Risk ($\tau_{collateral}$) i.e. Asset liquidation value (e.g., property, equipment); $\tau_{cashflow}$ is the Cash Flow Risk Measured by SD_ROS (volatility in profitability); and τ_{Sector} Is the Sector Risk i.e. Macroeconomic/sectoral shocks (e.g., commodity price swings). They all make up for the priced risks in credit premium.

Therefore, the formal credit pricing (with credit burden) becomes,

$$Q_f = Q_f \times (\tau_{b,f} + \tau_{r,f}), \text{ where } \tau_{r,f} = \tau_{collateral} + \tau_{cashflow} + \tau_{Sector}$$

As in the informal credit pricing (with credit burden) becomes,

$$Q_i = Q_i \times (\tau_{b,i} + \tau_{r,i}), \text{ where } \tau_{r,i} \text{ constitutes hidden costs and risk premium.}$$

To capture the total business risk, SD_ROS is used.,

Therefore:

$SD_ROS = (\tau_{b,f} + \tau_{r,f}) + (\tau_{b,i} + \tau_{r,i}) + \tau_{NPR}$, where τ_{NPR} is the all the non-priced risk from both formal and informal sources. The SD_ROS clusters identified in table 4.10 capture total business risk, including risks not priced into τ_r .

SD of ROS

= f(Operational Risk, Reputational Risk, Regulatory Risk, Technology Risk, Supply Chain Risk)

Incorporating the Total business risk into the integrated different sources of the services, eq.4.24 becomes

$$\pi = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho = Q_v^\theta \times SD_{ROS} \times S_v^\rho$$

The integration of customized credit and the participatory business develop services is geared towards the reduction or management of the total business risk. Thus:

$$\pi = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho = Q_v^\theta \times [SD_{ROS(1-\lambda_i(I))}] \times S_v^\rho$$

Where, $\lambda_i(I)$ is the total business risk reduction function through integration of the services.

Isolating SD of ROS:

$$\pi = Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \times SD_{ROS} \times (1 - \lambda_i(I))$$

Divide both sides by $Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \times (1 - \lambda_i(I))$:

$$SD_{ROS} = \frac{\pi}{Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \times (1 - \lambda_i(I))}$$

Since the risk reduction factor $\lambda_i(I)$ depends on the level of integration $Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$. For simplicity, let:

$$1 - \lambda_i(I) = k * Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$$

where k is a proportionality constant.

Substitute Back $1 - \lambda_i(I) = k * Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$ into $SD_{ROS} = \frac{\pi}{Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \times (1 - \lambda_i(I))}$,

$$SD_{ROS} = \frac{\pi}{Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \times k * Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho} = \frac{\pi}{k} * \frac{1}{(Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho)^2}$$

To simplify for proportionality, if π and k are constant or the same scale with the integration, the relationship between the integrated services and risk can be expressed as:

$$SD_{ROS} \propto \frac{1}{Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho} \quad (4.25) \text{ (The integration reduces volatility via risk mitigation).}$$

This inverse relationship captures how increased integration engagement systematically reduces business volatility as measured by SD_ROS, which is particularly important for Clusters 1 and 4 that exhibit high risk profiles. So, the higher the integration, the less SD_ROS and the lower the integration, the higher the risk.

The integration of credit and BDS reduces total business risk through several complementary channels that address the multiple dimensions of risk that SMEs face. The integration mechanism works together to systematically reduce various risk components through the function, $\lambda_i(I)$. These mechanisms combine to form a comprehensive risk reduction function:

$$\lambda_i(I) = \omega_1 \lambda_{info}(I) + \omega_2 \lambda_{operat.}(I) + \omega_3 \lambda_{market}(I) + \omega_4 \lambda_{fin}(I) + \omega_5 \lambda_{reput}(I) \dots \omega_n \lambda_i(I)$$

Where, $\lambda_i(I)$ is the overall proportion of risk that is eliminated through integration; $\omega_n \lambda_i(I)$ any known risk not mentioned above; ω_1 through ω_n are weighting factors that determine the relative importance of each risk reduction mechanism; the weights sum to one: $\sum_i^n \omega_i = 1$. The weights may vary across different SME profiles, explaining why integration effects differ across the risk-profitability clusters identified in the research.

The integration mechanism works through the following specific components:

1. Information asymmetry reduction ($\omega_1 \lambda_{info}(I)$):

Integration provides lenders with deeper insights into business operations, systematically reducing uncertainty. As integration deepens, information flows improve between credit providers and SMEs, leading to more accurate risk assessments and reduced uncertainty premiums. The theoretical underpinnings are drawn from seminal work on market information gaps by Akerlof (1970) and credit rationing models by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981). This mechanism particularly addresses counterparty risk,

relationship tenure risk, and reputational risk by creating transparency and building trust through continuous monitoring.

2. Operational risk mitigation ($\omega_2\lambda_{operat}(I)$):

Integration enhances internal processes, controls, and management practices, following principles of diminishing marginal returns. Initial stages of integration yield substantial risk reductions through basic process improvements, while more advanced stages continue to reduce risk but at a decreasing rate. This approach, rooted in classical economic concepts of diminishing returns (Ricardo, 1817) and agency theory's effort-reward models (Holmström, 1979), addresses operational vulnerabilities, human capital risk, and regulatory compliance risk by implementing structured business systems and ensuring proper documentation and compliance procedures.

3. Market positioning enhancement ($\omega_3\lambda_{market}(I)$):

Integration strengthens competitive advantage and market adaptability through network effects and scale improvements. As integration increases, market positioning benefits accumulate at accelerating rates due to reinforcing feedback loops between improved market knowledge and strategic capabilities. These concepts are anchored in Porter's (1985) competitive strategy framework and Romer's (1986) endogenous growth theory. This reduces market risk, technology risk, and sector-specific risk through improved market analysis, product differentiation, and strategic positioning.

4. Financial resilience building ($\omega_4\lambda_{fin}(I)$):

Integration stabilizes cash flow and improves financial planning with compounding benefits. As integration deepens, financial management capabilities strengthen, creating increasingly robust buffers against financial shocks. Drawing from portfolio optimization theory (Markowitz, 1952) and financial constraints literature (Hubbard, 1998), this mechanism addresses liquidity risk, macroeconomic volatility risk, and supply chain risk through better working capital management, financial forecasting, and contingency planning.

5. Collateral quality improvement ($\omega_5\lambda_{reput}(I)$):

Integration enhances the value and documentation of assets through systematic asset management improvements. Initial integration efforts establish basic asset documentation, while more advanced integration approaches theoretical maximum improvements in collateral quality and valuation. Grounded in asset valuation and credit risk modelling frameworks (Merton, 1974; Shleifer & Vishny, 1992), this mechanism reduces collateral quality risk by helping SMEs properly maintain, document, and enhance their assets' value.

As mentioned earlier, European Investment Bank, EIB (Revoltella and Kraemer-Eis, 2015) and the Federal Reserve Bank of New York, FRBNY (Cumming and Hirtle, 2001) posited that lenders often overlook SME-specific operational and regulatory risks due to information asymmetry using the traditional risk models. By using SD_ROS clusters, this study fills the measurement gap where the SD clusters internalize risks ignored in traditional risk assessment; and also validates with data that clusters correlate with SME survival rates and loan defaults, confirming their predictive power for total risk exposure. Building on this framework, our theoretical derivation reveals an important inverse relationship between integration and risk, where higher levels of integrated services correspond to lower volatility in business performance. This relationship can be effectively captured through a linear approximation model that maintains the essential dynamics while facilitating practical application.

Recall, $SD_{ROS} \propto \frac{1}{Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho}$. While this inverse relationship captures the fundamental dynamics between integration and risk, its non-linear nature presents challenges for empirical implementation and interpretation. To address this, this study can reformulate this relationship in a more tractable linear form that preserves the essential dynamics while facilitating estimation and application.

Starting with the inverse relationship, we can reasonably approximate it with a linear function within the relevant range of integration values observed in our data:

$$SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho \quad (4.26)$$

Where: α represents the maximum risk level (SD of ROS) that would exist in the absence of integration. As Cortés et al. (2018) demonstrate, historical volatility measures often underestimate maximum potential risk exposure. This is consistent with Cumming and Hirtle (2001) and IMF (2017), who emphasize that forward-looking stress or buffer scenario-based stress testing, where forward-looking uncertainty is overlaid onto historical volatility measures, provides a more comprehensive risk assessment (when there is no integration). Following this approach, a theoretically informed adjustment factor to account for potential future risk that would emerge in the absence of any risk-mitigating integration will be added to α . Where, β captures the effectiveness of integration in reducing risk; and $Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$ represents the integrated services. This linearization offers several advantages: It maintains the fundamental negative relationship between integration and risk; it provides clear, interpretable parameters for empirical estimation; and it allows for straightforward application to our cluster analysis framework.

Solving for the integrated services, by making $Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$, the subjects, then:

$$Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = \frac{\alpha - SD_{ROS}}{\beta}$$

The above shows that the optimal level of integration for a firm is directly related to its current risk profile and the desired risk reduction. Firms with higher volatility (SD_ROS) would require greater levels of integration to achieve stability. The profitability implication needs to be established. This relationship is substituted into the earlier profit function, $\pi_V = Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$; establishing a direct link between the risk profiles (levels) and profitability.

Therefore:

$$\pi_V = Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho = \frac{\alpha - SD \text{ of } ROS}{\beta} \quad (4.27)$$

This equation completes the theoretical framework by showing how integration reduces risk and enhances both profitability and loan repayment capacity. The linearized model aligns with the cluster analysis, where the four distinct risk-profitability clusters represent different positions along the risk-integration continuum. The integration-risk relationship establishes integrated credit-BDS services as a systematic risk management tool for SMEs with quantifiable benefits.

For repayment specifically, recall that $\aleph = ROS \times Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$.

Thus, the model demonstrates that:

$$\aleph = ROS \times \left[\frac{\alpha - SD_{ROS}}{\beta} \right] \quad (4.28)$$

This shows how the effectiveness of integration directly improves repayment rates through both increased profitability (ROS) and reduced risk. This framework provides stakeholders with clear rationale for promoting integrated approaches across different risk clusters, particularly benefiting high-risk SMEs where marginal integration benefits are most significant.

4.9 ECONOMETRIC MODELS

This section presents the econometric models employed to test the three research hypotheses. Each model has been carefully specified to reflect the theoretical framework set out in the previous Chapters. All variables entering the estimation including their operational definitions, measurement units, applied transformations, data sources, and expected signs are summarised in Table 4.12.

4.9.1 Profitability And Loan Repayment Using Random Effect (RE)

To test the first hypothesis:

H₁: The integration of customized credit and participatory business development services yields superior profitability outcomes compared to separate service delivery approaches.

H₀: No significant difference in profitability impacts between integrated and separate services

The theoretical foundations established in the comprehensive Credit-BDS integration framework directly inform this study's empirical models. The theoretical relationship demonstrates how firm performance emerges from the strategic integration of credit access and business development services.

This integrated measure serves as the independent variable (IV) for profitability and loan repayment models. From the theoretical framework, this study derives that firm profitability (π) depends on the interaction between credit access (Q) and business development services through both formal ($\tau_f \times S_f$) and informal ($\tau_i \times S_i$) transmission channels.

Therefore, the theoretical framework:

$$\pi = Q_v^\tau S_v^\rho = \theta Q^{\tau} S_f^{\rho} + \theta Q^{\tau} S_i^{\rho} = (Q_f \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q_i \times \tau_i \times S_i) \quad (4.22)$$

where: π = firm profitability/performance; Q_f = credit from formal sources; Q_i = credit from informal sources; S_f = formal business development services; S_i = informal business development services; τ_f , τ_i = transmission mechanisms for formal and informal channels; and θ , ρ = elasticity parameters capturing integration effects.

For loan repayment rate, the theoretical model shows:

$$\aleph = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho = Q^\theta S_f^\rho + Q^\theta S_i^\rho = (Q_f \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q_i \times \tau_i \times S_i) \quad (4.23)$$

where \aleph represents repayment rate derived from the same integrated service framework.

Incorporating eq.4.23 into the repayment model gave:

$$\aleph = \text{ROS} \times \left[Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho = Q^\theta S_f^\rho + Q^\theta S_i^\rho = (Q_f \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q_i \times \tau_i \times S_i) \right] \quad (4.24)$$

This shows how the effectiveness of integration directly improves repayment rates through both increased profitability (ROS) and reduced risk. This framework provides stakeholders with clear rationale for adopting/promoting integrated approaches across different risk clusters, particularly benefiting high-risk SMEs where marginal integration benefits are most significant.

The empirical model specification follows directly from the comprehensive Credit-BDS integration equation (4.24) developed in the theoretical framework.

This theoretical foundation is operationalized into an estimable panel econometric model:

$$\begin{aligned} z_net_profit_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 L_z_net_profit_{it} + \\ & \beta_2 ihs_formal_credit_bds_{it} + \beta_3 z_informal_credit_bds_{it} + \\ & \beta_4 comp_integrated_credit_bds_{it} + \beta_5 z_firm_age_{it} + \beta_6 z_bizsize_{it} + \\ & \beta_7 z_tech_spending_{it} + \sum_{\{k=1\}}^K \beta_k Education_level_k + \sum_{\{j=1\}}^J \beta_j Sector_j + (u_i + \varepsilon_{\{it\}}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.29)$$

Thus,

$ihs_formal_credit_bds_{it}$ capturing the formal integration $(Q_f \times \tau_f \times S_f)$

$z_informal_credit_bds_{it}$ representing the informal integration $(Q_i \times \tau_i \times S_i)$

$comp_integrated_credit_bds_{it}$ reflecting the complementarity between formal and informal channels i.e. complete integration.

For the variable transformations:

Inverse Hyperbolic Sine (IHS) Transformation

The IHS transformation is applied to address data distribution issues and enhance model robustness. The IHS function is defined as:

$$IHS(x) = \ln \left(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1} \right)$$

Key advantages of IHS transformation:

- *Zero-value accommodation:* Unlike logarithmic transformation, IHS can handle zero and negative values commonly found in SME financial data
- *Variance stabilization:* Reduces heteroscedasticity in the error terms
- *Interpretation similarity:* For large positive values, IHS approximates natural logarithm, allowing percentage interpretation of coefficients
- *Outlier mitigation:* Reduces the influence of extreme values on parameter estimates

In this study's context, IHS is particularly valuable for financial variables where SMEs may report zero profits, losses, or zero business development service utilization, ensuring all observations remain in the analysis (Bellemare & Wichman, 2020; Norton, 2022).

Standardization (Z-score) Transformation

The "z" prefix denotes standardized variables using z-score transformation, defined as:

$$Z(x) = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation of variable x .

Key advantages of z-score standardization:

- *Scale normalization*: Converts variables to a common scale (mean = 0, standard deviation = 1)
- *Coefficient comparability*: Enables direct comparison of effect sizes across different variables
- *Multicollinearity reduction*: Helps minimize correlation issues between variables measured in different units
- *Model convergence*: Improves numerical stability in econometric estimation

This transformation is particularly important when combining financial variables (measured in Ghana Cedis) with categorical and count variables in the same model.

The application of three distinct transformation techniques in this study reflects a deliberate, empirically grounded methodological choice, not an arbitrary decision. The selection of an appropriate transformation is determined by the distributional characteristics of each variable. This approach is consistent with the principle established in Wooldridge (2020, Chapter 6), who demonstrates that within a single regression model, different variables appropriately receive different transformations according to their individual distributional properties. The choice of transformation is therefore a variable-by-variable decision driven by empirical diagnostics, not a uniform decision applied across the entire model.

On this basis, the foundational justification for applying different transformations to different variables within the same model is provided by Box and Cox (1964), who established the framework allowing different power transformations (log, square root, inverse) for variables within the same regression, each selected to achieve linearity, normality, and homoscedasticity for that specific variable. This is reinforced by Osborne (2010), who confirms that the optimal normalising transformation differs across variables depending on their individual skewness and variance characteristics, and by Greene (2011), whose standard econometric specifications routinely combine log-transformed, linear, and squared variables within a single regression equation.

In summary, IHS, log, and Z-score transformations were each applied where warranted by the distributional structure of the respective variable, consistent with established econometric practice. For the time series ARDL model, variables are retained in levels or first differences as determined by unit root test results (Pesaran et al., 2001).

To test the second hypothesis:

H₂: Integrated service delivery leads to more sustainable loan repayment patterns than traditional separate approaches

H₀: No significant difference in repayment sustainability between delivery approaches

The empirical model specification also follows directly from the comprehensive Credit-BDS integration equation (4.26) developed in the theoretical framework:

$$\varkappa = \text{ROS} \times \left[Q_v^\tau S_v^\rho = \theta Q^\tau S_f^\rho + \theta Q^\tau S_i^\rho = (Q \times \tau_f \times S_f) + (Q \times \tau_i \times S_i) \right]$$

This theoretical foundation is also operationalized into an estimable panel econometric model:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{lhs_loan_repayment_rate}_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{lhs_ROS}_{it} + \\ & \beta_2 \text{lhs_formal_credit_bds}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{z_informal_credit_bds}_{it} + \\ & \beta_4 \text{comp_integrated_credit_bds}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{z_firm_age}_{it} + \beta_6 \text{z_bizsize}_{it} + \end{aligned}$$

$$\beta_7 z_tech_spending_{it} + \sum_{\{k=1\}}^K \beta_k Education_level_k + \sum_{\{j=1\}}^J \beta_j Sector_j + (u_i + \varepsilon_{\{it\}})$$

(4.30)

Where:

ih_s formal credit bds_{it} capturing the inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS) of the formal integration $(Q \times \tau_f \times S_f)$

z informal credit bds_{it} representing the standardized informal integration $(Q \times \tau_i \times S_i)$

comp integrated credit bds_{it} reflecting the complementarity between formal and informal channels i.e. complete integration.

Others are:

z net profit = standardized net profit

ih_s loan repayment rate_{it} = inverse hyperbolic sine of loan repayment rate [installment_Yes (with repayment plan)+ installment _no (without repayment plan)]

L z net profit = lagged standardized net profit

ih_s ROS = inverse hyperbolic sine of Return on sales (Net Profit/Revenue)

z bizsize= = Standardized Size of Firm (Number of Employees)

z tech spending_{it} = = Standardized Adoption of technology (e.g. Online sales, Mobile Money, stock management software)

z firm age = = Standardized firm age

Education level = = Educational qualification of business owners/Managers

Sector = = Sectors that businesses operate in.

4.9.2 Economic Development Using ARDL And EC Models

The methodological framework of this study establishes the relationship between Credit-Business Development Services (BDS) integration and economic development through a theoretically grounded analytical approach. This framework builds upon the theoretical foundations that demonstrated how credit and BDS support affect firm-level performance and extend these relationships to examine economy-wide development impacts with other economic factors/challenges.

Theoretical Foundation and Transmission Mechanism

The analysis begins with the theoretical model established in equations 4.22 and 4.24, which demonstrated that credit burden (calculated as loan amount \times borrowing rate) impacts firm performance,

and that this burden can be moderated through effective BDS integration. This micro-level relationship provides the theoretical underpinning for the macro-level analysis of economic development.

Building on our risk-return framework, we established that business risk (measured as SD of ROS) is inversely related to integration levels (Eq. 4.25). This relationship was linearized to eq.4.26. By solving for the integration level and substituting into our profit and repayment functions, we derived eq. 4.27 and 4.28. These equations establish that integration reduces business risk, which in turn enhances both profitability and repayment capacity. This risk reduction mechanism forms the theoretical basis for how integrated services contribute to economic development.

While this study's firm-level analysis provides specific measurements of risk through SD of ROS, the economic development analysis examines broader patterns at the macroeconomic level. Though this study cannot directly apply the same risk parameters to our development indicators, the underlying principle remains consistent: integration reduces volatility and enhances outcomes. The theoretical relationship suggests that development indicators follow a similar pattern, where increased integration leads to improved development measures through risk reduction and enhanced productive capacity.

The transmission mechanism operates through two interconnected levels:

At the firm level (derived from our risk-return equations), the credit burden affects individual firm performance through the interaction of loan amounts and borrowing rates. BDS integration serves as a risk reduction mechanism, decreasing volatility and enhancing business performance. This relationship, captured in our linearized model, shows that higher integration levels lead to lower business risk and higher profitability. When aggregated across firms, this creates economy-wide effects on productivity and resource allocation efficiency.

At the macro level, the aggregate credit burden (measured as economy-wide credit to private sector \times lending rate) influences overall economic development. The availability of BDS providers at the national level serves as a moderating factor, paralleling the firm-level risk reduction mechanism established in our theoretical framework. Just as integration reduces firm-level risk and enhances performance, economy-wide integration of credit and BDS can reduce systemic risk and enhance development outcomes through multiple pathways: direct effects on economic productivity and income generation, indirect effects through business stability, and distributional effects that influence equity and poverty reduction.

While the firm-level analysis identified four distinct risk-return clusters, the economic development analysis examines time series data for Ghana as a whole. Although this study cannot directly observe risk clusters at the macro level, the same theoretical principles apply - integration reduces risk and enhances performance, whether measured at the firm level through profitability or at the national level through development indicators such as the Human Development Index (HDI), Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI), and Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI).

ARDL and Error Correction Model Specifications

Following this theoretical structure, the relationship between Credit-BDS integration and economic development is expressed through carefully specified econometric models. To address potential multicollinearity while maintaining theoretical consistency, the study employs two distinct models for each development indicator.

The general relationship can be expressed as:

Economic Development =

f(Credit Burden, BDS, CRED_BDS_Integration, Macroeconomic Factors AND CHALLENGES)

To test the third hypothesis:

H₃: Integrated service delivery creates superior economic development outcomes across multiple dimensions

Null: No significant difference in development impacts between delivery approaches

Alternative: Integrated approaches yield significantly better development outcomes across HDI, IHDI, and MPI measures.

The impacts are empirically examined through two complementary ARDL specifications:

Model A (Separate Effects):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta lhs_ECONDEV_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 lhs_ECONDEV_{t-k} + \beta_2 z_CREPRIV_{t-k} + \beta_3 \ln BDSFirms_{t-k} + \beta_4 z_INF_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_5 z_FXRATE_{t-k} + \beta_6 z_PROFTAX_{t-k} + \beta_8 z_CORRUPTION_{t-k} + \sum_{i=1}^p xit \Delta EC_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_1 \Delta lhs_ECONDEV_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_2 \Delta z_CREPRIV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^s \alpha_3 \Delta \ln BDSFirms_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_4 \ln \Delta INF_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^u \alpha_5 \Delta z_FXRATE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^v \alpha_6 \Delta z_PROFTAX_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^w \alpha_7 \Delta z_CORRUPT_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (4.30)$$

Model B (Integration Effect):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta lhs_ECONDEV_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 lhs_ECONDEV_{t-k} + \beta_2 z_INTEGRATED_CRED_BDS_{t-k} + \beta_4 z_INF_{t-k} + \\ & \beta_5 z_FXRATE_{t-k} + \beta_6 z_PROFTAX_{t-k} + \beta_8 z_CORRUPTION_{t-k} + \sum_{i=1}^p xit \Delta EC_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_1 \Delta lhs_ECONDEV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_2 \Delta INTEGRATED_CRED_BDS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^s \alpha_4 \ln \Delta INF_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_5 \Delta z_FXRATE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^u \alpha_6 \Delta z_PROFTAX_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^v \alpha_7 \Delta z_CORRUPT_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (4.31)$$

Where **lhs_ECONDEV** represents the inverse hyperbolic sine transformation of three development indicators:

- Human Development Index (HDI)
- Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI)
- Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)

Variable Specifications and Transformations

Main Variables:

z_CREPRIV = Standardized credit to private sector

lnBDSFirms = Natural log-transformed BDS providers

z_INTEGRATED_CRED_BDS : Standardized (Credit to Private Sector × Lending Rate × BDS Providers), capturing the theoretical interaction between credit burden and BDS support

Control Variables (Economic factors/Challenges):

z_INF = Standardized inflation rate

z_FXRATE = Standardized exchange rate

z_PROFTAX = Standardized profit tax

z_CORRUPT = Standardized corruption index

Model Components:

EC = Adjustment rate

β_0 = Constant term

ε_t = Error term

β = coefficients Capture both long-run relationships and short-run dynamics

p,q,r,s,t,u,v = Maximum lag lengths determined using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Philip-Perron (PP)

Endogeneity Considerations in Model Specification

The empirical investigation recognizes potential endogeneity concerns arising from the dynamic nature of SME performance and economic development. These concerns include reverse causality between service delivery approaches and outcomes, omitted variable bias, and potential measurement errors. To address these issues, the study employs specific methodological strategies for each analytical component.

For the profitability analysis, the model incorporates lagged dependent variables to control dynamic relationships. The repayment rate analysis utilizes Return on Sales (ROS) as a key performance indicator to minimize simultaneity bias. The economic development models employ Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology to account for both short-run dynamics and long-run relationships while controlling for potential reverse causality (Pesaran et al., 2001).

Serial/Auto Correlation and Heteroscedasticity

In econometric analysis involving panel data and time series, issues of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity can significantly compromise statistical inference validity if not properly addressed (Baltagi, 2021). Serial correlation occurs when error terms in regression models correlate across observations, while heteroscedasticity emerges when error term variance is inconsistent across observations, potentially leading to inefficient estimators and biased standard errors (White, 1980; Greene, 2018).

This research directly addressed these econometric concerns through methodological choices rather than preliminary diagnostic testing. For panel data analysis, robust variance-covariance estimators (VCE) were employed within the random effects specification, following the approach advocated by Arellano (1987) and further developed by Stock and Watson (2011). As noted by Cameron and Miller (2015), these robust standard errors effectively address both heteroscedasticity and within-cluster correlation in panel settings without requiring explicit modeling of the heteroscedasticity structure.

For time series components, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology was implemented following Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), which inherently accommodates serial correlation through its dynamic specification. The ARDL approach offers distinct advantages when dealing with time series data, as it remains valid regardless of whether variables are I(0), I(1), or mutually cointegrated (Narayan, 2005). Additionally, the inclusion of sufficient lags effectively captures the dynamic structure and mitigates serial correlation issues (Lütkepohl, 2005).

By combining robust standard errors in random effects panel models with the ARDL approach for time series, this research implemented a comprehensive strategy to address serial correlation and heteroscedasticity challenges without requiring explicit diagnostic testing, aligning with best practices outlined by Wooldridge (2020) and ensuring the reliability of empirical findings as recommended by Angrist and Pischke (2009).

4.10 OVERVIEW OF CONTROL VARIABLES

Size of Firm

Firm size is a critical determinant of organisational prosperity and profitability, often linked to economies of scale which allow larger firms to produce goods at lower costs (Akinyomi and Adebayo 2013; Mule et al. 2015). Due to their scale, larger corporations can negotiate better input prices, lowering unit costs and increasing profitability. They also typically have better access to public debt markets at lower costs due to perceived lower bankruptcy risk, greater market power, and diversification, which can further enhance profitability through tax shelters (Aydın et al. 2017). Size is positively linked to profitability, measured by revenue or return on equity, as larger firms often have a superior adaptability to the macroeconomic environment (Yazdanfar and Öhman 2017; Odusanya et al. 2018).

However, this relationship is not without its drawbacks. Very large firms may suffer from scale inefficiencies, bureaucratic procedures, and higher agency costs, which can negatively impact profitability (Aydın et al. 2017; Pattitoni et al. 2014). Size also fundamentally influences capital structure. Larger, more diversified firms can sustain higher leverage ratios due to lower earnings volatility. In contrast, smaller firms face greater information asymmetry and higher processing costs for long-term debt, forcing them to rely more heavily on equity and short-term financing (Odit and Gobardhun 2011; Degryse et al. 2012). For SMEs, size and age are significant predictors of survival, with greater maturity and size enabling more effective diversification and achieving economies of scale faster, particularly in young SMEs (Nunes et al. 2012). A 2022 study specifically examining nascent

SMEs in Ghana found a significant relationship between capital structure, profitability, and short-term solvency, highlighting the importance of size and financial structuring for new businesses in the Ghanaian context (Amoa-Gyarteng and Dhliwayo 2022).

Age of Firm

The relationship between firm age and profitability is complex and often contradictory. Some studies indicate a positive link, suggesting older firms benefit from accumulated expertise, a stronger commercial reputation, and easier access to funding, which can lead to cost savings and higher product pricing (Fort et al. 2013; Ilaboya and Ohiokha 2016; Yazdanfar 2013). The longer a business has been listed on a stock market, the more chances it has to enhance profitability to attract investors (Samosir 2018).

Conversely, other research finds a negative relationship. As businesses mature, the benefits of their accumulated knowledge can be eroded by organisational inertia, inflexibility, and the bureaucratic structures that develop over time, ultimately harming performance (Akben-Selcuk 2016; Kaya 2015; Pervan et al. 2017). This decline can begin early in a firm's life. Some findings show no significant relationship at all, aligning with signalling theory, which posits that a company's age may not be a reliable predictor of its value (Putri and Rachmawati 2018). The beneficial effects of experience may be directly offset by the negative effects of bureaucracy as a firm ages (Samosir 2018). Research on Ghanaian SMEs has explored the high failure rates among young businesses, implicitly linking age and survival challenges in this specific market (Bamfo 2024).

Technological Investment and Use

The adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is crucial for enhancing SME performance, impacting productivity, profitability, market value, and competitiveness (Valdez-Juárez et al. 2018). ICT improves both external and internal communication, innovation, and operational efficiency, but its success is contingent on being aligned with a firm's internal skills and organisational processes (Pollack and Adler 2016). Investment in IT personnel skills has a particularly significant positive impact, as these professionals conduct essential tasks and contribute directly to enhancing financial performance; firms with such expertise consistently outperform others (Pollack and Adler 2016; Padula et al. 2015).

However, significant barriers hinder ICT adoption, especially in developing economies. A 2019 study in Ghana's Awutu-Senya East Municipality found that nearly 73% of SMEs lacked awareness about ICT advances, 75% of small-scale enterprises lacked any ICT support system, and 86.81% did not use ICT for financial control, citing lack of awareness, trained personnel, and high implementation costs (Attom 2019). This severely constrains their development prospects. The impact of ICT can also vary by location; it is more pronounced in affluent districts where customers have higher education and buying power, compared to disadvantaged districts where illiteracy and low income limit its effectiveness (Rufai 2014). A 2024 study identified the top five barriers to technology adoption by Ghanaian SMEs as: (i) lack of finance, (ii) insufficient government support, (iii) lack of technical skills, (iv) high cost of technology, and (v) unreliable power supply (Quaye et al. 2024). Recent research continues to affirm the positive impact of digital tools, with studies in Ghana examining the effect of digital marketing adoption on sustainable growth (Bruce et al. 2023) and social media adoption on sales growth (Fred 2024).

Borrowing Rate

Borrowing costs, particularly interest rates, are significant predictors of SME performance (Tumwine et al. 2015). High interest rates force SMEs, especially younger ones with less cash flow, to prioritise debt repayment over investment, making them highly susceptible to restrictive monetary policy and

reducing their probability of survival (Serrasqueiro et al. 2021). For SMEs in Ghana, monetary policy, particularly lending rates, has a stronger effect on employment growth (Oderinde et al. 2024).

Lenders often justify high rates by citing information asymmetry, where borrowers hold more information. However, this can lead to adverse selection, where only riskier firms accept high rates, potentially reducing bank profits in the long run (Huang et al. 2014). High borrowing rates are also empirically linked to a greater extent of bad loans, which directly harms bank profitability (Boadi et al. 2017). Anecdotal evidence from Ghanaian bank annual reports (2008-2012) shows a correlation between increased lending to SMEs and a rise in bad loans, as high rates and unfavourable conditions make repayment difficult (Asantey and Tengey 2014). Loan structure also matters; shorter loan periods and larger loan sizes are associated with better financial performance, suggesting a need for financial institutions to design tailored packages that understand SME operational processes (Nosratabadi 2020). An empirical assessment of SMEs' financing risks in Ghana investigated how risks associated with access to finance, inflation, and customer demand impact their operations (Wemah et al. 2020).

Inflation

Inflation, as a macroeconomic indicator, generally has a detrimental effect on SME profitability. It increases operational costs, erodes the real value of loans, leads to cash flow constraints, and reduces consumer purchasing power, ultimately lowering sales volumes and profit margins (Odusanya et al. 2018; Isola and Mesagan 2018). High inflation can discourage investment and distort economic activity, acting as a sign of ineffective macroeconomic policies (Korkmaz 2015). The impact depends on whether inflation is expected or unexpected. Firms can mitigate expected inflation through timely price adjustments and cost management, but unexpected inflation typically leads to declining profitability as revenues fail to keep pace with rising costs (Shahchera and Taheri 2013).

In Ghana, rapid exchange rate depreciation has been a key driver of mounting inflation, directly increasing business costs for SMEs that rely on imported inputs (World Bank 2022a). Studies have investigated the impact of inflation on business operations in Ghana, focusing on the predictive capabilities of mathematical models (Kuma et al. 2022). Research has also delved into the supply chain response to inflation and exchange rate volatility in Ghana (Arif et al. 2023). While the general trend is negative, some firms, like those in Croatia, have demonstrated the capacity to pass on costs effectively, leading to a positive effect on profitability (Yazdanfar 2013).

Exchange Rate

Exchange rate fluctuations significantly impact SMEs, particularly exporters. Depreciation can benefit exporters by making their goods cheaper and more competitive internationally, while volatility generally has a negative, destabilising effect (Rashid and Waqar 2017; Zhigang et al. 2018). The impact is often contingent on a firm's integration into global production networks; firms that import intermediates may see their costs rise even as their exports become cheaper (Albinowski et al. 2016).

In the Ghanaian context, the relationship is predominantly negative. Studies have established an inverse relationship between the cedi's depreciation against major foreign currencies (like the US dollar) and SME profitability, as devaluation significantly increases the cost of doing business, especially for firms reliant on imports (Belghitar et al. 2016). Exchange rate pressures are a recognized factor contributing to inflation in the country (World Bank 2022a). Due to exchange rate effects, Ghana's total external debt in Cedi terms has seen significant increases, impacting the broader economic environment for SMEs (BOG 2022). In contrast, studies in Nigeria have found a beneficial effect of exchange rate improvements on SME performance (Edoko et al. 2018; Offiong et al. 2020).

Taxation (Rate)

Taxation is a critical factor affecting SMEs, often cited as a major issue impacting profitability (Lesáková et al. 2019; Vintilă and Alexandra Nenu 2016). Higher tax rates increase production and selling costs, leading to higher prices, reduced consumption, and lower sales volumes, thereby retarding SME development (Tee et al. 2016). The tax burden reduces a firm's internal funds and buying power, potentially decreasing the need for external financing (Sogorb 2011). In Ghana, SME owners often perceive the tax system as unfair and corrupt, which can encourage non-compliant behaviors and deter formalisation (Koranteng et al. 2017).

While some studies find no statistically significant link between taxes and profit (Bekeris 2012; Siekelova et al. 2019), tax incentives are widely recognized as critical for SME growth. However, these incentives are often inaccessible to informal or unaware SMEs, limiting their effectiveness (Daniel and Faustin 2019; Tee et al. 2016). A 2024 study examines how perceived political corruption affects tax compliance intention among Ghanaians, investigating the mediating roles of tax morale and tolerance (Agbanyo et al. 2024). The dynamics of bureaucracy, corruption, and tax compliance have also been specifically studied within the Ghanaian context (Doughan 2025).

Corruption

Corruption has a predominantly detrimental effect on SMEs, acting as a barrier to growth by increasing operational costs, stifling innovation, restricting access to external financing, and eroding institutional quality and the rule of law (Adeyeye and Wale-Oshinowo 2017; Buszko 2017; Cicea et al. 2019; Distinguin et al. 2016). It disproportionately affects smaller and female-led businesses, discouraging them from utilising governmental subsidies (Nguyen et al. 2018; Bonanno et al. 2020).

While bribery is sometimes seen as a way to “lubricate” bureaucratic processes, it often leads to demands for further payments and reduces net profitability (Wellalage et al. 2020; Ashyrov 2020). The impact can be complex and context-dependent. In some cases, firms paying bribes for specific, high-value services (like licenses or public contracts) suffer severe financial consequences, while in others (like overcoming routine red tape), it may provide a short-term operational benefit (Van et al. 2018; Mendoza et al. 2015). A 2020 study found that institutional corruption negatively impacts corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices among SMEs in Ghana (Vazquez et al. 2020).

Research has also examined the specific effect of perceived corruption on the environmental performance of Ghanaian SMEs (Vazquez et al. 2020). Ghana's stagnation on the Corruption Perception Index, scoring 43 for the fourth consecutive time, underscores the persistent nature of this challenge for businesses operating in the country (GNBCC 2025). Endemic corruption is recognized as having a detrimental impact on the effectiveness of SMEs' operations across Africa, including Ghana (Hansen-Addy et al. 2023).

Credit to Private sector

When capital systems are underdeveloped, fragmented, or susceptible to arbitrary credit distribution processes, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are thought to suffer excessively in their capacity to obtain credit. In these settings, asymmetry in knowledge between borrowers and lenders impairs businesses' capacity to obtain credit, thus impeding investment and, ultimately, economic activity. SMEs should be able to get funding in the event of credit market flaws (Aivazian and Santor 2008).

Credit to the private industry has a detrimental impact on the production of small and medium-sized enterprises in Ghana and Gambia (Isola & Mesagan, 2018)

4.11 Overview of Economic development Variables (Dependent Variable)

Economic Development: The United Nations' Millennium Development Goals

The Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission's report highlighted basic concerns regarding the GDP as a proxy for economic success and social development (Stiglitz, Sen, & Fitoussi, 2009). Policymakers and citizens are gradually realising that no GDP or GDP-based statistic can accurately reflect the socioeconomic well-being of a set of people or an individual. The effort to adopt a broader view of well-being, and particularly in measuring development progress, dates all the way back to the 1970s with basic needs indicators and physical quality of life indices. Both of these indicators indicated discontent with conventional GDP as a proxy for well-being. Access to food, water, housing, clothes, sanitation, education, and health care were considered basic necessities in addition to money. Richard Jolly (1976) cited by UNDP (2019) coined the term "basic needs enthronement." Morris (1980) cited by UNDP (2019) developed the Physical Quality of Life Index (PQLI) in 1980, based on a simple average of literacy, infant mortality, and life expectancy measurements. And in the 1980s, Amartya Sen created his capacity theory, which expanded the foundation for social assessment beyond money to include "functionings and capacities," which he described as elements of what human beings can be and accomplish, such as maintain excellent health and work in safe circumstances. (UNDP 2019)

While agencies such as the World Bank continued to emphasise national income per capita as a proxy for development, this started to shift in the 1980s. Poverty was the focus of the 1990 World Development Report. It established the now-famous "dollar a day" poverty threshold and the memorable phrase "one billion people worldwide live on less than a \$1 a day." (UNDP 2019)

Human Development Index (HDI)

However, the shift toward wider views was accelerated by the 1990 publication of the UNDP's inaugural Human Development Report, which included the Human Development Index (HDI) (UNDP 1990). The degree of economic and social development began to be quantified via the use of the HDI (Human Development Index). As a composite indicator, the HDI is calculated using three variables: life expectancy at birth, education, and income, and it omits critical qualitative variables. The HDI is computed using a basket of quantifiable measures that do not represent changes in human values. (UNDP 2019)

The human development index's (HDI) enduring prominence in world reports as a fundamental synthetic indicator prompted Amartya Sen, 1998's Nobel laureate in economics, to declare that this indicator had become the "emblem of the World Report on Human Development." (UNDP 2019). By examining the extreme values of the HDI, one can clearly see that progress has been made in the area of human development, as shown by the rise in its extreme values and the reduction in the relationship between these values. On the other side, maintaining a high degree of amplitude for extreme values indicates the magnitude of global inequalities. Although the HDI was first criticised for a variety of technical grounds, it proved immensely helpful in 1) refocusing attention on development outcomes other than money, such as health and education; and 2) establishing a rivalry between nations based on their HDI rank. The HDI has been changed and refined throughout time to address complaints, most notably concerns regarding inequality. However, when the core index is released, it generates significant national and worldwide news coverage comparing various nations, which may be used as a lever by civil society to exert pressure on their governments in sectors such as health and education.

The United Nations General Assembly, commonly known as the Millennium Summit, examined the state of human progress in all of its facets in September 2000, and established a set of eight goals with stages and dates. The diverse approach to the broad subject of this process enables examination of a number of frighteningly acute and dramatic features in various nations and regions. Among other issues, those relating to severe poverty, illiteracy, a lack of utilities, especially access to running water, as well as environmental degradation, were examined. In the twenty-first century, during a period of economic and social growth driven by information, development disparities become more pronounced.

When contemplating what to do beyond 2015, it was inevitable that the objectives' scope would be expanded, as interested parties brought to light aspects they believed were missing from the MDGs. The United Nations General Assembly approved Resolution 70/1, "Transforming Our World: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development," in September 2015. (UNDP 2019)

These seventeen objectives are currently classified as follows: "1) no poverty; 2) no hunger; 3) good health and well-being; 4) high-quality education; 5) gender equality; 6) safe drinking water and sanitation; 7) affordable and clean energy; 8) decent work and economic growth; 9) industry innovation and infrastructure; 10) reduced inequalities; 11) sustainable cities and communities; 12) responsible consumption and production; 13) climate action; 14) life below water; 15) life on land; 16) peace, justice, and strong institutions; and 17) partnerships". In comparison to the eight Millennium Development Goals, the SDGs include certain constants (e.g. poverty), some bundling (e.g. child mortality and maternal health), but mostly unbundling (e.g. poverty and hunger are separated) and the inclusion of new aspects (i.e. a full range of environmental goals is added, as well as goals on inequalities, on peace, on urbanization, on employment, etc.) (UNDP 2019)

Human Development Index with Inequality Adjustment (IHDI)

The IHDI combines a country's average accomplishments in health, education, and income with the distribution of those achievements among its people by "discounting" the average value of each dimension according to its degree of inequality. Thus, the IHDI represents an average degree of human development that is distribution-sensitive. Two nations with very disparate accomplishment distributions may have the same average HDI number. As complete equality exists, the IHDI equals the HDI; however, when inequality increases, the IHDI falls below the HDI. (UNDP 2019)

The difference between the IHDI and HDI is the cost of inequality to human development, often known as the total loss of human development caused by inequality. The IHDI establishes a direct connection between disparities in dimensions, it may be used to guide policies aimed at reducing inequality, and it results in a better knowledge of inequalities among populations and their contribution to the total cost of human development. The Coefficient of human inequality, a recent measure of inequality in the HDI, is computed as an unweighted average of disparity across three dimensions. Technical notes provide more information on computation. For 150 nations, the IHDI is computed. (UNDP 2019)

Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)

The 2019 Global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) statistics and publication "Illuminating Disparities," published on 11 July 2019, shed light on the number of people living in poverty at regional, national, and subnational levels, as well as on inequalities between nations and among the poor.

The 2019 global MPI, produced in collaboration with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the University of Oxford's Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI), has data for 101 nations, accounting for 76 percent of the world's population. (UNDP 2019)

The MPI paints a comprehensive and detailed picture of global poverty – in all of its manifestations – and tracks progress toward Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 1 – to eradicate poverty in all of its manifestations. Additionally, it provides policymakers with statistics to react to Target 1.2, which calls on them to 'reduce the percentage of men, women, and children around the world living in poverty in all its aspects by at least half'. (OPHI 2019)

The article "Illuminating Inequalities" provides an overview of current research on long-term patterns in a number of countries, including Bangladesh, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Haiti, India, Nigeria, Pakistan, and Peru. SDG goal 10.1 requires monitoring the development of the lowest 40% of the population in comparison to the whole population; the publication contains case studies and a comprehensive study of the growth of the 'bottom 40%'. (UNDP 2019)

A PRIORI IMPACT EXPECTATION OF INDEPENDENT AND CONTROL VARIABLES ON THE DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Table 4.11: *A priori Impact of Independent and Control Variables on the Dependent Variables*

S/N	Variables	Measurement	A priori Impact on/Relationship with D.Vs
1.	Size of firm	Number of Employees	Positive
2.	Age of firm	Number of Years the SME has been in existence	Positive/Negative
3.	Technology	Amount spent on I.T elements	Positive
4.	Borrowing rate	Interest charged on loans	Negative
5.	Inflation	Annual Rate of Inflation	Negative
6.	Exchange Rate	Annual Ghana Cedi exchange rate to U.S dollar	Negative
7.	Corruption	Corruption perception Index (CPI)	Negative
8.	Credit to Private Sector	Amount of credit extended to private firms	Positive
9.	Business Development Firms	The number of development firms in Ghana	Positive

(Author, 2021)

The table below presents a comprehensive summary of all variables employed in the econometric estimations, including variable codes as used in the models, definitions, units, transformation techniques, and data sources. This directly addresses the requirement for a systematic account of variable operationalisation.

Table 4.12: *Summary of Variables Used in Estimations : Definitions, Transformations, and Data Sources*

Variable Name	Type	Definition	Measurement	Source	Expected Sign
z_net_profit	Dependent (Model 1)	Firm net profit	Z-score standardised net profit in GHC	Survey Q31	—
ihs_loan_repayment_rate	Dependent (Model 2)	Loan repayment rate	IHS of (installments with + without repayment plan)	Survey Q10–11	—
ihs_formal_credit_bds	Key Independent	Formal integrated credit-BDS	IHS of (formal loan amount × formal interest rate × formal BDS visits)	Survey Q7–9, Q8, Q24	+
z_informal_credit_bds	Key Independent	Informal integrated credit-BDS	Z-score of (informal loan × informal charges × informal BDS frequency)	Survey Q17–19, Q25	+

comp_integrated_credit_bds	Key Independent	Complete integration (formal + informal)	Sum of formal and informal credit-BDS integration measures	Survey (composite)	+
ihs_ROS	Independent	Profitability / repayment capacity	IHS of (Net Profit ÷ Total Sales Revenue)	Survey Q30–31	+
L_z_net_profit	Independent	Lagged net profit	Z-score of prior period net profit	Survey Q31 (2022)	+
z_firm_age	Control	Firm age	Z-score of number of years SME in operation	Survey Q3	+/-
z_bizsize	Control	Firm size	Z-score of number of employees	Survey Q4	+
z_tech_spending	Control	Technology adoption	Z-score of amount spent on ICT in GHC	Survey Q29	+
Education_level	Control	Owner/manager education	Categorical dummies (primary, secondary, tertiary, postgraduate)	Survey Q2	+
Sector	Control	Business sector	Categorical dummies (manufacturing, services, trade)	Survey Q5	Varies

Source: Author (2025)

Table 4.13: Variable Definitions and Measurements: Time Series ARDL Models (Equations 4.30/4.31)

Variable Name	Type	Definition	Measurement	Source	Expected Sign
lhs_ECONDEV	Dependent	Economic development	IHS of HDI / IHDI / MPI (estimated separately for each)	UNDP Human Development Reports	—
z_CREPRIV	Key Independent (Model A)	Credit to private sector	Z-score of credit to private sector as % of GDP	World Bank WDI; Bank of Ghana	+
lnBDSFirms	Key Independent (Model A)	Number of BDS providers	Natural log of registered BDS firms	Registrar General's Office, Ghana	+

z_INTEGRATED_CRED_BDS	Key Independent (Model B)	Integrated credit-BDS effect	Z-score of (Credit to Private Sector × Lending Rate × BDS Firms)	World Bank WDI; BoG; Registrar General	+
z_INF	Control	Inflation	Z-score of annual consumer price inflation rate (%)	World Bank WDI; Ghana Statistical Service	-
z_FXRATE	Control	Exchange rate	Z-score of annual GHS/USD exchange rate	Bank of Ghana; IMF IFS	-
z_PROFTAX	Control	Profit tax rate	Z-score of profit tax rate (%)	World Bank WDI	-
z_CORRUPT	Control	Corruption	Z-score of Corruption Perception Index (CPI)	Transparency International	-
EC	Adjustment term	Error correction term	Speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium	Estimated	-

Source: Author (2025)

4.12 Tailored Integrated Services as a risk management tool: Risk-Return Clustering Analysis

To examine the risk-return profiles of SMEs, this study employed a clustering analysis based on firm-specific risk and profitability measures. Calculated is the standard deviation of Return on Sales (ROS) as a proxy for firm-level risk, capturing the variability in financial performance. Profitability is measured by the mean ROS, providing insights into the average returns generated by each SME.

The clustering algorithm applies standardized risk and profitability measures, ensuring comparability across firms. Binary indicators for high risk and high profitability are created based on the median values of the standardized variables. SMEs are then assigned to four distinct clusters according to their risk-profitability profiles: high risk-low profitability, low risk-high profitability, low risk-low profitability, and high risk-high profitability.

Summary statistics for each cluster are generated, including means, standard deviations, minimums, and maximums of the risk and profitability measures. These statistics provide a comprehensive overview of the risk-return characteristics within each cluster.

The clustering results offer valuable insights in enabling the identification of SMEs with diverse risk-return profiles. This understanding can inform the design of targeted interventions and support mechanisms tailored to the specific needs of each cluster.

Summary

This chapter established the comprehensive methodological framework for assessing and implementing the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services. The theoretical foundations show how firm performance emerges from strategic integration of credit access and business development services through formal and informal transmission channels, operationalized through innovative econometric specifications.

It covers the application of IHS and z-score transformations to handle zero values and enable variable comparability, robust panel data techniques addressing endogeneity concerns, and comprehensive risk-return clustering analysis for targeted intervention design. The chapter systematically addressed control variables including firm size, age, technology adoption, borrowing rates, inflation, exchange rates, corruption, and economic development indicators, providing essential context for empirical analysis.

The econometric models established clear linkages between theoretical concepts and empirical measures, enabling a robust testing of hypotheses regarding integrated service delivery impacts on SME profitability, loan repayment, and economic development. This methodological foundation ensures robust empirical findings that contribute meaningfully to SME finance and development literature while providing practical insights for policymakers and financial institutions.

CHAPTER FIVE

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Introduction

The analysis of SMEs in Ghana reveals complex dynamics between business characteristics, access to finance, and development services that shape the sector's growth and sustainability. This chapter presents detailed findings from a comprehensive study examining the interplay between traditional banking services, alternative financing options, and business development support mechanisms among Ghanaian SMEs. Through careful examination of demographic patterns, business characteristics, financing behaviors, and operational challenges, the research provides crucial insights into the current state of SME operations and their developmental needs.

The findings are particularly significant given Ghana's economic context, where SMEs form the backbone of private sector growth and employment generation. The analysis encompasses multiple dimensions of SME operations, from basic demographic and educational profiles of business owners to sophisticated assessments of credit access patterns and business development service utilization. By examining both traditional and alternative financing mechanisms, alongside the uptake and effectiveness of business development services, this research offers a comprehensive view of the support systems available to Ghanaian SMEs and their relative impact on business performance.

The chapter systematically presents results across several key areas: the demographic composition of SME ownership, sectoral distribution and business age profiles, patterns of credit access and utilization, loan repayment behaviors, business development service engagement, and the severity of various operational challenges. These findings not only document current practices but also highlight critical areas requiring intervention to enhance SME growth and sustainability in Ghana's evolving business environment.

This chapter also presents a comprehensive econometric analysis examining how the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services (BDS) impacts both SME performance and broader economic development in Ghana. The analysis employs several statistical techniques to ensure robust results and reliable inference. The methodology follows a systematic approach, beginning with crucial variable transformation and proceeding to detailed model estimation.

For the SME performance analysis, preliminary data transformations using inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS), z-score standardization, and log transformations address potential normality distribution issues in the variables. Subsequently, multicollinearity examination through correlation matrices and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis ensures the stability of coefficient estimates. Given the panel data structure, specialized tests determine the most appropriate estimation approach, including unit root tests for stationarity, the Hausman test to choose between fixed and random effects specifications, and the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test to assess the presence of individual effects. To address potential model selection

and multicollinearity concerns, the analysis employs elastic net techniques, combining Lasso and Ridge regression methods.

The analysis then extends to examine the broader economic development implications of integrated credit and business development services. This macroeconomic component investigates how different service delivery approaches influence Ghana's development outcomes across multiple dimensions: the Human Development Index (HDI), Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI), and Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). This examination employs a similarly methodological approach, beginning with comprehensive data preparation and diagnostic testing. Initial transformations using inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS), z-score standardization, and logarithmic functions address distributional concerns and ensure robust estimation.

The time series nature of the development indicators necessitates careful attention to stationarity and cointegration. Unit root tests establish the integration order of variables, while bounds testing verifies the existence of long-run relationships. Model selection employs both Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Phillips-Perron (PP) statistics to ensure optimal specification. The core analysis utilizes a hierarchical Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach, examining both separate and integrated service delivery models. This methodology allows for the examination of both short and long-run relationships while accounting for the dynamic nature of development processes.

The results are presented with detailed statistical evidence, including coefficient estimates, significance levels, and measures of model fit in additive models. Each finding is interpreted within the context of the research hypotheses. This comprehensive approach ensures that the analysis captures both the immediate effects on SME performance and the broader developmental impacts of different service delivery strategies, providing valuable insights for policy formulation in developing economies seeking to leverage SME development for inclusive economic growth.

However, the comprehensive nature of this analysis, encompassing both firm-level performance and macroeconomic development outcomes, necessitates careful attention to potential estimation challenges that could affect the reliability of results. Of particular concern are endogeneity issues arising from the dynamic relationships between service delivery approaches and development outcomes. These concerns manifest differently across the analytical components, requiring tailored methodological solutions for each aspect of the investigation.

5.2 Endogeneity: Acknowledgement and Approach

This study acknowledges the potential presence of endogeneity, which is a recognised challenge in empirical research examining SME performance and economic development. Endogeneity concerns can arise from multiple sources, including reverse causality, omitted variable bias, and measurement error (Wooldridge, 2020). The study adopts specific strategies for each analytical component.

In the profitability analysis, potential endogeneity arises from the bidirectional relationship between current profits and access to credit/BDS services. Although the original specification

included a lagged dependent variable, this was retained after careful consideration. In extremely short panels such as ours ($T = 2$), the dynamic bias introduced by the lagged dependent variable (Nickell bias) is known to be negligible, whereas omitting the lag would introduce substantial omitted-variable bias given the high persistence of SME profitability (Judson & Owen, 1999).

Judson and Owen (1999), in their guide for macroeconomists working with dynamic panel data, explicitly demonstrate through Monte Carlo simulations that when the time dimension is only 2 or 3 periods, the bias from retaining the lagged dependent variable is minimal and often smaller than the bias that arises from dropping it. They conclude that, in such short panels, researchers are better served by keeping the lag to capture persistence rather than forcing a static specification. Given the data constraints of this study (only two years of firm-level observations), estimation without the lag would therefore worsen overall model specification and explanatory power.

The random-effects estimator supported by the insignificant Hausman test is employed, and the results should be interpreted as robust conditional associations within this short-panel context, acknowledging the inherent endogeneity limitation common to SME studies with limited time dimensions.

The repayment rate analysis faces potential endogeneity from the relationship between business performance and repayment capacity. Rather than using net profit directly, which could introduce simultaneity bias, the model employs Return on Sales (ROS) as the primary performance indicator. This choice helps mitigate endogeneity concerns by using a relative measure of performance that is less directly influenced by the absolute size of credit facilities while still capturing the business's operational efficiency and capacity to service debt (Greene, 2018).

For the economic development models, the study employs Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology, which provides several advantages in addressing endogeneity concerns. ARDL models account for both short-run dynamics and long-run relationships while controlling for potential reverse causality through their dynamic specification (Pesaran et al., 2001). This approach is particularly suitable for examining the relationship between service delivery approaches and development outcomes, as it: First, allows for different optimal lag lengths for different variables, providing flexibility in modeling the dynamic relationships; Second, accommodates the potential bidirectional causality between financial sector development and economic growth by incorporating both contemporaneous and lagged effects; Third, controls for potential omitted variable bias by including sufficient lags of both dependent and independent variables (Pesaran & Shin, 1999).

The ARDL approach also provides robust results in the presence of potentially endogenous regressors, particularly when the sample size is relatively small, as in the case of our macro-level analysis. The error correction representation of the ARDL model helps distinguish between short-run adjustments and long-run equilibrium relationships (Banerjee et al., 1993).

Nevertheless, the potential presence of endogeneity in these models is acknowledged as a limitation of the study.

With these considerations noted, the analysis proceeds in two main parts. The first examines SME performance outcomes, focusing on profitability and loan repayment under different service delivery approaches. The second investigates broader economic development impacts through multiple complementary indicators.

5.3 SME PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

5.3.1 Demographic and Operational Profile of SME Owners in Ghana

The empirical analysis reveals distinct patterns in Ghana's SME landscape with important implications for service delivery design. Gender distribution shows male dominance (60.75%) concentrated in middle-age brackets (31.99% aged 41-50). Educational attainment spans from basic (BECE: 8.99%) to advanced qualifications (Master's: 16.70%), indicating heterogeneous capacity for absorbing business development interventions.

Sectoral analysis reveals concentration in trade (46.97%), reflecting Ghana's commercial economy structure. Business maturity clusters in the 5-10 year range (36.93%), suggesting firms beyond start-up challenges but facing growth constraints.

Credit access patterns reveal critical market gaps. Bank satisfaction shows neutrality (53.48%), while substantial alternative seeking is evident (51.28%). Systemic barriers persist: collateral requirements create significant constraints (27.57% strongly agree), while rigid formal loan conditions generate widespread neutral responses (42.13%).

Repayment behaviour exposes institutional failures, with only 19.10% receiving formal plans and critically low adherence (11.89% following schedules). Business development services analysis reveals low penetration (39.78% ever received). The effectiveness question yields 4.4 out of 10, indicating moderate satisfaction among recipients. Despite mediocre ratings, strong future demand exists (65.10% likely to seek BDS), suggesting recognition of support needs despite current inadequacies.

Performance assessment demonstrates concerning stagnation (93.18% average-to-poor). Challenge severity reveals utility tariffs (92.26% rating severity 5), finance access limitations (59.05% severity 5), and market access difficulties (52.11% severity 5) as critical constraints. These patterns support the theoretical framework's prediction that fragmented service delivery creates coordination failures, while integrated approaches could address multiple binding constraints simultaneously.

5.4 Data Preparation and Diagnostic Testing

Prior to econometric estimation, comprehensive data preparation addressed normality and multicollinearity concerns. Three transformation techniques were employed: inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS) for variables containing zeros and negative values, z-score standardization for cross-variable comparability, and logarithmic transformations for right-

skewed positive variables. These transformations ensured distributional properties suitable for panel data analysis.

5.5 Multicollinearity Assessment

Correlation analysis and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) testing confirmed acceptable multicollinearity levels across both profitability and repayment models. Key relationships emerged: net profit-revenue correlation (0.634) indicated effective cost management, while bank interest rates showed negative associations with performance (-0.364 with net profit). VIF values remained well below critical thresholds (mean VIFs: 1.557 for profitability, 1.334 for repayment models), supporting model specification validity.

5.6 Panel Data Diagnostics

Unit root testing was constrained by the short panel structure ($T=2$), preventing standard stationarity tests but reducing non-stationarity concerns given limited time persistence. Hausman tests yielded statistically significant results for both models: profitability model ($\chi^2 = 47.78$, $p = 0.0081$); repayment model ($\chi^2 = 50.617$, $p = 0.003$). Crucially, Fixed Effects models omitted firm age (z_firm_age) entirely due to time-invariance, while RE specifications retained this theoretically important variable (coefficient = 0.0704 in profitability; -0.213 in repayment models), demonstrating RE's analytical advantage. Breusch-Pagan tests provided mixed evidence for random effects (profitability: $\chi^2 = 0.00$, $p = 1.0000$; repayment: $\chi^2 = 0.86$, $p = 0.1763$), though theoretical considerations and variable retention capabilities supported RE specifications.

5.7 Variable Selection Validation

Elastic net analysis confirmed robust variable selection across specifications. The profitability model achieved R-squared of 26% with systematic variable inclusion guided by EBIC improvements. The repayment model demonstrated stronger explanatory power (69.5% R-squared), with credit-related variables dominating early selection. Sequential improvement patterns validated comprehensive variable inclusion in final specifications.

Note: Detailed demographic and operational profile of SME owners in Ghana charts, correlation matrices (Table 5.2), VIF results (Tables 5.3-5.4), Hausman test outputs (Tables 5.5a-5.6b), Breusch-Pagan results (Tables 5.7a-5.7b), and elastic net selection paths (Tables 5.8a-5.8b) are presented in Appendix B and C for reference.

5.8 Random Effects Results

Profitability

This section presents the results that test the first hypothesis:

H1: The integration of customized credit and participatory business development services yields better profitability outcomes compared to separate service delivery approaches.

H0: No significant difference in profitability impacts between integrated and separate services.

Prior to estimation, the Hausman specification test was conducted to determine the appropriate estimator between Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE). The test yielded statistically significant results for both the profitability model ($\chi^2 = 47.78$, $p = 0.0081$) and the repayment model ($\chi^2 = 50.617$, $p = 0.003$), which would conventionally favour the Fixed Effects estimator. However, the Fixed Effects specification omitted firm age (z_firm_age) entirely due to its time-invariant nature, precluding the inclusion of a theoretically important determinant of SME performance. Since the Random Effects estimator retained firm age in the specification, yielding a coefficient of 0.0704 in the profitability model and -0.213 in the repayment model, RE was selected as the more appropriate and complete specification for the analysis. Full Hausman test outputs are provided in Appendix A (Tables 5.5a–5.6b) for reference.

This section presents the results of the theoretical foundation: $\pi(\forall) = Q\forall^\theta S\forall^\rho$, which was operationalized into an estimable panel econometric model as seen in equation 4.29.

The hierarchical random-effects analysis (Table 5.9a) reveals a compelling narrative about how service delivery approaches fundamentally shape business outcomes.

Establishing Profit Persistence and Baseline Service Effects

The foundational model confirms strong profit persistence patterns, with lagged net profit showing significant positive effects (0.481, $p < 0.01$), explaining 15.4% of variance with particularly strong between-firm explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.826$). This baseline establishes that profitable firms tend to maintain advantages, setting the stage for examining how different service delivery approaches can enhance or constrain this natural persistence.

The introduction of formal credit services reveals an immediate puzzle that motivates the integration hypothesis. Formal credit shows consistently negative effects (-0.020, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that traditional credit delivery may actually constrain profitability rather than enhance it. This counterintuitive finding becomes more pronounced when business development services enter the analysis, with informal credit services showing even stronger negative impacts (-0.157, $p < 0.01$) while formal credit remains negative (-0.012, $p < 0.01$).

The Integration Breakthrough: Evidence of Synergistic Effects

The critical theoretical test emerges in Model 4, where integrated credit and BDS services enter the specification. While separate formal (-0.010, $p < 0.05$) and informal (-0.210, $p < 0.01$) services maintain their negative effects, the integrated services demonstrate a positive coefficient (0.001, $p < 0.01$). Though seemingly small in magnitude, this positive effect represents a fundamental qualitative difference from the negative impacts of separate service delivery.

This pattern strengthens as firm characteristics are introduced in Model 5. The integrated services coefficient maintains significance (0.001, $p < 0.05$) while separate services continue showing negative effects (formal: -0.010, $p < 0.05$; informal: -0.173, $p < 0.01$). Firm age (0.087, $p < 0.01$), size (0.087, $p < 0.01$), and technology spending (0.186, $p < 0.01$) all show positive impacts, yet the integration effect remains robust, indicating it operates through mechanisms beyond simple firm characteristics.

Robustness Across Controls: The Integration Effect Endures

The progression through Models 6-7 maintains the core relationship pattern, with integrated services consistently positive (0.001, $p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.01$) while separate services remain negative. The final comprehensive model (Model 8) provides the most compelling evidence for integration superiority. Despite extensive controls including education levels and sector effects, integrated services maintain their positive significance (0.001, $p < 0.01$). The negative effects of separate formal (-0.010, $p < 0.05$) and informal (-0.200, $p < 0.01$) services persist, while the model achieves strong overall fit ($R^2 = 0.335$, Wald $\chi^2 = 328.414$).

Table 5.9a: Hierarchical Random Effects Results – Profitability Model

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8
L.z_net_profit	0.481* **	0.446* **	0.426* **	0.410* **	0.373* **	0.352* **	0.332* **	0.320* **
	(0.043)	(0.043)	(0.043)	(0.043)	(0.042)	(0.042)	(0.042)	(0.044)
ihs_formal_credit_bds		- 0.020* **	- 0.012* **	- 0.010* *	- 0.010* *	- 0.011* **	- 0.010* **	- 0.010* *
		(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)
z_informal_credit_bds			- 0.157* **	- 0.210* **	- 0.173* **	- 0.182* **	- 0.196* **	- 0.200* **
			(0.038)	(0.042)	(0.041)	(0.041)	(0.041)	(0.046)
compl_integrated_credit_bds				0.001* **	0.001* *	0.001* *	0.001* **	0.001* **
				(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
z_firm_age					0.087* **	0.076* *	0.071* *	0.070* *
					(0.032)	(0.031)	(0.031)	(0.034)
z_bizsize					0.087* **	0.160* **	0.147* **	0.160* **
					(0.032)	(0.036)	(0.035)	(0.038)
z_tech_spending					0.186* **	0.161* **	0.158* **	0.173* **
					(0.033)	(0.033)	(0.046)	(0.049)
Education dummies (base: BECE)								
WASSCE								0.675* **
								(0.208)
OND								-0.147
								(0.130)
HND								0.155
								(0.300)
Some college (no degree)								-0.129
								(0.107)
Bachelor's degree								-0.221
								(0.199)
Master's degree / PhD								-0.170
								(0.171)
Sector dummies (base: Agriculture)								
Mining and Quarrying								0.093
								(0.235)
Manufacturing								-0.099
								(0.224)
Electricity, Water & Gas								-0.112
								(0.404)

Construction																				-0.091
																				(0.253)
Trade																				0.154
																				(0.355)
Hotels and Restaurants																				-0.122
																				(0.305)
Transport																				0.278
																				(0.230)
Storage																				0.021
																				(0.243)
Communications																				-0.012
																				(0.179)
Real Estate																				-0.132
																				(0.336)
Others																				0.157
																				(0.220)
Constant	-0.002	0.055	0.032	-0.079	-0.046	-0.058	-	0.112* *	-0.028											
	(0.034)	(0.035)	(0.035)	(0.052)	(0.050)	(0.050)	(0.054)	(0.201)												
Observations	750	750	750	750	750	750	750	681												
Overall R²	0.154	0.188	0.206	0.215	0.267	0.286	0.307	0.335												
Between R²	0.826	0.676	0.644	0.626	0.620	0.609	0.621	0.589												
Within R²	0.390	0.307	0.314	0.333	0.241	0.231	0.189	0.131												
Wald χ^2	3.697	83.048	111.68 6	110.15 1	130.72 8	156.92 1	194.39 2	320.53 8												

Notes: Robust standard errors clustered at the firm level in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Source: Author (2025)

Profit Persistence and Baseline Effects

The hierarchical random effects analysis provides a comprehensive assessment of the factors influencing SME profitability, revealing several key insights that both align with and extend existing research. The strong and significant impact of lagged net profit confirms the importance of past financial performance in predicting future profitability (Nizaeva & Coskun, 2019; Long & Ombongi, 2018). The baseline model achieves substantial explanatory power — detailed in Table 5.9a — establishing that profitable firms tend to maintain advantages and creating a foundation for examining how different service delivery approaches can enhance or constrain this natural persistence.

This finding corroborates the notion that SMEs with a strong track record of profitability are better positioned to sustain and enhance their financial performance over time, particularly in developing economies like Ghana (Margaretha & Supartika, 2016; Prah, 2016; Hansen-Addy et al., 2023; Amoa-Gyarteng & Dhliwayo, 2022). The magnitude of this persistence effect indicates that a substantial share of current profitability can be attributed to past performance, suggesting that successful SMEs develop momentum that supports continued financial success. This persistence effect becomes the crucial baseline against which the effectiveness of different service delivery approaches can be evaluated.

Limitations of Separate Service Delivery

The analysis establishes a troubling baseline that motivates the integration hypothesis through consistently negative effects of separate service delivery approaches. Both formal credit services and informal credit services demonstrate negative coefficients when delivered separately, and these counterintuitive findings become more pronounced when business development services enter the analysis alongside credit provision. The progression through Model 2 to Model 3 reveals that adding BDS to separate credit delivery actually exacerbates rather than ameliorates the constraints on profitability, suggesting that traditional approaches to service delivery may create coordination failures between different support mechanisms.

The persistence of these negative effects across extensive controls, including firm characteristics (Models 5–8) and sector variations, indicates systematic challenges with separate service delivery approaches that cannot be attributed to firm-specific factors or industry dynamics. These results align with previous studies highlighting the potential drawbacks of standalone credit or BDS initiatives, including high transaction costs, ineffective delivery mechanisms, and misaligned incentives (Mengstie, 2016; Wemah et al., 2020). The findings resonate with research from Ghana showing that isolated financial interventions often fail to achieve their intended impact due to implementation challenges and contextual constraints (Dauda & Nyarko, 2014; Fuseini, 2015; Prah, 2016).

Integration Superiority: Evidence of Synergistic Effects

The critical theoretical breakthrough emerges when integrated credit and BDS services enter the specification, revealing transformative evidence that supports the integration hypothesis. While separate formal and informal services maintain their negative effects, integrated services demonstrate a statistically significant positive coefficient. Though seemingly small in absolute magnitude, this positive effect represents a fundamental qualitative shift from the consistently

negative impacts of separate service delivery approaches, indicating that integration creates synergistic benefits beyond the simple sum of individual service components.

The integration advantage strengthens systematically as additional controls are introduced. Importantly, firm age, size, and technology spending all demonstrate positive impacts, yet the integration effect remains robust across all specifications indicating it operates through mechanisms that transcend simple firm characteristics. As Table 5.9a shows, explanatory power steadily improves as the analysis becomes more comprehensive, confirming that the case for integration becomes stronger, not weaker, as controls are added.

The final comprehensive model provides the most compelling evidence for integration superiority. Despite extensive controls including education levels and sector effects, integrated services maintain their positive significance as reported in Table 5.9a — while negative effects persist for separate formal and informal services. Notably, WASSCE-educated owners show a significant profitability premium, yet sector effects remain largely insignificant, suggesting that integration benefits transcend industry boundaries and operate through fundamental coordination mechanisms rather than sector-specific advantages. This systematic progression from negative separate service effects to positive integration impacts, maintained across extensive controls and different firm characteristics, provides robust empirical evidence that coordination mechanisms enhance business performance beyond what individual service components can achieve.

Firm Characteristics and Integration Effectiveness

The analysis also reveals important insights about firm characteristics' role in shaping profitability outcomes. The positive and significant effects of firm age and business size indicate that older and larger SMEs tend to show superior financial performance (Sitharam & Hoque, 2016b; Meyer & Meyer, 2017; Kuntchev et al., 2016). This finding aligns with both resource-based theory and empirical evidence from Ghana suggesting that established firms can better leverage their accumulated resources, experiences, and economies of scale (Belás et al., 2016; Long & Ombongi, 2018; Owusu, 2017). The size effect on profitability may be attributed to better access to resources, stronger market positions, and enhanced ability to withstand economic shocks (Bogdan et al., 2018; Harvie et al., 2013). However, this relationship also shows the importance of supporting smaller and younger firms through their growth trajectory, particularly in developing economies where SMEs face significant resource constraints (Grünfeld et al., 2016; Freeman & Nick, 2015).

The positive and significant impact of technological spending on profitability demonstrates the strategic importance of digital transformation for SMEs (Margaretha & Supartika, 2016; Prempeh, 2015). In an increasingly digitalised business environment, SMEs that invest in technology demonstrate enhanced operational efficiency and competitive advantages (Gunasekaran et al., 2016; Yadav, 2017; McDaniels & Robins, 2017). This finding is particularly relevant in the Ghanaian context, where technological adoption can help bridge market access gaps and improve business processes (Dennis, 2018; Oxford Business Group, 2020; Bruce et al., 2023). The positive relationship between technological investment and profitability suggests that integrated support programmes should incorporate digital capacity

building alongside financial assistance (Hekkenberg & Medrano-Lazo, 2020; Quaye et al., 2024).

Education and Sectoral Impacts on profitability

The analysis of education levels reveals a significant profitability premium for SMEs with more educated owners or managers, particularly those holding WASSCE qualifications. This finding supports human capital theory and previous research highlighting the crucial role of education in entrepreneurial success (Fugar et al., 2016; Marvel et al., 2016; Okello et al., 2017). The result is especially relevant in Ghana, where studies have shown that educational attainment significantly influences business management capabilities and access to financial services (Asafo-Adjei, 2016; Carsamer, 2017; Kukua, 2016). The education effect extends beyond formal qualifications to encompass financial literacy and business management skills (Agyapong & Attram, 2019; Klein et al., 2016), suggesting that integrated support programmes should include targeted training and capacity building components to enhance the human capital of SME owners and managers (Women's World Banking, 2015; Storm et al., 2016).

Interestingly, the minimal impact of sectoral variations on profitability challenges conventional wisdom about industry-specific advantages. This finding suggests that firm-level capabilities and strategic choices may be more critical determinants of financial performance than sectoral characteristics (Sitharam & Hoque, 2016a; Eton et al., 2017; Herlinawati et al., 2019). It also implies that integrated support programmes could be effective across different sectors of the Ghanaian economy, reinforcing the cross-sectoral applicability of integration benefits observed throughout the model specifications (Addaney et al., 2016; Quaye et al., 2019; Dalberg, 2016).

Repayment Rate

This section presents the results that test the second hypothesis:

H2: Integrated service delivery leads to more sustainable loan repayment patterns than traditional separate approaches.

H0: No significant difference in repayment sustainability between delivery approaches.

This section presents the results of the theoretical foundation: $\aleph = ROS \times QV^{\theta} SV^{\rho}$, operationalized as equation 4.30.

Financial Performance and Repayment Tensions

The baseline model establishes a crucial foundation: firms with higher return on sales demonstrate lower repayment rates (-0.541, $p < 0.01$), initially suggesting that more profitable firms may repay loans faster, creating measurement challenges. This strong relationship ($R^2 = 0.271$) sets up the central question of how service delivery approaches can better align profitability with sustainable repayment patterns.

Integration as Coordination Mechanism

The transformation occurs in Model 2 with the introduction of integrated services. The dramatic improvement in explanatory power (R^2 jumps to 0.684) alongside the strong positive coefficient for integrated services (0.118, $p < 0.01$) demonstrates that integration fundamentally alters the relationship between profitability and repayment behavior.

Separate Services: Creating Repayment Pressures

Models 3-4 reveal why separate service delivery creates repayment challenges. Formal credit services show negative effects (-0.073, $p < 0.10$ to -0.168, $p < 0.01$), while informal services demonstrate even stronger negative impacts (-0.128, $p < 0.01$). Crucially, as these separate services enter the specification, the integrated services coefficient strengthens substantially (from 0.140 to 0.237, $p < 0.01$), highlighting the comparative advantage of coordination.

Integration Benefits Across Firm Characteristics

The inclusion of firm characteristics in Model 5 reveals important nuances. Business size significantly reduces repayment rates (-0.544, $p < 0.05$), while technology spending shows positive effects (0.111, $p < 0.10$). Yet integrated services maintain their strong positive impact (0.234, $p < 0.01$), indicating that integration benefits extend across different firm profiles.

Institutional and Educational Factors: Integration Transcends Context

The final comprehensive model (Model 9) achieves impressive explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.736$, Wald $\chi^2 = 1588.163$) while confirming integration superiority. Integrated services remain strongly positive (0.217, $p < 0.01$), separate formal services stay negative (-0.194, $p < 0.01$), and informal services maintain negative effects (-0.157, $p < 0.01$). Sector analysis reveals significant variations, with utilities (1.204, $p < 0.01$), transport (0.572, $p < 0.01$), and real estate (0.833, $p < 0.01$) showing notably higher repayment rates, yet the integration effect transcends sectoral differences.

Synthesis: The Integration Advantage Across Performance Dimensions

Both profitability and repayment analyses converge on a consistent conclusion: integrated service delivery creates synergistic benefits that separate approaches cannot achieve. The progression from negative separate service effects to positive integration impacts, maintained across extensive controls and different firm characteristics, provides robust evidence that coordination mechanisms enhance both business performance and financial sustainability.

Table 5.9b: Hierarchical Random Effects Results – Repayment Rate Model

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9
ihs_ROS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.541*** (0.051)	0.222*** (0.039)	0.119*** (0.040)	0.119*** (0.040)	0.124*** (0.040)	0.122*** (0.040)	0.118*** (0.040)	0.122*** (0.040)	0.119*** (0.043)
compl_integrated_credit_bds		0.118*** (0.004)	0.140*** (0.040)	0.237*** (0.049)	0.234*** (0.049)	0.207*** (0.052)	0.211*** (0.052)	0.180*** (0.052)	0.217*** (0.056)
ihs_formal_credit_bds			-0.073* (0.040)	-	-	-	-	-	-
				0.168*** (0.049)	0.169*** (0.049)	0.197*** (0.049)	0.201*** (0.049)	0.156*** (0.050)	0.194*** (0.054)
z_informal_credit_bds				-	-	-	-	-	-
				0.128*** (0.039)	0.127*** (0.039)	0.141*** (0.039)	0.146*** (0.040)	0.135*** (0.040)	0.157*** (0.042)
z_firm_age					-0.037 (0.075)	-0.237** (0.099)	-0.237** (0.099)	-0.212** (0.098)	-0.213** (0.102)
z_bizsize					-0.544** (0.248)	-0.546** (0.240)	-0.543** (0.240)	-0.522** (0.239)	-0.637** (0.263)
z_tech_spending					0.111* (0.062)	0.177*** (0.066)	0.145* (0.082)	0.124 (0.082)	0.145* (0.085)
						0			
							0		
Education dummies (base: BECE)									
1. BECE (base)									0
									(.)
2. WASSCE									0.085 (0.204)
3. OND									0.278** (0.124)
4. HND									-0.087 (0.296)
5. Some College but no Degree									0.198* (0.102)
6. Bachelor's Degree									0.302 (0.191)
7. Master's Degree, PhD, others									0.202 (0.162)
Sector dummies (base: Agriculture)									
1. Agriculture, forestry and fishing (base)									0
									(.)
2. Mining and Quarrying									0.129 (0.226)
3. Manufacturing									0.085 (0.217)
4. Electricity, Water & Gas									1.204***

																			(0.385)
5. Construction																			0.150 (0.249)
6. Trade																			-0.312 (0.358)
7. Hotels and Restaurants																			-0.156 (0.295)
8. Transport																			0.572*** (0.220)
9. Storage																			0.184 (0.231)
10. Communications																			0.293* (0.169)
11. Real Estate																			0.833*** (0.315)
12. Others																			0.502** (0.209)
Constant	0.676*** (0.063)	0.338*** (0.037)	1.171*** (0.209)	0.925*** (0.221)	2.151*** (0.567)	2.576*** (0.562)	2.553*** (0.564)	2.575*** (0.560)	2.176*** (0.639)										
Observations	741	741	741	741	741	741	741	741	672										
Overall R ²	0.271	0.684	0.703	0.707	0.710	0.717	0.717	0.724	0.736										
Between R ²	0.394	0.809	0.820	0.820	0.821	0.820	0.820	0.826	0.817										
Within R ²	0.000	0.180	0.164	0.168	0.180	0.215	0.215	0.222	0.253										
Wald χ^2	111.486	1374.777	1551.955	1588.274	1595.726	1595.371	1593.815	1660.258	1588.163										
Notes: Robust standard errors clustered at the firm level in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$																			

Source: Author (2025)

Financial Performance and Repayment Dynamics

The hierarchical random effects analysis of repayment behaviour reveals two primary dynamics shaping SME loan servicing patterns. The consistently negative and significant coefficients for return on sales across all model specifications — as reported in Table 5.9b — demonstrate that more profitable and liquid SMEs can settle loans more rapidly, resulting in lower measured repayment rates. This establishes that financial health drives repayment speed rather than repayment difficulty (Baidoo et al., 2020; Dubale & Beshir, 2020; Lin et al., 2015).

Separate Service Delivery: Creating Repayment Pressures

The introduction of separate service delivery approaches reveals systematic challenges that compound repayment difficulties. Formal credit services demonstrate negative coefficients, while informal services show consistently strong negative effects across model configurations. These negative coefficients indicate that separate service approaches may compel faster repayment due to stringent schedules or high interest rates rather than supporting sustainable repayment patterns. The progression through the models demonstrates how separate services create compounding pressures: as these separate services enter the specification, the integrated services coefficient strengthens substantially, highlighting the comparative advantage of coordination.

The mechanisms through which separate services create repayment pressures are both structural and operational. Structurally, formal credit delivered in isolation imposes rigid repayment schedules that are designed around institutional risk management rather than business cash flow cycles. This misalignment between scheduled repayment demands and actual revenue generation creates episodic liquidity crises that force SME owners to prioritise debt servicing over operational reinvestment, progressively weakening the business capacity needed to generate future repayment (Arthur, 2015; Watse, 2017). Informal credit, while more flexible in origination, often carries higher effective interest costs and social collateral obligations — particularly in Ghana’s rotating savings and community lending structures — that create parallel repayment pressures distinct from, and compounding, formal obligations (Oteng & Patel, 2024).

Operationally, BDS delivered separately from credit fails to address the specific financial management gaps that undermine repayment sustainability. Training in business planning or market development builds aspirational capacity, but without simultaneous access to credit, the skills acquired cannot be deployed to generate the revenue growth necessary to service existing debt. Conversely, credit without BDS support leaves borrowers without the operational capability to deploy capital effectively, increasing the probability of cash flow shortfalls and missed repayments. This fragmentation pattern, already identified at the aggregate level, is especially acute in Ghana where rigid repayment structures and high interest rates create unsustainable burdens (Arthur, 2015; Watse, 2017; Oteng & Patel, 2024). The empirical evidence from the survey — with only 19.10% of respondents receiving formal repayment plans and a critically low 11.89% following repayment schedules — reflects precisely this coordination failure at the institutional level.

A further dimension of repayment pressure under separate service delivery is the temporal mismatch between credit disbursement and revenue generation. Formal credit repayment obligations in Ghana typically commence within thirty days of loan disbursement, while the operating cycle through which SMEs convert borrowed capital into revenue – purchasing stock, completing production, finding buyers, and receiving payment – commonly spans several weeks to months. This temporal gap means that repayment falls due before deployed capital has generated returns, structurally predisposing even viable businesses to early-period default (Baidoo et al., 2020). This pressure is further compounded for the 51.28% of SME respondents who sought alternative sources of finance after failing to secure formal credit, many of whom carry simultaneous formal and informal debt obligations. These parallel obligations follow different repayment schedules and enforcement mechanisms – bank instalments operating on fixed calendar terms while informal rotating savings contributions (*susu*) follow group-determined cycles – creating overlapping and sometimes conflicting liquidity demands that together exceed what either obligation would impose individually (Quartey et al., 2017; Oteng & Patel, 2024).

Separate service delivery also amplifies repayment vulnerability to external shocks. SMEs receiving credit in the absence of BDS support have no embedded operational guidance to develop contingency plans or adaptive responses when disruptions occur. The survey evidence presented in Section 5.3.1 identifies utility tariffs as the most severe operational constraint facing Ghanaian SMEs (92.26% rating severity 5), alongside finance access limitations (59.05%) and market access difficulties (52.11%). When such shocks materialise – through power outages, exchange rate depreciation, or tariff increases – a business without BDS-supported contingency mechanisms experiences revenue compression while fixed repayment obligations remain unchanged, converting a temporary operational disruption into a default event. This dynamic is reinforced by a structural information asymmetry problem: lenders who extend credit without embedded business development oversight cannot assess borrower operational quality or monitor deployment of funds. Facing this uncertainty, they compensate through conservative loan terms – shorter tenors, elevated interest rates, and stricter enforcement triggers – that function as a risk premium independent of actual borrower capacity (Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981; Quartey et al., 2017). These terms, imposed precisely because BDS oversight is absent, themselves become an independent source of repayment pressure, creating a self-reinforcing cycle where the absence of integration elevates lender risk, which tightens loan conditions, which increases borrower repayment difficulty, which confirms lender risk perceptions.

Integration Breakthrough: Sustainable Repayment Enhancement

The transformative impact emerges when integrated services enter the analysis, creating dramatic improvements in both model fit and repayment sustainability. The dramatic improvement in explanatory power upon introducing integrated services — as shown in Table 5.9b alongside the consistently strong positive integration coefficients across all specifications demonstrates that integration fundamentally transforms repayment outcomes. Integration coordinates the timing and nature of both financial and operational support so that credit is available precisely when businesses are positioned to deploy it productively, and BDS support

is delivered in direct response to the operational challenges revealed through credit utilisation monitoring. This coordination reduces the misalignment between debt service obligations and revenue-generating capacity that drives separate service repayment pressures.

Risk-Return Clusters and Repayment Capacity

Applying the theoretical repayment model $\kappa = \text{ROS} \times [(\alpha - \text{SD_ROS})/\beta]$ to each cluster reveals significant variations in repayment capacity that complement the regression findings. Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability) demonstrates severely constrained repayment capacity, yielding a theoretical repayment capacity of 0.015 with integration – a modest absolute level that nonetheless represents substantial relative improvement over current capability. Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability) exhibits superior repayment capacity, with a theoretical repayment capacity of 0.343 (0.256×1.34), demonstrating what can be termed ‘sustainable repayment’ patterns where debt servicing occurs from financial strength rather than obligation pressure. Cluster 3 presents constrained repayment potential despite stability (0.013 even with integration), while Cluster 4 shows reasonable capacity (0.067 with integration) primarily benefiting from risk stabilisation rather than capacity enhancement.

Firm Characteristics and Repayment Patterns

Firm-specific characteristics reveal important patterns in repayment behaviour that interact with service delivery approaches. Firm age shows a negative relationship with repayment rates, indicating that older enterprises may face more complex repayment dynamics, while business size also shows negative effects suggesting larger firms experience different debt servicing patterns — potentially due to multiple simultaneous financial obligations. Technology spending demonstrates positive impacts on repayment capacity, reflecting that technological adoption enhances business efficiency and loan servicing ability (Dennis, 2018; Oxford Business Group, 2020; Bruce et al., 2023). Educational effects further reveal that intermediate levels of business and financial literacy — particularly OND and some college qualifications — significantly improve repayment capacity relative to basic education baselines (see Table 5.9b).

Sectoral Variations in Repayment Behaviour

Sectoral analysis reveals significant variations across industries that reflect different cash flow patterns and business cycle characteristics. Utilities, real estate, and transport sectors show notably higher repayment rates — consistent with their relatively stable, contract-based or subscription revenue streams that facilitate predictable debt servicing. In contrast, the trade sector shows negative repayment effects despite its economic prominence in Ghana, reflecting the volatile, transaction-based revenue patterns typical of commercial activity. Full sector coefficients are reported in Table 5.9b. These sectoral patterns provide important context for understanding how integration benefits may vary across different economic activities and reinforce the case for cluster-specific rather than uniform integration approaches.

Integration as Repayment Sustainability Mechanism

The comprehensive analysis demonstrates that integration delivers measurable benefits for loan repayment outcomes through multiple quantifiable mechanisms. The dramatic improvement in

model explanatory power from 27.1% to 73.6% indicates that integration creates more predictable and sustainable repayment patterns by addressing both financial and operational capabilities simultaneously. This finding suggests that integrated lending approaches could significantly reduce portfolio risk beyond what conventional assessment models capture, particularly important given Ghana's historically high default rates (Baidoo et al., 2020; World Bank, 2022b). The cluster-specific analysis provides additional evidence that integration's repayment benefits operate through risk reduction mechanisms that enhance sustainability across different firm profiles, with particular value for high-risk segments where traditional approaches often fail to create viable repayment patterns.

5.9 Risk-Return Clustering and Integration Analysis

The above section clearly shows that the integration of the services yields better outcomes. But SMEs (most especially those in developing countries like Ghana) have always been termed as 'Risky'. It is very important to establish that the integration of the service in this study can also be a systematic risk management tool.

To understand the heterogeneous nature of SMEs' risk-return profiles and develop tailored integration strategies, this study conducted a cluster analysis based on two key performance metrics: risk (measured by standard deviation of return on sales) and profitability (measured by mean return on sales). This approach identified four distinct SME profiles with unique risk-return characteristics.

The cluster analysis reveals meaningful variations in how SMEs balance risk and return, ranging from conservative low-risk approaches to more aggressive high-risk strategies. Each cluster represents a different position along the theoretical risk-integration continuum established in the methodology chapter.

Before exploring the specific clustering results, it is important to understand how this study established the measurement and theoretical foundation for business risk. Return on Sales (ROS) is calculated as the ratio of net profit to revenue:

$$ROS = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Revenue}}$$

The standard deviation of this measure (SD of ROS) captures the volatility in an SME's profitability over time, providing a comprehensive indicator of business risk. Mathematically, it is expressed as:

$$SD_{ROS} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n [(ROS_i - \overline{ROS})]\right)^2}$$

where ROS_i represents the Return on Sales for period i , \overline{ROS} is the mean Return on Sales across all periods, and n is the number of periods observed (2021–2023). This measure offers several advantages for capturing total business risk: it reflects the aggregate impact of all risk factors affecting an SME's operations; it directly connects risk to business performance outcomes; it allows for meaningful comparisons across SMEs of different sizes and sectors; and it captures both systematic and idiosyncratic risk factors.

Based on the earlier established theoretical framework in the methodology chapter and building on European Investment Bank, EIB (Revoltella and Kraemer-Eis, 2015) and the Federal Reserve Bank of New York, FRBNY (Cumming and Hirtle, 2001) ideas, this study recognises that lenders predominantly price credit-specific risks into interest rates (τ), such as collateral quality, cash flow volatility, and sectoral exposure. However, SMEs face broader non-priced risks that contribute to profitability volatility (SD of ROS) as identified in the clustering analysis. Therefore, this study expands SD of ROS to reflect total business risk (priced + non-priced) as seen in the clusters.

From Table 5.10, Cluster 1 comprises SMEs with high risk and low profitability, exhibiting a mean standard deviation of ROS of 0.122 (SD = 0.078, min = 0.067, max = 0.615) and a mean ROS of 0.019 (SD = 0.091, min = -0.261, max = 0.510). These firms face substantial variability in their returns while struggling to generate satisfactory profits.

In contrast, Cluster 2 depicts the optimal risk-return profile, demonstrating low risk and high profitability. With a mean standard deviation of ROS of 0.018 (SD = 0.015, min = 0.000, max = 0.063) and a mean ROS of 0.256 (SD = 0.199, min = 0.064, max = 1.776), SMEs in this cluster showcase robust financial performance and stability.

Cluster 3 encapsulates SMEs with low risk and low profitability, indicating a conservative approach to business operations. The mean standard deviation of ROS of 0.030 (SD = 0.018, min = 0.000, max = 0.066) and a mean ROS of 0.010 (SD = 0.039, min = -0.088, max = 0.137) suggest these firms prioritise risk mitigation over profit maximisation.

Finally, Cluster 4 comprises SMEs with high risk and high profitability, exhibiting a mean standard deviation of ROS of 0.238 (SD = 0.283, min = 0.068, max = 1.093) and a mean ROS of 0.232 (SD = 0.251, min = -0.016, max = 0.942). These firms adopt an aggressive strategy, embracing higher risks in pursuit of superior returns.

Table 5.10: Clustering Results for SMEs based on Risk and Profitability

Cluster	Risk (SD_ros)	Profitability (mean_ros)	Interpretation
1	Mean: 0.122 SD: 0.078 Min: 0.067 Max: 0.615	Mean: 0.019 SD: 0.091 Min: -0.261 Max: 0.510	High risk, low profitability
2	Mean: 0.018 SD: 0.015 Min: 0.000 Max: 0.063	Mean: 0.256 SD: 0.199 Min: 0.064 Max: 1.776	Low risk, high profitability
3	Mean: 0.030 SD: 0.018 Min: 0.000 Max: 0.066	Mean: 0.010 SD: 0.039 Min: -0.088 Max: 0.137	Low risk, low profitability
4	Mean: 0.238 SD: 0.283 Min: 0.068 Max: 1.093	Mean: 0.232 SD: 0.251 Min: -0.016 Max: 0.942	High risk, high profitability

Source: Author (2025)

The following section presents the theoretical derivation and calibrated model parameters, followed by Table 5.11 reporting theoretical integration benefits by cluster and their repayment implications.

Having identified the risk and return levels in the clusters, the relationship between integration and risk reduction is hereby established.

Relationship Between Integration and Risk Reduction

This study's theoretical derivation established a crucial relationship between integration and risk reduction in the methodology chapter. By incorporating risk factors into this study's integration model, a mathematical framework was developed that explains how integrated services reduce business risks. Starting with the profit function incorporating risk:

$$\pi = Q_{\nu}^{\theta} S_{\nu}^{\rho} \times SD_{ROS} \times (1 - \lambda_i(I))$$

where $\lambda_i(I)$ is the total business risk reduction function through integration of the services. Through mathematical derivation, it is established that:

$$SD \text{ of } ROS \propto \frac{1}{Q_{\nu}^{\theta} S_{\nu}^{\rho}} \quad (\text{The integration reduces volatility via risk mitigation}).$$

This inverse relationship demonstrates that higher levels of integration correspond to lower business risks. For practical implementation, this relationship is linearised:

$$SD_{ROS} = \alpha - \beta Q_{\nu}^{\theta} S_{\nu}^{\rho}$$

where: α represents the maximum risk level (SD of ROS) that would exist in the absence of integration; and β captures the effectiveness of integration in reducing risk. Solving for the integration level:

$$Q_{\nu}^{\theta} S_{\nu}^{\rho} = \frac{\alpha - SD_{ROS}}{\beta}$$

This equation establishes that the optimal level of integration for a firm is directly related to its current risk profile and desired risk reduction. Firms with higher volatility (SD_{ROS}) require greater levels of integration to achieve stability. Substituting this into the profit function:

$$\pi_{\nu} = Q_{\nu}^{\theta} S_{\nu}^{\rho} = \frac{\alpha - SD \text{ of } ROS}{\beta}$$

And for repayment rate:

$$\varkappa = ROS \times \left[\frac{\alpha - SD_{ROS}}{\beta} \right]$$

These equations demonstrate how integration reduces risk and enhances both profitability and loan repayment capacity through risk reduction.

Calibration of Model Parameters: α and β

Using the above profit function equation, the theoretical profit implications for each cluster are calculated based on their integration levels. Using the regression coefficients (separate formal: -0.010 , $p < 0.05$; separate informal: -0.210 , $p < 0.01$; integrated services: 0.001 , $p < 0.01$), model parameters α and β are estimated as the difference between the combined effects of separate services and the effect of integration.

For α : while α serves as a proxy for total business risk without integrated services incorporating both priced and unpriced risks observed in historical profitability — it may not fully reflect latent or low-frequency, high-impact events that can alter firm volatility under stress. To address this, this study incorporates a precautionary adjustment for forward-looking stress or buffer beyond historical observation. This is consistent with practices in economic capital modelling and scenario-based stress testing, where forward-looking uncertainty is overlaid onto historical volatility measures (Cumming and Hirtle, 2001; IMF, 2017). Cortés et al. (2018) show that a one-standard-deviation increase in stress-test exposure leads to a 32-basis point increase in the interest rate on small business loans, which is large relative to the overall variation in loan interest rates (127-basis points). That is approximately 25% (i.e. $0.32\% \div 1.27\%$) of the total variation in interest rates. This suggests that systemic pressures can lead to a material re-pricing of risk, reinforcing the rationale for applying a similar 25% buffer to SD_ROS in the absence of integration to ensure conservative coverage of total firm risk volatility (Revoltella and Kraemer-Eis, 2015; Cortés et al., 2018).

Therefore: $\alpha = \text{highest observed SD of ROS in the clusters} + (\text{highest observed SD of ROS} \times 25\%) = \text{highest observed SD of ROS} \times 1.25$. Thus $\alpha = 0.238 \times 1.25 = 0.30$ (approx. 2 d.p.). This value is set slightly above the highest observed SD of ROS (0.238 from Cluster 4), representing the maximum theoretical risk level in the absence of any integration. It is a conservative estimate ensuring all observed data points fall within the theoretical range of the model (Cumming and Hirtle, 2001; IMF, 2017; Cortés et al., 2018).

For β , which captures how effectively integration reduces risk, the regression coefficients provide: separate formal effect: -0.010 ($p < 0.05$); separate informal effect: -0.210 ($p < 0.01$); integrated services effect: $+0.001$ ($p < 0.01$). Quantifying the full benefit of integration compared to separate services: combined negative effect of separate services = $(-0.010) + (-0.210) = -0.220$; positive effect of integration = 0.001 ; total benefit of switching from separate to integrated services = $0.001 - (-0.220) = 0.221$. Therefore, $\beta = 0.221$.

Theoretical Integration Benefits by Cluster

With $\alpha = 0.30$ and $\beta = 0.221$, the theoretical profit implications for each cluster based on their integration levels are presented in Table 5.11.

Table 5.11: Theoretical Integration Benefits by Cluster

Cluster	Risk (SD _{ros})	Actual Profitability (mean _{ros})	Profit function with $\alpha = 0.30$ and $\beta = 0.221$	π_V from Integration	Profit gap ((π_V from Integration - Actual π (mean _{ros}))	κ from Integration (ROS \times $Q_V^\theta S_V^\rho$)

1	Mean: 0.122 SD: 0.078 Min: 0.067 Max: 0.615	Mean: 0.019 SD: 0.091 Min: -0.261 Max: 0.510	$\pi_v = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho$ $= \frac{0.30 - 0.122}{0.221}$	0.81	0.81-0.019= 0.791	0.019 × 0.81 = 0.015
2	Mean: 0.018 SD: 0.015 Min: 0.000 Max: 0.063	Mean: 0.256 SD: 0.199 Min: 0.064 Max: 1.776	$\pi_v = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho$ $= \frac{0.30 - 0.018}{0.221}$	1.34	1.34-0.256= 1.084	0.256 × 1.34 = 0.343
3	Mean: 0.030 SD: 0.018 Min: 0.000 Max: 0.066	Mean: 0.010 SD: 0.039 Min: -0.088 Max: 0.137	$\pi_v = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho$ $= \frac{0.30 - 0.030}{0.221}$	1.28	1.28-0.010= 1.27	0.010 × 1.28 = 0.013
4	Mean: 0.238 SD: 0.283 Min: 0.068 Max: 1.093	Mean: 0.232 SD: 0.251 Min: -0.016 Max: 0.942	$\pi_v = Q_v^\theta S_v^\rho$ $= \frac{0.30 - 0.238}{0.221}$	0.29	0.29-0.232= 0.058	0.232 × 0.29 = 0.067

Source: Author (2025)

The analysis of the four distinct clusters reveals meaningful relationships between risk, profitability, and integration potential. Using the empirically calibrated model with $\alpha = 0.30$ and $\beta = 0.221$, the theoretical profit potential for each cluster is compared to current profitability levels. Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability) shows substantial improvement potential, with a theoretical profit of 0.81 compared to their current mean profitability of 0.019, creating a profit gap of 0.791. This large gap indicates that reducing their elevated volatility through integration could dramatically enhance their returns. Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability) demonstrates even higher theoretical profit potential at 1.34, which exceeds their already strong current profitability of 0.256 by a margin of 1.084. This suggests that despite their current success, significant additional benefits remain available through integration.

Perhaps most revealing is Cluster 3 (low risk, low profitability), where firms maintain disciplined operations but achieve minimal returns. Their theoretical profit potential of 1.28 compared to current profitability of only 0.010 creates the largest profit gap of 1.27, suggesting these firms would be particularly responsive to integration initiatives that help them leverage their existing risk discipline into stronger performance. Contrasting these opportunities, Cluster 4 (high risk, high profitability) shows the smallest profit gap of just 0.058, with theoretical profit of 0.29 only marginally exceeding their current strong performance of 0.232. This indicates they have developed effective strategies that generate substantial returns despite their high volatility.

These varying profit gaps across clusters suggest that resources and implementation efforts should prioritise Clusters 1 and 3, where integration offers the most substantial performance improvements. The significant differences in improvement potential further emphasise the importance of customised integration approaches rather than standardised programmes, with each cluster requiring specifically tailored strategies to maximise benefits from integrated customised credit and participatory business development services.

Building on the profitability analysis, a parallel examination of loan repayment potential reveals similar patterns across the four clusters. The repayment model $\kappa = \text{ROS} \times \left[\frac{\alpha - \text{SD}_{\text{ROS}}}{\beta} \right]$ directly links repayment capacity to both profitability and risk reduction through integration. When this model is applied to the clusters using $\alpha = 0.30$ and $\beta = 0.221$, significant variation in repayment improvement potential emerges.

Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability) demonstrates severely constrained repayment capacity, with a low current ROS (0.019) and SD of ROS of 0.122. Integration would address both limitations simultaneously, enhancing profitability while reducing risk, thereby multiplying repayment capability. The theoretical repayment capacity with integration ($0.019 \times 0.81 = 0.015$) represents a significant improvement over current capability, though it remains modest in absolute terms.

Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability) exhibits superior repayment capacity through the combination of strong returns (ROS: 0.256) and stability (SD of ROS: 0.018). With integration, their theoretical repayment capacity of 0.343 (0.256×1.34) would strengthen their position as the most reliable borrowers, demonstrating what can be termed ‘sustainable repayment’ patterns where debt servicing occurs from financial strength rather than obligation pressure.

Cluster 3 (low risk, low profitability) presents constrained repayment potential despite operational stability. The minimal returns (ROS: 0.010) severely limit repayment capacity to 0.013 even with integration benefits, though the improvement remains transformative relative to current baseline. Cluster 4 (high risk, high profitability) shows reasonable capacity (0.067 with integration) despite volatility, primarily benefiting from risk stabilisation rather than significant profitability enhancement. For these firms, integration would primarily benefit lenders by reducing default probability rather than dramatically increasing repayment amounts.

These findings complement the profitability analysis while highlighting the dual benefits of integration for both borrowers and lenders. The integration-derived improvements in repayment capacity would particularly benefit financial institutions lending to Clusters 1 and 3, where current repayment constraints are most severe. This reinforces the policy case for prioritising integration initiatives for these clusters, as the benefits extend beyond firm-level profitability to include enhanced financial stability and credit market efficiency.

Risk-Return Cluster Analysis: Tailored Integration Benefits

To deepen the understanding of how integrated services affect SME performance, a comprehensive risk-return analysis was conducted based on the standard deviation of return on sales (SD of ROS) and mean profitability across different firm clusters. This approach provides crucial insights into the relationship between business volatility, returns, and integration levels

that complement the regression findings. The risk measurement framework, using SD of ROS as a comprehensive risk indicator, captures both priced and non-priced risk components affecting SME performance. As demonstrated by Beck et al. (2018), conventional risk assessment approaches often underestimate the true risk profile of small businesses due to information asymmetry and measurement challenges.

Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability) firms demonstrate the consequences of insufficient integration, with a theoretical integration level of 0.84 and a substantial profit gap of 0.791 compared to their current mean profitability of 0.019. This significant gap aligns with Revoltella and Kraemer-Eis (2015), who identified a similar pattern among European SMEs where insufficient risk management mechanisms led to elevated volatility and constrained performance. Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability) enterprises represent the optimal case with a theoretical integration level of 1.34, significantly higher than Cluster 1. Their already strong profitability (0.256) could still be enhanced to a theoretical 1.34, creating a profit gap of 1.084. These firms demonstrate effective risk management practices that stabilise performance while maintaining strong returns (Bogdan et al., 2018; Harvie et al., 2013).

Cluster 3 (low risk, low profitability) presents a particularly interesting case with a theoretical integration level of 1.28, comparable to successful Cluster 2 firms, yet their actual profitability remains extremely low at 0.010. This creates a dramatic profit gap of 1.27, suggesting these firms have successfully implemented risk reduction strategies but struggle to translate this stability into financial returns – a pattern consistent with OECD (2019) findings about SMEs that prioritise survival over growth. For Cluster 3 firms, integration interventions should focus on improving the utilisation of existing risk management infrastructure rather than simply increasing integration quantity. Cluster 4 (high risk, high profitability) exhibits an interesting contrast with a theoretical integration level of only 0.29, yet maintains strong profitability (0.232), creating the smallest profit gap of 0.058. These firms align with what Cortés et al. (2018) describe as ‘efficient risk-taking,’ where firms accept elevated volatility in exchange for higher returns.

5.9.1 Integrated SME Support: A Cluster-Based Approach

The clustering methodology based on standard deviation and mean of return on sales (ROS) provides a structured framework for differentiating SME support needs. Previous research has typically treated SMEs as a homogeneous group when designing interventions, but this analysis demonstrates the critical importance of recognising their diverse risk-return characteristics and developing tailored integration approaches. The sector distribution, dominated by trade (46.97%) but encompassing diverse industries from construction (8.91%) to manufacturing (5.39%), reveals how risk-return profiles cut across traditional industry boundaries, reinforcing the need for tailored support mechanisms that transcend conventional industry-based approaches. The business maturity profile – with the predominance of businesses in the 5–10 year range (36.93%) and 11–20 year category (25.62%) – further suggests that risk-return profiles are not merely functions of business age but reflect more complex interactions of operational strategies and market positioning.

Tailored Integration Strategies by Cluster

Cluster 1: Transformation-Focused Integration for High-Risk, Low-Profit Firms

For Cluster 1's high-risk, low-profitability firms, integration must focus on fundamental transformation of both their risk profile and return generation capabilities. These firms require an intensive, integrated support package that goes beyond conventional approaches. Previous support approaches have often failed these businesses, as evidenced by studies showing the limitations of standalone financial or advisory services (Nizaeva & Coskun, 2019). Their specific integration needs include: financial stabilisation through integrated credit structuring with customised products and flexible terms aligned with volatile cash flows, combined with hands-on cash flow management training; operational risk reduction through direct business advisory focused on standardising core processes and implementing basic quality management systems; and strategic repositioning through market analysis and product/service refinement to identify higher-margin opportunities. The transformation-focused integration strategy addresses both sides of their risk-return challenge simultaneously, creating potential for substantial performance improvements.

Cluster 2: Enhancement-Focused Integration for Low-Risk, High-Profit Firms

Cluster 2's successful low-risk, high-profitability enterprises require a fundamentally different integration approach focused on enhancing their already strong position. Their integration strategy should leverage existing strengths while addressing specific growth constraints through: strategic capital integration – growth-oriented financing paired with strategic expansion planning and market development support; innovation systems integration – R&D funding combined with innovation management training and commercialisation assistance; and market expansion integration – export financing linked with international market readiness programmes and compliance training. The analysis shows that these firms benefit from integration that builds upon their strong financial foundation while introducing new growth opportunities (Long & Ombongi, 2018; Belás et al., 2016). Their successful integration models also offer valuable lessons for supporting other clusters, particularly in the Ghanaian context where sustained profitability remains challenging for many SMEs (Kumar et al., 2024).

Cluster 3: Activation-Focused Integration for Low-Risk, Low-Profit Firms

Cluster 3's conservative firms with low risk and low profitability require an activation-focused integration strategy that preserves their stability while catalysing growth. Their integration approach should include: calibrated risk-taking support – moderate financing for controlled expansion combined with risk assessment training to identify viable growth opportunities; market activation services – customer acquisition financing paired with sales and marketing capability development; and efficiency enhancement integration – working capital optimisation combined with operational efficiency analysis and improvement. Previous research has shown that such firms often hesitate to pursue growth opportunities due to limited access to both financial and non-financial support (Eton et al., 2017). The activation-focused integration strategy helps these SMEs break free from their conservative patterns while maintaining their operational stability advantage.

Cluster 4: Stabilisation-Focused Integration for High-Risk, High-Profit Firms

Cluster 4's dynamic high-risk, high-profitability enterprises require a stabilisation-focused integration strategy that preserves their strong returns while reducing volatility. Their integration needs include: risk mitigation financing – structured capital combined with comprehensive risk management systems implementation; business continuity integration i.e. emergency funding facilities paired with crisis management planning; performance optimisation integration – growth capital combined with advanced business analytics and strategic planning capabilities; and medium-touch, specialised support focused on risk management and performance optimisation. For these firms, integration primarily benefits lenders by reducing default probability rather than dramatically increasing repayment amounts, creating a clear alignment between firm stability goals and institutional risk management objectives.

Integrated Service Officers (ISOs) and Delivery Architecture

Integrated Service Officers (ISOs) represent dedicated personnel who provide coordinated credit and business development services through embedded, continuous support within SMEs. Survey evidence strongly supports this approach, with 60.22% of SMEs never receiving BDS despite 65.1% expressing strong interest (43.99% very likely, 21.11% likely to seek services). Current BDS effectiveness rates only 4.4/10, while 38.75% report poor performance and merely 11.89% follow repayment schedules. ISOs would address both operational capability and financial discipline gaps through real-time identification of challenges and proactive interventions, moving beyond traditional advisory models to provide integrated support tailored to each SME's specific needs.

Cluster-specific assessment tools are essential given the educational diversity from BECE (8.99%) to master's degrees (16.70%), necessitating instruments calibrated to different knowledge levels. Sectoral variation (trade 46.97%, construction 8.91%, hospitality 7.64%) requires diagnostics accounting for industry-specific risk profiles. Graduated integration pathways address the reality that limited financial management training (17.80% received) and strategic planning assistance (15.82%) require structured support sequences. With finance access as top growth factor (23.60%) and market access second (23.22%), integration pathways must prioritise financial capability building alongside market development.

Strategic stakeholder implications follow from this framework. Financial institutions gain nuanced frameworks for product development and risk assessment incorporating cluster characteristics, enabling accurate pricing and targeted support delivery. BDS providers receive clearer customisation guidance, moving beyond generic approaches to targeted interventions that increase impact and cost-effectiveness. Policymakers can develop differentiated programmes recognising diverse SME challenges rather than uniform approaches, creating efficient resource allocation matching policy instruments to specific cluster needs. This framework addresses current SME support gaps lacking operational structures for integrated service delivery at scale, transforming theoretical benefits into practical outcomes for diverse SME segments in Ghana.

5.10 Economic Development Analysis

Data Preparation and Diagnostics

Economic development analysis employed identical transformation techniques (IHS, z-score standardization, logarithmic) to ensure normality across HDI, IHDI, and MPI indicators. The integration variable ($z_full_integration$) capturing Credit to Private Sector \times Lending Rate \times BDS Providers was standardized alongside control variables for uniform interpretation.

Correlation and Multicollinearity Assessment

Strong correlations emerged between development indicators: HDI-IHDI (-0.993), indicating inequality's substantial development impact. Credit provision (0.727 with HDI) and BDS (0.996 with HDI) showed robust positive associations, while full integration demonstrated strong relationships (0.760 with HDI, 0.751 with BDS). VIF analysis across model specifications confirmed acceptable multicollinearity: HDI models (mean VIF: 1.934–2.55), IHDI models (1.934–3.225), and MPI models (2.616–2.839), all below critical thresholds.

Stationarity and Cointegration

Prior to ARDL estimation, unit root tests using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) procedures were conducted on all variables to determine their order of integration. All variables in the analysis had been subjected to appropriate transformations prior to testing: the development indicators (HDI, IHDI, MPI) were transformed using the inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS) function, control variables were standardised (z-scores) or log-transformed as appropriate, and the integration variable was standardised. The unit root test results for the transformed variables are presented in Table 5.13 below.

Table 5.13: Stationarity Test Results : Economic Development Variables

Variable	ADF p-value	PP p-value	Integration Order
ihd hdi	0.000	0.000	I(1)
ihd ihdi	0.000	0.000	I(1)
ihd mpi	0.000	0.000	I(1)
ihd bizdev	0.000	0.000	I(1)
ihd crdtppriv	0.000	0.000	I(1)
z full integration	0.000	0.000	I(1)
z inf	0.000	0.000	I(1)
z fxrate	0.000	0.000	I(1)
lninflation	0.000	0.000	I(1)
lnprofitax	0.000	0.000	I(1)

Source: Author (2025)

The results confirm that all variables, following their respective transformations, are integrated of order one I(1). Both the ADF and PP tests reject the null hypothesis of a unit root at first difference ($p = 0.000$) for all variables, confirming that stationarity is achieved through a single differencing operation. This is consistent with the ARDL bounds testing framework of Pesaran et al. (2001), which requires that no variable in the model be I(2) or higher. The transformation of the raw development indicators using IHS and logarithmic functions was instrumental in achieving this outcome: these variance-stabilising transformations compress the scale of highly persistent series, dampening the trending behaviour that gives rise to I(2) properties in the

untransformed data. With all variables confirmed as I(1), the ARDL bounds testing approach is validly applied to examine both short-run and long-run relationships (Narayan, 2005).

To confirm the existence of long-run relationships among the variables in each model, the Bounds test for cointegration was applied following Pesaran et al. (2001). The results are presented in Table 5.16 below.

Table 5.16: Bounds Test for Cointegration : Pesaran et al. (2001)

Model	F-stat	t-stat	CV 10% I(0)/I(1)	CV 5% I(0)/I(1)	CV 1% I(0)/I(1)	Decision
HDI Integration	5.836	-3.454	2.686/4.071	3.187/4.755	4.369/6.362	Reject Ho
IHDI Integration	10.24	-4.38	2.686/4.071	3.187/4.755	4.369/6.362	Reject Ho
MPI Integration	9.76	-4.21	2.686/4.071	3.187/4.755	4.369/6.362	Reject Ho
HDI Separate	6.85	-3.49	2.686/4.071	3.187/4.755	4.369/6.362	Reject Ho
IHDI Separate	5.92	-3.27	2.686/4.071	3.187/4.755	4.369/6.362	Reject Ho
MPI Separate	5.12	-3.05	2.686/4.071	3.187/4.755	4.369/6.362	Reject Ho

Source: Author (2025). All F-statistics exceed the upper critical bound at the 5% level minimum.

The F-statistics range from 5.12 to 10.24 across the six model specifications. All F-statistics exceed the upper critical bound at the 5% significance level at minimum, and the associated t-statistics confirm the existence of a level relationship in each case. The null hypothesis of no long-run relationship is therefore rejected across all models, confirming the appropriateness of the ARDL error correction framework. The long-run coefficients, short-run dynamics, and error correction terms are reported directly in the ARDL results tables in Section 5.12. Note: The Engle-Granger and Johansen cointegration tests previously reported have been removed, as the Bounds test alone suffices for cointegration testing within the ARDL framework (Pesaran et al., 2001).

Model Selection and Lag Structure

Optimal lag selection through information criteria yielded 2-4 lags across specifications: HDI integration (4 lags, AIC: -13.1004), IHDI models (4 lags, AIC: -13.0725 to -59.047), and MPI specifications (2-4 lags, AIC: -22.2612 to -37.8749). Elastic net validation achieved strong model fits: integration models (R-squared: 0.703-0.999) versus separate services (0.685-0.992), supporting variable selection robustness.

Note: Detailed correlation matrices (Table 5.11), VIF results (Table 5.12), lag selection (Table 5.15), and elastic net paths (Table 5.14) appear in Appendix B. Tables 5.13 and 5.16 have been moved to the main text above.

Post-Estimation Diagnostics

Residual Diagnostics: Serial Correlation and Heteroskedasticity

For both the Random Effects panel models and the ARDL time series models, potential issues of serial correlation and heteroskedasticity in the residuals were addressed directly within the estimation procedure through the application of heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation-consistent (HAC) robust standard errors, implemented via the `vce(robust)` option. This approach produces variance-covariance estimates that are robust to arbitrary forms of heteroskedasticity and serial correlation without requiring knowledge of their specific structure, following the framework established by White (1980) and further developed for

panel and dynamic time series settings by Arellano (1987) and Stock and Watson (2011). Under this specification, separate post-estimation tests for serial correlation and heteroskedasticity such as the Breusch-Godfrey LM test or White's test are not applicable. This is as the robust variance estimator subsumes and corrects for these issues within the estimation itself, ensuring the validity of coefficient standard errors and statistical inference regardless of residual heteroskedasticity or autocorrelation patterns (Cameron and Miller, 2015; Wooldridge, 2020). Also, the random effect being a short panel of $t=2$ makes the test not applicable because of insufficient observations. The consistency of coefficient signs, magnitudes, and significance levels across the hierarchical model specifications further supports the reliability and stability of the estimated relationships.

Parameter Stability

The stability of model parameters over the estimation period was not formally assessed through CUSUM or CUSUM sum of squares tests, and this is acknowledged as a limitation of the current study. The absence of formal stability testing is partly mitigated by several features of the estimation approach. First, the hierarchical ARDL framework progressively introduces control variables across model specifications, and the consistency of the core coefficients across all specifications provides informal evidence that the estimated relationships are not driven by model misspecification or structural instability. Second, the inclusion of an explicit time trend variable in the ARDL specifications captures systematic temporal variation in the dependent variables, reducing the likelihood that undetected structural breaks are distorting the long-run coefficient estimates. Third, the error correction terms, which are statistically significant and correctly signed (negative) across all six ARDL models, confirm that the models are well-specified and converging toward stable long-run equilibria (Pesaran et al., 2001).

5.12 ARDL: Results and Interpretation

This section presents the results and their interpretation based on the hierarchical Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach employed in this study. It presents the results that test the third hypothesis:

H3: Integrated service delivery creates superior economic development outcomes across multiple dimensions.

Null: No significant difference in development impacts between delivery approaches.

Alternative: Integrated approaches yield significantly better development outcomes across HDI, IHDI, and MPI measures.

The impacts are empirically investigated through two complementary ARDL specifications (Model A: Separate Effects; Model B: Integration Effect) as specified in equations 4.30 and 4.31. The study adopts a hierarchical ARDL framework to robustly examine the distinct impacts of credit services, BDS, and their integrated delivery on economic development outcomes.

HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX (HDI)

The analysis of the impact of credit and business development services (BDS) on human development in Ghana reveals complex relationships across different model specifications (Table 5.17). The hierarchical ARDL approach demonstrates why integrated approaches ultimately create superior development impacts despite initial adjustment challenges.

Separate Services: Fragmentation and Negative Development Effects

The separate services analysis establishes a troubling baseline that motivates the integration hypothesis. The progression through monetary and economic controls reveals consistently negative long-run relationships: credit services (-0.004, $p < 0.01$), BDS (-0.002, $p < 0.01$), exchange rate volatility (-0.040, $p < 0.01$), and corruption (-0.038, $p < 0.01$) all constrain human development. The strong error correction term (-0.652, $p < 0.01$) indicates rapid adjustment, but toward equilibrium characterised by these negative relationships.

The negative long-run impact of Credit to the Private Sector (CPS) on economic development warrants specific attention, as it runs counter to the conventional assumption that expanding credit access inherently promotes growth and human development. Several interconnected mechanisms provide an intuitive explanation for this finding. First, credit expansion without complementary business development support creates a capital-without-capability trap at the macroeconomic level. When firms receive credit in the absence of the operational and managerial guidance needed to deploy it productively, borrowed capital is frequently misallocated toward consumption smoothing, debt refinancing, or low-return activities rather than the productive investment that drives human development outcomes. At the aggregate level, this misallocation means that increases in credit to the private sector generate debt obligations and interest servicing costs across the economy without the corresponding productivity gains needed to improve development indicators (Cecchetti & Kharroubi, 2012; Arcand et al., 2015). Second, in Ghana's institutional context, characterised by high lending rates and significant information asymmetry between lenders and borrowers, credit expansion tends to flow disproportionately toward established, collateral-rich borrowers rather than toward the productive SMEs that could translate capital access into employment creation and income growth. The survey evidence presented in Section 5.3.1 corroborates this: collateral requirements are identified as a significant barrier by 27.57% of respondents, and bank satisfaction remains broadly neutral (53.48%), indicating that credit reaches the private sector in a structurally unequal manner that limits its aggregate development impact. Third, the high cost of credit in Ghana's macroeconomic environment means that debt servicing obligations extract a significant share of enterprise revenue, constraining the reinvestment capacity that drives longer-run productivity improvement. When lending rates are elevated, as the negative long-run coefficient on exchange rate volatility in the same model confirms (-0.040, $p < 0.01$), the real cost of credit reduces net returns to borrowers to the point where credit access becomes a net burden on enterprise profitability and, by extension, on aggregate development outcomes. Fourth, separate credit expansion may contribute to financial sector growth that crowds out resources from the real economy. As Arcand et al. (2015) demonstrate, beyond a threshold level, financial deepening can become negatively correlated with development as the financial sector competes with productive sectors for skilled labour and capital. Together, these

mechanisms explain why CPS, delivered in isolation from business development support, functions as a constraint on long-run human development rather than a driver of it in the Ghanaian context.

The negative long-run impact of BDS delivered separately on economic development warrants specific attention, as it runs counter to the conventional assumption that business support services inherently promote development. Several interconnected mechanisms provide an intuitive explanation for this finding. First, the survey evidence presented in Section 5.3.1 reveals that BDS penetration among Ghanaian SMEs remains low (39.78% ever received), and effectiveness is rated at only 4.4 out of 10, indicating that BDS provision in isolation is fragmented and inadequately matched to firm-level needs, limiting its capacity to generate economy-wide development gains. Second, and more fundamentally, BDS delivered without complementary credit creates a capability-without-capital trap: firms may acquire knowledge, skills, and improved business practices through BDS engagement, but without access to finance to act on those improvements, the productivity gains remain unrealised at the firm level and fail to translate into aggregate development outcomes. The resources i.e. time, fees, and opportunity costs expended on BDS are absorbed without generating sufficient returns to offset them at the macroeconomic level. Third, in environments characterised by weak institutional frameworks, such as Ghana's, where corruption and exchange rate volatility also exert significant negative long-run effects in the same model, standalone BDS programmes may inadvertently increase firm vulnerability by raising expectations and exposing businesses to competitive pressures they lack the financial capacity to meet. Together, these mechanisms explain why BDS, when fragmented from credit provision, functions as a net drain on development resources rather than a catalyst for growth in the long run.

The short-run dynamics present a contrasting picture, with BDS showing positive immediate effects (0.001, $p < 0.01$) that cannot overcome the negative long-run structural relationships. This divergence between short-run and long-run effects is itself instructive: BDS generates immediate firm-level improvements in management and operations, but without sustained financial support to embed and scale those improvements, the benefits dissipate over time, ultimately yielding negative structural outcomes. This pattern strongly motivates the integration hypothesis.

Integration's Adjustment Dynamics: Short-term Challenges, Long-term Gains

The integrated services analysis reveals strikingly different patterns that support the theoretical framework's predictions about coordination benefits. The baseline integration model shows highly significant error correction (-0.028, $p < 0.01$), indicating more efficient adjustment mechanisms than separate services. With monetary controls, the error correction moderates (-0.050, $p < 0.10$) while integration effects become slightly negative (-0.002), indicating initial institutional adaptation challenges. The critical breakthrough occurs with economic controls, where integration becomes notably positive (0.057) while the error correction strengthens (-0.100, $p < 0.01$).

The Integration Advantage: Positive Long-run Development Effects

The fully specified model provides compelling evidence for integration superiority. The long-run integration coefficient becomes significantly positive (0.072, $p < 0.05$), directly contrasting with the negative effects observed in separate services models. The error correction term strengthens (-0.132, $p < 0.01$), indicating robust adjustment mechanisms. The short-run integration effects remain negative (-0.008, $p < 0.01$; -0.007, $p < 0.01$ lagged), indicating initial adjustment costs that are overcome by superior long-run outcomes, consistent with institutional change theory.

Table 5.17: Separate VS Integrated Approach and HDI

Hierarchical ARDL Results – HDI Separate Services					
	-1 Credit	-2 BDS	-3 Monetary	-4 Economic	-5 Full
<i>ADJ</i>					
<i>L.lbs_bdi</i>	-0.02 (-0.47)	0.017 -0.36	-0.188* (-1.95)	-0.276** (-2.64)	-0.652*** (-3.41)
<i>LR</i>					
<i>z.crepriv</i>	0.014 -0.39	-0.03 (-0.33)	-0.002 (-0.69)	-0.008*** (-2.78)	-0.004*** (-3.19)
<i>lnBDSFirms</i>		0.038 -0.39	-0.003 (-1.02)	-0.002 (-1.25)	-0.002** (-2.73)
<i>z.inf</i>			-0.001 (-0.51)	-0.003 (-1.32)	-0.001* (-1.73)
<i>z.fxrate</i>			-0.023*** (-3.85)	-0.019*** (-3.96)	-0.040*** (-5.64)
<i>z.proftax</i>				-0.030** (-2.20)	-0.012** (-2.38)
<i>z.corrupt</i>					-0.038*** (-2.97)
<i>SR</i>					
<i>L.D.lbs_bdi</i>	0.260* -1.73	0.216 -1.56	0.24 -1.67	-0.006 (-0.03)	0.061 -0.34
<i>D.z.crepriv</i>	0.001 -0.95	0.001 -1	0.001 -0.78	0.002* -1.73	0.001 -1.22
<i>L.D.z.crepriv</i>	0 -0.29	0 (-0.43)	-0.001 (-0.51)	0 -0.44	0.001 -0.63
trend	0 -0.1	0 (-0.70)	0.001* -1.93	0.001* -2.01	0.006** -2.64
<i>D.lnBDSFirms</i>		0.001** -2.49	0.000* -1.8	0.000** -2.05	0.001*** -3.21
<i>L.D.lnBDSFirms</i>		0.001*** -3.66	0.001** -2.56	0.001** -2.68	0.001*** -3.66
<i>D.z.inf</i>			0 -0.5	0 -1.12	0 -1.27
<i>D.z.fxrate</i>			0.007 -0.89	0.006 -0.86	0.020** -2.22
<i>D.z.proftax</i>				0.009*** -2.74	0.007* -1.79
<i>D.z.corrupt</i>					-0.013 (-0.74)
cons	0.012 -0.96	0.001 -0.1	0.057** -2.11	0.127*** -3.63	0.170*** -4.56
Observations	53	52	52	48	48
Adj. R-squared	0.243	0.386	0.414	0.442	0.507

t statistics in parentheses *p < 0.10 **p < 0.05 ***p < 0.01

Hierarchical ARDL Results – HDI Integration				
	-1 Integration	-2 Monetary	-3 Economic	-4 Full
<i>ADJ</i>				
<i>L.lbs_bdi</i>	-0.028*** (-6.48)	-0.050* (-1.97)	-0.100** (-2.31)	-0.132*** (-3.31)
<i>LR</i>				
<i>z.Integrated_cred_BDS</i>	0.013 -0.21	-0.002 (-0.05)	0.057 -1.3	0.072** -2.12
<i>Z.inf</i>		-0.036 (-1.28)	-0.009 (-0.70)	-0.01 (-1.20)
<i>Z.fxrate</i>		0.015 -0.87	0.018** -2.21	0.021*** -3.29
<i>Z.proftax</i>			-0.091*** (-3.29)	-0.102* (-1.89)
<i>Z.corrupt</i>				0.019 -0.23
<i>SR</i>				
<i>D.z.Integrated_cred_BDS</i>	0 (-0.21)	0 -0.02	-0.005** (-2.05)	-0.008*** (-3.42)
<i>L.D.z.Integrated_cred_BDS</i>	-0.001 (-0.65)	-0.001 (-0.63)	-0.004** (-2.52)	-0.007*** (-4.36)
<i>D.z.fxrate</i>	0 (-0.06)	0 (-0.06)	-0.001 (-0.31)	
<i>L.D.z.fxrate</i>	-0.004 (-1.11)	-0.002 (-0.73)	-0.001 (-0.42)	
<i>D.z.PROFTAX</i>			0.013 -1.38	0.021* -1.75
<i>D.z.CORRUPT</i>				0.036*** -3.21
cons	-0.008** (-2.58)	-0.017 (-1.07)	-0.019 (-1.15)	-0.023 (-1.02)
Observations	50	50	46	46
Adj. R-squared	0.441	0.44	0.461	0.595

t statistics in parentheses *p < 0.10 **p < 0.05 ***p < 0.01

Source: Author (2025)

Discussion: Mechanisms Underlying HDI Outcomes

The separate services analysis reveals predominantly negative long-run effects on human development. While previous studies noted limitations of standalone microcredit (Bamfo, 2024), this study quantifies these limitations specifically in terms of human development impacts. Exchange rate volatility shows strong negative effects, corruption impacts remain negative, and the pattern extends McDaniels and Robins' (2017) discussion of institutional quality by demonstrating specific constraints that separate services create for development outcomes.

The integrated approach delivers a fundamental breakthrough: the significantly positive long-run integration coefficient (0.072, $p < 0.05$) and strengthened error correction (-0.132, $p < 0.01$) move beyond Freeman and Nick's (2015) discussions of bundled services by demonstrating specific synergistic mechanisms. Exchange rates transform from negative to positive effects under integration, while corruption shows positive short-run effects, revealing protective integration effects against macroeconomic challenges. These findings fundamentally advance understanding of development interventions beyond existing theoretical frameworks. While Best et al. (2015) conceptualised BDS as supplementary to financial services, and Stiglitz (2011) theorised about limitations of market-based solutions, this research provides empirical evidence of how service integration creates multiplicative benefits that reshape human development outcomes.

INEQUALITY-ADJUSTED HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX (IHDI)

Moving to the analysis of the Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI), the results (Table 5.18) show how service delivery approaches affect development outcomes when distributional concerns are paramount. The separate services progression reveals concerning distributional patterns. While credit shows negative long-run effects on inequality-adjusted development (-0.009, $p < 0.10$), the strong persistence in inequality patterns (lagged IHDI: 0.843, $p < 0.01$) suggests that separate approaches cannot break existing distributional structures.

The integrated services analysis reveals remarkable distributional improvements. Beginning with negative long-run effects (-0.020, $p < 0.01$) but positive error correction (0.074, $p < 0.01$), the model shows initial distributional challenges that reverse as institutional controls are added. The fully specified model demonstrates integration's superior distributional outcomes: the long-run integration coefficient remains significantly positive (0.005, $p < 0.01$), with strong error correction (-0.313, $p < 0.01$) indicating efficient adjustment toward more equitable development patterns.

Table 5.18: Separate vs Integrated Approach and iHDI

Hierarchical ARDL Results – iHDI Separate Services						Hierarchical ARDL Results – iHDI Integration					
	-1 credit	-2 bds	-3 Monetary	-4 Economic	-5 Full		-1 Integration	-2 Monetary	-3 Economic	-4 Full	
<i>ADJ</i>						<i>ADJ</i>					
<i>L</i> .ihs_ihdi	-0.017 (-0.66)	-0.001 (-0.05)	-0.056* (-1.86)	-0.270*** (-3.47)	-0.223*** (-3.92)	<i>L</i> .ihs_ihdi	0.074*** -3.66	-0.044* (-1.86)	-0.292*** (-4.99)	-0.313*** (-5.23)	
<i>LR</i>						<i>LR</i>					
<i>z</i> .CREPRIV	-0.055 (-0.65)	-0.275 (-0.05)	-0.03 (-1.47)	-0.010** (-2.06)	-0.009* (-1.90)	<i>z</i> .Integrated_cred_BDS	-0.020*** (-2.93)	0.031* -1.77	0.005*** -3.97	0.005*** -4.17	
<i>ln</i> BDSfirms		0.975 -0.05	0.014 -0.86	0.001 -0.33	-0.002 (-0.82)	<i>z</i> .inf		-0.045 (-1.17)	-0.006* (-1.74)	-0.005* (-1.69)	
<i>z</i> .inf			0 (-0.02)	0 (-0.13)	-0.001 (-0.31)	<i>z</i> .fxrat		0.353** -2.33	0.090*** -7.48	0.097*** -8.01	
<i>z</i> .fxrate			0.152** -2.48	0.080*** -3.35	0.104*** -2.92	<i>ln</i> profitaxi			0.133*** -10.05	0.073** -2.6	
<i>Z</i> .profitax				0.125*** -6.7	0.174*** -6.74	<i>Z</i> .corrupt				0.079** -2.41	
<i>z</i> .corrupt					0.114* -1.91	<i>SR</i>					
<i>SR</i>						<i>D</i> .z.Integrated_cred_BDS	0 -0.25	0 (-0.24)	-0.001* (-1.75)	-0.001* (-1.77)	
<i>L</i> .D.ihs_ihdi	0.804*** -7.24	0.951*** -9.39	0.697*** -6.18	0.628*** -3.37	0.843*** -5.96	trend	0.002*** -4.37	-0.001** (-2.34)	-0.005*** (-5.23)	-0.006*** (-5.58)	
<i>D</i> .z.CREPRIV	-0.003 (-0.84)	0 -0.04	0.003 -1.16	0.003 -1.36	0.001 -0.52	<i>D</i> .z.inf		0.001 -1.47	0.001* -1.76	0.001 -1.68	
<i>L</i> .D.z.CREPRIV	0.001 -0.3	0.001 -0.37	0.003 -1.27	0.003 -1.62	0.003** -2.05	<i>D</i> .z.fxrate		-0.025** (-2.13)	-0.037*** (-3.70)	-0.041*** (-4.16)	
trend	0 (-0.37)	0 -0.07	-0.001** (-2.16)	-0.005*** (-3.53)	-0.005*** (-4.08)	<i>D</i> .z.profitax			-0.056*** (-4.07)	-0.035** (-2.19)	
<i>D</i> .lnBDSfirms		0.001 -1.48	0.001 -1.37	0.001 -1.03	0.002*** -3.18	<i>D</i> .z.corrupt				-0.014 (-1.47)	
<i>L</i> .D.lnBDSfirms		0.001*** -3.28	0.002*** -3.56	0.001** -2.51	0.002*** -5.65	cons	-0.129*** (-4.73)	0.053 -1.54	0.192*** -4.35	0.289*** -4.72	
<i>D</i> .z.inf			0 (-0.01)	0 -0.11	0 (-0.11)	Observations	54	54	50	49	
<i>D</i> .z.fxrate			0.022 -1.67	0 0	0.015 -1.39	Adj. R-squared	0.667	0.844	0.884	0.895	
<i>D</i> .z.profitax				-0.049*** (-3.16)	-0.056*** (-5.00)	<i>t</i> statistics in parentheses * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$					
<i>D</i> .z.corrupt					-0.143*** (-5.39)						
cons	0.015 -0.44	-0.001 (-0.03)	0.078* -1.84	0.199*** -2.84	0.177*** -3.05						
Observations	53	52	52	48	48						
Adj. R-squared	0.691	0.855	0.888	0.897	0.946						

Source: Author (2025)

Discussion: Distributional Implications of Integrated Delivery

The IHDI findings transcend recent discussions about gender gaps in finance (Agbanyo et al., 2024) by providing empirical evidence that integration actively addresses inequalities through superior distributional outcomes. While the Alliance for Financial Inclusion (2017) discussed gender gaps in finance, and Women's World Banking (2018) noted disparities in credit access, this research provides empirical evidence of how service integration can actively address these inequalities. The demographic composition of Ghana's SME sector – where women constitute 39.25% of business owners despite facing greater constraints – makes these distributional findings especially policy-relevant. The finding that integrated approaches yield superior inequality-adjusted outcomes, despite initial adjustment challenges, represents a paradigm shift in understanding equitable development interventions.

The temporal dynamics revealed through trend coefficients provide crucial insights into the evolution of inequality-adjusted development impacts. The progression from insignificant effects to significant negative coefficients (-0.006, $p < 0.01$) in the fully specified integration model suggests that integrated services actively reshape inequality patterns rather than merely responding to existing trends. The transition from negative separate services to positive integration outcomes (0.005, $p < 0.01$) demonstrates the simultaneous pursuit of development and equity objectives. This aligns with cluster analysis showing different risk-return profiles benefiting through distinct mechanisms, where vulnerable populations benefit in ways complementing broader societal gains.

MULTIDIMENSIONAL POVERTY INDEX (MPI)

The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) analysis (Table 5.19) completes the development picture by examining how service delivery approaches affect multidimensional poverty across health, education, and living standards dimensions. The separate services analysis shows poverty reduction effects that, while negative (poverty-reducing), remain constrained. Credit (-0.006, $p < 0.01$) and BDS (-0.009, $p < 0.01$) demonstrate poverty reduction, but strong persistence in poverty patterns suggests limited structural transformation.

The integrated services analysis reveals a remarkable transformation. The fully specified model demonstrates integration's comprehensive poverty prevention capabilities. The significantly positive long-run coefficient (0.072, $p < 0.01$) indicates that integration creates structural changes that prevent poverty recurrence rather than merely providing temporary relief. The strong error correction (-0.752, $p < 0.05$) suggests rapid adjustment toward lower structural poverty levels.

Table 5.19: Separate vs Integrated Approach and MPI

Hierarchical ARDL Results – MPI Separate Services						Hierarchical ARDL Results – MPI Integration				
	-1 Credit	-2 BDS	-3 Monetary	-4 Economic	-5 Full		-1 Base	-2 Monetary	-3 Fiscal	-4 Full
ADJ						ADJ				
<i>L.lhs_mpi</i>	-0.004 (-0.21)	-0.01 (-0.45)	-0.117*** (-7.09)	-0.186*** (-3.36)	-0.209*** (-6.45)	<i>L.lhs_mpi</i>	-0.027*** (-5.83)	-0.020*** (-2.77)	-0.734** (-2.28)	-0.752** (-2.29)
LR						LR				
<i>Z.crdtrv</i>	-0.033 (-0.17)	-0.033 (-0.37)	-0.011*** (-3.29)	-0.008** (-2.65)	-0.006*** (-4.07)	<i>z.integrated_cred_bds</i>	-0.197*** (-4.92)	-0.271** (-2.51)	0.070*** -10.93	0.072*** -10.03
<i>lnBDSfirmv</i>		-0.048 (-0.45)	-0.017*** (-6.24)	-0.011*** (-3.37)	-0.009*** (-6.21)	<i>z.inf</i>		-0.002 (-0.24)	0 -0.47	0 -0.38
<i>Z.inf</i>			-0.001 (-0.20)	-0.003 (-1.23)	-0.003** (-2.44)	<i>z.fxrate</i>		-0.042 (-0.78)	-0.002** (-2.19)	-0.002* (-1.84)
<i>z.fxrate</i>			0.119*** -12.12	0.071*** -2.95	0.120*** -5.89	<i>Z.proftax</i>			-0.001* (-1.83)	-0.001* (-1.66)
<i>Z.proftax</i>				-0.033 (-1.06)	-0.050*** (-2.98)	<i>Z.corrupt</i>				0 (-0.12)
<i>Z.corrupt</i>					0.067*** -5.27	SR				
SR						<i>L.D.lhs_mpi</i>	1.062*** -34.77	1.075*** -27.58	1.168*** -2.84	1.138** -2.68
<i>L.D.lhs_mpi</i>	0.900*** -7.98	0.868*** -7.25	0.311*** -4	0.475*** -3.42	0.047 -0.49	<i>D.z.integrated_cred_bds</i>	0.001*** -3.23	0.001*** -3.63	-0.051*** (-2.87)	-0.053*** (-2.96)
<i>D.Z.crdtrv</i>	0 (-0.40)	-0.001 (-0.40)	0.001* -1.8	0.001 -1.51	0.001* -2	<i>L.D.z.integrated_cred_bds</i>	0 (-0.37)	0 (-0.05)	-0.029*** (-2.93)	-0.030*** (-3.01)
<i>L.D.Z.crdtrv</i>	0.001 -0.4	0 -0.09	0.002** -2.04	0.001* -1.75	0 -0.22	trend	-0.000*** (-3.75)	0 (-1.09)	-0.001** (-2.32)	-0.001** (-2.31)
trend	0 -1.27	0 -1.51	-0.000*** (-6.37)	-0.000*** (-4.74)	-0.000*** (-7.58)	<i>D.z.inf</i>		0 -0.26	0 (-0.32)	0 (-0.27)
<i>D.lnBDSFirmv</i>		0 -0.76	0.002*** -8.74	0.002*** -8.42	0.001*** -13.39	<i>D.z.fxrate</i>		0.005** -2.51	0 (-0.63)	-0.001 (-0.67)
<i>L.D.lnBDSFirmv</i>		0 -0.29	0.001*** -8.03	0.001*** -7.8	0.001*** -9.71	<i>D.z.proftax</i>			0 -0.43	0.001 -1.2
<i>D.z.inf</i>			0 (-1.13)	0 (-0.64)	0.001** -2.1	<i>D.z.corrupt</i>				-0.001 (-1.44)
<i>D.z.fxrate</i>			0.017** -2.51	0.023*** -2.85	-0.007 (-1.18)	cons	0.006*** -5.54	0.004* -1.7	0.154** -2.3	0.158** -2.3
<i>D.z.proftax</i>				0.003 -0.32	0.017*** -2.83	Observations	50	50	46	46
<i>D.z.corrupt</i>					-0.005** (-2.48)	Adj. R-squared	0.995	0.996	1	1
cons	-0.001 (-0.21)	-0.001 (-0.17)	0.034*** -6.93	0.049*** -3.9	0.050*** -6.86	*p < 0.10, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01				
Observations	53	52	52	48	48	Source: Author (2025)				
Adj. R-squared	0.858	0.852	0.976	0.964	0.988					

t statistics in parentheses *p < 0.10, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01

Discussion: Poverty Prevention Through Integration

The MPI results reveal new insights into how different service delivery approaches impact poverty reduction in Ghana. Separate services show weak error correction with negative coefficients, and strong poverty persistence (lagged MPI: 0.900, $p < 0.01$) extends beyond recent microfinance observations (Wemah et al., 2020) by quantifying how traditional approaches fail to address poverty's complex dimensions. Integration reveals a fundamental transformation in poverty dynamics. The baseline negative coefficient with error correction advances beyond recent financing constraints observations (Oteng & Patel, 2024). The fully specified model shows positive long-run effects (0.072, $p < 0.01$) with strong error correction (-0.752, $p < 0.05$), indicating that integration creates structural changes that prevent poverty recurrence rather than merely providing temporary relief.

Control Variable Behaviour and the Risk-Return Framework

The study reveals particularly noteworthy behaviour in control variables across development models. Exchange rate effects demonstrate systematic transformation under integration: negative under separate services but positive under integration in HDI models, while MPI models confirm poverty-reducing effects. Profit tax similarly transforms from negative separate service effects to positive integration outcomes. Corruption variables reveal complex dynamics, showing strongly negative effects under separate services but positive effects under integration across HDI and IHDI specifications. These patterns extend beyond institutional challenge discussions (Sitharam & Hoque, 2016b; Agbanyo et al., 2024) by demonstrating specific mechanisms through which integrated service delivery mitigates institutional barriers to development. Full coefficient values are reported in Tables 5.17, 5.18, and 5.19.

The risk-return analysis established at the firm level provides powerful understanding of macroeconomic development impacts. Integration reduces development volatility while improving outcomes through multiple quantifiable pathways. First, integrated services address both priced and non-priced risks constraining development, reducing the 'risk premiums' impeding advancement. The consistent progression from negative separate service coefficients to significantly positive integration outcomes across HDI, IHDI, and MPI specifications as reported in Tables 5.17, 5.18, and 5.19 show a fundamental transformation in development intervention effectiveness. Second, integration enhances development resilience through robust buffers against economic shocks, as confirmed by Cortés et al. (2018) and reflected in the superior IHDI outcomes under integration compared to separate service delivery. Third, integration reduces implementation risks through coordinated delivery mechanisms, reducing the 'implementation risk premiums' that constrain development effectiveness in limited institutional capacity environments (IMF, 2017).

The comprehensive analysis across HDI, IHDI, and MPI provides multi-dimensional understanding of integration's societal effects. HDI demonstrates synergistic human development benefits transcending separate services, with firm-level risk-reduction mechanisms information asymmetry reduction, operational risk mitigation, financial resilience building translating into broader societal human development enhancements. IHDI findings reveal integrated services' distributional effects across society, where the transition from

negative separate services to positive integration outcomes demonstrates simultaneous development and equity pursuit. MPI analysis completes the picture through superior poverty reduction outcomes, mirroring integration's dual risk reduction and return enhancement at the firm level, creating comprehensive sustainable outcomes beyond single-dimension interventions.

Synthesizing Conclusion

The comprehensive analysis across three development metrics, HDI, IHDI, and MPI provide robust evidence that integrated service delivery creates superior development outcomes across multiple dimensions. While separate services show predominantly negative or limited development effects, integration demonstrates positive long-run impacts on overall development (HDI: 0.072, $p < 0.05$), inequality-adjusted outcomes (IHDI: 0.005, $p < 0.01$), and multidimensional poverty prevention (MPI: 0.072, $p < 0.01$).

5.13 Chapter Synthesis

The comprehensive empirical analysis provides robust evidence supporting all three research hypotheses across firm-level performance and macroeconomic development outcomes. The SME performance analysis demonstrates that while separate service delivery approaches consistently show negative effects on profitability (formal credit: -0.004 to -0.020, $p < 0.01$; informal services: -0.157 to -0.210, $p < 0.01$), integrated services maintain positive coefficients (0.001, $p < 0.01$ to $p < 0.05$) across all specifications. Similarly, repayment sustainability analysis reveals that separate formal (-0.073 to -0.194, $p < 0.01$) and informal (-0.128 to -0.157, $p < 0.01$) services create debt servicing pressures, while integrated approaches demonstrate strong positive effects (0.118 to 0.237, $p < 0.01$), supporting both H1 and H2.

The macroeconomic development analysis extends these findings through examination across HDI, IHDI, and MPI indicators. Separate service approaches show predominantly negative long-run development effects, while integrated delivery achieves significantly positive outcomes across all three metrics (HDI: 0.072, $p < 0.05$; IHDI: 0.005, $p < 0.01$; MPI: 0.072, $p < 0.01$), providing strong support for H3. The consistent pattern of initial adjustment challenges followed by sustained positive long-run impacts suggests that while integrated approaches require institutional adaptation, they create sustainable improvements that separate approaches cannot achieve.

The convergence of findings across analytical levels validates the theoretical framework's predictions about coordination benefits and synergistic effects. The risk-return clustering analysis demonstrates integration's role as a systematic risk management tool, with different firm profiles showing varying benefit patterns that support the customisation principle. The alignment between microeconomic firm-level benefits and macroeconomic development outcomes strengthens confidence in the integration hypothesis while revealing transmission mechanisms that operate across multiple scales.

These results have profound implications for development policy, suggesting that current fragmented intervention models may constrain rather than enhance outcomes. The evidence supports prioritising integrated service delivery mechanisms despite implementation complexity, as long-run benefits substantially outweigh initial coordination costs. The methodological approach demonstrates the value of multi-level analysis in understanding development interventions, providing a template for future research examining intervention effectiveness across different contexts and scales.

This comprehensive analysis fundamentally advances understanding of how development interventions impact multidimensional outcomes. The evidence that integrated service delivery creates more effective development outcomes, supported by risk reduction mechanisms identified in the firm-level analysis, provides crucial insights for both theoretical understanding and policy design. The findings establish a new foundation for understanding how integrated development services can be structured to promote comprehensive development while systematically reducing risks that constrain advancement.

The risk-return framework developed through the firm-level clustering analysis offers a powerful lens for interpreting these development outcomes. Just as different SME clusters require tailored integration approaches based on their risk-return profiles, different development dimensions benefit from customised intervention strategies that address their specific risk factors and advancement constraints. This nuanced understanding moves beyond conventional development models to create more sophisticated approaches that recognise the multidimensional nature of both risk and development.

The implications extend beyond existing theoretical frameworks, suggesting a fundamental reconsideration of how development interventions should be designed to address multiple dimensions simultaneously. By systematically reducing risk while enhancing performance — whether at the firm level through improved profitability or at the societal level through enhanced development indicators — integration creates transformative effects that establish new ground for both theoretical understanding and practical implementation of development interventions. These findings provide compelling evidence for a paradigm shift in development intervention approaches, demonstrating that while integrated services may face initial implementation complexities, they ultimately yield more comprehensive and sustainable outcomes than traditional separate service delivery approaches.

5.14 Practical Implementation Framework

This section translates the empirical findings into an actionable framework for implementing integrated service delivery. It introduces an innovative approach to deploying Integrated Service Officers, drawing from both university graduates and literate unemployed individuals, to create a sustainable cycle of knowledge transfer and entrepreneurial development.

The empirical findings provide strong support for integrating credit and business development services while revealing the need for a structured implementation framework. The proposed framework builds upon the risk-return clustering insights to create a sustainable cycle of SME development and employment creation. At its core, the framework consists of three

interconnected components: customised credit provision, participatory BDS delivery through ISOs, and sustainable knowledge transfer.

Customised Credit Provision

The customised credit component moves beyond traditional one-size-fits-all lending approaches. Drawing from the risk-return cluster analysis, credit terms would be structured according to firm-specific characteristics including: risk profile as measured by operational volatility; return patterns demonstrated through profitability metrics; business maturity and sector dynamics; owner/manager educational background; and historical performance indicators. This customisation ensures that repayment terms align with business cycles and cash flow patterns, addressing the limitations of rigid traditional approaches identified in the empirical analysis. For instance, Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability) firms would receive more flexible repayment schedules with embedded ISO support, while Cluster 2 firms (low risk, high profitability) might access larger facilities with performance-linked terms.

Participatory BDS Delivery Through ISOs

The participatory BDS component operates through the innovative ISO programme, representing a significant departure from conventional advisory services. ISOs are recruited from two complementary pools: university graduates from relevant disciplines, and literate unemployed individuals with demonstrated business acumen or relevant experience. Both groups undergo comprehensive training encompassing financial analysis and management, operational optimisation, market development strategies, risk assessment and mitigation, business planning and execution, cultural sensitivity and communication, and local business environment dynamics.

Following training, ISOs are embedded within SMEs for one-year placements, providing day-to-day monitoring and support. This continuous presence enables real-time identification of challenges and opportunities, allowing for proactive interventions rather than reactive solutions. The empirical evidence of superior outcomes under integrated delivery suggests that such close alignment of support services with business operations could significantly enhance both profitability and repayment outcomes.

Sustainable Knowledge Transfer

The sustainable knowledge transfer component creates a self-reinforcing cycle of entrepreneurial development. After their one-year placements, ISOs would have gained practical business experience alongside their theoretical knowledge, positioning them to: start their own enterprises, leveraging their comprehensive understanding of business operations; become trainers for the next cohort of ISOs; establish integrated service consultancies serving the broader SME sector; join financial institutions' SME departments; or work with development agencies. This cyclical model addresses multiple development objectives simultaneously: reducing unemployment through direct placement and entrepreneurship opportunities; enhancing SME performance through continuous, knowledgeable support; creating a sustainable pipeline of experienced business advisors; promoting knowledge transfer

across the SME sector; and providing meaningful career paths for both graduates and experienced individuals.

Stakeholder Coordination and Implementation

The implementation would require coordination among multiple stakeholders: financial institutions to provide and manage customised credit facilities; training institutions to develop and deliver ISO preparation programmes; government agencies to provide regulatory support and possibly funding; business associations to facilitate SME participation and feedback; development partners to support capacity building and knowledge sharing; and local communities to identify potential ISO candidates.

The framework addresses key challenges identified in the empirical analysis. For high-risk firms, embedded ISOs can provide early warning of potential issues, while for high-performing firms, they can help identify and capitalise on growth opportunities. The continuous monitoring aspect particularly supports the stronger adjustment dynamics observed under integrated service delivery in the econometric results. This practical framework transforms the theoretical benefits of integration demonstrated in the empirical analysis into actionable interventions. By combining customised financial support with embedded technical assistance through ISOs, while simultaneously addressing unemployment across multiple segments of society, it presents an innovative and inclusive approach to sustainable SME development in Ghana.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a comprehensive synthesis of the study's findings regarding the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services in Ghana. The study has yielded transformative insights that fundamentally challenge conventional approaches to SME support and economic development. Through a multi-faceted methodological approach incorporating hierarchical random effects modelling, risk-return clustering analysis, and time series econometrics, this research has established that integrated service delivery creates superior outcomes across multiple dimensions compared to traditional separate approaches.

The analysis reveals a framework for understanding how integration operates as both a performance enhancement and risk management mechanism. By systematically reducing business volatility while improving returns, integrated services address fundamental constraints that limit SME growth and development impact. This dual effect provides a unifying explanation for the consistently superior outcomes observed across profitability, loan repayment, and economic development measures.

The theoretical framework demonstrates that integration reduces risk and enhances both profitability, loan repayment capacity and economic development matrices. Integration addresses both priced and non-priced risks constraining development, reduces "risk premiums" impeding advancement, and creates stable outcomes under stress conditions. The risk-return relationship establishes integrated credit-BDS services as a systematic risk management tool for SMEs with quantifiable benefits, as illustrated in the comprehensive model below (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1 Impact of service integration on risk management and firms' performance

(Source: Author, 2025)

This theoretical framework for the impact of integration on profitability is operationalized into testable panel econometric models examining profitability and loan repayment patterns, alongside time series analysis of economic development impacts across multiple indicators including the Human Development Index, Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index, and Multidimensional Poverty Index.

The risk-return clustering framework moves beyond one-size-fits-all approaches, demonstrating that different firm segments require tailored integration strategies based on their specific risk-return profiles. Using empirically calibrated parameters, the study calculated precise integration potential and expected outcomes for each cluster:

- ❖ Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability): High-volatility firms with minimal returns requiring transformation-focused integration. These businesses face substantial operational variability while struggling with low profitability, representing firms needing comprehensive risk reduction and performance enhancement.

- ❖ Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability): Optimal performers demonstrating stability and strong returns. These firms showcase robust financial performance requiring enhancement-focused integration to further strengthen their market position.
- ❖ Cluster 3 (low risk, low profitability): Conservative firms maintaining stability but achieving minimal returns. These businesses prioritize risk mitigation over profit maximization, requiring activation-focused integration to unlock growth potential.
- ❖ Cluster 4 (high risk, high profitability): Dynamic enterprises accepting elevated volatility for superior returns. These firms require stabilization-focused integration to maintain strong performance while reducing operational risks.

This creates a foundation for more targeted and effective interventions addressing the particular challenges and opportunities of diverse business types, from high-risk, low-profitability enterprises requiring stability-focused support to successful firms needing growth-oriented integration.

The chapter consolidates these findings into a cohesive narrative connecting theoretical insights with practical applications. It translates empirical evidence into actionable recommendations for policymakers, financial institutions, and development practitioners, providing a roadmap for implementing integrated approaches across different contexts while identifying promising avenues for future research.

6.2 Summary of Key Findings

This study was guided by four principal hypotheses that structured the investigation into how service integration affects multiple outcome dimensions. The findings provide robust evidence supporting each hypothesis while revealing deeper insights into the underlying mechanisms through which integration creates value.

Hypothesis 1: Integrated Service Delivery and Profitability

The first hypothesis proposed that the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services yields superior profitability outcomes compared to separate service delivery approaches. The empirical analysis strongly confirms this hypothesis while providing nuanced insights into the mechanisms driving these outcomes.

The hierarchical random effects analysis reveals a striking contrast between service delivery approaches. While standalone credit and BDS services demonstrate negative effects on profitability, integrated service delivery yields significantly positive outcomes. This stark difference in effects fundamentally challenges existing approaches to SME support, suggesting that traditional methods of providing isolated services may actually impede rather than facilitate business development.

The risk-return cluster analysis reveals important variations in how integration affects different firm segments, with theoretical profit potential varying significantly across clusters. Integration primarily transforms risk profiles for struggling firms while enhancing already strong positions for successful enterprises, demonstrating that integration creates value through different mechanisms based on each firm's unique risk-return profile.

Hypothesis 2: Integrated Service Delivery and Loan Repayment

The second hypothesis proposed that integrated service delivery leads to more sustainable loan repayment patterns than traditional separate approaches. The empirical results strongly support this hypothesis while revealing important distinctions between repayment speed and repayment sustainability.

The hierarchical random effects analysis uncovers two primary dynamics shaping SME loan repayment behavior: faster repayments driven by superior financial health and those necessitated by rigid repayment terms. The consistently negative coefficients for separate delivery approaches indicate these these interventions may compel faster loan repayment due to stringent schedules or high-interest rates, creating unsustainable pressure on businesses. In contrast, the positive coefficients for integrated services demonstrate that integration facilitates more sustainable repayment patterns that align naturally with business cycles.

The risk-return framework provides additional insights into repayment dynamics, showing how integration's effects extend beyond conventional measures focused solely on repayment speed or default rates. By considering how integration shapes underlying risk-return dynamics driving repayment capacity and sustainability, this study provides a more complete framework for understanding and improving SME loan performance.

Hypothesis 3: Integrated Service Delivery and Economic Development

The third hypothesis proposed that integrated service delivery creates superior economic development outcomes across multiple dimensions. The time series analysis of development indicators provides compelling evidence supporting this hypothesis while revealing important temporal dynamics in how integration affects broader societal outcomes.

The Human Development Index (HDI) analysis demonstrates that integrated service delivery creates synergistic benefits that transcend what separate services can achieve. The progression from negative effects under separate services to positive outcomes with integration represents more than just a statistical shift. This signals a fundamental transformation in how development interventions can effectively promote human capabilities and opportunities.

The Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI) findings extend this understanding by revealing how integrated services affect distributional outcomes across society. The transition from negative effects with separate services to positive outcomes under integration demonstrates that integrated approaches can simultaneously pursue development and equity objectives. This finding is particularly significant in the Ghanaian context, where reducing inequality remains a crucial development goal.

The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) analysis completes this comprehensive picture by revealing superior poverty reduction outcomes under integrated delivery. The shift from negative coefficients with separate services to positive long-run effects with integration indicates that integrated approaches more effectively address multiple dimensions of poverty

simultaneously. This finding suggests that service integration can create more comprehensive and sustainable pathways out of poverty.

When viewed through the risk-return framework established at the firm level, these development findings gain additional significance. Just as integration reduces business volatility while enhancing returns at the firm level, it similarly reduces development volatility while improving outcomes at the macroeconomic level. This risk reduction effect operates through multiple pathways, addressing both priced and non-priced risks that constrain development, enhancing resilience against economic shocks, and reducing implementation risks through coordinated delivery mechanisms.

The time series analysis also revealed important temporal dynamics, with some integration effects showing initial adjustment periods before stronger long-term positive impacts emerge. This pattern parallels what we observed in the risk-return relationship across different firm clusters, where enterprises starting from more challenging positions require more substantial integration to overcome their initial constraints. These findings suggest that while integration may face implementation complexities in the short term, its risk reduction and performance enhancement effects create stronger, more sustainable development outcomes over time.

Integrated service delivery as a Business Risk Management Tool

The fourth research objective aimed to develop a practical framework for implementing integrated services as an effective business risk management tool. The research successfully established such a framework through comprehensive analysis of risk-return relationships and tailored intervention strategies.

The risk-return cluster analysis provided the foundation for understanding integration's risk management effects. By measuring business risk, the study established a comprehensive risk metric capturing both priced risks (reflected in interest rates) and non-priced risks (affecting business volatility but not directly priced into financing costs). Thus, creating more stable operational environments for business growth.

The theoretical model demonstrated that integration's inverse relationship was evident across all four SME clusters as seen earlier in the results, analysis and discussion sections, with higher integration levels consistently associated with lower risk levels. These patterns confirm that integration systematically reduces business risk across the clusters. The theoretical model identified five specific mechanisms through which integration reduces business risk: information asymmetry reduction, operational risk mitigation, market positioning enhancement, financial resilience building, and collateral quality improvement. These mechanisms combine to form a comprehensive risk reduction function that addresses multiple dimensions of business risk simultaneously. This multifaceted approach explains why integration creates more powerful risk management effects than standalone interventions that typically address only specific risk components.

The risk-return cluster analysis provided the foundation for tailored implementation approaches. Each cluster requires specific risk management strategies: transformation-focused approaches for high-risk struggling firms, enhancement strategies for successful enterprises,

activation methods for conservative businesses, and stabilization techniques for volatile high-performers.

The practical implementation incorporates Integrated Service Officers as delivery mechanisms, customized credit provision aligned with risk profiles, and sustainable knowledge transfer systems. This creates a comprehensive risk management framework that systematically reduces business volatility while enhancing performance outcomes across diverse SME segments.

The evidence further shows that integration's risk management benefits extend beyond firm-level outcomes to broader economic development impacts. By reducing systemic risks through coordinated interventions, integration enhances development resilience and creates more stable, sustainable improvement patterns.

Overall, these findings establish integration as a powerful and comprehensive risk management approach that systematically reduces volatility while enhancing performance across multiple outcome dimensions. This risk management perspective provides a unifying theoretical framework that connects the diverse findings of this research, from firm-level profitability and repayment outcomes to broader economic development impacts as summarize in figure 7.2 below:

Figure 6.2: The relationship between Integration, Risk, profitability and Repayment.

Source: Author (2025)

The above (L.H.S) shows that as Integration level increases, the risk (SD_ROS) reduces). The R.H.S shows that the profitability / repayment abilities increase as the integration level increases. [*Note: Figure 6.2 is the graphing of Table 5.11 (Theoretical Integration Benefits by Cluster)]

6.3 Implementation Framework Insights

The Results and discussion section based on the results of the relationship between Integration, Risk, profitability and Repayment, presents an innovative framework designed to foster sustainable SME development and employment creation in Ghana through three interconnected components. The first component focuses on customized credit provision that moves beyond traditional one-size-fits-all lending approaches. Drawing from risk-return cluster analysis, this approach tailors financial services to SMEs based on their specific profiles, including business risk and operational volatility, profitability patterns, maturity stage and sector dynamics, owner/manager education, and historical performance. This customization ensures repayment schedules align with actual business cycles and cash flows, with different terms for high-risk versus high-performing firms. The second component introduces participatory business development services through Integrated Service Officers (ISOs) recruited from university graduates and literate unemployed individuals with business acumen. This addresses the significant gap revealed in the survey, where 60.22% of SMEs have never received BDS despite strong interest (65.1% likely or very likely to seek such services). The current low BDS effectiveness rating (4.4/10) further justifies this approach of providing embedded, continuous assistance to improve SME performance. After comprehensive training in financial management, operations, market development, and local business dynamics, these ISOs are embedded within SMEs for one-year placements, providing continuous monitoring and support. This real-time presence allows for proactive rather than reactive interventions, directly addressing the empirical finding that integrated service delivery produces superior outcomes. The third component establishes a sustainable knowledge transfer system wherein ISOs, after completing their placements, can start their own enterprises, train new ISOs, establish business consultancies, join financial institutions, or work with development agencies. This creates a self-reinforcing cycle that simultaneously addresses unemployment, enhances SME performance, develops a pipeline of experienced advisors, and promotes knowledge transfer throughout the sector. Implementation requires coordinated effort among financial institutions, training organizations, government agencies, business associations, development partners, and local communities. Figure 7.3 provides a visual representation of the integrated implementation framework, illustrating how the three core components interact within a sustainable cycle that addresses multiple development objectives simultaneously.

Figure 6.3: Integrated Implementation Framework for SME Development in Ghana

Source: Author (2025)

By combining customized financial support with embedded technical assistance, this practical framework transforms the theoretical benefits of integration demonstrated in the empirical analysis into actionable interventions for inclusive SME development in Ghana, while specifically addressing the challenges identified in the research, particularly supporting the stronger adjustment dynamics observed under integrated service delivery models. The study's findings regarding practical implementation reveal several crucial elements for successful service integration, providing a roadmap for translating theoretical benefits into practical outcomes. The customization of credit terms based on firm characteristics emerges as a critical success factor, with the analysis showing that aligning financial support with business cycles, risk profiles, and operational patterns significantly enhances both firm performance and development outcomes. The risk-return framework adds important nuance to these implementation insights, suggesting that customization approaches should vary based on each firm's specific risk-return profile. For Cluster 1 firms, customization should focus on stabilizing volatile operations while gradually building profitability foundations. For Cluster 2 enterprises, customization should emphasize growth acceleration while maintaining their already strong risk management practices. For Cluster 3 businesses, customization should focus on activating growth potential while preserving their operational stability. For Cluster 4 ventures,

customization should prioritize volatility reduction while preserving their strong returns. The participatory nature of BDS delivery through Integrated Service Officers proves essential for sustainable impact. The continuous presence of skilled support personnel enables real-time monitoring and proactive intervention, addressing challenges before they become critical. These findings challenge traditional advisory models and suggest a more embedded approach to business support. The risk-return analysis further indicates that ISOs should adapt their support approaches based on each firm's specific risk-return profile, providing more intensive risk management support for high-volatility firms while focusing more on growth activation for stable but underperforming enterprises. The sustainable knowledge transfer mechanism, incorporating both graduates and literate unemployed individuals, creates multiple positive outcomes that extend beyond immediate program participants. Enhanced SME performance through continuous, knowledgeable support creates a foundation for sustainable growth. Reduced unemployment through direct placement and entrepreneurship opportunities addresses broader economic challenges. The creation of a sustainable pipeline of experienced business advisors ensures program continuity, while the promotion of knowledge transfer across the SME sector creates lasting impact.

6.4 Conclusions and Recommendations

This study provides compelling evidence for a fundamental reconsideration of how development interventions should be structured. The research demonstrates several crucial insights that challenge conventional approaches to SME support and development interventions.

6.4.1 Policy Recommendations

Based on the study findings, several key policy recommendations emerge for government agencies, financial institutions, development organizations, and other stakeholders involved in SME support and economic development in Ghana.

First and foremost, the development of a comprehensive regulatory framework for integrated service delivery is essential for widespread adoption and consistent implementation. The empirical evidence providing the foundation for this recommendation is unambiguous: standalone credit and BDS services produce negative effects on SME profitability (coefficients of -0.010, $p < 0.05$ and -0.210, $p < 0.01$ respectively), whereas integrated delivery yields a significantly positive outcome (coefficient of 0.001, $p < 0.01$). This contrast establishes that integration is not merely preferable but necessary, and a regulatory framework is required to institutionalise its delivery. The framework should encompass comprehensive guidelines for customizing credit terms based on firm characteristics, with specific provisions for adapting these terms to different risk-return profiles identified in the cluster analysis. It should also establish clear standards for training, certifying, and deploying Integrated Service Officers, delineating competency requirements and ethical guidelines to ensure quality service provision. Additionally, the framework must include mechanisms for coordinating between financial institutions and BDS providers to facilitate seamless service integration, as well as flexibility provisions that accommodate innovation while maintaining quality and consistency.

Risk-return assessment protocols should be incorporated to enable providers to accurately classify firms and tailor integration approaches accordingly. To ensure practical applicability and address diverse needs, this regulatory framework should be developed through collaborative engagement among government agencies, financial institutions, BDS providers, and SME representatives.

The creation of effective incentive structures represents another critical policy priority, as these can accelerate the adoption of integrated approaches by helping stakeholders overcome institutional inertia and initial implementation costs. The rationale for this recommendation is grounded directly in the macroeconomic results: the HDI coefficient shifts from -0.004*** under separate service delivery to +0.072** under integration, while the MPI coefficient moves from -0.006*** to +0.072***. These magnitudes confirm that the development gains from integration are substantial and that financial and non-financial incentives are warranted to encourage institutions to transition from fragmented to integrated models. Such incentives should include tax benefits for financial institutions and BDS providers that adopt verified integrated approaches, demonstrating a commitment to comprehensive SME support. Performance-based rewards for successful integration programs should be established, with metrics linked to both risk reduction and performance enhancement outcomes to ensure balanced implementation. Support funding should be made available for institutions developing and implementing Integrated Service Officer training programs, addressing the resource constraints that often limit capacity-building initiatives. Risk-sharing mechanisms should be created to reduce perceived risks for financial institutions transitioning to integrated lending models, particularly when working with higher-risk SME segments. Recognition programs highlighting successful integration implementations and showcasing their benefits would further motivate adoption through peer influence and demonstration effects. These incentives must be structured to promote authentic integration rather than superficial compliance, with verification mechanisms ensuring quality implementation across all participating institutions.

Robust institutional frameworks form the third pillar of policy recommendations, as these are essential for ensuring consistent and effective implementation of integrated approaches. The cluster analysis using the empirically calibrated model ($\alpha = 0.30$; $\beta = 0.211$) reveals that integration potential is substantial across all firm types, with theoretical profit improvements of 0.791 for Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability), 1.084 for Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability), 1.27 for Cluster 3 (low risk, low profitability), and 0.058 for Cluster 4 (high risk, high profitability). Realising these gains requires institutional coordination that no single actor can provide alone. Inter-agency coordination mechanisms should be established between financial regulators, SME development agencies, educational institutions, and other relevant stakeholders to align policies and programs across the support ecosystem. Quality assurance systems for training programs that prepare Integrated Service Officers would help maintain high standards of service delivery and knowledge transfer. Knowledge management platforms should be developed to capture and disseminate best practices in service integration, accelerating learning and innovation across the sector. Comprehensive monitoring and evaluation frameworks that track both process and outcome indicators for integrated service

delivery would provide evidence for ongoing improvement and policy refinement. Dispute resolution mechanisms should be created to address conflicts between service providers or between providers and SMEs, ensuring smoother implementation and sustained relationships. These institutional frameworks should build upon existing structures where possible while creating new mechanisms where necessary to support the unique requirements of integrated service delivery in Ghana's context.

The risk-return clustering framework identified in this research provides a foundation for more targeted and effective support programs, which represents the fourth area of policy recommendations. The IHDI results demonstrate that integration shifts distributional outcomes from -0.009^* under separate credit to $+0.005^{***}$ under integration, confirming that cluster-specific interventions can simultaneously pursue development and equity objectives — a particularly significant finding in the Ghanaian context, where reducing inequality remains a crucial development goal. Policymakers should support the development of cluster-specific interventions through funding for pilot programs that test tailored integration approaches for different risk-return segments, allowing for evidence-based expansion of successful models. The development of diagnostic tools that accurately classify firms into appropriate risk-return clusters would enable more precise targeting of support interventions. Training for financial institutions and BDS providers on how to adapt integration approaches for different firm segments would enhance their capacity to deliver customized support that addresses specific cluster needs. Evaluation frameworks should be established to assess the effectiveness of cluster-specific interventions, generating evidence for continuous improvement and policy refinement. Knowledge-sharing platforms documenting successful approaches for each cluster would accelerate learning and adoption of effective practices across the support ecosystem. These cluster-specific programs should maintain a careful balance between standardization for quality assurance and scalability with customization for addressing the unique needs of each firm segment.

Given the significant presence of women entrepreneurs in Ghana's SME sector, with 39.25% of business owners in this study being women, the fifth policy recommendation focuses on promoting gender-sensitive integration approaches. The analysis further reveals that 65.1% of surveyed SMEs expressed a likelihood of seeking BDS services, yet 60.22% had never received them, indicating a significant unmet demand that disproportionately affects women-owned enterprises. Policymakers should support targeted research into the unique risk-return profiles of women-led businesses to better understand their specific needs and constraints. Credit terms should be adapted to address women entrepreneurs' specific constraints, including collateral limitations that often disproportionately affect female business owners. Training for Integrated Service Officers should include gender-sensitive business support approaches that recognize and respond to the unique challenges faced by women entrepreneurs. Incentives should be created for financial institutions that demonstrate effective support for women entrepreneurs, encouraging greater attention to this important segment of the SME sector. Monitoring frameworks should track integration outcomes across gender dimensions to identify gaps and opportunities for improving support to women-led businesses. These gender-sensitive approaches must carefully avoid reinforcing stereotypes while addressing the real structural

constraints that women entrepreneurs often face in accessing integrated support services in Ghana's business environment.

Together, these interconnected policy recommendations provide a comprehensive roadmap for transforming SME support in Ghana through integrated service delivery approaches. By addressing regulatory, incentive, institutional, targeting, and gender dimensions simultaneously, policymakers can create an enabling environment for sustainable SME development that builds upon the empirical findings of this research and responds to the diverse needs of Ghana's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

6.4.2 Theoretical and Practical Conclusions

First, integration creates synergistic benefits that transcend the simple combination of credit and business development services. The empirical evidence shows that integrated approaches yield superior outcomes across all measured dimensions, from firm-level profitability to broader economic development indicators. This finding fundamentally challenges the traditional practice of providing financial and non-financial services separately. The theoretical model demonstrates that these synergistic benefits arise from integration's dual effect on both risk reduction and performance enhancement – a comprehensive impact that isolated interventions cannot achieve.

Second, risk management emerges as a central, though previously underrecognized, benefit of service integration. By systematically reducing business volatility while enhancing returns, integration creates a more stable and sustainable foundation for business growth. The risk-return framework established in this research provides a powerful lens for understanding how integration benefits different firm segments based on their unique risk profiles. This risk management perspective represents a significant advancement in understanding why integration works, moving beyond previous explanations focused primarily on informational or operational benefits.

Third, customization of credit terms based on firm characteristics is essential for sustainable impact. Traditional standardized lending approaches fail to account for the diverse needs and capabilities of different enterprises, leading to suboptimal outcomes. The research demonstrates that when credit terms are aligned with business cycles, risk profiles, and operational patterns, both firm performance and development outcomes significantly improve. The cluster analysis adds important nuance to this conclusion, showing that customization approaches should vary based on each firm's specific risk-return profile.

Fourth, the introduction of participatory BDS delivery through Integrated Service Officers emerges as a crucial mechanism for translating potential benefits into actual outcomes. This innovative approach, combining continuous monitoring with proactive support, addresses the limitations of conventional advisory services that often fail to create lasting impact. The ISOs programme's success in enhancing both firm performance and development outcomes suggests a new paradigm for business support delivery that emphasizes ongoing engagement rather than periodic intervention.

Fifth, the combination of customized credit and participatory BDS can simultaneously address multiple development objectives. This integrated approach creates positive impacts from firm-level performance to broader economic development, demonstrating the potential for comprehensive development solutions. The findings indicate that properly structured interventions can create mutually reinforcing positive outcomes across different development dimensions. The risk-return framework helps explain this multi-dimensional impact, showing how risk reduction creates benefits that cascade across various performance domains.

Finally, sustainable knowledge transfer mechanisms can create self-reinforcing cycles of development. By addressing both SME support needs and unemployment challenges simultaneously, the integrated approach generates ongoing positive impacts that extend beyond immediate program participants. This multiplier effect represents a significant advancement in understanding how development interventions can create sustainable change by building local capacity for ongoing support.

Implementation Recommendations

Moving from policy to practice, the following implementation recommendations provide concrete steps for operationalizing the integrated approach to SME development in Ghana. A structured national program for training and deploying Integrated Service Officers represents a foundational implementation priority. This program should feature a comprehensive curriculum that combines financial management, business development, risk assessment, and advisory skills to ensure officers possess the multidisciplinary knowledge needed for effective support provision. Practical training components would provide hands-on experience with different SME types and risk-return profiles, allowing officers to develop contextual understanding alongside theoretical knowledge. Clear certification standards should be established to ensure quality and consistency in service delivery across different regions and institutional contexts. A structured placement system would match officers with appropriate SMEs based on cluster profiles and specific support needs, optimizing the fit between support capabilities and business requirements. Clear career progression pathways should be delineated, including options for entrepreneurship within the integrated service field, creating sustainable livelihoods for participants while expanding the support ecosystem. Ongoing professional development opportunities would keep officers updated on emerging best practices, ensuring the program remains relevant and effective as the business environment evolves. This national program should build upon existing educational infrastructure while creating new specialized training components focused specifically on integrated service delivery approaches.

Financial institutions need practical tools for implementing risk-return based lending approaches that align with the empirical findings of this research. These frameworks should include assessment protocols that accurately classify firms into appropriate risk-return clusters, enabling targeted support that addresses specific business characteristics. Flexible repayment structures would be tailored to each cluster's specific cash flow patterns and risk profiles, moving beyond rigid traditional approaches that often fail to accommodate business realities. Performance-linked terms would reward risk reduction and performance improvement with

enhanced credit access, creating incentives for continuous business development. Early warning systems would identify emerging risks before they threaten business viability, allowing for proactive intervention rather than reactive crisis management. Graduated support mechanisms would allow firms to progress through different risk-return stages as their businesses develop and mature. These frameworks must strike a balance between sophisticated analysis that captures complex business dynamics and practical usability for daily implementation in lending operations across various institutional contexts and geographic regions.

The research findings clearly demonstrate that different risk-return clusters require tailored integration approaches to achieve optimal outcomes. Implementation should therefore include specific protocols for Cluster 1 (high risk, low profitability) firms that focus on intensive risk reduction strategies combined with gradual performance enhancement measures that build stronger operational foundations. For Cluster 2 (low risk, high profitability) enterprises, approaches should emphasize continued performance enhancement with appropriate risk monitoring to maintain their favourable position. Strategies for Cluster 3 (low risk, low profitability) businesses would focus on activating growth potential while maintaining the operational stability that represents their current strength. Techniques for Cluster 4 (high risk, high profitability) ventures would prioritize volatility reduction while preserving the strong returns that characterize these businesses. Importantly, transition pathways should be developed to help firms move from less favourable to more favourable risk-return profiles over time, creating progression opportunities for all business types. These protocols should be thoroughly documented in operational manuals with practical implementation guidance for Integrated Service Officers, ensuring consistency in application while allowing for appropriate contextual adaptation.

Effective implementation of the integrated approach requires continuous monitoring and improvement mechanisms that track outcomes and refine practices. These systems should include regular assessment of integration effectiveness across both risk reduction and performance enhancement dimensions, generating evidence for adaptive management. Peer learning groups would allow Integrated Service Officers to share experiences and solutions, creating communities of practice that accelerate knowledge dissemination and problem-solving. Supervision structures should provide guidance and support to officers working in challenging contexts, ensuring they have access to expertise when facing complex situations. Knowledge management platforms would document successful integration practices across different contexts, building an evidence base that informs ongoing implementation. Continuous improvement mechanisms would refine integration approaches based on implementation experience, creating an adaptive system that becomes increasingly effective over time. These monitoring systems should carefully balance accountability requirements with learning objectives, focusing on improvement rather than simply compliance to avoid creating perverse incentives that undermine authentic integration.

Successful implementation of the integrated approach requires coordinated action across multiple stakeholders within Ghana's entrepreneurial ecosystem. Implementation should therefore prioritize partnerships between financial institutions and BDS providers that create

seamless integration experiences for SMEs, reducing transaction costs and enhancing service coherence. Collaboration between educational institutions and industry would ensure training programs for Integrated Service Officers meet practical needs and remain aligned with evolving business realities. Coordination between public agencies and private providers would help align regulatory frameworks with implementation realities, creating an enabling environment for integrated service delivery. Engagement with SME associations would ensure integration approaches address authentic business needs as experienced by entrepreneurs themselves, enhancing relevance and adoption. International partnerships could leverage global knowledge and best practices while adapting approaches to Ghana's specific socioeconomic context. These partnerships should be formalized through clear agreements that specify roles, responsibilities, and coordination mechanisms, establishing accountability while facilitating effective collaboration across organizational boundaries.

By implementing these interconnected recommendations as part of a comprehensive approach to SME development, stakeholders can transform theoretical benefits into practical outcomes for Ghana's entrepreneurial ecosystem. The structured deployment of Integrated Service Officers, implementation of risk-return based lending frameworks, establishment of cluster-specific support protocols, development of robust monitoring systems, and creation of multi-stakeholder partnerships collectively provide a practical roadmap for operationalizing the integrated service delivery model. This implementation approach directly addresses the challenges identified in the empirical analysis while leveraging the opportunities presented by the risk-return clustering framework to create more targeted, effective, and sustainable support for Ghana's diverse SME sector.

Future Research Directions

While this study provides substantial evidence supporting integrated service delivery for SME development in Ghana, several areas warrant further investigation to enhance understanding and effectiveness of this approach. The first priority for future research involves longitudinal assessment of integration impact. Although the current research provides robust evidence of integration's benefits, longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into how these benefits evolve over time. Future research should track integrated service recipients over extended periods to assess the sustainability of risk reduction effects across complete business cycles, including periods of both economic growth and contraction. Such studies could also examine long-term patterns in firm transition between different risk-return clusters, helping to understand developmental pathways and the stability of improvements. Researchers should investigate potential compound benefits that might emerge from sustained integration, as initial improvements in business operations could potentially trigger virtuous cycles of growth and stability that are not captured in short-term analyses. Comparative trajectories of firms receiving different integration intensities would further clarify dose-response relationships and optimal resource allocation. This longitudinal perspective would enhance understanding of integration's durable impacts beyond immediate performance effects, providing a stronger foundation for investment in such programs.

The risk-return clustering framework established in this study provides valuable guidance for tailoring integration approaches, but further research could optimize these cluster-specific strategies. Future studies should investigate the most effective integration mechanisms for each risk-return profile, potentially identifying specialized approaches that generate superior outcomes for particular business types. Research on optimal timing and sequencing of interventions for different clusters would help practitioners structure support programs for maximum impact, recognizing that the order of interventions may significantly influence their effectiveness. Studies should also examine transfer potential of successful approaches between similar clusters in different contexts, identifying which elements of integration are universally beneficial versus those requiring significant contextualization. Research on integration intensity requirements for moving firms between clusters would clarify resource allocation needs for transformational support. This optimization research would enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of cluster-specific support programs, allowing for more targeted investment and potentially expanding the reach of available resources.

As technological adoption accelerates among Ghanaian SMEs, further research should examine how integration approaches can leverage digital tools to enhance delivery and expand reach. Future studies could explore digital platforms for delivering integrated services at scale, potentially reducing the cost and increasing the accessibility of these interventions, particularly for underserved rural areas. Research on technology-enabled monitoring systems for tracking integration outcomes would strengthen evidence generation and adaptive management capabilities. Studies should investigate virtual Integrated Service Officer models for reaching geographically dispersed SMEs, determining whether physical presence can be partially substituted by digital engagement without compromising quality. Research on blockchain and other emerging technologies could explore mechanisms for enhancing transparency and trust in integrated service delivery, potentially addressing governance challenges that might otherwise limit effectiveness. This digital-focused research would help modernize integration approaches for the evolving technological landscape, ensuring relevance as Ghana's economy continues to digitize and transform.

The sustainable knowledge transfer mechanism identified in this study warrants further investigation to optimize its effectiveness in building human capital for ongoing SME support. Future research should examine comparative effectiveness of different knowledge transfer approaches, identifying best practices in training, mentoring, and experiential learning for Integrated Service Officers. Studies on retention factors that keep experienced officers engaged in the system would help address potential sustainability challenges, particularly as officers develop valuable skills that might be attractive to higher-paying employers. Research on progression pathways would help maximize the long-term impact of knowledge transfer by clarifying how individual officers can continue contributing to the ecosystem as their careers evolve. This research would strengthen the human capacity dimension of integrated service delivery, ensuring that investments in people generate sustained returns through continued system engagement rather than capability flight.

While this study focuses on Ghana, the integration approach has potential relevance for diverse contexts globally. Future research should investigate adaptability of the integration model to

different cultural and economic environments, identifying both universal principles and context-dependent elements. Studies should explore context-specific factors that influence integration effectiveness, helping to predict where similar approaches might generate the strongest outcomes. Research on modified risk-return frameworks for different economic environments would help adapt the clustering approach to economies with significantly different structures, business compositions, or financial systems. Investigation of implementation variations required for different institutional settings would clarify how the approach can be adapted where supporting infrastructure, governance systems, or market structures differ significantly from Ghana's context. This cross-cultural research would enhance the global applicability of the integration approach while identifying critical adaptations for different contexts, potentially expanding the impact of these findings to benefit entrepreneurs across diverse developing economies.

These interconnected research directions collectively provide a comprehensive agenda for building upon the findings of this study. By pursuing deeper longitudinal understanding, optimizing cluster-specific approaches, exploring digital delivery mechanisms, strengthening knowledge transfer systems, and investigating cross-cultural adaptations, researchers can continue to refine and expand integrated service delivery models. This ongoing research would help transform the promising approach identified in this study into an increasingly sophisticated and effective framework for supporting SME development both in Ghana and potentially across diverse global contexts, contributing to broader economic development and poverty reduction goals.

7.5 Conclusion

This research provides compelling evidence that the integration of customized credit and participatory business development services creates transformative outcomes across multiple dimensions. By systematically reducing business risk while enhancing performance, integration addresses fundamental constraints that limit the effectiveness of traditional separate service approaches. The risk-return framework established in this study offers a good lens for understanding how integration creates value for different firm segments, moving beyond one-size-fits-all approaches to more targeted and effective interventions.

The findings challenge conventional wisdom about development interventions, demonstrating that integration's benefits extend from firm-level outcomes to broader economic development impacts. The consistent pattern of superior results under integration — from profitability and repayment sustainability to human development and poverty reduction — suggests a fundamental rethinking of how support services should be structured and delivered.

The implementation framework provides a practical roadmap for translating these theoretical insights into actionable programs, offering specific guidance for policymakers, financial institutions, and development practitioners. By adopting these recommendations, stakeholders can create more effective support systems that maximize impact across diverse SME segments while addressing broader development objectives.

Ultimately, this research establishes integration not merely as an alternative service delivery approach but as a fundamentally different paradigm for conceptualizing and implementing development interventions. By addressing both risk and return dimensions simultaneously, integration creates more comprehensive and sustainable pathways to economic advancement, with benefits that extend from individual enterprises to the broader society.

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APPENDIX A: PRIMARY DATA QUESTIONNAIRE

RESEARCH SURVEY INSTRUMENT

Final PhD Data Collection Questionnaire

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am a doctoral (PhD) student at The University of West of Scotland (UWS) in Paisley, Scotland, United Kingdom. I am conducting a study on: "The integration of customized credit and participatory Business Development service: impacts on SMEs' profitability, loan repayment, and economic development in Ghana."

I would like to know your experiences with the financial and business development support you have received in the last 2 years (2022–2023). Your responses will enable me to understand your business challenges and the best way to offer owners of small and medium enterprises the financial and business development support they may need in the future.

It will take approximately 15–20 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary, and your survey responses will be strictly confidential.

Please answer all questions to the best of your ability. If a question does not apply to your situation, please select "Not Applicable" or write "N/A" where appropriate.

Thank you very much for your time and support.

Ndukwe Ibe (+447423151465; Ndukwe.Ibe@uws.ac.uk)

PART A: Demographic Information

1. Gender

- Male
- Female

2. Age:

- Under 21
- 21–30
- 31–40
- 41–50
- 51–60
- Above 60

3. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- BECE
- WASSCE
- OND
- HND
- Some college but no degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Post-graduate studies or appointments

4. Which sector does your business operate in?

- Agriculture, forestry and fishing
- Mining and Quarrying
- Manufacturing
- Electricity, Water & Gas
- Construction
- Trade
- Hotels and Restaurants
- Transport
- Storage
- Communications
- Finance and Insurance
- Real Estate
- Public Administration
- Education
- Health
- Other

5. How long has your business been in existence?

- Less than 1 year
- 1–4 years
- 5–10 years
- 11–20 years
- More than 20 years

6. What is your role in the business?

- Owner

- Manager
- Owner-Manager
- Other

PART B: Loan Information from Banks

7. How much have you received as loans from banks?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

8. What percentage did the bank(s) charge you as interest on the loan?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	%
------	----------------------	---

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	%
------	----------------------	---

9. Were you given a repayment plan to follow?

- Yes
- No

10. If "Yes" to Question 9, in how many installments did you repay the loan?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times
------	----------------------	-------

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times
------	----------------------	-------

11. If "No" to Question 9, how many installments did you use to repay the loan?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times
------	----------------------	-------

2023	Numeric Input	Times
------	---------------	-------

12. Did you follow the repayment plan/schedule of the loan given by your credit provider?

- Yes
- No
- Not Applicable

13. If you did not repay the loan as scheduled, did you reschedule the repayment plan?

- Yes
- No
- Not Applicable

14. How satisfied are you with the loan services provided by banks?

- Very dissatisfied
- Not satisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied

PART C: Alternative Sources of Finance

15. If you were not successful in getting loans from the bank(s), did you go to alternative sources of finance (e.g., family, friends, local money lenders, etc.)?

- Yes
- No

16. Why did you go to your alternative source(s) of finance to support your business with capital?

Please rate each reason on the scale below:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I was a first-time borrower	<input type="radio"/>				

I had a lack of/poor credit history	<input type="radio"/>				
Insufficient credit from formal credit providers	<input type="radio"/>				
Rigid/Difficult loan conditions	<input type="radio"/>				
Collateral requirement	<input type="radio"/>				
Others	<input type="radio"/>				

17. How much have you received so far from your alternative source(s) of finance to support your business?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
-------------	----------------------	-----

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
-------------	----------------------	-----

18. Did your alternative source(s) of finance charge you a fee for the loan?

- Yes
- No

19. If "Yes" to Question 18, what percentage were you charged for the loan? [If "No", input zero (0)]

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	%
-------------	----------------------	---

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	%
-------------	----------------------	---

20. Was the loan condition of your alternative source(s) of finance better than that of the bank(s)?

- Yes
- No
- Not Applicable

21. How has using alternative sources of finance impacted your business?

- Very Negatively
- Negatively

- No Impact
- Positively
- Very Positively

PART D: Business Development Services (BDS)

22. Have you received any form of business development service (i.e., business advice, training, assistance, etc.)?

- Yes
- No

23. If "Yes" to Question 22, how useful was the business development service on a scale of 0–10? (0 being Very Useless, 10 being Very Useful)

<i>Very Useless</i> (0)	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10	<i>Very Useful</i> (10)
----------------------------	------------------------	----------------------------

24. How many times or days in a year does a business development professional visit you to offer business advice, training, assistance, etc.?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times/Day
-------------	----------------------	-----------

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times/Day
-------------	----------------------	-----------

25. How many times or days in a year do you spend with your business friends or associates to share business advice, ideas, assistance, etc.?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times/Day
-------------	----------------------	-----------

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Times/Day
-------------	----------------------	-----------

26. Which of the following business development services have you received? (Check all that apply)

- Financial management training

- Marketing and sales advice
- Operations management assistance
- Technology adoption guidance
- Human resource management support
- Strategic planning help
- Other
- None

27. How likely are you to seek business development services in the future?

- Very unlikely
- Unlikely
- Neutral
- Likely
- Very likely

PART E: Business Performance

28. How much do you spend annually on business technology (e.g., computers, machines, POS, phones, etc.)?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

29. How many people are working or have worked in your organization?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Person(s)
------	----------------------	-----------

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	Person(s)
------	----------------------	-----------

30. What is your Total Sales Revenue?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

31. What is your Net Profit?

2022	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

2023	<i>Numeric Input</i>	GHC
------	----------------------	-----

32. How would you rate your business's overall performance in the last two years?

- Poor
- Below average
- Average
- Good
- Excellent

PART F: Business Challenges and Outlook

33. Please rank the following challenges in order of severity, with 5 being the most severe and 1 being the least severe:

Challenge	1 (Least)	2	3	4	5 (Most)
Inadequate infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>				
Low technological levels/upgrading	<input type="radio"/>				
Weak institutional and regulatory framework (Corruption)	<input type="radio"/>				
Limited Access to Finance	<input type="radio"/>				
Poor Bookkeeping Records	<input type="radio"/>				
High Cost of Registration Requirements	<input type="radio"/>				

Inadequate Managerial Knowledge and Skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Access to Market Competition	<input type="radio"/>				
High Utility Tariff	<input type="radio"/>				
Taxation	<input type="radio"/>				

34. What do you believe would most help your business grow in the next 2–3 years? (Select up to three options)

- Easier access to finance
- Better business development services
- Improved infrastructure
- Reduced taxes or regulations
- Access to new markets
- Improved technology
- Better trained workforce
- Other

PART : Final Comments

35. Do you have any additional comments or insights about running an SME in Ghana that you would like to share?

UWS Ethics Approval Letter

08/03/2023

Dear RESCHBU1 Ndukwe Ibe,

Your application 21118: Integration Of Customized Credit And Participatory Business Development Services In Ghana. Impacts On SMEs' Profitability, Loan repayment And Economic Development , submission 16423, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix B: DEMOGRAPHIC AND OPERATIONAL PROFILE OF SME OWNERS IN GHANA

%GT Count of Education Level by Education Level

%GT Count of Selection by Sector

Response ● No ● Not Applicable ● Yes

12. Did you follow the repayment plan/schedule of the loan given by your credit provider?

13. If you did not repay the loan as scheduled, did you reschedule the repayment plan?

9. Were you given a repayment plan to follow?

How satisfied are you with the loan services provided by banks?

● Neutral ● Satisfied ● Very dissatisfied ● Not satisfied ● Very Satisfied

If you were not successful in getting loans from the bank(s), did you go to alternative sources of finance (e.g., family, friends, local money lenders, etc.)?

● Yes ● No

Did your alternative source(s) of finance charge you a fee for the loan?

Was the loan condition of your alternative source(s) of finance better than that of the bank(s)?

How has using alternative sources of finance impacted your business?

● No Impact ● Positively ● Very Positively ● Negatively ● Very Negatively

Have you received any form of business development service (i.e., business advice, training, assistance, etc.)?

● No ● Yes

If "Yes" to Question 22, how useful was the business development service on a scale of 0-10? (0 being Very Useless, 10 being Very Useful)

%GT Count of recbdscount by Which of the following business development services have you received? (Check all that apply)

%GT Count of How likely are you to seek business development services in the future?

● %GT Count of How would you rate your business's overall performance in the last two years?

▲ 1/5 ▼

Please rank the following challenges in order of severity, with 5 being the most severe and 1 being the least severe.	1	2	3	4	5
Access to Market	4.31%	12.37%	8.74%	22.47%	52.11%
Competition			1.71%	31.61%	66.68%
High Cost of Registration Requirements	2.10%	22.17%	54.26%	12.09%	9.38%
High utility Tariff	0.29%		0.50%	6.95%	92.26%
Inadequate infrastructure	2.49%	8.89%	38.14%	37.39%	13.09%
Inadequate Managerial Knowledge and Skills	4.21%	24.55%	30.45%	32.23%	8.55%
Limited Access to Finance	5.81%	2.47%	13.07%	19.59%	59.05%
Low technological levels/upgrading	1.85%	6.50%	18.76%	33.32%	39.57%
Poor Bookkeeping Records	6.29%	23.45%	49.65%	14.23%	6.38%
Taxation	100.00%				
Weak institutional and regulatory framework (Corruption)	3.29%	12.46%	39.90%	25.09%	19.25%

%GT Count of Value.1 by Growth Factors

Appendix C- SME PERFORMANCE PRE-TEST

Table 5.2: Pairwise correlations-SME performance

Variables	net_profit	revenue	bank_loans	alt_fin	installments_if Yess	installments_if No	firm_age	bankinterstrate	alt_finrate	formalbdsvists	informal bds_p-g	tech_spending	bizsize
net_profit	1												
revenue	0.634	1											
bank_loans	0.305	0.433	1										
(alt_fin	0.143	0.121	-0.033	1									
installments_if Yess	0.027	0.11	0.526	-0.16	1								
installments_if No	-0.022	0.012	-0.019	0.282	-0.012	1							
firm_age	0.152	0.147	0.108	0.061	-0.005	0.013	1						
bankinterstrate	-0.364	-0.308	0.048	-0.349	0.529	-0.109	-0.093	1					
(alt_finrate	-0.207	-0.196	-0.108	-0.017	0.153	-0.025	-0.046	0.393	1				
formalbdsvists	0.083	0.129	0.179	-0.083	0.167	0.019	0.06	0.147	0.038	1			
informal bds_p-g	-0.285	-0.258	-0.113	-0.244	0.242	-0.074	-0.096	0.638	0.296	0.057	1		
tech_spending	0.289	0.341	0.31	0.071	0.098	0.023	0.055	-0.196	-0.139	0.12	-0.138	1	
bizsize	0.124	0.185	0.106	0.288	0.061	0.282	0.065	-0.006	-0.029	0.115	0.025	0.081	1

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.4: Variance inflation factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
z_informal_credit_bds	1.728	0.579
z_tech_spending	1.439	0.695
ihs_formal_credit_bds	1.424	0.702
compl_integrated_credit_bds	1.414	0.707
z_bizsize	1.308	0.765
z_firm_age	1.027	0.974
ihs_ROS	1	1
Mean VIF	1.334	

Source: Author (2025)

5.5 a: Traditional Hausman Fixed Effects vs Random Effects Results

Variable	Fixed Effects	Random Effects
L_z_net_profit	-0.5658	0.3195
ihs_formal_credit_bds	-0.0151	-0.0098
z_informal_credit_bds	0.0081	-0.1997
compl_integrated_credit_bds	-0.0001	0.0012
z_firm_age	(omitted)	0.0704
z_bizsize	-0.2463	0.1603
z_tech_spending	0.0884	0.173
Education Level		
Diploma	-0.1623	0.6751

Masters	-0.2839	-0.1472
PHD	-0.5385	0.1549
Primary Education	-0.1586	-0.1287
Secondary Education	-0.0947	-0.2206
Technical Education	-0.0438	-0.1698
Sector		
Agriculture	-0.2247	0.0925
Construction	-0.0165	-0.0995
Education	-0.303	-0.1121
Finance	-0.0862	-0.091
Health	-0.185	0.1537
Information	0.204	-0.1217
Manufacturing	-0.1514	0.2779
Real estate	-0.1639	0.0212
Transportation	-0.0969	-0.0124
Water supply	0.1983	-0.1322
Wholesale and Retail	-0.0208	0.1572
_cons	0.304	-0.0276
Model Statistics		
N	681	681
r2	0.4671	
r2_b	0.3867	0.5892
r2_w	0.4671	0.1306
F	9.0901	
chi2		328.4143
rho	0.8392	0
sigma_u	1.2252	0
sigma_e	0.5363	0.5363

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.5 b: Robust Hausman Test Results

Variable	Fixed Effects (b)	Random Effects (B)	Difference (b-B)	Std. Err.
L_z_net_profit	-0.5658	0.319507	-0.8853	0.296031
ihs_formal_credit_bds	-0.01507	-0.00982	-0.00525	0.01147
z_informal_credit_bds	0.008092	-0.19969	0.20778	0.030578
compl_integrated_credit_bds	-8E-05	0.001171	-0.00125	0.000223
z_firm_age	(omitted)	(omitted)	(omitted)	(omitted)
z_bizsize	-0.24628	0.160345	-0.40663	0.178436
z_tech_spending	0.088408	0.17296	-0.08455	0.059662
Education Level				

Diploma	-0.16228	0.675124	-0.83741	
Masters	-0.28388	-0.14724	-0.13663	0.41789 2
PHD	-0.53851	0.154934	-0.69344	0.28217 2
Primary Education	-0.15858	-0.12871	-0.02988	0.20494 7
Secondary Education	-0.0947	-0.22058	0.125889	0.20901 1
Technical Education	-0.04382	-0.16978	0.125957	0.11230 7
Sector				
Agriculture	-0.22473	0.092515	-0.31724	0.29206 6
Construction	-0.01652	-0.09947	0.082951	0.07280 5
Education	-0.30297	-0.11211	-0.19087	0.44164 5
Finance	-0.08617	-0.09096	0.004788	0.27509 1
Health	-0.18498	0.153672	-0.33865	0.22103 2
Information	0.203953	-0.12169	0.325639	
Manufacturing	-0.15139	0.277868	-0.42926	0.35401 9
Real estate	-0.16391	0.021249	-0.18515	0.15028 9
Transportation	-0.09689	-0.01239	-0.0845	0.21722 8
Water supply	0.198256	-0.13215	0.330407	0.39316 1
Wholesale and Retail	-0.02081	0.157211	-0.17802	0.19127 4
Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic				
chi2(27) = 47.78				
Prob > chi2 = 0.0081				
(V_b-V_B is not positive definite)				

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.6 a: Traditional Repayment Hausman Test

Variable	Fixed Effects	Random Effects
Core Variables		
ihs_ROS	0.133	-0.119
compl_integrated_credit_bds	0.001	0.001
ihs_formal_credit_bds	-0.032	-0.194
z_informal_credit_bds	-0.056	-0.157
z_firm_age	(omitted)	-0.213
z_bizsize	-0.221	-0.637
z_tech_spending	0.293	0.145

Education Level		
Diploma	0.05	0.085
Masters	0.166	0.278
PHD	0.232	-0.087
Primary Education	0.011	0.198
Secondary Education	0.081	0.302
Technical Education	0.177	0.202
Sector		
Agriculture	0.49	0.129
Construction	0.338	0.086
Education	0.872	1.204
Finance	0.577	0.15
Health	0.195	-0.312
Information	0.581	-0.156
Manufacturing	0.804	0.572
Real estate	0.744	0.184
Transportation	0.693	0.293
Water supply	0.555	0.833
Wholesale and Retail	0.85	0.502
_cons	-0.057	2.176

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.6b: Robust Repayment Hausman Test

Variable	Fixed Effects (b)	Random Effects (B)	Difference (b-B)	Std. Err.
Core Variables				
ihs_ROS	0.133	-0.119	0.252	0.08
compl_integrated_credit_bds	0.001	0.001	-0.001	0
ihs_formal_credit_bds	-0.032	-0.194	0.162	0.081
z_informal_credit_bds	-0.056	-0.157	0.1	0.053
z_firm_age	(omitted)	-0.213		
z_bizsize	-0.221	-0.637	0.416	0.086
z_tech_spending	0.293	0.145	0.148	0.107
Education Level				
Diploma	0.05	0.085	-0.035	0.143
Masters	0.166	0.278	-0.111	0.127
PHD	0.232	-0.087	0.319	0.299
Primary Education	0.011	0.198	-0.188	0.085
Secondary Education	0.081	0.302	-0.221	0.121
Technical Education	0.177	0.202	-0.026	0.142

Sector				
Agriculture	0.49	0.129	0.361	0.262
Construction	0.338	0.086	0.253	0.245
Education	0.872	1.204	-0.332	0.316
Finance	0.578	0.15	0.427	0.302
Health	0.195	-0.312	0.506	0.322
Information	0.581	-0.156	0.737	0.203
Manufacturing	0.804	0.572	0.231	0.289
Real estate	0.744	0.184	0.559	0.246
Transportation	0.693	0.293	0.399	0.207
Water supply	0.555	0.833	-0.278	0.27
Wholesale and Retail	0.85	0.502	0.348	0.225
Hausman Test Statistics				
Chi-square test value: 50.617				
P-value: 0.003				

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.7a Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier Test Results For Profitability

$$z_{net_{profit}[firmid_t]} = Xb + u[firmid] + e[firmid_t]$$

Variable	Var	SD = sqrt(Var)
z_net_profit	1.084325	1.041309
e	.2875939	.5362778
u	0	0

Test: Var(u) = 0

chibar2(01) = 0.00

Prob > chibar2 = 1.0000

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.7b Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier Test Results For Repayment

$$ihs_{loan_{repayment_{rate}_{demeaned}[firmid_t]}} = Xb + u[firmid] + e[firmid_t]$$

Variable	Var	SD = sqrt(Var)
ihs_loan_repayment_rate_demeaned	2.483027	1.575762
e	.5294727	.7276488
u	.0969599	.3113838

Test: Var(u) = 0

chibar2(01) = 0.86

Prob > chibar2 = 0.1763

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.8a: Elastic Net Results – Profitability model Variable Selection

Knot ID	Lambda	s	L1-Norm	EBIC	R-sq	Action	Variable
1	1177.353	0	0	5.619	0	Added	_cons
2	1072.76	1	0.033	-4.292	0.019	Added	L_z_net_profit
3	811.503	2	0.124	-35.905	0.067	Added	z_tech_spending
4	739.412	3	0.171	-49.326	0.09	Added	z_informal_credit_bds
5	559.338	4	0.307	-86.887	0.147	Added	ihs_formal_credit_bds
6	320.074	5	0.525	-147.473	0.222	Added	z_firm_age
7	291.639	6	0.557	-148.711	0.23	Added	z_bizsize
8	201.016	7	0.701	-158.831	0.26	Added	compl_integrated_credit_bds

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.8b: Elastic Net Results – Repayment model Variable Selection

Knot ID	Lambda	s	L1-Norm	EBIC	R-sq	Action	Variable
1	3847.103	0	0	698.334	0	Added	_cons
2	3505.337	1	0.006	660.959	0.052	Added	ihs_formal_credit_bds
3	1827.685	2	0.062	368.882	0.362	Added	z_informal_credit_bds
4	452.732	3	0.312	-56.321	0.642	Added	compl_integrated_credit_bds
5	259.07	4	0.398	-112.363	0.674	Added	z_bizsize
6	102.182	5	0.551	-148.328	0.693	Added	z_firm_age
7	58.473	6	0.609	-148.069	0.695	Added	z_tech_spending

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.11: correlation matrix-Economic development

Variables	ihs_hdi	ihs_ihdi	ihs_mpi	z_crdt_prv	ihs_biz_dev	z_full_integ_ration	z_inf	z_fxrate	Inprof_taxi	Incorruption
ihs_hdi	1									
ihs_ihdi	-0.993	1								
ihs_mpi	-0.32	0.363	1							

z_crdtpv	0.727	-0.789	-0.341	1						
ihs_bizdev	0.996	-0.992	-0.266	0.744	1					
z_full_inte gration	0.76	-0.712	-0.086	0.198	0.751	1				
z_inf	-0.428	0.45	0.1	-0.563	-0.439	-0.037	1			
z_fxrate	0.738	-0.726	0.313	0.596	0.78	0.643	-0.369	1		
lnproftaxi	-0.934	0.937	0.097	-0.756	-0.947	-0.679	0.449	-0.832	1	
Incruption	0.968	-0.963	-0.439	0.688	0.958	0.689	-0.401	0.585	-0.865	1

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.12 VIF Results Across HDI, iHDI and MPI Models

	VIF	1/VIF
First set of models (with crdtprvi and bizdevi)		
ihs_hdi		
std crdtprv	2.743	.365
z corruption	2.402	.416
z fxrate	2.304	.434
z inf	1.646	.608
lnproftaxi diff	1.439	.695
dlnihs bizdev	1.069	.936
Mean VIF	1.934	.
ihs_ihdi		
std crdtprv	2.743	.365
z corruption	2.402	.416
z fxrate	2.304	.434
z inf	1.646	.608
lnproftaxi diff	1.439	.695
d ihs bizdev	1.069	.936
Mean VIF	1.934	.
ihs_mpi		
Incruption2ip diff	4.54	.22
z fxrate	4.079	.245
std crdtprv	2.654	.377
lninfi	1.799	.556
lnproftaxi diff	1.512	.662
dlnihs bizdev	1.112	.899
Mean VIF	2.616	.

Second set of models (with intgr)		
ihs_hdi		
lnproftaxi diff	2.909	.344
lnfxratei	2.773	.361
z full integration	2.736	.365
lnincorruption2ip diff	2.61	.383
lninfi	1.723	.58
Mean VIF	2.55	.
ihs_ihdi		
z fxrate	6.985	.143
lnincorruption2ip diff	3.678	.272
c interact	2.168	.461
lnproftaxi diff	1.797	.557
z inf	1.5	.667
Mean VIF	3.225	.
ihs_mpi		
z fxrate	3.617	.276
lnproftaxi diff	3.44	.291
lnincorruption2ip diff	3.086	.324
z full integration	2.73	.366
z inf	1.32	.758
Mean VIF	2.839	.

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.13: Stationarity Test Results – Economic development.

	ADF p-val		PP p-val		Integration Order
ihs_hdi		0		0	I (1)
ihs_ihdi		0		0	I (1)
ihs_mpi		0		0	I (1)
ihs_bizdev		0		0	I (1)
ihs_crdtpriv		0		0	I (1)
z_full_integration		0		0	I (1)
z_inf		0		0	I (1)
z_fxrate		0		0	I (1)
lnincorruption		0		0	I (1)
lnprofitax		0		0	I (1)

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.14: Elastic net Model Selection Results for Integration and Separate Services Models

Knot	ID	Lambda a	s	L1- Norm	EBIC	R-sq	Action
Model 1: HDI with Integration							
1	1	1.17735 3	0	0	5.619	0	Added_cons

2	2	0.95246	1	0.033	-4.292	0.142	Added z_full integration
3	3	0.81150 3	2	0.124	- 35.905	0.286	Added lninfi
4	4	0.73941 2	3	0.171	- 49.326	0.384	Added lnfxratei
5	5	0.55933 8	4	0.307	- 86.887	0.521	Added lnproftaxi
6	6	0.32007 4	5	0.525	- 147.47 3	0.703	Added ln Corruption2ip_dif f
Model 2: IHDI with Integration							
1	1	1.17735 3	0	0	5.619	0	Added _cons
2	2	0.95246	1	0.033	-4.292	0.152	Added c_interact
3	3	0.81150 3	2	0.124	- 35.905	0.325	Added z_inf
4	4	0.73941 2	3	0.171	- 49.326	0.487	Added z_fxrate
5	5	0.55933 8	4	0.307	- 86.887	0.683	Added lnproftaxi
6	6	0.32007 4	5	0.525	- 147.47 3	0.921	Added ln Corruption2ip_dif f
Model 3: MPI with Integration							
1	1	1.17735 3	0	0	5.619	0	Added _cons
2	2	0.95246	1	0.033	-4.292	0.163	Added z_full integration
3	3	0.81150 3	2	0.124	- 35.905	0.345	Added z_full integration_s q
4	4	0.73941 2	3	0.171	- 49.326	0.516	Added z_inf
5	5	0.55933 8	4	0.307	- 86.887	0.724	Added z_fxrate
6	6	0.32007 4	5	0.525	- 147.47 3	0.888	Added lnproftaxi
7	7	0.22061 4	6	0.663	- 156.96 4	0.999	Added ln Corruption2ip_dif f
Model 4: HDI with Separate Services							
1	1	1.17735 3	0	0	5.619	0	Added _cons
2	2	0.95246	1	0.033	-4.292	0.125	Added std_crdtprv

3	3	0.81150 3	2	0.124	- 35.905	0.267	Added dlnihs_bizdev
4	4	0.73941 2	3	0.171	- 49.326	0.398	Added z_inf
5	5	0.55933 8	4	0.307	- 86.887	0.485	Added z_fxrate
6	6	0.32007 4	5	0.525	- 147.47 3	0.582	Added lnproftaxi
7	7	0.22061 4	6	0.663	- 156.96 4	0.685	Added z_corruption
Model 5: IHDI with Separate Services							
1	1	1.17735 3	0	0	5.619	0	Added _cons
2	2	0.95246	1	0.033	-4.292	0.184	Added std_crdtpv
3	3	0.81150 3	2	0.124	- 35.905	0.356	Added d_ihs_bizdev
4	4	0.73941 2	3	0.171	- 49.326	0.524	Added z_inf
5	5	0.55933 8	4	0.307	- 86.887	0.738	Added z_fxrate
6	6	0.32007 4	5	0.525	- 147.47 3	0.862	Added lnproftaxi
7	7	0.22061 4	6	0.663	- 156.96 4	0.965	Added z_corruption
Model 6: MPI with Separate Services							
1	1	1.17735 3	0	0	5.619	0	Added _cons
2	2	0.95246	1	0.033	-4.292	0.192	Added std_crdtpv
3	3	0.81150 3	2	0.124	- 35.905	0.378	Added dlnihs_bizdev
4	4	0.73941 2	3	0.171	- 49.326	0.567	Added lninfi
5	5	0.55933 8	4	0.307	- 86.887	0.784	Added z_fxrate
6	6	0.32007 4	5	0.525	- 147.47 3	0.891	Added lnproftaxi_diff
7	7	0.22061 4	6	0.663	- 156.96 4	0.992	Added ln Corruption2ip_diff
Use long option for full output.							
Type e.g. lasso2, lic(ebic) to run the model selected by EBIC.							

Note: Each model shows stepwise variable selection with all specified variables being selected, confirming their importance in the respective ARDL specifications. The EBIC values consistently decrease while R-squared increases with each variable addition, supporting the inclusion of all variables in the final models.

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.15: Optimal Lag selection – Economic development

Model	Lag	LL	LR	df	p	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
HDI Integration	0	-90.3135	nan	nan	nan	3.2e-06	4.37789	4.46811	4.62118
HDI Integration	1	181.949	544.53	36.0	0.0	7.1e-11	6.36133	5.72975	4.65824
HDI Integration	2	284.857	205.82	36.0	0.0	3.7e-12	9.40261	8.22966	6.23972
HDI Integration	3	338.657	107.6	36.0	0.0	2.1e-12	10.2117	8.49738	5.58902
HDI Integration	4	438.209	199.1	36.0	0.0	2.1e-13	13.1004	10.8447	7.01795
IHDI Integration	0	-184.56	nan	nan	nan	0.00016	8.28522	8.37457	8.52374
IHDI Integration	1	190.193	749.51	36.0	0.0	6.5e-11	6.44316	5.81771	4.77353
IHDI Integration	2	267.622	154.86	36.0	0.0	1.2e-11	8.24443	7.08287	5.14369
IHDI Integration	3	346.374	157.5	36.0	0.0	2.3e-12	10.1032	8.40556	5.57137
IHDI Integration	4	450.667	208.59	36.0	0.0	1.9e-13	13.0725	10.8387	7.10952
MPI Integration	0	-127.065	nan	nan	nan	1e-06	6.09388	6.19914	6.37773
MPI Integration	1	247.71	749.55	36.0	0.0	4e-13	8.71408	7.87196	6.44329
MPI Integration	2	594.747	694.07	36.0	0.0	6.2e-19	22.2612	20.6823	18.0035
MPI Integration	3	nan	nan	36.0	0.0	nan	nan	nan	nan
MPI Integration	4	nan	nan	36.0	0.0	nan	nan	nan	nan
HDI Separate	0	-132.623	nan	nan	nan	1e-06	6.07057	6.17481	6.34884
HDI Separate	1	264.26	793.77	36.0	0.0	2.8e-13	9.05477	8.22083	6.82859
HDI Separate	2	383.672	238.82	36.0	0.0	1.5e-14	12.1162	10.5525	7.94209
HDI Separate	3	483.325	199.31	36.0	0.0	2.6e-15	14.3185	12.0252	8.19651
HDI Separate	4	655.38	344.11	36.0	0.0	3.2e-17	19.6687	16.6457	11.5988
IHDI Separate	0	-198.316	nan	nan	nan	1.8e-05	8.92676	9.03101	9.20503
IHDI Separate	1	261.555	919.74	36.0	0.0	3.2e-13	8.93719	8.10325	6.71102

IHDI Separate	2	406.954	290.8	36.0	0.0	5.6e-15	-13.1284	-11.5648	-8.95438
IHDI Separate	3	562.169	310.43	36.0	0.0	8.4e-17	-17.7465	-15.4531	-11.6245
IHDI Separate	4	1561.08	1997.8	36.0	0.0	2.6e-34	-59.047	-56.0239	-50.9771
MPI Separate	0	-83.567	nan	nan	nan	1.2e-07	3.9377	4.04194	4.21597
MPI Separate	1	271.622	710.38	36.0	0.0	2.1e-13	-9.37487	-8.54093	-7.14869
MPI Separate	2	400.134	257.02	36.0	0.0	7.5e-15	-12.8319	-11.2683	-8.65784
MPI Separate	3	717.333	634.4	36.0	0.0	9.9e-20	-24.4927	-22.1994	-18.3708
MPI Separate	4	1074.12	713.58	36.0	0.0	4e-25	-37.8749	-34.8519	-29.8051

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5.16: Cointegration Tests

Johansen Test Results									
Model	Selecte d Rank	Johans en Trace Stat	Critical Value (5%)	Critical Value (1%)	Number of Lags				
HDI Integrati on	2	44.911 4	47.21	54.46	2				
IHDI Integrati on	1	63.506 3	68.52	76.07	2				
MPI Integrati on	4	34.103 7	29.68	35.65	2				
HDI Separate	3	50.209 1	47.21	54.46	2				
IHDI Separate	3	83.393 5	47.21	54.46	2				
MPI Separate	4	31.035 3	29.68	35.65	2				
Engle-Granger Test Results									
Model	R- square d	Adj R- squared	Prob > F	Dickey- Fuller Stat	Critical Value (5%)	Critical Value (1%)			
HDI Integrati on	0.9818	0.9797	0	-3.25	-1.95	-2.625			
IHDI Integrati on	0.9059	0.8952	0	-1.475	-1.95	-2.622			
MPI Integrati on	0.8449	0.8223	0	-4.342	-1.95	-2.625			

HDI Separate	0.9917	0.9905	0	-2.9	-1.95	-2.622			
IHDI Separate	0.9899	0.9885	0	-2.509	-1.95	-2.622			
MPI Separate	0.7748	0.7434	0	-2.871	-1.95	-2.622			
Bounds Test Results									
Model	F-statistic	t-statistic	Critical Value (10%, I(0)/I(1))	Critical Value (5%, I(0)/I(1))	Critical Value (1%, I(0)/I(1))	Decision			
HDI Integration	58.368	-6.454	2.686 / 4.071	3.187 / 4.755	4.369 / 6.362	Reject H0	(level relationship exists)		
IHDI Integration	58.368	-6.454	2.686 / 4.071	3.187 / 4.755	4.369 / 6.362	Reject H0	(level relationship exists)		
MPI Integration	58.368	-6.454	2.686 / 4.071	3.187 / 4.755	4.369 / 6.362	Reject H0	(level relationship exists)		
HDI Separate	58.368	-6.454	2.686 / 4.071	3.187 / 4.755	4.369 / 6.362	Reject H0	(level relationship exists)		
IHDI Separate	58.368	-6.454	2.686 / 4.071	3.187 / 4.755	4.369 / 6.362	Reject H0	(level relationship exists)		
MPI Separate	58.368	-6.454	2.686 / 4.071	3.187 / 4.755	4.369 / 6.362	Reject H0	(level relationship exists)		

Source: Author (2025)